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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 3, Number 4, September, 2023 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remain indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

Associate Professor Bashir Suleiman

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CALL FOR ARTICLES

The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

Submission of Manuscripts & Assessment Fee

Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Dr. Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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Assessment of Deposit Money Banks on Financial Performance in Nigeria Banking System

Inobemhe, Aliyu Mohammed¹

Correspondence E-mail: mohammedinobemhe20@gmail.com

Tel: +2348026662926

Okoro, Edwin Okafor

¹Department of Banking and Finance, School of Business Studies, Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi

²Department of Business Administration, Chrisland University, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study investigated the deposit money banks' (DMBs) and financial performance in Nigeria during a 21-year span, from 2001 to 2021. The study specifically examined whether the bank size, monetary policy rate and inflation rate have a substantial impact on the financial performance of DMBs. Secondary data from the annual financial statements of eight chosen deposit money banks in Nigeria were used in the study. Panel regression analysis and ordinary least squares were used to thematically analyze the data that were produced. The study revealed that bank size has a significant negative impact on financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria, monetary policy rate do not exert any significant impact on the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria and inflationary pressures have no significant impact on the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria. Amongst other recommendations the study recommends that Bank size has a significant negative impact on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria. Banks should ensure they maintain capital adequacy and liquidity management to impact on bank performance.

Keywords: Deposit Money Bank, Bank size, inflation rate, monetary policy rate.

Introduction

The primary focus of the banking sector around the world is on taking deposits from the general public and using those deposits to lend to credit-worthy borrowers for investments, loans, and other purposes. Overdrafts, loans, advances, business funding agreements, local purchase order financing, etc. are all common forms of bank credit. Akinlo and Mofoluwaso (2014) observed that depository money banks' (DMBs) primary function is to give bank credit, also known as lending. Lending, which entails the risk that the borrower may not repay the loan as agreed, and paying a fixed rate of interest on term deposits, are two activities that make up the global banking industry. There is a chance that lending rates will decline, which would mean that the bank would earn less on investments than it would on deposits (Biabani, Gilaninia & Mohabatkhah, 2012).

The management of credit risk takes place in a setting that is unique to the banking sector and is both complex and unpredictable. However, banks provide loans and advances to people, businesses, and the government in order for them to carry out investments and other development activities. By doing this, banks help the economy expand and develop while also generating a profit that will meet shareholders' expectations. Unfortunately, DMB's profitability in Nigeria has been severely and adversely impacted for some time due to the steadily rising loan quality of assets, high levels of non-performing loans, and significant provisions for loan losses. The economic growth and efficiency of the economy are hampered by these NPLs (Karim, Chan & Hassan, 2010). In light of this, the work will assess the factors that contribute to non-performing loans and how they affect the profitability of DMBs in Nigeria from 2001 to 2021.

In order to conduct monetary policy inside an economy, Taiwan (2018) observes that monetary authorities employ the credit view and its sub-channels, the interest rate channel and the bank lending channel. For instance, an expansionary monetary policy that uses the interest channel would cut interest rates to lower the cost of capital, which would simultaneously raise investment and expenditure as well as aggregate demand and output. On the other hand, an expansionary monetary policy through the bank lending channel raises bank deposits and reserves, leading to a rise in the accessibility of bank loans, which promotes investment and consumer spending. This study is based on developing and putting into practice a viable framework for monetary policy which requires an understanding of the bank lending channel. According to Mishkin (2019), the foundation of the bank lending channel is the unique function that banks perform within the financial system in addressing issues with asymmetric information and other flaws in credit markets. Banks frequently act as financial middlemen who provide money to particular borrowers who lack access to credit markets. The magnitude of the external finance premium, which is the difference

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between the costs of a firm's externally generated funds (via issuing equity or debt) and its internally generated funds, reflects the imperfections (retained earnings). This implies that banks provide indirect finance while serving as financial mediators between SSUs and SDUs, building on their unique function in directing funds for productive use. According to Gambacorta and Mistrulli (2004), only big businesses issue commercial papers as a result, during monetary contractions, small and large enterprises display different behaviors, which minimizes the significance of the bank lending channel.

The contrasts between small and large businesses during monetary contractions typically do not cut against the bank lending perspective. In this regard, Kashyap, Stein and Wilcox (2013) noted that monetary authorities' contraction reduces the supply of loans to small businesses, and that small businesses expand their account payables in pursuit of alternative sources of financing. Large companies are simultaneously experiencing a surge in the demand for their account payables, which forces them to issue more commercial papers in order to secure additional external funding. Therefore, a rise in commercial papers would allow major companies to moderately and imperfectly replace banks' financial intermediation role. Despite the importance of the bank lending channel in directing capital toward productive uses, Kim and Sohn (2017) contend that loans do not play a crucial role since the initial impact of a monetary policy contraction on interest rates is felt through deposits rather than loans. In accordance with the banking theory of credit creation, this study challenges the claim made by the above scholars on the crucial function of loans, as banks do not lend existing money but instead generate new money.

Akinola (2022) investigated how bank size affected the financial results of listed deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The relationship between bank size and financial performance was also explored, as well as the moderating impact of adequate internal control. The study used an ex-post facto research strategy since secondary data were taken from 10 DMBs' published annual reports in Nigeria for the 12-year period between 2006 and 2017. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data (multiple regression analysis). According to the analysis's findings, the proxies for bank size (total assets, personnel count, and client deposits) all had a cumulative impact on return on asset for financial performance. Also, the effectiveness of internal controls as a moderating factor improved the impact of bank size on financial performance. The study came to the conclusion that the combination of total asset, personnel count, and client deposits, which served as proxies for bank size had an impact on financial performance.

Alfadhli and AlAli (2021) examined how Kuwaiti banks' financial performance was affected by their size. According to the study's analysis, the number of employees, the number of bank-owned branches, and customer deposits have a negative association with financial success, however shareholder ownership has a positive link. Kachumbo (2020) used panel data analysis to examine the factors influencing the financial performance of commercial Fintech banks in Kenya. The capital adequacy ratio, customer size, and the amount of loan advances given to customers served as proxies for the independent variable, and return on equity served as a proxy for the dependent variable. According to the findings, there is a negative and significant association between capital sufficiency and client volume and financial performance.

In their study of the financial performance of Kenya's quoted banks, Nyabaga and Wepukhulu (2020) examined the impact of business characteristics. The study's results utilizing regression analysis show that adequate capital and bank size have a considerable favorable impact on return on equity and return on asset. The return on equity and return on asset are negatively impacted by asset adequacy. Other studies operationalized financial performance using proxies like ROA and ROE (Aladwann, 2015; Jaouad & Lahsen, 2018). Only ROA was employed in this study as a stand-in for financial performance. The literature review is therefore founded on bank size and financial performance. Al-Homaidi, Tabash, Farhan and Almaqtari (2018), on the other hand, used a panel data analytic methodology to assess the effect of bank-specific characteristics on the profitability of 60 Indian banks. The results demonstrate that asset size and client deposits, which represent the size of the bank, had a favorable impact on profitability as evaluated by ROA and ROE. Using panel data from 43 banks from 2007 to 2016, Mwangi, Makau and Kosimbei (2014) determined the impact of bank size (total asset) on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study's findings demonstrated that total assets had a favorable impact on ROA and ROE. The study also discovered that a bank's financial performance increases with its size.

The study is grounded in agency theory because bank managers, who act as agents in this situation, may make self-serving decisions that could be detrimental to stockholder interests. Conflicts of interest and information asymmetry may arise because a variety of decisions impacting the resources of the principal's firm are delegated to the agents, according to agency theory (principal-agent dilemma). According to Rozina and Jewel (2017), when an agent chooses to act in his or her interests rather than that of their principal, this is known as a principal-agent issue (moral hazard). Due to the agent's insider trading and the control measures put in place by the principle to prevent the agent from pursuing personal interests, the principal is responsible for agency fees such as the costs incurred. Agency costs are necessary evils because they are less expensive than the costs associated with letting management pursue their own agenda at the expense of the primary. When one person (the

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principal) gives another person (the agent) permission to act on their behalf, an agency relationship is established. Understanding the interactions between agents and principals is done using agency theory. In a specific business transaction, the agent represents the principal and is responsible for acting in the principal's best interests, putting the interests of the principal before their own (Fadun, 2013).

According to the fundamental nature of information asymmetry, the principal-agent models of agency theory can be broadly divided into three kinds. Models with ex-post asymmetric information fall under the first category. Following the signature of the contract between the principal and himself, the agent in these models receives certain private information. These models are called moral hazard models. Models with asymmetric ex-ante information are in the second class. Before the contract is signed, the agent in these models already knows confidential information. Adverse selection models are those that fit this description. The third class of signaling models is related in a close way. In these models, the informed agent may communicate his private information to the principal via a signal (Shadnam, 2014). Because the agent's ability to cover potential losses in the future is unpredictable, and because the principal is unaware of the needs and wants of the agents, the principal will design the contract to receive some profits from the agents. The principal wants to assign the contract in a way that increases his profit while paying the agent for carrying out the duty that is expected of him (Ibrahim, Saiful & Kayes, 2021). The formula is expressed as the probability expected (prob.exp.) of the utility of the principal:

$$\text{Exp. } U_p = \text{Exp. } F(\text{capability})_a - F(\text{agent's cost}) \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (i)$$

Where;

Exp. U_p : Expected Utility from the Principal

Exp. $F(\text{capability})_a$: Expected from the function of agent's capability

$F(\text{Agent's cost})$: The function of agent's cost.

Al-Amin, Siddikur and Imran (2021) examined the effect of non-performing loans (NPLs) on the financial performance of all Bangladeshi listed banks. In order to determine the impact of the non-performing loan ratio (NPLR), capital adequacy ratio (CAR), inflation (INF), and provision maintenance ratio (PMR) on the return on asset, the study examined data from the preceding 23 years, from 1997 to 2019. The study used the OLS and VAT models, the Test of Heteroscedasticity, the Test of Normal Distribution, and the Unit Root Test to analyze the OLS regression. It discovered that all independent variables, including NPLR, CAR, INF, and PMR, are statistically significant in explaining the dependent variable. Ibitomi and Micah (2021) study investigated how non-performing loans affect the liquidity of Nigeria's deposit money banks. In order to examine the relationship between the explained variable (banks' liquidity) and Non-Performing Loans (NPL), a panel regression analysis was conducted on data of 15 quoted DMBs from 2009 to 2019. In addition, the explanatory variables Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Bank Size (BS), Loan Growth (LG), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and Inflation were taken into account. Only four variables were found to be significantly correlated with banks' liquidity in the study: Non-Performing Loans, Capital Adequacy Ratio, Bank Size, and Inflation. The other three, Gross Domestic Product, Loan Growth, and Monetary Policy Rate, were found to be negligible. The finding also revealed that NPLs has negative effect on banks' liquidity while CAR, BS and INF showed positive relationship.

In Indonesian banks, Dewi and Badjra (2020) assessed the impact of NPL, LDR, and Operating costs of operating income (BOPO) on return on income. According to the report, BOPO is the most important component that has a substantial impact on bank profitability. The inferential study shows that BOPO and NPL both have a negative and considerable impact on profitability or return on assets. The study makes the suggestion that if banks experience increased profitability, policymakers should improve their management and operational effectiveness. Nyarko-Baasi (2018) evaluated the effects of nonperforming loans on the profitability of a few chosen commercial banks in Tanzania and Ghana, respectively. The panel regression model with fixed effects was utilized in the investigation. The findings indicated a link between non-performing loans and banks' degree of profitability. The outcome supported the information asymmetry theory and the theory of poor management. Using a straightforward regression model for data analysis, Akter and Roy (2017) investigated the effects of bank-specific characteristics on non-performing loans (NPLs) in the banking sector. The study discovered that while return on equity and the ratio of loans to assets had a negative but significant impact on non-performing loans, the capital adequacy ratio had a negative but minor relationship with NPLs. Their research also revealed a substantial positive association between non-performing loans and total loan and net interest margin (NPLs).

Objectives of the Study

The Study Specifically;

1. To find out whether bank size has significant impact on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria;

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2. Determine if monetary policy rate affected DMBs’ financial performance in Nigeria; and
3. Ascertain the extent to which inflation rate has impacted on DMBs’ financial performance.

Research Questions

The following research questions are thus posed by this study:

1. Does bank size have significant impact on DMBs’ financial performance in Nigeria?
2. Does monetary policy rate affect DMBs’ financial performance in Nigeria?
3. Does inflation rate have significant impact on DMBs’ financial performance in Nigeria?

Methodology

This study utilizes a longitudinal research design, which is based on the hypothesis that it will involve repeated observations of the same variables over the course of 21 years, from 2001 to 2021. The complete population of this study consists of the 19 recognized Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria that have been granted international and domestic authorization by the Central Bank of Nigeria. Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc are some of these as international authorizations. While the following deposit money institutions are authorized by the government: Citi Bank Nigeria Limited, Eco Bank Nigeria Plc, Heritage Bank Limited, Keystone Bank Limited, Polaris Bank Plc, Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc, Standard Chartered Bank Ltd, Sterling Bank Plc, Titan Trust Bank Limited, Unity Bank Plc, and Wema Bank Plc (CBN, 2021). The study adopts eight (8) international licensed deposit money banks as sample of the study out of the nineteen (19) deposit money banks in Nigeria for the period 2001 to 2021. These include Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa Plc and Zenith Bank Plc. This is due to their official annual data on the variables of the study can be accessed from the appropriate designated government agencies including the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and National Bureau of statistics (NBS) for the period covered by the study, 2001 to 2021. The case studies for the study were chosen using judgmental sampling approaches. The Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS) and Panel Data Regression techniques were utilized in the study to analyze the data. The eight (8) chosen banks were covered using panel data regression while the pooled OLS covered the individual variable data. The goal of the two methods is to compare their output. Additionally, panel data approach was used in the study. As a result, when discussing an estimator for the regression model’s coefficients, the term fixed effect estimator’ is employed. The fixed effect model is provided in its generalized form by;

$$Y_{it} = \delta_0 + \beta x_{it} + \mu_{it} + v_{it} \text{ ----- (i)}$$

Where;

Y_{it} = dependent variable

δ_0 = intercept

βx_{it} = vector of explanatory variable

μ_{it} = individual specific effect

v_{it} = error term

The Hausman Test was used to determine if the Fixed Effect Model or Random Effect Model is more appropriate for the investigation. The fixed effect model's generalized form is provided by;

$$Y_{it} = \delta + \beta x_{it} + \epsilon_i + \epsilon_{it} \text{ ----- (ii)}$$

Where;

ϵ_i = cross sectional error term

ϵ_{it} = individual observational error term

As a functional form of the following equations, the researchers propose the panel information model below:

MODEL 1

$$ROA = F(BKS, MPR, INF) \text{ ----- (iv)}$$

MODEL 11

$$ROE = F(BKS, MPR, INF) \text{ ----- (v)}$$

While the econometric form of the model is:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BKS_{it} + \beta_2 MPR_{it} + \beta_3 INF_{it} + e_{it} \text{ ----- (vi)}$$

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BKS_{it} + \beta_2 MPR_{it} + \beta_3 INF_{it} + e_{it} \text{ ----- (vii)}$$

i = cross-sectional variables from 1, 2, 3, -----21

t = time series variables from 1, 2, 3, -----21

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e = error term

Where;

ROA_{it} = Return on Assets of bank i at the end of year t proxy for bank performance.

ROE_{it} = Return on Equity of bank i at the end of year t proxy for bank performance.

BKS_{it} = Bank Size

MPR_{it} = Monetary policy rate

INF_{it} = Inflation rate

Inflation = $\frac{CCP\ Index - HCP\ Index}{CCP\ Index} \times 100$

Theoretical expectation is depicted as: $\beta_2, \beta_3 < 0$ and $\beta_1 > 0$

β_0 is to take care of the Constant Variable.

B_1 is the coefficient of Bank Size (BKS) which is expected to be greater than zero ($\beta_1 > 0$). That is a positive relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigeria is expected. B_2 is the coefficient of Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) which is expected to be less than zero ($\beta_2 < 0$). That is a negative relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigerian is expected. Finally, β_3 is the coefficient of Inflation Rate (INFL) which is expected to be less than zero ($\beta_3 < 0$). That is a negative relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigerian is expected.

This study uses Return on Assets and Return on Equity to capture its dependent variable depicting banks' performance in Nigeria. The measurement, for the calculation of Return on Assets is as follows:

$$ROA = \frac{\text{Net Profit After Tax}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

$$ROE = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Equity}}$$

While, the independent variables of this study can be measured thus:

1. Bank Size = Total Assets.
2. Monetary Policy Rate = Overnight rate banks charges one another to borrow funds.
3. Inflation Rate = $\frac{CCP\ Index - HCP\ Index}{CCP\ Index} \times 100$.

Results

Question 1

To what extent is the influence of bank size, monetary policy rate and inflation rate on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria (ROA)?

Table 1: Panel Regression Result for the ROA Equation

Variable	<i>Fixed effects</i>				<i>Random effects</i>			
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
Constant	10.534	0.00	8.965	0.00	8.952	0.02	7.504	0.05
BKS	-0.920	0.00	-0.875	0.00	-0.838	0.01	-0.754	0.02
MPR	-0.046	0.27	-0.046	0.27	-0.073	0.53	-0.076	0.49
INFL	-0.035	0.29	-0.001	0.97	0.021	0.82	0.037	0.67
R-sq.	0.634		0.66		0.062		0.085	
Adj. R-sq.	0.603		0.63		0.027		0.045	
F-stat.	21.502		20.49157		1.761		2.134	

Source: Author's computations

It can be seen that the goodness of fit statistics has improved drastically over the pooled OLS estimates in each of the estimations. The goodness of fit statistics values is also better in the fixed effects estimates than in the random effect's estimates. The adjusted R-squared value in the fixed effects estimates shows that about 60 percent of systematic variations in ROA for the banks are captured in the model with control, while 63 percent is captured in the model without control. Thus, the focus of the analysis in this study is on fixed effect estimations. The focus is on the particular contribution of the individual variables to return on asset (ROA) of the banks.

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Question 2

To what extent is the influence of bank size, monetary policy rate and inflation rate on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria (ROE)?

Table 2: Panel Regression result for the ROA equation

Variable	Fixed Effects				Random Effects			
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
C	0.985	0.00	0.947	0.00	1.152	0.06	1.171	0.07
BKS	-0.030	0.09	-0.025	0.16	0.022	0.67	0.021	0.69
MPR	-0.008	0.22	-0.008	0.22	-0.011	0.54	-0.011	0.54
INFL	0.004	0.39	0.005	0.32	0.014	0.33	0.014	0.35
R-squared	0.469		0.473		0.144		0.144	
Adj.R-squared	0.425		0.425		0.112		0.106	
F-statistic	10.476		9.806		4.505		3.840	

Source: Author’s computations

The adjusted R-squared values for the fixed effects estimates are also larger than those of the pooled OLS and the random effects estimates. This again justifies the efficiency of the fixed effects approach to the estimation for this study. The important focus of the analysis is on the coefficients of the explanatory variables. The coefficient of both monetary policy rate and inflation rate also fail the significance tests at the 5 percent level. This shows that, just like ROA, the external macroeconomic factors do not have significant impact on the return to equity of DMBS in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This finding support previous studies by Olaoluwa and Shomade (2017) and Kim and Sohn (2017) where the role of interest rate was demonstrated to be more related to deposits rather than to loans in the Nigerian and developed country context. In the same vein, inflation rate was found to have no impact on financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria. Thus, external or macroeconomic factors do not explain the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria, especially in terms of ROA. This outcome is crucial and shows that financial performances of banks in Nigeria are essentially disconnected from macroeconomic occurrences in the country. In particular, the result indicates that whether the banks charge higher or lower interest rates, the operational efficiency of the banks do not change significantly.

Moreover, rising price level in the economy (or economic instability) also do not influence the financial profitability of the banks. This outcome portends both positive and negative implications. In the first place, it shows that banks in Nigeria may not necessarily fail or run into serious balance sheet even when inflationary pressures are high. Thus, these banks appear to be effectively shielded from the external macroeconomic factors in terms of their operational activities. On the other hand, this result suggests that the banking system is not linked to the real sector in Nigeria. Thus, when the real sector is facing price decimation, the banking system, which is expected to bear the brunt of the real sector financial woes, is not essentially affected. Thus, the banking system does not appear to be playing its financial roles effectively in the economy.

Conclusion

Though banks offer many services, most of them are related to credit and cash management which are critical aspects of liquidity among the banks. A major risk of systemic failure is characterized by the rate of non-performing loans in the banking system. Thus, proper focus on its main activities from both the policy and operational perspectives are essential. These perspectives particularly involve appropriate strategies for the management of lending activities that are geared towards contributing greatly to bank performance, productivity and long run stability of the system. In this study, the role of deposit money banks and other related aspects of the banking system in Nigeria were examined in relation to their impacts on the financial performance of these banks. It has been shown that indeed, bank size has a significant negative impact on financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria, monetary policy rate do not exert any significant impact on the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria and inflationary pressures have no significant impact on the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered:

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1. Bank size has a significant negative impact on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria. Banks should ensure they maintain capital adequacy and liquidity management to impact on bank performance.
2. Monetary policy rate adopted by Central Bank through its prudential guidelines must make sure that their monetary policies measures address the financial system in order to influence bank performance. From the foregoing the regulatory agencies in Nigeria have more responsibilities to carry out in terms of guiding the banks in their loan policies and operations more properly. It is known that much dependence on loan strategies that are high-risk tends to result in higher loan defaults in the banking system. Hence, the regulatory agencies need to regulate the lending visa-visa the deposit and liquidity stance of banks on a regular basis.
3. Government through central banks should embark on fiscal/monetary policies that targets reduction of high inflation rate through adoption of contractionary/expansionary measures.

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Assessment of Non-Performing Loans and Financial Performance on Deposit Money Banks (DMB) in Nigeria Banking System

*Aguwamba, S. M.¹

Email: aguwambas.iuokada.edu.ng

Inobemhe, Aliyu Mohammed²

Correspondence E-mail: mohammedinobemhe20@gmail.com

Tel: +2348026662926

¹Department of Banking and Finance, Igbinedion University, Okada, Edo State

²Department of Banking and Finance, School of Business Studies, Auchu Polytechnic, Auchu, Edo State

Abstract

This study investigated the impact of non-performing loans of deposit money banks' (DMBs) performance in Nigeria within a period of twenty-one (21) years, that is 2001 to 2021. The study specifically examined the effect of non-performing loans on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria; and evaluated the extent to which provision for loan-losses have affected DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria. The study used secondary data obtained from annual financial statement of eight selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. The data generated were thematically analysed with the aid of ordinary least square and panel regression analysis. The findings of the study revealed that non-performing loans have unequivocally negative impact on the financial performance on DMBs in Nigeria, thus, reduces both return on assets and return on equity of the banks in Nigeria. The study therefore, offered recommendations including the need for banks to be more proactive and mindful of the provision for loan losses. Thus, this provision should be used as a strategic means for managing loans and ensuring effective prediction of loan behaviour within banks.

Keywords: Non-Performing loans, lending rate, loan-losses, loan behaviour

Introduction

Globally, the banking industry is primarily concerned with accepting deposits from the general public and making those deposits available to credit-worthy borrowers in the form of loans for purchases, investments, and other uses. According to Akinlo and Mofoluwaso (2014), bank credit often includes overdrafts, loans, advances, business funding agreements, local purchase order financing, etc. Thus, one of the core roles of deposit money banks (DMBs) is to provide bank credit, commonly known as lending. In essence, loans stand in for investments and are often included in banks' lengthened assets. People and organizations apply for loans. When a household's surplus of income over expenditure is negative, the households look to banks for loanable funds (Somoye, 2019). DMBs examine criteria such the purpose of the loan, liquidity risk, repayment mechanism, and source of repayment when making loans to people, households, businesses, and governments (Somoye, 2019). As a result, loans and advances made by DMBs are frequently of a temporary nature. This explains why the loan officers' effective and efficient credit analyses are what provide loan portfolios in DMBs their value. As a result, the responsibility of the credit expert is to ensure that loans authorized have a respectable qualitative composition.

In Nigeria, the CBN (2010) mandated through its practical guidelines that licensed banks review their credit portfolios continuously, at least once every quarter, in order to identify any deterioration in credit quality. Additionally, a credit facility should be deemed non-performing once any of the following conditions exist: (i) where interest or principal is due and unpaid for 90 days or more and interest payments equal to 90 days, (ii) interest or more have been capitalized rescheduled or rolled over into a new loan. Thus, they classified non-performing credit facilities into three categories namely, substandard, doubtful or lost (Biabani, Gilaninia & Mohabatkhah, 2012). Therefore, it is unnecessary to explain that sizable NPLs could have a detrimental impact on the level of private investment, raise deposit liabilities, and limit the availability of bank lending to the private sector. Bhattarai (2017) asserts that the failure of banks is the direct result of a high level of non-performing loans in the banking system. Given that the banking system serves as the hub around which other economic sectors operate, any shock to the system would undoubtedly have a detrimental impact on the economy as a whole. Due to significant non-performing loans and worsening cost of efficiency, several banks in emerging nations, including Nigeria, failed between the 1990s and the

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early 2000s (Podpiera & Weill, 2008). NPLs were determined to be a significant barrier to banks' profitability in both emerging countries and mature nations, as seen in their balance sheets (Abiola & Olausi, 2014).

According to Somoye (2019), over 10 percent of all loans granted in Nigeria between 1991 and 2018 were NPLs, and this upward tendency has significantly contributed to bank distress. In many instances, bank defaulting debtors were discovered to have abandoned their debt responsibilities and gone to other unknowing banks to get into fresh debt agreements, which were again likely to develop into nonperforming loans. Status updates on a bilateral basis were ineffective in identifying such suspect multiple loan defaulters. As a result, it has become essential to have a single information database from which to get the necessary combined credit information on borrowers. This led to the formation of the Credit Risk Management System by the Central Bank of Nigeria. There are basic economic functions that banks are supposed to carry out. To ensure an effective distribution of the deposits under their care, they must serve as financial intermediaries and facilitate the payment system. The term 'banking' today refers to the indigenous laws and practices of the geopolitical units and units that make up today's Nigeria (Ojo & Somoye, 2016). According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2010), modern banking began in Nigeria in the second half of the nineteenth century, when Elder Dempster began transferring money in specie from one region to another in an effort to expand the nation's shipping industry. As a result, the banking sector existed before Nigeria gained political independence. Many times, a significant buildup of non-performing loans has been linked to the incidence of banking sector failure due to insolvency (Fofack, 2005). The ownership structure, size, and operational reach of the Nigerian banking sector have changed throughout time. Eighty-nine (89) banks operated in Nigeria's banking system before it was consolidated in 2005. This system, known as the universal banking system (UBS), had no restrictions on the share capital investments that banks might make in other financial service industries. Due to the UBS's interconnected subsidiaries, other financial entities with banks as minority or majority shareholders proliferated, and the regulatory institution had supervisory bottlenecks. The development of the Global Financial Crisis (GFC) in 2007-2008 resulted in the decrease in oil prices and drastically reduced profits on investment in the oil industry. The banking system was put in a position of significant credit risk due to the accompanying capital outflow. As the number of non-performing loans increased and had negative economic effects, the asset quality of Nigerian banks drastically declined. The situation exacerbated as a result of the GFC's aftereffects, which caused the banks' non-performing loan (NPL) ratio to reach an all-time high of 37.3 percent in 2009. The banks' capacity to provide loans to the real sector was hampered by their toxic asset glut and severe liquidity issues. Many banks had to scale back operations and reduce spending in order to overcome the obstacles (Vardar & Ozguler, 2015). The borrower must make a cash payment to ensure that the outstanding unpaid interest does not exceed 90 days if: i) interest or principal is due and unpaid for 90 days or more; and ii) interest payment equal to 90 days or more have been capitalized, rescheduled, or rolled over into a new loan (except where facilities have been reclassified as performing). From this study, it can be seen that non-performing loans and bank return on assets in Nigeria primarily have an inverse connection (NDIC, 2018).

This study is anchored on the agency theory. Fadun (2013) asserts that the theory is predicated on the idea that bank managers, who act as agents in this situation, might engage in self-serving activities that could jeopardize the interests of stockholders. In a specific business transaction, the agent represents the principal and is responsible for acting in the principal's best interests, putting the interests of the principal before their own. The agency theory's principal-agent models can be roughly divided into three kinds, each reflecting a fundamental aspect of information asymmetry. The models with ex-post asymmetric information are the first class. After the principal and agent signed the contract, the agent in these models receives certain confidential information. They are referred to as 'moral hazard models.' The models with ex-ante asymmetric information belong to the second class. In these models, the agent already possesses confidential information before the contract is signed. Adverse selection models are what these models are called. The third class of signaling models is closely related. In these models, the informed agent may send the principal a signal that contained his personal information (Shadnam, 2014). Because the agent's ability to cover potential losses in the future is unpredictable, and because the principal is unaware of the needs and wants of the agents, the principal will design the contract to receive some profits from the agents. The principal wants to assign the contract in a way that increases his profit while paying the agent for carrying out the duty that is expected of him (Ibrahim, Saiful & Kayes, 2021).

Cundo, Pandoyo and Mohammad (2022) examined the effects of macroeconomic factors, including inflation projections, and bank-specific characteristics, such as return on asset, equity to asset ratio, and bank size. Data panel analysis was used to analyze the study. The study shows that non-performing loans are significantly impacted negatively by Return on Assets. While inflation has a beneficial impact on non-performing loans, equity to asset ratio and bank size have a large positive impact. Kamal (2022) investigates the impact of non-performing loans on profitability while controlling for operating effectiveness. Multiple regression, route analysis, and descriptive data analysis methods were employed. According to the

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study, non-performing loans have a little but positive impact on operating efficiency, whereas operating efficiency has a small but negative impact on profitability. The statistical analysis of the direct impact of non-performing loans on profitability demonstrates that, even in the presence of operating efficiency, non-performing loans have a negative and considerable influence on profitability. The study reveals that the relationship between NPL and ROA is unaffected by operating efficiency. But there is a statistically significant and unfavorable correlation between non-performing loans and profitability. In their study, Joseph & Okike (2021) assessed the effect of non-performing loans on Nigerian bank enterprises' profitability. For a period of ten (10) years, this study used secondary data from the NDI's Annual Report and Statement of Accounts (2010-2019). The statistical methods for regression were used to analyze the data. The outcome showed that there is no correlation between Nigerian banks' return on assets (ROA) and their non-performing loans (NPL). The maximization of shareholder value revealed a connection between Nigerian banks' NPL and Return on Equity (ROE).

Ozurumba (2016) investigated the effect of non-performing loans on the performance of a few commercial banks in Nigeria from 2000 to 2013. The analysis of the study's secondary data, which was derived from the annual reports and accounts of the chosen banks during the study period, used the ordinary least square method and ratio analysis. The findings showed that NPLs and bank performance as assessed by ROE had an adverse connection, with an increase in NPLs leading to a fall in ROE. The study came to the conclusion that the effects of NPLs on banks cannot be understated because they pose a serious danger to the banks' ability to continue operating as corporations.

Objectives of the Study

Therefore, the study specifically:

1. examines the effect of non-performing loans on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria;
2. evaluates the extent to which provision for loan-losses has affected DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria; and
3. ascertains whether lending rate has a significant influence on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study provides answers to the following research questions:

1. Do non-performing loans have effect on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria?
2. Does provision for loan-losses affect DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria?
3. Does lending rate have any significant influence on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria?

Methodology

The study employs a longitudinal research method, which is predicated on the fact that it includes repeated observations of the same variables throughout a 21-year period, from 2001 to 2021. The population of this study consists of all nineteen Nigerian deposit money banks that have been approved and are authorized on a national and international level by the Central Bank of Nigeria. As examples of international Authorization, there are Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc. While Citi Bank Nigeria Limited, Eco Bank Nigeria Plc, Heritage Bank Limited, Keystone Bank Limited, Polaris Bank Plc, Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc, Standard Chartered Bank Ltd, Sterling Bank Plc, Titan Trust Bank Limited, Unity Bank Plc and Wema Bank Plc are Deposit Money Banks with National Authorization. Out of the 19 deposit money banks in Nigeria operating between 2001 and 2021, the study uses eight (8) internationally licensed deposit money institutions as its sample. These include Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc. This is because for the study's study period, 2001 to 2021, official annual data on the study's variables may be obtained from the proper designated government institutions, including the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). In order to choose which cases to study, the study used judgmental sampling approaches. Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS) and Panel Data Regression were both used in the study's data analysis. In contrast to panel data regression, which covered the eight (8) chosen banks, pooled OLS covered the individual variable data. It is essential to compare the outcomes of the two methods. A panel data methodology was used in the study as well. The term 'fixed effect estimator' is therefore used to describe an estimator for the regression model's coefficients. The fixed effect model's generalized form can be found in;

$$Y_{it} = \delta_0 + \beta X_{it} + \mu_{it} + v_{it} \text{ ----- (ii)}$$

Where;

Y_{it} = dependent variable

δ_0 = intercept

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βx_{it} = vector of explanatory variable

μ_{it} = individual specific effect

v_{it} = error term

To determine whether the Random Effect Model or Fixed Effect Model is most appropriate for the study, the Hausman Test was employed. The generalized form of the fixed effect model is given by;

MODEL 1

$$ROA = F(NPL, PLL, LDR) \text{-----(iv)}$$

MODEL 11

$$ROE = F(NPL, PLL, LDR) \text{----- (v)}$$

While the econometric form of the model is:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NPL_{it} + \beta_2 PLL_{it} + \beta_3 LDR_{it} + e_{it} \text{----- (vi)}$$

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NPL_{it} + \beta_2 PLL_{it} + \beta_3 LDR_{it} + e_{it} \text{----- (vii)}$$

i = cross-sectional variables from 1, 2, 3-----21

t = time series variables from 1, 2, 3 -----21

e = error term

Where;

ROA_{it} = Return on Assets of bank i at the end of year t proxy for bank performance.

ROE_{it} = Return on Equity of bank i at the end of year t proxy for bank performance.

NPL_{it} = Non-performing loans of bank i at the end of year t

NPL = Non-performing loan

Total Loan

PLL_{it} = Provision for loan losses

Provision for loan loss = Pre-Tax Income + Loan Loss Provision / Net Charge Offs.

LDR_{it} = Lending Rate

Lending Interest Rate = Principal x Rate x Time.

Theoretical expectation is depicted as: $\beta_1, \beta_3 < 0$ and $\beta_2 > 0$

β_0 is to take care of the Constant Variable, β_1 is the coefficient of Non-Performing Loans (NPL) which is less than zero ($\beta_1 < 0$). This is because it is expected to be negatively related to Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). β_2 is the coefficient of Provision for Loan losses (PLL) which is expected to be greater than zero ($\beta_2 > 0$). That is a positive relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigeria is expected. While β_3 is the coefficient of Lending Rate (LDR) which is expected to be less than zero ($\beta_3 < 0$). That is, a negative relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigeria is expected. That is a negative relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigerian is expected. This study will use Return on Assets, Return on Equity and net profit margin to capture its dependent variable depicting banks' performance in Nigeria.

Results

Research Question 1

Does provision for loan-losses affect DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Data

<i>Variable</i>	Mean	Max.	Min.	Std. Dev.	Skew.	Kurt.	J-B	Prob.	Obs.
<i>ROA</i>	2.02	34.87	-31.06	4.00	-0.04	56.36	19928.20	0.00	168
<i>ROE</i>	0.37	4.73	-0.47	0.71	3.98	19.23	2286.39	0.00	168
<i>NPL</i>	8.22	41.07	0.88	8.62	1.97	6.45	191.81	0.00	168
<i>PLL</i>	14.33	37.47	-28.00	7.23	-2.37	17.02	1533.27	0.00	168
<i>LDR</i>	63.30	102.31	15.44	18.87	-0.17	2.14	6.05	0.05	168

Source: Authors' computations, 2022

Average non-performing loan ratio (i.e., ratio of the amount of non-performing loans to total loan disbursement) is 8.22, suggesting that about 8.2 percent of loans by deposit money bank selected in the study is lost within the reporting year on average. Thus, banks in Nigeria are performing less effectively in terms of loan administration with the attendant high loan losses in the system. The mean value of NPL is generally positively skewed at 1.97, indicating that more of the non-performing

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loans recorded by the banks in our sample are generally less than the reported mean value. However, there are large values of non-performing loans among the banks in the sample, with maximum value of non-performing loan of 41.07 percent. This shows that there are banks in Nigeria that have excessive non-performing loan ratios, and this is quite appalling for these banks. The standard deviation value for the non-performing loan ratio variable is higher than the mean value, which indicates that there is a high level of divergence in the non-performing loan conditions of banks in Nigeria. Average ratio of provision for loan to total loans disbursed is 14.33, indicating that 14 percent of loan disbursed are predicted to be bad loans. This is a high loan failure rate in the banking system in Nigeria. There are different perspectives to this condition in the banking system in Nigeria, including weak internal loan management systems and the ever-present macroeconomic instability that exacerbate the tendency for loan failure in the economy. In relation to this outcome, average loan to deposit ratio (LDR) is 63.3 percent. Given that this variable shows the level of risk-taking by these DMBs, the high LDR shows that more banks are taking high risks in terms of loan disbursement in Nigeria, especially in relation to their liquidity conditions.

For the macroeconomic and policy variables, average inflation rate is also 12.2, which is double digits, with maximum value at 23.79 percent. These are high inflation values for the country and also underscore the risk of difficult loan repayments over the years. Interest rate is 15.8 percent on average with a standard deviation of 4.3, suggesting that the mean value is relatively representative among the economies. Average interest rate is higher than average inflation rate (as to be expected), thus demonstrating that the macroeconomic stability matters for ensuring stable bank lending activities. The Jarque-Bera statistics for all the variables are all significant at the 5 percent level, which shows the absence of normality in their respective data distributions. This outcome is to be expected since a panel of different banks was adopted for the datasets. Hence, the result shows that bank-level characteristics may be exerting strong heterogeneous influences for the behaviour of the datasets. This is a strong basis for providing a panel-form analysis in the regression process for the study.

The variables in the study are also considered in terms of the individual banks in order to highlight the main banks that provide strong dimensions in the data series. The mean and standard deviation of the variables are reported in Table 2. It is seen that the average ROA is highest for Guarantee Trust Bank and Access Bank at 3.8 percent and 3.37 percent respectively. On the other hand, Union Bank had the lowest ROA for the banks at 0.24 percent. Surprisingly, Union Bank also has the highest standard deviation value for the ROA variable, indicating that the bank experienced the highest level of instability in the ROA over the period of the study. UBA has the highest average ROE, indicating that the banks performed better than the others in terms of management of shareholders' funds. Again, Union Bank had the least ROE value of 0.07 on average, which therefore shows that the bank had the least financial performance indicators over the period of the study. For the non-performing loans, the ratio is highest for Union Bank at 14.72 percent. This outcome gives some indication that the bank with the highest non-performing loans also had the poorest financial performance ratios in Nigeria. In terms of loan risk taking however, Access Bank had the highest indication at 74.74 for the loan to deposit ratio, while First Bank was recorded as the biggest bank in the sample as shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Individual Banks

Bank	ROA		ROE		NPL	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. De.
Access Bank	3.37	7.26	0.14	0.10	6.81	4.79
Fidelity Bank	1.31	1.12	0.16	0.13	10.92	9.53
First Bank Holding	1.80	1.11	0.34	0.22	13.54	12.43
First City Monumental Bank	1.39	1.14	0.31	0.42	6.51	7.10
Guaranty Trust Bank	3.80	0.82	0.39	0.57	4.84	3.90
Union Bank of Nig	0.24	8.08	0.07	0.18	14.72	10.79
United Bank for Africa	1.57	0.78	1.05	1.50	5.49	5.62
Zenith Bank	2.67	0.70	0.45	0.83	2.93	1.42
	PLL		LDR			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.		
Access Bank	15.29	4.81	74.74	15.44		
Fidelity Bank	13.80	6.46	65.52	16.75		

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First Bank Holding	12.99	4.93	59.84	10.17
First City Monumental Bank	16.59	4.93	71.32	19.42
Guaranty Trust Bank	16.65	3.25	73.55	18.24
Union Bank of Nig	13.27	16.23	55.76	19.93
United Bank for Africa	11.31	3.64	45.44	15.18
Zenith Bank	14.71	3.29	60.19	16.59

Source: Authors' computations, 2022

Only GTB and Zenith Banks exhibited relatively upward trends in their NPL for the period. This shows that these banks have been having some form of increases in the NPL for the period, although the general ratio is very low for the banks, when compared to banks like Union, Fidelity and First Banks. Thus, it appears that banks with relatively low NPL are those that are experiencing some form of increase over the years. Banks like FCMB, UBA and Access have done quite well in bringing down their NPL from high levels to very low levels over the years. On the other hand, there are strong fluctuations in the NPL of banks like Union, Zenith and First Bank. Generally, the trends in Nigerian banks indicate that there are heavy fluctuations in the rate of non-performing loans, while many banks have succeeded in bringing down their NPL between 2001 and 2021.

Research Question 2

Do non-performing loans, provision for loan losses and Lending rate have significant effect on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria (ROA)?

The results of the fixed and random effects model for return on assets as the bank performance variable are presented in table 3. It can be seen that the goodness of fit statistics has improved drastically over the pooled OLS estimates in each of the estimations. The goodness of fit statistics values is also better in the fixed effects estimates than in the random effects estimates. The adjusted R-squared value in the fixed effects estimates shows that about 60 percent of systematic variations in ROA for the banks are captured in the model with control, while 63 percent is captured in the model without control. Thus, the focus of the analysis in this study is on fixed effect estimations.

Table 3: Panel Regression Result for the ROA Equation

Variable	<i>Fixed effects</i>				<i>Random effects</i>			
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
Constant	10.534	0.00	8.965	0.00	8.952	0.02	7.504	0.05
NPL	-0.042	0.00	-0.022	0.04	-0.076	0.05	-0.055	0.16
PLL	--	--	0.053	0.00	--	--	0.091	0.05
LDR	-0.002	0.59	-0.005	0.30	0.008	0.68	-0.005	0.79
R-sq.	0.634		0.66		0.062		0.085	
Adj. R-sq.	0.603		0.63		0.027		0.045	
F-stat.	21.502		20.49157		1.761		2.134	

Source: Authors' Computations, 2022

The focus is on the particular contribution of the individual variables to return on asset (ROA) of the banks. This is done by considering the signs and significance of the coefficient of the explanatory variables. In the result, the coefficient of NPL is negative and significant at the 1 percent level in the estimates without PLL and passes the significance test at the 5 percent level for the estimates with PLL (although the coefficient is negative). This result shows that non-performing loans have a significant negative impact on the return on assets of DMBs in Nigeria. The effect of NPL is however stronger for the estimates without PLL than for estimates with PLL included. Thus, the result suggests that the debilitating effect of non-performing loans on ROA is weaker when the provisions for loan losses are not taken into cognizance.

The effectiveness of loan loss provision in boosting ROA of the DMBs is observed by considering that the coefficient of PLL in the model, which is positive and significant at the 1percent level. This result shows that provision for loan losses tend to lead to improvement in ROA of the banks. Thus, banks with effective loan loss provision management tend to perform better in terms of ROA than banks without this mechanism. The coefficient of loan to deposit ratio fails the significance test at the 5 percent level in both estimates, indicating that credit risk-taking of banks does not significantly affect their ROA in Nigeria. This implies that although such risk taking may directly influence the direction of non-performing loans for the DMBs, its direct impact on ROA is not significant. The coefficient of bank size is significant at the 1 percent level for both estimates.

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This shows that the size of banks matter for their ROA performance. Essentially, bigger banks are shown to exhibit lower financial performance in terms of return on assets.

For the other external factors in the model, the result shows that the impact of interest rate and inflation rate on ROA of the banks are both insignificant since the coefficients of both variables fail the significance test even at the 5 percent level. Thus, the two factors which are external to the banks are shown as irrelevant in terms of explaining the ROA of the banks over the period of the analysis. Rising interest rates may lead to more incidences of non-performing loans, but they do not influence the ROA of the banks. In the same vein, price changes are shown to be weak in influencing the pattern of return on assets of the DMBS in Nigeria.

Research Question 3

Do non-performing loans, provision for loan losses and Lending rate have significant effect on DMBS' financial performance in Nigeria (ROE)?

The section presents the results of the estimates of the impact of NPL and other variables on ROE of the banks. The adjusted R-squared values for the fixed effects estimates are also larger than those of the pooled OLS and the random effects estimates. This again justifies the efficiency of the fixed effects approach to the estimation for this study. The important focus of the analysis is on the coefficients of the explanatory variables. In the results, the coefficient of NPL is significant at the 1 percent level and is negative. This result supports the outcome of the ROA equation and shows that non-performing loans unequivocally lead to decline in the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria. The negative impact is the same for both the estimates with PLL and without PLL, indicating that the presence of PLL does not influence the impact of NPL on ROE of DMBS in Nigeria. This is unlike the outcome of the ROA equation. The coefficient of PLL in the model is positive and significant at the 1 percent level. This also shows that provision for loan losses has a significant positive impact on the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria, irrespective of the measure of performance used.

Table 4: Panel Regression Result for the ROA Equation

Variable	Fixed Effects				Random Effects			
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
C	0.985	0.00	0.947	0.00	1.152	0.06	1.171	0.07
NPL	-0.006	0.00	-0.006	0.00	-0.016	0.02	-0.016	0.02
PLL			0.003	0.19			-0.001	0.90
LDR	-0.005	0.00	-0.006	0.00	-0.014	0.00	-0.014	0.00
R-squared	0.469		0.473		0.144		0.144	
Adj.R-squared	0.425		0.425		0.112		0.106	
F-statistic	10.476		9.806		4.505		3.840	

Source: Authors' Computations, 2022

The coefficient of the LDR passes the significance test at the 1 percent level. This shows that the loan risk-taking activities of the DMBS significant limit the return on equity of the banks. Thus, although this risk taking does not affect the asset quality management of the banks, this study shows that it directly reduces the return on equity or the management of shareholders' funds among the banks. Thus, risks on loans are shown to directly be linked to lower shareholders' value rather than asset management of the banks in Nigeria. This is an important aspect of this study where it is demonstrated that risk taking on loans may not influence the asset quality or internal operational management of the banks but the shareholders' funds in the banks. Essentially, there is evidence that the agency problem between the shareholders and the managers is critically triggered when bank managers engage in risking loan management activities. This is because the managers are shown to be prone to pushing the effects on non-performing loans to shareholders' interests rather than directly on the asset management of the banks. The coefficient of both monetary policy rate and inflation rate also fail the significance tests at the 5 percent level. This shows that, just like ROA, the external macroeconomic factors do not have significant impact on the return to equity of DMBS in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study shows that non-performing loans have strong direct and unequivocal negative impact on financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria. This finding is in line with studies by Ibitomi & Micah (2021), and Somoye (2019). The presence of a provision for loan losses in the bank, however, mitigates the unfavorable impacts. The financial performance

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indicator of ROA makes this particularly pertinent. Essentially, the conclusion implies that rising non-performing loans affect banks' returns on assets or operational efficiency more severely when loan loss provisions are low. Non-performing loans have a minimal and ineffective influence on ROA when there is a loan loss reserve. This study has shown that loan loss provisions have the ability to reduce the negative effects of non-performing loans on the ROA of DMBs in Nigeria, which is a highly significant finding. These results are consistent with Abdulai, Ahmad and Ajape (2022), Olszak, Chodnicka-Jaworska, Kowalska and Witaa (2018), Arajo, Lustosa and Paulo (2018) and Arbak (2017) who found that loan loss provision, is fundamentally counter-cyclical in Nigeria during times of financial crisis.

Conclusion

The influence of non-performing loans and other associated elements of the Nigerian banking system on the financial performance of these institutions were explored in this study. In order to ensure improvements in performance for the banks in the sampled nations, it has been demonstrated that reducing the non-performing loans in connection to loan and cash management is essential. The study also shows that, despite the fact that increased provisions for loan losses can be a bank's strategic move in projecting default and overall loan failure, these provisions have a negative impact on profitability in Nigeria's banking industry. In essence, risk-controlling in credit activities is a crucial issue in the banking sector, necessitating that bank managers and professionals develop strategic solutions for liquidity management that can reduce credit risks and bad debts. Also, the study has demonstrated that how non-performing loans affect bank financial performance is influenced by how the banks manage their loan loss provisions. Therefore, banks should take a more proactive approach and pay attention to the loan loss provision. These provisions should essentially be used as a strategic tool for controlling loans and guaranteeing accurate loan behavior forecast inside the institutions.

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Assessment of Reading Habits between Male and Female English Students in Federal College of Education Kano State, Nigeria

***Danfulani, A. Nafisah¹**

Email: naffylani@yahoo.com

Tel: 08034004691

Ibrahim, Rakiya Usman²

Email: ruibrahim08@gmail.com

Tel: 08065404756.

Musa, Alhassan Abubakar Ph.D.³

Email: alhassanabubakar73@yahoo.com

Tel: 08065497719.

¹Department of English, Federal College of Education, Zaria

²Federal College of Agricultural Produce Technology.

³Department of Arts Education, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba.

Abstract

This research assessed reading habits between male and female English students in Federal College of Education Kano State. This study adopted survey research method with a total population of 420. With the aid of simple sampling techniques, 172 was sampled and participated in the study. The researchers administered 210 questionnaires but after editing and those with incomplete or unlikely response were rejected final copies utilized were 172. Chi-square was used to analyze the data obtained. The result shows that habits follow gender line with regards to the time spent for reading. The paper concluded that both male and female students were involved in reading and sex was found to be influential in the time and duration they choose to read. It is therefore recommended that provision of light in the evening be improved from 3 hours to six so as to encourage all students to read more

Keywords: Reading, Habit, Gender, Academic success.

Introduction

Undergraduate students on campuses across the nation read in order to pass their exams. For this to happen, however, decisions have to be taken as to where to read, what time to read and how much time to spend reading as their reading habits has become a tropical issue for school authorities. Therefore, the pertinent questions here are: “where do undergraduates students living in the campus prefer to go to and read? What time of the day and for how long?” A typical campus may provide an array of places that encourage students to go to read, but students are known to improvise places that are either inconvenient or devoid of necessary facilities. A serious undergraduate student has long discovered the importance of reading since secondary school days. Reading is indeed essential not only for academic success but also for intellectual growth, Steve (2018). However, reading requires sustained, focused attention that demands powers of memory and imagination. It is quite unlike watching television, video games or even surfing the internet that are considered passive activities. In fact, reading forces the individual to think as he works his brain out, while watching only allows him to escape. Reading therefore cannot be said to be an easy job at all. Perhaps as a result of this, college of education students of nowadays do not seem to read as much as they should. Consequently, they do not seem to believe in the role that reading plays in the development of one’s life, including academic success on the campus.

Ideally, College of education students are supposed to read hard in order to pass their exams. Evidence from campuses however suggests that the amount of reading they engage in leaves much to be desired (Besty, 2015). Lecturers across the nation have raised alarm at various fora about the unpreparedness of students before lectures

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and even during exams. Reading assignments during sessions are equally not taken seriously by the students, and submission dates for term papers and assignments are widely flouted with impunity. The refrain, not only in Nigeria but worldwide, is that this generation of students are not exactly serious when it comes to reading. These students are strangers to point of reference and underlying cadences that govern the development of written English (Charles, 2020). Although there is little research on students' reading and studying habits, many students have characteristics that put them at risk of academic failure. David (2016), said many of them find themselves in the colleges of education without the necessary skills to read or write even simple composition. And neither is their comprehension any better. However, this situation should not be allowed to continue and efforts to redress must be explored. Among these is the need to first understand the reading habits of these students.

One other reason for the fall in reading habit is said to be the distractions faced by students all over the country. Peter (2021) opined that recreational activities like sport and passive ones like TV and video games have indeed eaten deep into the spare time of students. So does the advent of the cell phone and the internet. Add these to the additional responsibilities heaped on students and the reason for inadequate reading will be pretty obvious. But Esther (2013), found the opposite to be true. Students do have tremendous leeway in their leisure activities and do have sufficient time available to study. According to this researcher, students are choosing not to spend time reading or studying by engaging in escapist activities like chatting on the net, then watching TV and playing video games. As a direct result of this, many students today are not strong readers and they regularly report that they don't like to read. And this apply to both leisure and for exams reading.

Poor reading habits at tertiary institutions may have deep causes that go back to early childhood experiences. The ability to read cannot be acquired overnight much less sustaining it over time. Studies have shown that catching them young may be the best strategy to inculcate sustainable reading habits. Dickson (2017) found that children who were already readers prior to beginning school came from homes in which literacy was engaged. He stated that one activity that was consistently found in the home of early readers was reading. Such children therefore came from homes in which family members read and one in which the children were read to and encouraged to read on regular basis. Lami, (2018) said this habit once internalized translate into a lifelong ability to read. It follows then that where this early childhood training was not developed, individuals would have little or no tendency to read. This may be one of the reasons for the non-reading behavior of college of education students in Nigeria today. Commenting on the reading habits of American students in the Washington Post, Charles (2010) wrote that "we have a generation of young adults away from home for the first time, free to enjoy the most experimental place of their lives, yet they are choosing books like 13 years old girl". But at least they are reading something when compare to most Nigeria NCE students who hardly read at all.

The blame for poor reading habits may not be heaped on parents alone. Schools equally share some portion of the blame. Schools needs to encourage students to do voluntary recreational reading which in itself can foster academic reading. Monsteve (2017) and Lami (2018), argue that low level of voluntary reading may be due to the fact that most school reading instructions are oriented to skill building and preparation for standardized tests with little overt reading for enjoyment. To the best knowledge of the researchers, not much research has been conducted on the reading habits and behaviour of college of education students in the country (Gimba, 2011). However, it is well known that reading is the cornerstone for success not just academically but throughout life. A study conducted by Gimba (2011), found evidence that supported this assumption and established correlation between reading and Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) for students of both sexes. However, despite the obvious implication of this finding, concerns have been raised in several quarters about the declining reading habits by college of education students in Nigeria. Extant studies conducted by Muri (2016) showed students' inadequate reading and study skills among both public and private tertiary institutions. This trend appears to be worldwide as complaints emanate from all countries. The inadequacy in reading affects not only reading for leisure but also for academic success. On campuses across the nation, there seems to be a latent belief among students that one can as well pass exams without doing much reading (John, 2016). A little reading, the cliché goes, could just be enough to see one through his exams (Lami, 2018). Indeed, a common observation by many lecturers is that students do not seem particularly

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motivated to read on a regular basis. Many students come to class unprepared and more often than not postpone any reading until the night before the exam. This problem is irritating and frustrating for many teachers and school administrators. It is against the above backdrop that this study investigates where, when and for how long students in College of Education Kano read. These points could serve as a starting point for any action towards encouraging students to read more in our colleges of education.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to determine the reading habits of male and female students of English in Federal College of Kano. The specific objectives are

1. to identify the preferred reading place among male and female English students in Federal College of Education
2. to examine the preferred reading duration among male and female English students in Federal College of Education.
3. To determine the preferred reading time among male and female English students in Federal College of Education

Research Questions

4. What is the preferred reading place among male and female English students in Federal College of Education?
5. What is the preferred reading duration among male and female English students in Federal College of Education?
6. What is the preferred reading time among male and female English students in Federal College of Education?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the above objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were framed for the study:

1. H₀₁: There is no significant different on preferred reading place between male and female English students in Federal College of Education
2. H₀₂: There is no significant difference on preferred reading duration between male and female English students in Federal College of Education
3. H₀₃: There is no significant difference on preferred reading time between male and female English students in Federal College of Education?

Methodology

The final year NCE students of school of languages in first semester of 2021 represented the population and were surveyed. Being in their final year, this body of students were thought to be the most avid readers in the school of languages. School has an enrolment of 210 students in year 300 levels in four areas of specialization namely: English, Hausa, Arabic and French. Therefore, the population of the study consists of 300 level English students during the 2021/2022 academic session. A questionnaire was developed for this study and 15 minutes is required for its filling. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed during class place. The students were first briefed about the research and were assured that their responses would remain anonymous and confidential. The copies of the questionnaire were given out and collected back after completion before the end of the class place. A total of 4 questions were completed by each student. The data were summarized and percentages were calculated. Chi-square test was also carried out on the data for three of the questions with a view to finding whether significant relationship exists between male and female on the one hand and place, time and place for reading, on the other. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions while inferential statistics of chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The alpha value was set at 5% or 0.05 and the P-value provided. The usual decision rule for chi-square test applies to this study. That is we accept the null hypothesis (H₀) or reject the alternate hypothesis (H₁) if calculated value is less than the table value, and we reject the H₀ and accept the H₁ if the calculated value is greater than the table value.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference on preferred reading place between male and female English students in Federal College of Education

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Table 1: Chi-Square Test of difference on preferred reading place between male and female English students

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.000 ^a	1	.938
Likelihood Ratio	8.318	1	.216
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.640	1	.200
N of Valid Cases	2		

a. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.

Source: Author's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

The chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance obtained from the chi-square mathematical and statistical table is 0.0039. Since the Pearson chi-square value which is 0.938 is greater than the chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance which is 0.0039, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that there is no significant different on preferred reading place between male and female English students in Federal College of Education. Since we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis, we conclude that there is significant difference between reading habits of male and female English students and their preferred place for reading. This means a reading habits of male and female English students does not dictate the place where a student goes to read.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference on the preferred reading duration between male and female English student in Federal College of Education.

Table 2: Chi-Square Test of difference on the preferred reading duration between male and female English student

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.000 ^a	1	.724
Likelihood Ratio	8.318	1	.216
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.640	1	.200
N of Valid Cases	2		

a. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.

Source: Author's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

The chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance obtained from the chi-square mathematical and statistical table is 0.0039. Since the Pearson chi-square value which is 0.724 is greater than the chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance which is 0.0039, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on the preferred reading duration between male and female English student in Federal College of Education. Since we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis, we conclude that there is significant differences between reading habits of male and female English students and their preferred time for reading. This means a reading habits of male and female English students dictates the time of the day or night when he or she goes to read.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant different between male and female students of English and the amount of time spent reading.

Table 3: Chi-Square Test different between male and female students of English and the amount of time spent reading

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.000 ^a	1	.801
Likelihood Ratio	8.318	1	.216
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.640	1	.245
N of Valid Cases	2		

a. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.

Source: Author's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

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The chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance obtained from the chi-square mathematical and statistical table is 0.0039. Since the Pearson chi-square value which is 0.801 is greater than the chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance which is 0.0039, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between male and female students' of English and the amount of time spent reading. Since we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis, we conclude that there is significant difference between reading habits of male and female English students and the amount of time they spend reading. The alternate hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The null hypothesis one which states that there is no significant relationship between reading habits of male and female English students' and their preferred place for reading was accepted after Chi-square test. The test revealed that the calculated value χ^2 (0.938) was less than the table value (0.0039) and therefore we reject the null hypothesis. In other words, reading habits of male and female English students does not dictate where students go to read. This finding is in line with Leary (2014) who opined that male and female place of reading has no significant bearing with their academic performance.

The null hypothesis two which states that there is no significant relationship between reading habits of male and female English students and their preferred time for reading was rejected after Chi-square test. The test revealed that the calculated value χ^2 (0.724) was greater than the table value (0.0039); we reject the null hypothesis. In other words, reading habits of male and female English students dictates the time of the day when students go to read. This finding is also in line with the research conducted by Gimba (2011) who concluded that male and female English students determine the time to read.

Null hypothesis three which states that there is no significant relationship between reading habits of male and female English students and the amount of time spent reading was accepted after the Chi-square test. The test revealed that the calculated value of χ^2 (0.801) was less than the table value (0.0039) we reject the null hypothesis. In other words, reading habits of male and female English students does not dictate the amount of time students spent reading. However, this finding is slightly different from the research conducted by lami (2018) who concluded that reading habit of male and female do dictate to some extent the amount of time students spends reading

Conclusion

This paper set out to assess the reading habits of students of English language, Federal college of Education Kano. Both male and female students were involved and gender was found to be influential in the time they chose to study, but not so with regard to place and amount of time they spent reading. It appears that girls preferred evenings for their reading while boys preferred night time. This implies that overall, students prefer to read between 6:00pm to midnight, a place that necessarily requires availability of light.

Recommendations

Based on the above, the following recommendations are made;

1. School authorities should endeavor to make light available during this peak place for reading. This should be from 6:00pm to at least 11:00pm so as to allow a six hours stretch. Such a stretch will go a long way in encouraging more reading among students.
2. School can successfully encourage reading generally by initiating school based programmes in which time is set aside daily for compulsory leisure and academic reading.
3. conducive atmosphere must readily be made available.

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Assessment on utilization of instructional strategies for Physics teaching among government secondary school Teachers in Oyo state

Adewuyi, Adejoke Serah¹

Email: serahjoke@gmail.com

Tel: 07069404118

Akanbi, Abdulrasaq Oladimeji²

Email: akanbi.ao@unilorin.edu.ng

Tel: 08033780316

¹Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

²Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract

The study examined the assessment on utilization of instructional strategies for Physics teaching among government secondary school Teachers in Oyo state. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school physics teachers in Oyo state during the 2021/2022 academic session. 343 (Male 189; Female 154) physics teachers makes up the sample size of the study. The sample size was arrived at by using a descriptive design. A researcher-designed questionnaire titled “Methods Used for Teaching Senior School Physics Questionnaire (MUTSSPQ)”. was used, the reliability coefficient of the instrument 0.67 was obtained. Data were analysed using mean and rank order to answer research question while t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were employed to test the hypothesis at significance level of 0.05. Findings revealed that discussion method, demonstration method, assignment method, Physical laboratory method, simulation method and cooperative method were always used while analogies and Anecdotes, science at home, guided discovery problems, competitive method, dramatization method, brainstorming, Socratic Method, lecture method, think-pair-share and peer method were sometimes used. It was concluded that the methods used by senior school Physics teachers regardless of gender and educational qualifications are similar. It was recommended that encouragement of the utilization of appropriate and inductive teaching methods is paramount for the effective teaching of physics at the senior secondary education level.

Keyword: teaching method; physics teacher; senior school

Introduction

Physics instruction involves more than just putting formulas on a whiteboard. By creating a learning environment where students may explore and comprehend how the physical world functions and connect challenging scientific topics to their everyday lives, it entails assisting students in developing new perspectives on the world (Vosniadou, 2019). The senior school physics curriculum is designed to equip students with the knowledge and competencies required to address challenges and make informed decisions in their daily lives. To thrive in a rapidly advancing scientific and technological society, students must possess knowledge, problem-solving acumen, creative thinking, and critical reasoning (Haruna & Hassan, 2017). Consequently, preparing students for the demands of everyday existence becomes paramount. However, Physics education has not always been carried out effectively, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria (Rosli & Phang, 2021). Many students in underdeveloped nations attempt to memorize solely mathematical formulas instead of developing the requisite conceptual knowledge while solving Physics issues, which leads to a woefully inadequate learning outcome in Physics (Bansal & Ramnarain, 2023). As a result, researchers such as (Ali, 2023; Gudyanga & Jita, 2019) have linked students' poor learning outcomes in Physics to the teaching method used by Physics teachers, (Asyari et al., 2022). According to these studies, some Physics teachers begin problem-solving exercises by writing formulae and manipulating mathematical equations to arrive at the solution without providing interpretation and explanations of Physics. Teachers emphasize active student participation in order to develop students' understanding during Physics problem-solving activities in a well-organized classroom instructional setting (Samormob & Phusawisot, 2020). Physics teachers have a challenging task since teaching Physics involves a lot of foundational tasks and the use of numerous instructional methods. The delivery of materials from the teacher to the students is known as a teaching method. It is a comprehensive design with methodical steps that incorporate a particular delivery method for the training (Goga & Şerban, 2018). When teaching Physics, teachers employ a variety of methods such as Inquiry Method

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(Acar & Tuncdogan, 2019), The Laboratory Method (Cevikbas et al., 2023), Simulation Method (Jones & Barrett, 2017), Discussion Method (Rajaguru & Park, 2021), Lecture Method, (Nordmann et al., 2021), Dramatization Method (Kauts (2021; Uguma & Obiekezie 2018) and Role Play Method (Goga & Şerban, 2018) just to mention a few, depending on the subject and the needs of the students, a variety of methods of instruction might be used. Each method has its strengths and weaknesses, and the effectiveness of each method depends on various factors such as the students' prior knowledge, the teacher's expertise, and the availability of resources. Different attitudes and cognitive styles that the students have in response to the subject being covered are the cause of the different teaching methods (Nja et al., 2019). According to Collet and Nakawa, (2022), there is a strong correlation between teaching methods, student personalities, and learning preferences. Therefore, Cervin-Ellqvist et al., (2020) explains that ineffective learning will occur if the teaching methods is not in line with the students' abilities and learning pace. A teaching method serves as a conduit for conveying instructional content from educators to learners. In the context of physics education, it becomes crucial for physics instructors to possess a profound understanding of effective methodologies to impart knowledge to their students. The significance of teaching methods is underscored by the insights provided by Edward and Approach is a comprehensive strategy with a systematic approach to delivering the materials' contents. Students who are studying physics benefit from engaging instruction that encourages critical thinking. Students that participate actively during the Physics instructional process as a result of the use of proper teaching strategies are better equipped to understand physics concepts. When teaching physics, teachers employ a variety of methods to effectively captivate students within the classroom environment and cultivate their critical thinking abilities (Haruna & Gurjiya 2022), educators have at their disposal an array of instructional approaches (Asysyifa et al., (2019). The choice of teaching methods is contingent upon the specific concept to be conveyed and the students' individual interests. Numerous methodologies have proven to be efficacious tools for enriching students' grasp of physics. Araujo and Matos (2017); Hussain et al., (2011), in their studies analysed two specific teaching approaches in teaching physics. Uwizeyimana et al., (2018) conducted a study across five secondary schools in the Rusizi District of Rwanda, focusing on exploring the impact of teaching approaches on effective physics learning. Chinyere and Ifeanacho (2013) sampling, a cohort of 190 physics and mathematics students from the first-year class in two coeducational senior high schools. Murphy et al., (2022) categories four distinct preferred teaching methods. According to research, instructors' thoughts and judgments on their teaching method competences and skills are influenced by their gender (Eichler et al., 2023). Studies conducted by (Aziz & Butt, 2022; Enang 2022; Murphy et al., 2022) on influence of teachers' gender on their chosen teaching methods did not reveal any significant gender disparities. Alnahdi and Schwab, (2023); Öz, (2022) in their studies submitted that Female teachers evidently outperformed male teachers in practices and attitudes. While studies conducted by Amedu (2015) reported that male teachers outperformed their female teachers.

In a study conducted by Koirala et al., (2020) shows that higher qualification teachers, as well as trained teachers, have more techniques and skills of teaching, using methods, materials, evaluation scheme, feedback and other extra activities than the lower qualification and untrained teachers. The educational qualification of secondary school teachers does not affect their teaching competency (Ahmad & Khan, 2016). In another study of Pratibha (2017) opined that teachers' educational qualification and sex did not affect the overall teaching competency of teachers whereas teachers' educational qualification and sex had a significant influence on some aspects of teaching competency. It is against this background that it is important to examine the assessment on utilization of instructional strategies for Physics teaching among government secondary school Teachers and its influence on the moderating variables (gender, qualification and experience).

The methods and processes involved in imparting and acquiring knowledge of physics have generated significant debate among stakeholders. Many teachers, though, are ill-equipped to experiment with teaching physics in ways other than the conventional ones. Additionally, there have been several complaints that using a single method to teach various physics concepts prevents students from developing the necessary problem-solving skills in the classroom. As a result, students have been seen having difficulty understanding physics concepts, which gives rise to 'poor academic performance in physics and has been largely attributed to the methods used in physics classroom instructional delivery. Few studies have examined different teaching strategies such as the traditional teacher-centered method (Uwizeyimana et al., 2018), peer instruction and modelling instruction (Araujo & Matos, 2017) Scientific scientific inquiry vs. traditional lecture (Hussain et al., 2011). However, none of the aforementioned studies used a large population, were conducted in Oyo State, or took cognizance of the interventions of gender, teaching qualifications, or experience. Hence, it is worthwhile to assess the utilization of instructional strategies for physics teaching among government secondary school teachers in Oyo State, looking at such intervening variables as gender, teaching qualification, and experience.

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Objectives of the study:

4. Investigate the most common choice of instructional strategy among physics teachers in oyo state.
5. Assess the extent at which choice of instructional strategy have effect on male and female physics teachers in oyo state.
6. Examine the extent at which choice of instructional strategy have effect on teachers' qualification in oyo state.
7. Determine the extent at which choice of instructional strategy have effect on teachers' experience in oyo state.

Research Questions:

4. Which is the most common choice of instructional strategy among physics teachers in oyo state?
5. To what extent does choice of instructional strategy have effect on male and female physics teachers in oyo state?
6. To what extent does choice of instructional strategy have effect on teachers' qualification in oyo state?
7. To what extent does choice of instructional strategy have effect on teachers' experience in oyo state?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference between choice of instructional strategy on male and female physics teachers in oyo state.
2. There is no significant difference between choice of instructional strategy on teachers' qualification in oyo state.
3. There is no significant difference between choice of instructional strategy on teachers' experience in oyo state.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This aimed at describing the methods that are being used for teaching Physics at the secondary school level. This survey type was appropriate for this study as it enable the researcher to have a direct contact with the sample population that has the characteristics relevant to this work (Haruna, 2010). The use of descriptive design of survey type allowed the researcher to analyze facts and helps the researcher in developing an in-depth understanding of the research problem.

Population of the study consists of all Physics teachers in Senior Secondary schools across Oyo State during the 2021/2022 academic session. The specific focus was on public Physics teachers within the educational zone, Oyo State. 343 (Male189: Female154) physics teachers sampled makes up the sample size of the study. The sample size was arrived at by using purposive sampling technique.

A researcher-designed questionnaire was used for data collection in this study and titled "Methods Used for Teaching Senior School Physics Questionnaire (MUTSSPQ)". The questionnaire was split into sections A, B and C. Section A was used to gather the demographic data of the teachers such as gender, teaching qualification, and experience. Section B contained 25 items structured in a four-response-type of *always, sometimes, rarely and never* was used to gather data on the methods used for teaching senior school Physics. Section C contained glossary of teaching methods, in which the respondent was ask to indicate in the space provided, other teaching methods they used for classroom instructional delivery from the list of methods listed under glossary section.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the drafted questionnaire was given to three (3) lecturers from the Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, for the content validity of the instrument and the content validity index of 0.75 was obtained. The instrument was administered on 30 Physics teachers outside the proposed sampled population twice within an interval of three weeks using test re-test method, while Pearson's product-moment correlation was used to compare the two sets of scores. Thus, the reliability coefficient of 0.67 was obtained. The permission was sought from the authorities of the selected schools. The research assistants underwent an orientation to familiarize them with the study's objectives and the proper procedure for administering it to the participants. The approach employed for distributing the questionnaire copies in the selected schools was replicated for the collection process upon completion. To uphold ethical standards, the respondents were informed about the study's purpose, and the researchers assured them of the strict confidentiality of their responses. Upon the conclusion of the data collection exercise, genuine expressions of gratitude were conveyed to the authorities of the secondary schools that participated in the study. Top of Form Bottom of Form. The data gathered were subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using mean and rank order to answer research question one, while t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were employed to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05.

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Results

Table 1: Provide a Simple Descriptive Title for the Table

S/N	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
	Male	189	55.1
	Female	154	44.9
	Total	343	100.0

(Field Work, 2023)

Table 1 shows that out of 343 Physics teachers sampled for this study, 189 (55.1%) of them were males while 154 (44.9%) were females. Thus, the majority of Physics teachers sampled were males.

Table 2: Distribution of Participants by Qualification

S/N	Qualifications	Frequency	Percentage
	NCE	38	11.1
	BSc.	56	16.3
	BSc. (Ed.)	137	39.9
	M.Sc. / M.Ed.	69	20.1
	Others	43	12.5
	Total	343	100.0

(Field Work, 2023)

Table 2 reveals that 38 (11.1%) of the Physics teachers sampled for this study were NCE holders; 56 (16.3%) were B.Sc. holders; 137 (39.9%) were B.Sc. (Ed.) holders; 69 (20.1%) were M.Sc./ M.Ed. holders while 43 (12.5%) of the participants bagged other certificates. Thus, majority of the Physics teachers sampled for this study were BSc. (Ed.) holders.

Table 3: Distribution of Participants by Years of Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 5years	68	19.8
6 – 10years	215	62.7
More than 10years	60	17.5
Total	343	100.0

(Field Work, 2023)

Table 3 displays that 68 (19.8%) of the Physics teachers sampled were within 1 – 5years of teaching experience; 215 (62.7%) of them had taught for between six and ten years. while 60 (17.5%) of the Physics teachers had spent more than 10years in teaching service. Hence, majority of the Physics teachers sampled had taught for between six and ten years. To respond to the study questions, descriptive statistics of mean and rank were employed. The participants' responses on methods used for teaching Senior School Physics were subjected to item-by-item analysis of mean owing to the four-response format of the questionnaire's questions. Therefore, items whose mean scores closed to 1.0, 2.0, 3.0 and 4.0 were remarked as 'never', 'rarely', 'sometimes' and 'always' used respectively.

Research Question 1

Which is the most common choice of instructional strategy among physics teachers in Oyo state?

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Most Common Choice of Instructional Strategy Among Physics Teachers

S/N	Most Common Choice of Instructional Strategy Among Physics Teachers	Mean	Rank	Remark
4	Discussion Method	3.79	1 st	Always Used
9	Demonstrations	3.77	2 nd	Always Used
10	Assignment Method	3.72	3 rd	Always Used
1	Physical Laboratory Method	3.71	4 th	Always Used
3	Simulation Method	3.68	5 th	Always Used

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13	Cooperative Method	3.57	6 th	Always Used
16	Analogies and Anecdotes	3.38	7 th	Sometimes Used
25	Science at home	3.27	8 th	Sometimes Used
24	Guided Discovery Problems	3.13	9 th	Sometimes Used
12	Competitive Method	3.04	10 th	Sometimes Used
6	Dramatization Method	2.78	11 th	Sometimes Used
18	Brainstorming	2.65	12 th	Sometimes Used
7	Socratic Method	2.61	13 th	Sometimes Used
5	Lecture Method	2.59	14 th	Sometimes Used
14	Think-Pair-Share Method	2.57	15 th	Sometimes Used
19	peer teaching	2.52	16 th	Sometimes Used
20	Computation thinking method	2.34	17 th	Rarely Used
15	Story-Telling	2.21	18 th	Rarely Used
8	Field Trip/Excursion Method	2.06	19 th	Rarely Used
22	Science Quiz	1.79	20 th	Rarely Used
11	Resource Persons Method	1.43	21 th	Never Used
23	Fishbone	1.39	22 nd	Never Used
21	Reward discovery	1.37	23 rd	Never Used
2	Virtual Laboratory Method	1.31	24 th	Never Used
17	ICT Enabled Learning	1.28	25 th	Never Used

As revealed in Table 4, items ranked 1st, 2nd, up to 6th were always used for teaching Senior School Physics. This implies that discussion method, demonstration method, assignment method, Physical laboratory method, simulation method and cooperative method were *always* used for teaching Senior School Physics in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Also, items ranked 7th to 16th were *sometimes* used for teaching Senior School Physics. Thus, analogies and Anecdotes, science at home, guided discovery problems, competitive method, dramatization method, brainstorming, Socratic Method, lecture method, think-pair-share and peer methods were sometimes used for teaching Senior School Physics in Oyo State, Nigeria.

However, items ranked 17th to 20th and 21st to 25th were *rarely* and *never* used respectively for teaching Senior School Physics. Hence, computation thinking method, story-telling, field trip/excursion method and science quiz were *rarely* used while resource persons method, fishbone, reward discovery, virtual laboratory method and ICT Enabled Learning were *never* used for teaching Senior School Physics in Oyo State, Nigeria

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between choice of instructional strategy on male and female physics teachers in oyo state.

Table 5: t-test Statistics Showing the Difference in the Choice of Instructional Strategy on Male and Female Physics Teachers

Gender	No	Mean	S. D.	Df	t-value	Sig	Remark
Male	154	69.103	5.172	341	0.584	0.560	NS
Female	189	68.624	5.245				

*Insignificance at $p > 0.05$

Table 5 shows that the t-value 0.584 was attained with a p-value of 0.560 when computed at 0.05 alpha level. As a result of the p-value of 0.560 being higher than 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis one is retained. Therefore, no statistically significant difference existed in the methods used for teaching Senior School Physics based on gender.

Give a brief description of the statistics in Table 2 and show whether the analysis really tested the null hypothesis 1 or not. Explain whether the hypothesis should be rejected or retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between choice of instructional strategy on teachers' qualification in Oyo state.

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Table 6: ANOVA Summary of the difference in the choice of instructional strategy for teaching Physics based on teaching qualifications

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	511.347	4	127.837	2.271	.061
Within Groups	19026.834	338	56.292		
Total	19538.181	342			

Table 6 shows that the F -value of 2.271 with a p -value of 0.061 was obtained when computed at 0.05 alpha level. The null hypothesis two is preserved while the p -value of 0.061 has a significance level above 0.05. This suggests that there aren't any statistically significant differences between the methods used for teaching Senior School Physics and teaching qualifications.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between choice of instructional strategy on teachers' experience in Oyo state.

Table 7a: ANOVA Summary of the difference in the choice of instructional strategy for teaching Physics based on teachers experience

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	379.754	2	189.877	3.370	.036
Within Groups	19158.427	340	56.348		
Total	19538.181	342			

As revealed in Table 7a, the F -value of 3.370 with a p -value of 0.036 was obtained when computed at 0.05 alpha level. Given that the p -value of 0.036 is below 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis three is not retained. Consequently, this suggests that there was a statistically significant difference in the methods used for teaching Senior School Physics based on teaching experience ($F_{(2, 342)} = 3.370, p < 0.05$). After establishing a substantial difference between the means, which was shown in Table 7a, additional testing was done on the different combinations of means to determine the source of the discrepancy. The test was run at 0.05 alpha levels using Duncan's Post Hoc method. A statistical method called the Post Hoc is utilized to identify which of the many groups genuinely contributes to the difference. As shown in Table 7b, the difference seen in Table 7a was primarily caused by teachers with less than six to ten years of experience, who had the highest mean score (70.60), followed by those with experience of more than ten years (69.63), and those with less than one to five years of experience (68.06). As a result, teachers with 6 to 10 years of experience usually employ a variety of methods as opposed to those with more than 10 years and 1 to 5 years of experience.

Table 7b: Duncan's Post Hoc Pair-wise Comparisons of the Difference in the Choice of Instructional Strategy for Teaching Physics based on Teachers Experience

Teaching Experience	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
1 - 5years	68	68.0605	
More than 10years	60		69.6333
6 - 10years	215		70.6029
Sig.		.177	.405

Means for groups in symmetrical subsets are shown.

4. Sample size using the harmonic mean is 83.278.
5. The size of the groups varies. The group sizes' harmonic mean is employed. Type I error rates are not assured.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from this study revealed that discussion method, demonstration method, assignment method, Physical laboratory method, simulation method and cooperative method were *always* used for teaching Senior School Physics in Oyo State, Nigeria while analogies and Anecdotes, science at home, guided discovery problems, competitive method, dramatization method, brainstorming, Socratic Method, lecture method, think-pair-share and peer methods were *sometimes* used for teaching

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Senior School Physics in Oyo State, Nigeria. Since there is more to teaching physics than just putting formulas on a chalkboard, it entails applying variety of modern teaching methods that are prone to craft a setting for learning where students can investigate and comprehend how the physical world functions and aiding in the development of new perspectives among students. The paradigm of teaching physics has changed from a passive to an active production and interpretation of events. In order to create effective learning programs, teachers must learn to value the concepts that students bring to the classroom and comprehend the mechanisms through which conceptual change takes place. This conclusion is consistent with that of Tong et al., (2022), who found that students taught physics using the inductive method by their teachers demonstrated superior skills than those who were taught using the deductive method. On contrary, Tufail and Mahmood (2020) assert that secondary school science teachers prefer lecture and discussion methods for science teaching and are less interested in using the inquiry method and science project-based learning in their classrooms.

However, computation thinking method, story-telling, field trip/excursion method and science quiz were *rarely* used while resource persons method, fishbone, reward discovery, virtual laboratory method and ICT Enabled Learning were *never* used for teaching Senior School Physics in Oyo State, Nigeria. This finding corroborates Yuanyuan (2022) who revealed that teachers found it difficult to integrate suitable teaching methods in delivering their lessons. All the recommended teaching methods in Physics aim at a succession of well-structured experiences, ensuring that learning occurs as an activity while the student's mind is actively engaged. Methods like experimenting, inquiry, and conversation are typical of these. To ensure that learning occurs in the learners, physics teachers must adequately plan their lessons and provide excellent guidance. In the same vein, the outcomes of this study substantiate Huang (2022) as well as Blazar and Kraft (2016) whose study showed that there are a number of hindrances affecting teachers' integration of multiple teaching methods required for effectiveness of classroom instructional practices.

Also, findings obtained from this study revealed that no statistically significant difference existed in the methods used for teaching Senior School Physics based on gender. This indicates that male and female teachers used similar methods for teaching Senior School Physics. Gender is variable that plays an important role in teaching and learning. It alludes to the advantages and societal characteristics that are associated with gender. Distinct men and women in various countries are given distinct roles, attributes, and behaviors that are socially and culturally formed. This finding negates Hwang and Fitzpatrick (2021) whose study submitted that female teachers use integrated different teaching method in teaching than their males counterpart. This result is in line with Maqsood et al., (2018) whose study indicated that there is a significant difference between male and female teachers' methods of classroom management.

Given the influence of gender on teachers' usage of varieties of teaching methods, male teachers' methods appear to be less intrusive than those of female ones. Studies comparing the method of instruction, competencies and skills of instructors who are compared according to their genders provide a variety of outcomes in the literature. According to certain research, instructors' attitudes and impressions of their methods of instruction abilities and competences are influenced by their gender. This agrees with Shakir and Adeeb (2014) whose study provide evidence that the methods, abilities, and competences used by male and female teachers do not differ significantly. Previous studies have compassed the effectiveness of male instructors' lessons compared to those of female ones.

In addition, findings of this study showed that based on the teachers' qualifications, there were no statistically significant differences in the methods taken to teach senior school physics. This implies that Physics teachers regardless of their educational qualifications adopt comparable teaching methods in classroom instructional delivery in Oyo State, Nigeria. Enhancing the qualifications of Physics teachers through training has remained a focal point within global education systems. This emphasis is rooted in the perceived significance of robust training, as championed by Robinson, in shaping teacher performance. Undoubtedly, the effectiveness of teachers is intricately linked to the advancement of educational objectives that align with broader societal aspirations and challenges. Indeed, the outcomes of this study diverge from those of Hafeez (2021), who assessed the work performance of trained and untrained teachers and found that trained teachers exhibited superior performance. In contrast, Mueller's study (2022), which delved into the comparative efficacy of trained and untrained teachers, revealed no discernible variance in performance.

Furthermore, the findings of this study unveiled a noteworthy statistical discrepancy in the methods employed for teaching Senior School Physics, contingent upon the teachers' teaching experience. Therefore, teachers who were within 6 – 10years of experience always make use of a number of methods than those who had spent more than 10years and 1- 5years. The profile of teachers' experience has been attributed to their familiarities with skills or fields of knowledge acquired over years of actual classroom teaching practice which presumably resulted in superior understanding or mastery of the subject content and methods of instructional delivery. Hence, experience is knowledge or proficiency acquired by participation in or

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exposure to an event, issue, or topic to teaching given the years spent in teaching service. This study's findings substantiate studies such as Adedayo and Owolabi (2021) and Yasin (2021) all which submitted that use of various approaches for imparting instruction in their topic is influenced by their educational background and teaching experience.

Conclusion

It was concluded that the teaching methods always used by senior school Physics teachers are discussion method, demonstration method, assignment method, Physical laboratory method, simulation method and cooperative method. It also concluded that the methods used by senior school Physics teachers regardless of gender and educational qualifications are similar. However, discrepancy existed in the methods used by teachers due to their teaching experience. As a result, Physics teachers' profile of experience has been helpful in assisting them to familiarize with and integrate more methods into teaching given the skills or fields of knowledge acquired over years of classroom teaching practice which presumably resulted in superior understanding or mastery of the subject content and methods of instructional delivery.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proffered;

1. Encouragement of the utilization of appropriate and inductive teaching methods is paramount for the effective teaching of physics at the senior secondary education level.
2. Physics educators should consistently strive to incorporate a diverse range of teaching methods. These varied methodologies will foster a comprehensive understanding of Physics among students.
3. Eradicating gender disparities within the teaching profession is imperative. The promotion of gender equality among teachers is crucial for integrating contemporary teaching methods into the physics curriculum effectively.
4. The Ministry of Education should bolster policies that ensure a balanced distribution of experienced teachers and discourage the clustering of novice teachers in high-demand schools. This measure aims to prevent students from facing a revolving door of less experienced teachers, who, on average, might be less effective compared to their more seasoned counterparts.
5. Organizing conferences, workshops, and seminars for in-service Physics teachers, regardless of their qualifications or experience, is essential to enhance their knowledge and skills in implementing diverse teaching methods. This initiative will contribute to elevated quality in teaching and learning the subject at the senior school level.

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Correlation between Availability of Educational Resources and Academic Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Adamawa State

Shuaibu Abdullahi

Email: abdullahi.shuaiibu@gmail.com

Tel: +2348067653781.

Environmental and Life Sciences Education Department, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State.

Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between educational resources and biology students' academic performance in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational design. The target population of the study comprised 12,143 teachers and 731 principals of senior secondary schools in the five-education zone of Adamawa state. A sample of 221 teachers was used. The instruments used for data collection was Educational Resources Questionnaire tagged (ERQ). Mean and standard deviation were used to analyzed the data. The findings of the study are: availability of instructional aids is a significant predictor of senior secondary school Biology students' academic achievement, $F_{(1, 220)} = 14.368$, $p < 0.05$ school facilities is a significant predictor of senior secondary school students' academic achievement, $F_{(1, 220)} = 16.057$, $p < 0.05$ and adequacy of funding is a significant predictor of senior secondary school students' academic achievement, $F_{(1, 220)} = 26.145$, $p < 0.05$. It is recommended among others that government through the post primary school management board should make instructional aids available to schools to enable teachers teach effectively.

Keywords: Educational resource, Students' academic performance, Biology

Introduction

Education is the process of emancipation, civilization and development, and also a key that unlocks the development of personal and national potentials/national development (Ekokotu & Okeh, 2012). For this reason, the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) described education as an instrument par excellence for effective national development. Development ideas, scientific advancement, vocational and technological breakthrough, economic development are made possible by the educational theories and practices (Garuba, Agweda & Abumere, 2012). According to Tunde, Akintoye, and Adeyemo (2011), science education is crucial to the development of any country, which is why every country needs to take it seriously in all educational institutions. Biology, chemistry, and physics are the three subjects that make up science education; over the past year, enrollment in these subjects in our schools has been low, according to Aina (2012).

Biology is the study of animals and plants, and it helps develop the scientific literacy necessary for a nation to grow and develop. Ezeh (2006) asserts that a nation's capacity for scientific literacy will have a significant influence on how far it can advance. Scientific literacy is growing in popularity daily as a result of science and technology's global expansion and advancement. Biology explains human anatomy and physiology, health issues, and how to comprehend, deal with, and manage the microbes that surround us. Biology is a requirement for many tertiary institutions' science and science-related courses. If educational resources are sufficiently provided and used, Biology teaching and learning will be improved. The human and material resources found in schools may be regarded as educational resources.

The availability of qualified teachers, access to infrastructural facilities, the quality of teaching aids, the implementation of curricula, and funding are just a few examples of the many factors that Sharka (2008) defines as educational resources. Educational resources can be either human, material, or financial resources. This study looked into how funding, school resources, and teaching resources related to academic achievement among biology students. A useful educational tool that supports the educational objectives of secondary schools is instructional aid at the secondary school level. Secondary institutions A teacher will use instructional aides to help students understand and appreciate the lesson's goals by conveying to them the key information in a lesson. For effective teaching to occur and for learners' learning outcomes to change, the use of instructional materials is a requirement (Jimoh, 2009). Ikerionwu (2000) defined instructional aids in secondary schools as things or tools that help the teacher make learning relevant to the student. They are tools for helping people transfer information to one another (Adeoye, 2012). In other words, instructional materials increase the effectiveness of secondary education by enhancing the standard of both teaching and learning. It provides a variety of learning opportunities that can be used singly or in combination to meet various teaching and learning needs and to inspire students to become skilled technicians with a never-

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ending passion for learning. According to Okobia (2011), the benefits of using instructional materials in the classroom include, among other things, making the subject matter more realistic, explaining challenging concepts, having the learner experience what they are learning, igniting the learners' imaginations, avoiding misconceptions, and making learning interesting.

The goal of instructional materials is to increase the effectiveness of education by raising the standard of both teaching and learning. As a result, the use of instructional aids is dependent upon their accessibility in the classroom. Resources for secondary school education that are required for a high-quality secondary education outcome include infrastructure facilities as well.

Jimoh (2009) claims that by meeting the physical and emotional needs of the faculty and students at the school, secondary school infrastructure facilities play a crucial role in the realization of the goals and objectives of secondary education. The physical resources made available to secondary school staff and students to maximize their productivity in the teaching and learning process are known as infrastructural facilities.

The realization that the transfer of knowledge does not only take place in the four walls of the classroom from the teacher to the students but rather than learning takes place through discovery, exploration, interaction with the internal and external environment has necessitated the creative and innovative development of teaching and learning facilities that reflect these changes. Secondary schools exist to serve socio-economic and political needs of the ever-changing society; consequently, they are in constant interaction with their external environment. They receive inputs from the external environment in the form of human and material resources, process them and empty same into the society as finished products and services. The quality of the products bears a direct relationship with the quality of the facilities deployed in the process of the production.

Secondary school funding stands out as the mother of secondary education resources, because the availability of other secondary education resources is directly related to the level of secondary school funding. The financing of secondary education as an aspect of public finance embraces all aspects of funding of secondary schools, including the sources of funding and how the money earmarked for secondary education is spent especially for the purchase of goods and the services of human and materials. Thus, the financing of secondary education is a vital area of Economics of Education. The importance of adequate financing of secondary education cannot be over-stressed. Taggert (2003) argued that no organization could carry out its functions effectively without adequate financial resources at its disposal. Money is needed to pay staff, maintain the plant and keep the services going. This argument supported earlier findings that finance is of vital importance to education and economic growth (Omotade, 2004). Base on this background it is obvious that to sustain progress in the secondary school agenda and to attain the desired secondary education product, we need more efficiency in the use of human and material resources in education and sustainable policies to accelerate educational growth. Thus, this study investigated the relationship between educational resources and secondary schools Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa State.

The Federal Republic of Nigeria's 2014 National Policy on secondary education emphasizes the importance of equipping students with fundamental scientific knowledge, practical skills, and applied abilities to facilitate their further education. Achieving this goal hinges on the availability of sufficient educational resources, which are the most visible aspects of government educational provision and are regularly observed by stakeholders. Insufficient human and material resources can hinder the attainment of educational objectives, potentially resulting in inadequately prepared secondary school graduates who lack the necessary technical and applied skills for everyday life, rendering them less useful to society. Moreover, these graduates may struggle to meet the requirements of higher education, leading to dropouts or dismissals due to underperformance. These issues may stem from inadequate instructional methods, a lack of appropriate teaching aids for comprehensive understanding, and the improper implementation of the curriculum at the secondary school level.

Educational resources are pivotal to the teaching and learning process and directly impact students' academic performance. Consequently, there is a pressing need to ensure the provision of adequate educational resources in senior secondary schools. These schools are grappling with a multitude of problems, including inadequate resource allocation due to poor planning. Furthermore, there is a growing concern regarding the declining academic performance of students, particularly in English language and mathematics, in Adamawa state, especially in its rural and semi-rural areas. This decline is evident through poor performance in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE). In light of these challenges, this research seeks to investigate whether the availability of educational resources serves as a predictor of students' academic performance in Adamawa state.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated the relationship between availability of educational resources and academic performance in Biology among secondary schools' students in Adamawa State. Specifically, the study determined:

1. The relationship between availability of instructional aids and Biology students' academic achievement in Adamawa state.

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2. The relationship between availability of school facilities and Biology students’ academic achievement in Adamawa state.
3. The relationship between adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools and Biology students’ academic achievement in Adamawa state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the level of availability of instructional aids in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?
2. What is the level of availability of school facilities in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?
3. What is the level of adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional aids and Biology students’ academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant relationship between availability of school facilities and Biology students’ academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant relationship between adequacy of funding and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Methodology

The study employed a correlational design. The target population of the study comprised 12,143 teachers and 731 principals of senior secondary schools in the five-education zone of Adamawa state. A sample of 221 teachers was used. The instruments used for data collection was Educational Resources Questionnaire tagged (ERQ). It is a 26 – items questionnaire divided into three sections. The ERQ is based on five-point rating scale of vary high level (VHL), high level (HL), moderate level (MD), low level (LL) and very low level (VLL). Mean and standard deviation were used to analyzed the data.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of availability of instructional aids in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of availability of Instructional Aids in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	ITEM	n = 221	Mean	S. D
1	How available is Dictionary for teaching purpose		4.10	1.47
2	How available are Charts used for teaching		4.36	1.33
3	How available are Models for teaching		3.45	1.67
4	How available are Maps of the World for promoting learning and interest		3.10	1.63
5	How available are Textbooks in the library for student’s usage		3.34	1.64
6	How available are classroom Blackboards for teaching		3.16	1.61
7	How available are Simulation games that enhances learning		3.45	1.63
8	How available are Real objects for teaching purpose?		2.63	1.49
9	How available are Films and videos for audio- visual instructional approach of teaching?		3.98	1.47
10	How available are computers in the school for ICT purposes?		4.05	1.49
	Average Mean		3.56	

Analysis in Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of items on level of availability of instructional aids in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. A high level of availability of instructional aids in senior secondary schools was obtained as indicated by the average mean of 3.56.

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Research Question 2

What is the level of availability of school facilities in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Availability of School Facilities in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	ITEM	n = 221	Mean	S. D
11	How available are Classrooms rooms that accommodate students comfortably during classes		3.66	1.57
12	Are libraries available		4.07	1.50
13	How available are Library services		3.99	1.54
14	How available is portable water for drinking		3.73	1.62
15	How available is portable water for cleaning the school environment		3.39	1.67
16	How available are Staff rooms		3.57	1.54
17	How available are laboratories in the schools		3.73	1.43
18	How available are equipment in the Laboratories		3.64	1.43
19	How available are school gadgets in the Store room		3.60	1.46
20	How available are functional toilet system		4.37	1.00
Average Mean			3.77	

Result of analysis presented in Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of items on level of availability of school facilities in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The result shows that there is high level of availability of school facilities in senior secondary schools as indicated by the grand mean of 3.77.

Research Question 3

What is the level of adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Dev. of Level of Adequacy of Funding in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	ITEM	Mean	S. D
21	The allocation from the government is adequate	3.19	1.60
22	Internal generated funds from students school fees is a sufficient supplement	3.37	1.57
23	The fund from other educational organization is sufficient	3.54	1.54
24	The school source of fund increases per year	3.00	1.56
25	Parents P.T.A contribution has been a source of school funding.	3.17	1.55
26	Generally the secondary schools are well funded	3.32	1.48
Average Mean		3.27	

Analysis in Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of items on level of adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. An average mean of 3.27 indicates moderate level of adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional aids and Biology students’ academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Instructional Aids as Predictor of Biology Students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	18.278	1	18.278	14.368	.000 ^b
	Residual	278.609	219	1.272		
	Total	296.887	220			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), instructional aids

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Analysis in Table 4 shows that availability of instructional aids is a significant predictor of senior secondary school Biology students' academic achievement, $F_{(1, 220)} = 14.368$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 alpha level, we can conclude that the null hypothesis should be rejected. This means that availability of instructional aids significantly predicts senior secondary school students' academic achievement.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.248 ^a	.062	.057	1.12791

a. Predictors: (Constant), INSTRUCTIONAL AIDS

The result in Table 5 shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows that the availability of instructional aids explained 6.2% of the variance in students' academic Achievement.

Table 4c: Coefficients of Beta of Prediction between Instructional Aids and Students' Academic Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	1.536	.400		3.843	.000
	INSTRUCTIONAL AIDS	.417	.110	.248	3.790	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

The result in Table 4c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of availability of instructional aids and students' academic achievement. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.234, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that availability of instructional aids is significantly related to students' academic performance.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between availability of school facilities and Biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Table 5a: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of School Facilities as Predictor of Senior Secondary School Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20.281	1	20.281	16.057	.000 ^b
	Residual	276.606	219	1.263		
	Total	296.887	220			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), school facilities

Results in Table 5a shows that there is significant relationship between availability of school facilities and senior secondary school students' academic performance, $F_{(1, 629)} = 16.057$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 alpha level, we conclude that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that availability of school facilities is significantly related to senior secondary school Biology students' academic performance.

Table 5b: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.261 ^a	.068	.064	1.12385

a. Predictors: (Constant), school facilities

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The result in Table 5b shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows that the school facilities explained 6.8% of the variance in students' academic achievement.

Table 5c: Coefficients of Beta of Prediction between School Facilities and Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	1.652	.350		4.713	.000
	SCHOOL FACILITIES	.363	.091	.261	4.007	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

The result in Table 5c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of school facilities and students' academic achievement. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.316, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that school facilities is a significant predictor of academic performance.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between adequacy of funding and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Table 6a: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Relationship between Adequacy of Funding and Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	31.664	1	31.664	26.145	.000 ^b
	Residual	265.223	219	1.211		
	Total	296.887	220			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), adequacy of funds

Results of Analysis in Table 6a shows that there is significant relationship between adequacy of funding and senior secondary school students' academic performance, $F_{(1, 629)} = 26.145$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 alpha level, we can conclude that the null hypothesis should be rejected. This means that adequacy of funding significantly predicts senior secondary school students' academic performance.

Table 6b: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.327 ^a	.107	.103	1.10048

a. Predictors: (Constant), adequacy of funds

The result in Table 6b shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows that adequacy of funding explained 2.8% of the variance in students' academic performance.

Table 6c: Coefficients of Beta of Prediction between Adequacy of Funds and Students' Academic Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	1.650	.278		5.927	.000
	ADEQUACY OF FUNDS	.420	.082	.327	5.113	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

The result in Table 6c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of adequacy of funding and students' academic achievement. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.295, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that adequacy of funding is significantly related to students' academic performance.

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Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the relationship between educational Resources and Biology students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state. The following are the discussion of findings of this study. The finding revealed that there is significant relationship between availability of instructional aids and senior secondary school Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa State. This is because instructional materials, in the teaching-learning process, facilitate the learning of abstract concepts and ideas; keep the learners busy and active thus, increasing their participation in the lesson; save teachers' energy of talking too much; illustrate the concepts clearer and better than the teachers' words only; help overcome the limitations of the classroom by making the inaccessible accessible; help to broaden students' knowledge, increase their level of understanding as well as discourage rote-learning; help to stimulate and motivate learners.

The finding also indicates that there is significant relationship between school facilities and senior secondary school Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa State. This means that availability of school facilities would enhance students' academic performance. The availability of material and resources in the school is as important as the presence of qualified personnel and when there is no qualified personnel and required material resources, there will be no effective teaching and learning and hence it would affect student's performances. The finding of the study agrees with that of Ekundayo (2018) who found that there was a significant relationship between school facilities and students' achievement in the affective and the psychomotor domains. This suggests that when the school facilities are better put in place and in use better performance are expected from the students. In similar studies by Ayodele (2000) and Vandiver (2011), a significant positive relationship is found between availability of facilities and student academic performance. This aspect is a key in determining the academic performance of learners in schools, thus the state of school facility and attendance directly impact on academic performance of learners and school in general.

Furthermore, the finding revealed that there is no significant relationship between adequacy of funding and senior secondary school Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa State. The level of funds available to a large extent determines the quantity and quality of school objectives that will be achieved. This is because funding is important in the acquisition of basic human, financial and material resources needed to transform the objectives of the school into reality. The finding of this study agrees with that of Nwite (2016) who found significant relationship between financial allocation and students' performance. Nwite reported that adequate financial resource allocations to secondary schools significantly influence students' performance. The finding is also in-line with the study of Abdul-Rahaman, Ming, Abdul-Rahaman, Amadu and Abdul-Rahaman (2018) who found that government funding in the form of progressive free senior high school policy has a significant effect on students' academic performance in Schools in the Wa Municipality of the Upper West Region of Ghana. The finding also concurs with that of Van der Berg (2017) who confirms an overwhelmingly positive impact of funding on student success. The finding however contradicted that of Kerkvliet and Nowell (2014) and Naidoo and McKay (2018) who found no relationship between the amount received and performance. The finding also is in concordance with that of Jane (2020) whose findings of the study indicate that government funding of secondary education improves school attendance, access and facilitate acquisition of teaching and learning facilities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that availability of educational resources (instructional aids, school facilities and adequacy of funding) enhanced senior secondary schools Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. The government through the post primary school management board should make instructional aids available to schools to enable teachers teach effectively.
2. Adequate school facilities such as classrooms, laboratories, textbooks should be made available to provide an atmosphere and amenities for student success.
3. Government should be committed to the adequate funding of secondary education through appropriate budgetary allocation for the sustenance of secondary education in the country. The government should consider an upward review of the educational budget to meet up with the 26% and above allocation recommended by UNESCO.

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Correlation Between Self-Concept and Academic Achievement in Mathematics Among Senior Secondary School Students in Batagarawa Educational Zone, Katsina State

Musa, Aisha Hamis

Email: aishahamismusa1@gmail.com

Tel: 08056800088

Department of Science and Vocational Education Umar Musa Yaradua University, Katsina

Abstract

This study established the correlation between self-concept and academic achievement in Mathematics among senior secondary school students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina state. The study developed two objectives, research questions and tested corresponding hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance, respectively. It adopts descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of One Thousand Five Hundred and Eighty-Five (1585) which include 786 Male and 799 Female senior secondary school class two (SSS II) students in Batagarawa educational zone, katsina state public schools during the 2021/2022 academic session. Multistage sampling Technique was used to select the sample size of Two Hundred and Seven (207) class two (SSII) students during the 2021/2022 academic session in public schools in Batagarawa educational zone. A validated questionnaire titled Self-concept questionnaire (SCQ) with reliability index of 0.798 was used for data collection in this study. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient and t-test (Independent sample) statistic was used to test the null hypotheses. The results revealed that there is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary Mathematics students in Katsina state, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended that, orientation should be regularly given to students on how to improve their self-concept and academic achievement as it may help them elevate their performance in Mathematics.

Keywords: Self Concept, Academic Achievement, Mathematics and Students

Introduction

After More than a decade of neglect self-concept is enjoying renewed popularity and attention by both researchers and practitioners into self-concept research. There is growing awareness that of all the perception we experienced in the course of living, none has more profound significance than the perception we hold regarding our own personal existence, our concept of who we are and how we fit into the world self-concept is the information that we have about ourselves what we think we are like. Self-concept is person's perceptions of himself formed through experience and interpretations of the environment. Self-concept generally refers to the composite of ideas, feelings, and attitudes people have about themselves. Our self-perceptions vary from situation to situation and from one phase of our lives to another (Ajmal & Rafique, 2018).

The aim of education is to discover and develop the abilities and character of individual's in order to serve the society better. During most conversations, people deliberate and chat about self-concept and intelligence, you hear them saying "he is looking confident", "he possesses good qualities" "he is intelligent "he can do it better" and so on Experience develops Self-concept and yields the level of intelligence a person possesses in life. Having positive and better Self-concept makes students to show optimism about their potential for success in future. They show confidence and competence they believe in hard work, dedication, determination and commitment to school work. They always think about success and good qualities and strive for it. They are superior in themselves thinking if anyone else can do it, they can do it better, in all aspects of life. Globally, education is considered to be the most important instrument for change and national development. The educational institutions should emphasize intellectual activities, moral judgments, aesthetic judgments, self-realization, individual freedom, individual responsibility and self- control development.

The study of self-concept has awakened growing interest in psychological research of recent years. Despite the numerous studies devoted to it. However, it is difficult to find a unanimous, accepted definition of the term self-concept, given that it has been approached from different theoretical perspectives. However, there is agreement among the different researchers in that, the term self-concept has multidimensional nature in which global self-concept is on the top followed by academic, physical and social self-concept. Academic Self-concept helps the individual in various important moments of life; In judgment, in decision making and in other situations. Deshmukh (2010) believes that the self is responsible for many successes and failures, as it promotes a positive Self-Concept, promoting safety and personal trust to develop skills. Society plays a dominant role in shaping self-concept of a person. Self is in fact a complex whole, which consists of several parts and sub-parts which have functional inter-relationship. Self is not an inborn quality: it develops gradually as a result of social interaction. It is the

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totality of attitudes, Judgment and values of an individual relating to his behaviors, abilities and qualities. This means academic self-concept as the perception or structure that can include content, attitudes or evaluative judgments' and are used to make sense of the world, focus attention on one's goals and protect one's sense of basic worth. Each one has about himself, formed from experience and a relationship with the environment, where significant people play important role. Kumari & Chamundeswari (2013) in her study found that some psychological aspects like self-concept have great impact on the achievement of students and it helps in determining the level of competence among students' potentials. She also concluded that the way students behave in academic settings depends upon self-awareness. Individuals approach regarding his/her talents and hidden potentials strengthen his/her belief in self and the individual get better grades in school. Nwezeh (2011) also carried out studies on the effects of anxiety on school achievement and found that at the primary level, anxiety generally depressed scholastic achievement, and that school achievement tasks tend to lose their threatening implications as students gain experience in coping with them. Therefore, academic self-concept and achievement are dynamically interactive and reciprocal; each is mutually reinforcing that a positive (or negative) change in one facilitates commensurate change the other. Academic self-concept is more highly correlated with academic achievement than in general self-concept. Students with high self-concept approach school related tasks with confidence. Success in those tasks reinforces this confidence. The opposite pattern is likely to occur for children with low academic self-concepts.

The most critical measure of any educational system is the assessment of its students. The aim of any research is to determine the extent to which this objective is achieved. If not, why and what can be done to achieve it? The fact that modern education has different levels of aims suggests that we must measure the extent of its success in a variety of ways. The implication of this is that it is the level of objective that goes a long way to determine the term to use. In other words, it is the time frame that determines whether it is academic performance or achievement. Philosophers elucidated further that the performance of more than 645,000 children in 4000 public schools derived their education achievement through their performance scores over a long period of time. Cooper & Burgar (2010) defined academic performance as a quality of performance in terms of tasks and class exercises with academic content. It is a level of a given standard content and excellence; a qualified academic achievement. Mission and goals of the education system usually determine learning outcome. This suggests that learning outcome transcends cognitive assessment. It includes attitude and values. In research, learning outcome dwells on academic achievement and attitude of the students. therefore, this study set to find out the correlation between self-concept and academic achievement in Mathematics among senior secondary school students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina state

Despite the efforts put in place by the teachers and parents, education planners in teaching and learning process, few students achieve higher grades in their academic pursuit. Some score averages while the vast majority scores below average. Nowadays, students face a lot of crises in knowing themselves, having negative image about themselves. They woefully failed at many times during assessment, including those students who are opportune to be in good learning environments. Students are unwilling to accept blame, some abhor competition, unable to accept praise and these students end up achieving nothing at last. They always think about failures and do not see themselves as capable or competent to succeed because of their inadequacies. Some students develop a dependent academic behavior, especially girls that during examinations they usually rely on the boys in their classes for assistances. Such female students keep saying that boys are academically better because of traditional and family stereotype that males are superior to females. This indicates that there are some underlying factors in determining the academic success or failure of students that are at play. In view of this, various psychological and physiological factors are said to be contributing either positively or negatively to the academic achievement of students. These factors include: motivation, intelligence, self-efficacy, interest, personality, peer-group influences, adjustment behavior and parental socio-economic status. In schools, students are not given the opportunity to develop self-concept by not engaging them in tasks and skills which go beyond the mere playful expression of the pleasure, the child do not realize the need to work to recognition by striving to succeed in his academic achievement. As such, the child lack confidence in pursuing academic excellence and confidence in studies and therefore, develop a sense of inferiority complex which eventually leads to failure in school subjects, such as mathematics.

Objectives of the Study

1. Determine the relationship between student's self-concept and academic achievement in mathematics among senior secondary Schools in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.
2. Determine the difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.

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Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between Self-Concept and academic achievement in mathematics among senior secondary School students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State?
2. What is the difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

1. Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement in mathematics among senior secondary schools in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.
2. Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.

Methodology

This research employed descriptive survey research design in investigating the relationship between student’s self-concept and academic achievement in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey design is a method of collecting information by interviewing or administering a questionnaire to a sample of individuals within a small range (Haruna, 2010). It is a design that gathers information about prevailing conditions or situation for the purpose of description and interpretation. This design aimed at studying the existing relationships, prevailing practices, beliefs and attitudes held, processes and effects of developing trends. Hence, primary sources of data are to be used. Primary sources of data include questionnaires. This research design is relevant to this study because the researcher used questionnaire to collect information which are the same instruments to be used in this research design. Population of the study consist of all public senior secondary school class two (SSII) students in Batagarawa educational zone, Katsina State during the 2021/2022 academic session. This make the total of (1585) in the seven (7) Secondary Schools in educational zone. This is in line with the contention by Kothari (2004) who defines the target population as the total number of respondents in the total environment of interest. Multistage sampling Technique was used to select the sample size of Two Hundred and Seven (207) class two (SSII) students during the 2021/2022 academic session in public schools in Batagarwa educational zone. First stage of the sampling technique was simple random which was used to select three schools out of the seven school. Second stage involved the use of Research Advisers’ Table (cited in Haruna, 2010) to select the number of students based on the proportion of the population. For the purpose of data collection questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire entitled ‘Self-concept Questionnaire’ (SCQ) was developed by the researcher and was administered to the respondents who duly filled them on their own and provided the required data for the study. The information required was personal, factual or indicate an individual’s feelings or attitude. The instrument was made up of two sections (A and B). Section (A) is about demographic information of the respondents. While section (B) contain 30 items to responded using Strong Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D, Strongly Disagreed (SD) which represent student’s feelings on the items of the instrument. This instrument was used in the study to find out the relationship of students’ self-concept and academic achievement which is determined through responses made by the students by shading or ticking the appropriate option. The SCQ was validated by three relevant experts and after pilot study, the SCQ reliability was found to be 0.798 which made the instrument acceptable for the study.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviations of relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Self-concept	207	11.74	3.28
Achievement	207	20.61	5.30

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Table 1 present mean and standard deviations of relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State. Result obtained shows that the number of student self-concept is recorded as 207 and mean of 11.75 and standard deviations of 3.28, while academic achievement is recorded 207 and mean of 20.61 and standard deviations of 5.31.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State?

Table 2: mean and standard deviations difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept

Group	N	Mean	S D	SE
Physical	111	20.97	4.73	.44
Social	96	20.20	5.90	.60

Table 2 present mean and standard deviations of difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State. Result obtained shows that students with physical self-concept recorded a mean of 20.97 and standard deviations of 4.73, while students with social self-concept recorded a mean of 20.20 and standard deviations of 5.90.

Hypothesis Testing

H01: There is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.

Table.4: PPMCC of the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R-value	Alpha	P-Value	Decision
self-concept	207	11.7488	3.28791	0.50	0.05	0.47	Not significant
Achievement	207	20.6184	5.30838				

Table 4 present PPMC of the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State. Result obtained shows that r-value is 0.50, while p-value is 0.47. P-value is greater than alpha, hence the difference is not significance. Consequently, null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria is retained.

H02: There is no significant Difference between academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State

Table 5: Independent sample t-test of difference between academic achievement of mathematics students with physical self-concept and their counter parts with social self-concept

Variables	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	P-Value	Decision
Physical	111	20.9730	4.73375	1.03	205	.303	Not significant
Social	96	20.2083	5.90257				

Table 5 present independent sample t-test of difference between academic achievement of mathematics students with physical self-concept and their counter parts with social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State. Result obtained shows that t-value is 1.03, while p-value is 0.30. P-value is greater than alpha; hence the difference is not significance.

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Accordingly, null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant Difference between academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and their counter parts with social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria is retained.

Discussion of Findings

Finding shows that no significant relationship was observed between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with that of Obilor, (2012), who study the extent to which Self-concept of students' influence his subject choice and the results of the tests indicated that Mathematics Self- esteem is not significantly related to Mathematics Achievement. Otta, and Williams (2012) examined Self-concept and Vocational Interest among secondary school students the findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between self-concept and vocational interest. This means the development of Self-concept is a very important aspect of globalization, especially in the world today. Knowledge and awareness of Self-concept could help a person to be mentally prepared to face the challenges ahead.

Finding number two revealed that no significant Difference was found between academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and their counter parts with social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. The results revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between self-concept and Academic achievement among students. This is in accordance with the study done by Crawford (2013) asserted that a significant relationship exists between students' social confidence and their academic achievement scores.

Conclusion

The present study was conducted to find out the correlationhsip between self-concept and academic achievement in Mathematics among senior secondary school students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina state. therefore, Self-concept Questionnaire (SCQ) was developed, validated and used in the study. It was hypothesized that, there is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students' in Katsina State, Nigeria and that there is no significant relationship between academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Katsina State, Nigeria. The study revealed that, both self-concept and academic achievement have influence on achievement of students in Mathematics where female students perceived themselves with higher self-concept and academic achievement than the male students. Despite difference in self-concept and academic achievement, both students' performance did not differ significantly.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following are hereby recommended:

8. Students should be guided how to adjust their self-concept to enhance their academic achievement in Mathematics.
9. Students should be encouraged and guided to have good academic achievement so as to enhance their performance in schools.
10. Parents should encourage their children to develop good academic achievement to improve their academic achievement in different subjects in secondary schools.
11. Modern instructional facilities or resources shall be made available including Audio-visual, and multi-media gadgets which would be in tandem with the 21st century global world. This would help in addressing individual variability and interest among the students with different academic achievement.
12. Orientation should be regularly given to students on how to improve their self-concept and academic achievement as it may help them elevate their performance in mathematics and in other subjects.

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Correlation between Marital Instability and Academic Performance among Government Secondary School Students in Chikun Local Government Area, Kaduna State

Buba Mahmud¹

Email: mahmudbuba@gmail.com,

Tel: 0703 053 1155

Adamu Jibrilla²

Email: j.adam1438@gmail.com,

Tel: 0703 740 8344

Murtala Muhammad³

Email: muhatala55@gmail.com,

Tel: 0806 901 5927

¹Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

²Department of Physical Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

³Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

Abstract

The study investigated the correlations between marital instability and academic performance among government secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area, Kaduna State. Two objectives were formulated which lead to two research questions and two null hypotheses that guided this study. The population of this study is made up of 13876 secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. A total of 388 senior secondary school (188 males and 200 females) students were selected using simple random sampling techniques. The study adopted correlational research design. Questionnaire entitled Marital Instability Questionnaire (MIQ) was used for data collection and the reliability coefficients of 0.89 was calculated using Cronbach alpha. Linear regression analysis and independent sample *t* – test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The findings of the study revealed that: There is significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement, $r = .718$, $n = 388$, $p < .05$. There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability, t – value = -0.611 , $p > 0.05$. It is concluded that students who experience marital instability in their families tend to have different academic outcomes compared to those from stable family backgrounds. It is also concluded that both male and female students appear to be equally affected (or unaffected) by marital instability in terms of their academic performance. It is recommended among others that all marriage stakeholders should put every effort to solve marital crises in order to save the couples from broken home and save the children from adverse consequences of marital instability.

Keywords: Marital Instability, Academic achievement, gender

Introduction

Marriage has existed for as long as there have been humans. It can be considered an institution that has existed ever since man first set foot in the cosmos. Anderson (2015) argued that the institution of marriage is founded on the principle that men and women possess complementary qualities, the biological necessity of both a man and a woman for reproduction, and the recognition that children benefit from the presence of both a mother and a father. According to Ojukwu, Woko and Onuoha (2016) marriage is considered a cultural and universal phenomenon and is usually formalized through a wedding ceremony in many cultures. The husband and wife's traditional roles and responsibilities include cohabitating, limiting their sexual activity to one another, sharing financial resources, and being acknowledged as the children's primary caregivers who prioritize their wellbeing and well-informed education. Formal interactions, however, can only occur in a stable, mutually supportive family setting. Marriage is meant to be stable and eternal, but recent changes in family structures and marital values have redefined marriage institutions in most societies, including Nigeria. This has serious implications for the overall growth and well-being of the family's legitimate children as it becomes more fragile and unstable. With potential repercussions for people's well-being and social dynamics, marital instability—characterized by conflicts, separation, and divorce within marital relationships—has become a common problem across various societies. The institution of marriage is extremely important to culture and society

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everywhere, including Nigeria. However, the dynamics of families have changed as a result of shifting economic, social, and cultural factors, which has increased the incidence of unstable marriages. The phrase "marital instability" refers to a situation where a married couple is having relationship issues. It alludes to a marital crisis or issues between partners that could lead to a marriage ending in divorce, desertion, or separation. According to Katzenback and Smith cited in Oyeromi, Olaolu, Fadokun and Omiyale (2018), marital instability is characterized by arguments in which the couples involved perceive a threat to their needs, interests, or concerns. It is also viewed as a struggle between couples who have divergent needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or goals. A marriage or family according to Alika and Edosa (2012) is structurally stable or unstable. A marriage that is unstable lacks structural integrity due to arguments, fights, separation, or even divorce. These marriages are characterized by frequent arguments, disagreements, and domestic fights between the partners.

Marriage instability has been noted as a current social issue because it has a significant impact on many homes, particularly in Nigerian society. Like the proverbial adage "when two elephants fight, the grass suffers," the situation in most homes is such that even the children have become the burden bearers (Oleabhie & Ighalo, nd). According to Oleabhie and Ighalo (nd), this unpleasant experience frequently leaves them emotionally and psychologically unbalanced with feelings of depression, rage, and even frustration because they are caught between the opposing sides of their parent. Everywhere in the world, marriage is bound by customary rites and taboos. In the majority of cultures, the rituals and ceremonies surrounding marriage are primarily linked to fertility and serve to affirm how crucial marriage is to the survival of an individual or a society. According to Kolo cited in Oyeromi et al (2018), the love of money, freedom, the struggle for power control, poor communication, lack of preparation, or improper diagnosis and treatment of the issue are to blame for the decline in marital vows such as those to love, cherish, and honor. These marital vows have been replaced as a result of this decline by social ills like disaster, poor development, and a lack of appreciation, understanding, companionship, support, attraction, and forgiveness in poor sexual relationships.

The potential impact of marital instability on students' academic performance is one area of particular worry. Academic performance is an important aspect of a student's life because it shapes their educational and future career opportunities. The dynamics of a student's family, including their marital status, have a big impact on how happy and capable of succeeding in school they are. Marital instability can cause a child to experience a variety of stressors, which can affect their emotional and psychological health and possibly have an impact on how engaged and successful they are in school. Earlier studies has shown a link between students' academic performance and marital instability. As an illustration, Oleabhie and Ighalo (nd) found that there is a significant correlation between lack of motivation, depression, and nervous breakdown (caused by marital instability) and undergraduates' academic performance when they studied perceived effects of marital instability on undergraduates' academic performance in Benin city, Edo state. Chindo (2014) looked into the impact of marital issues on students' academic performance. The results showed a significant correlation between marital issues and married students' academic performance. Yongmin and Yuanzhang (2011) found that Children in two-biological-parent families with disruptions experienced slower academic growth than children in two-biological-parent families without disruptions. Simple evidence suggests that marital instability contributes to social, academic, and emotional issues like stress, tension, lack of motivation, and frustration to some extent. The academic performance of a child is undoubtedly negatively impacted by these manifestations (Alika & Edosa, 2012).

According to Fomby and Cherlin (2007) cited in Oyeromi, et al (2018), transitioning from a marital stable to an unstable home is frequently accompanied by declines in children's well-being and academic performance. Children are frequently neglected when marital instability occurs in homes where there are signs like fights and arguments between couples. And such careless neglect on the part of parents in providing the support and guidance required for their children's academic endeavors may result in children's subpar academic performance. Contradictory results have been found regarding the academic achievement of students by gender. According to some studies (Guidubaldo & Perry, 1985; Hetherington, 1985; Kaye, 1989 cited in Oyeromi, et al, 2018), boys in conflicting families have more adjustment issues than girls. According to Oyeromi, et al (2018), some researchers found no difference in the effects of marital instability on boys and girls, while other researchers found more detrimental effects for girls. According to research by Kaye in Oyeromi, Olaolu, Fadokun, and Omiyale (2018), boys and girls perform worse on achievement tests when compared to kids from intact families. Although the potential connection between marital instability and academic performance is becoming more widely acknowledged, there is still a lack of knowledge about the complex interactions between these variables in the particular context of Chikun Local Government Area. There haven't been many thorough investigations into the scope and makeup of this relationship. By conducting a methodical investigation into how marital instability may affect students' academic performance in the local context, this study

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seeks to close this gap. The current study, which is based on the experiences, examines the connection between marital instability and senior secondary students' academic performance in Chikun local government area of Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Marital instability is a pervasive social issue with far-reaching consequences that extend beyond the confines of the marital relationship itself. Among the various facets of society affected by marital instability, the academic performance of students in government secondary schools stands as a critical concern. In Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria, there is a growing concern that marital instability within the households of government secondary school students may be adversely impacting their academic performance. However, a comprehensive understanding of the correlations between marital instability and academic performance in this specific context remains lacking. This study seeks to address the following key issues: To what extent does marital instability within the households of government secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area influence their academic performance? Are there variations in the academic performance of male and female students from households characterized by varying degrees of marital instability? By exploring these questions, this research aims to provide valuable insights into the complex relationship between marital instability and academic performance among government secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the Study

This study investigated the correlation between marital instability and senior secondary school student's academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

The objectives of the study therefore are as follows:

4. To determine the extent to which marital instability relate to students' Academic Performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.
5. To find out if marital instability has influence on male and female student Academic Performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study.

4. What is the level of relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State?
5. What is the difference in the achievement scores of males and females students due to marital instability in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Null hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

4. **H₀₁**: There is no significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.
5. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females students due to marital instability in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational design. The population of this study is made up 13876 secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The sample of this study is 388 (188 male, 200 female) students drawn using Yamane (1967). Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the subjects. The study used questionnaire entitled Marital Instability Questionnaire (MIQ) for data collection. The questionnaire was duly validated and its reliability coefficient of 0.89 was calculated using Cronbach Alpha method. The terminal examination scores of the students were converted to standard scores and were used as students' academic performance. The data collected were analyzed using regression analysis and independent sample *t* test.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

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Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Relationship between Marital Instability and Students' Academic Performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State

S/N	ITEM	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	Children experiencing unstable home environments often display aggressive tendencies.	4.02	1.50	A
2	Offspring of divorced parents may exhibit deviant behavior due to a lack of supervision and behavioral guidance.	3.21	1.53	U
3	Children from divorced or separated families may become wayward, mischievous, unruly, and rebellious.	4.05	1.34	A
4	Kids of divorced parents have a higher susceptibility to child trafficking compared to those raised in intact families.	4.03	1.18	A
5	Offspring of divorced, separated, or abandoned mothers often miss out on quality education, proper socialization, and effective home upbringing.	4.24	1.13	A
6	Children from divorced families are more vulnerable to being exploited in child trafficking compared to those raised in intact households.	3.89	1.39	A
7	Children of divorced parents are more likely to end up working as domestic helpers.	3.80	1.10	A
8	Children of divorced or separated women frequently experience economic hardships.	3.02	1.44	U
Grand Mean		3.78		A

Source: Researcher's Analysis of Field Survey, 2022

Results of analysis in Table 1 show the mean and standard deviation of level of relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The grand mean of 3.78 indicate that the respondents agree that there exists some relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the achievement scores of males and females students due to marital instability in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students' academic Performance in in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State

Gender	N	Mean	S. D	Mean Difference
M	188	59.32	17.01	1.12
F	200	60.44	18.68	

Source: Researcher's Analysis of Field Survey, 2022

The results in Table 2 show the mean and standard deviation of male and female students in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The results shows that the mean academic performance of male and female students are 59.32 (SD = 17.01) and 60.44 (SD = 18.68) respectively. The mean difference in the academic performance of male and female students is 1.12 in favour of female students.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Table 3: Summary of Linear Regression Analysis of Relationship between Marital Instability and Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	R - value	Remark
1	Regression	65.451	1	65.451	410.035	.000 ^b	.718 ^b	H ₀₁ rejected
	Residual	61.614	386	.160				
	Total	127.065	387					

Source: Researcher's Analysis of Field Survey, 2022

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- a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Marital instability

Analysis in Table 3 shows Linear regression results conducted to test whether any significant relationship exist between marital instability and students’ academic performance. The results show that there is significant relationship between marital instability and students’ academic performance, $F_{(1, 387)} = 410.035$, $p < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is significant relationship between marital instability and students’ academic performance.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females Students due to marital instability in Chikun Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Table 4: Summary of Independent Sample t – test of Difference in the Achievement Scores of Males and Females due to Marital Instability

Gender	N	Mean	S. D	df	t – value	P – value	Remark
M	188	59.32	17.01	386	-0.611	.541	H ₀₂ retained
F	200	60.44	18.68				

Analysis in Table 4 shows the result of t – test carried out to test whether significant difference exist in the achievement scores of male and female students due to marital instability. The results show that there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability, $t_{(386, 0.05)} = -0.611$, $p > 0.05$. This implies that the null hypothesis is retained, that is there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between marital instability and students’ academic achievement. The finding agrees with that of Clarke, Vandell, McCartney, Owen, and Booth (2000) who found that marital conflicts at homes have negative impact on family characteristics and processes like economic position and parental responsiveness, and are associated with the children's cognitive performance. A similar finding was reported by Sun and Liin(2002) who found out that children in separated or divorced families performed more poorly on tests of cognitive ability at the age of 15 and 24 months than that of children from continuously married and intact families. This situation proves that parental marital conflict or instability affects students’ academic achievement.

The finding that there is a significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement holds important implications for both academia and society at large. This result underscores the interconnectedness of family dynamics and educational outcomes, shedding light on the potential impact of marital instability on students' performance in academic settings. The finding highlights the crucial role that the family environment plays in shaping students' academic achievement. Marital instability can introduce emotional turmoil, stress, and disruptions into the lives of students. Such disturbances may affect their ability to concentrate on studies, engage effectively in the learning process, and perform well academically. Marital instability often leads to emotional distress, anxiety, and feelings of insecurity among children. These negative emotions can have a direct impact on cognitive functioning and academic engagement. Students who experience marital instability at home might struggle with maintaining focus, managing their emotions, and coping with the challenges of schoolwork.

The findings also revealed that there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability. The finding is in consonant with that of Frost and Pakiz (1990) whose findings revealed no differences in various effects of marital conflicts between girls and boys. The researchers found no gender difference for self-reported anti-social behavior among adolescents from divorce families although, they found gender differences in other areas (such as truancy and social network). This result is agreement with the argument of Hetherington, 1989 as cited by Lester and Russell (2010) that boys and girls experience some disruption in play situations. In the same vein, the findings is in collaboration with that of Oyeromi, Olaolu, Fadokun and Omiyale (2018) who found that there is no significant difference between male and female students in their experience of family marital conflict.

The finding that there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability is an important result that contributes to our understanding of how gender might interact with the impact of family

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dynamics on academic performance. The finding suggests that, in the context of marital instability, both male and female students are similarly affected in terms of their academic achievement. This highlights a level of gender equality in how family dynamics, specifically marital instability, influence students' performance in educational settings. The absence of a significant difference in achievement scores between genders might indicate that marital instability affects students' academic performance irrespective of their gender. Both male and female students might experience similar emotional and psychological challenges stemming from family disruptions, which in turn impact their ability to focus, study effectively, and engage in their education.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that students who experience marital instability in their families tend to have different academic outcomes compared to those from stable family backgrounds. It is also concluded that both male and female students appear to be equally affected (or unaffected) by marital instability in terms of their academic performance.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. All marriage stakeholders should put every effort solve marital crises in order to save the couples from broken home and save the children from adverse consequences of marital instability.
2. Government should develop support programs and interventions that do not differentiate between male and female students but are designed to help all students cope with the potential challenges arising from marital instability.

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Effect of 5E's Instructional Model ... (Suleiman & John, 2023)

Effect of 5E's Instructional Model on Performance in Concept of Cell Division among Secondary School Students in Sokoto State, Nigeria

*Suleiman, Sa'adu Matazu¹

Email: saadu.matazu@udusok.edu.ng

Tel: 08065604343

John, Danladi¹

Email: danladijohn360@gmail.com

Tel: 07036952876

¹Department of Science and Vocational Education, Faculty of Education and Extension Services,
Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

Abstract

The study investigated the Effect of 5E's instructional Model on Performance in Concept of Cell Division among Secondary School Students in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of 14, 567 Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2021/2022 academic session in the six educational zones. Total sample of five hundred and twelve (512) Senior Secondary School class two students were used for the study. Purposive sampling technique was employed and instrument used for collection of data is Cell Division performance test (CDPT). The instrument was validated by experts in the department of Biological sciences Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and experienced secondary school biology teachers and reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Two objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and Standard Deviation. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance using Analysis of Covariance the three hypotheses were rejected. The findings of the study shows that students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model outperformed better than those taught using conventional method. The findings also revealed that female students taught using 5's instructional model performed better than their male counterpart. The study recommended among others that teachers should be trained on the use of 5E's instructional strategy in teaching cell division concepts.

Keyword: 5E's Instructional Model, Academic Performance and Cell Division

Introduction

Education is a fundamental human right and the structural key to sustainable development, peace and stability of a nation. In Nigeria, education is perceived as an instrument for achieving national objectives. Science and technology have been playing a major role towards the growth and development of any given nation. Biology as one of science subjects most especially in the secondary schools is key and paramount in science endeavor. According to the National Policy on Education (NPE 2013), the objective of biology at the senior school level is to develop interest in the subject, acquire interest in science, technology and mathematics, to apply scientific skills, to meet societal needs. Education is an instrument per excellence for the achievement of national development. One major key of Nigeria vision 20-20 is to provide students with vibrant and modern science education system that will provide meaningful learning (NPE, 2013). This opens opportunity for students to achieve maximum potentials and provide the nation with adequate and competent man power needs. Biology is a unique branch of natural sciences, however, like other natural sciences; it is concerned with the search for in-depth understanding of natural phenomena and events. Several studies such as that of Nelvin (2017), Mohammed (2016), Ibrahim (2015), Jesulowo (2019), were carried out to improve teaching and learning of biology.

The shift to inquiry-based pedagogical practices in the classroom may necessitate a transition from textbook-dependency as the main resource of science information to a more hands-on approach, where students are central to the learning episodes. Recent research findings have shown that an inquiry-based approach is beneficial to students and that even young children can learn through inquiry processes (Santrock, 2011). Despite the investment in science education, to meet up with the present challenge of the 21st century, Students' performance at SSCE had still been recorded very low in biology when compared with the number of enrolment of students over the years. (Okoli, 2015 Mohammed & Sakiyo 2017). The Chief Examiners report on Senior Secondary School Students achievement in biology revealed that, the subject had both the highest

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enrolment relative to other science subjects and recorded poor achievement in the senior school certificate examination (SSCE). Adeduran, (2001), Ajajun and Tayo (2007), observed that Nigerian Educational system is still confronted with poor academic performance. Aderogba (2006), is of the view that the academic performance of students in biology includes observation and measurable behavior of students at any point during a course, either in theory or practical. The academic performance consist of the students' scores at any particular time obtain from a teacher made test. In other words, academic performance can be placed with observed behavior or expectation of achieving a specific statement of objective. Researches have been conducted on factors which could affect the academic performance of students in sciences in an attempt to find out why students performances have been low (Unuroh,2004; Okebukola, 2005; Olanrewaju, 2009). Such studies considered students competence, instructional strategies and difficulties encountered in problem solving and learning outcomes.

Sokoto State Government however, are still implementing all necessary initiatives that will help to boost the morale of students in attaining educational success of students and teachers as a result of lack of tangible improvement in academic performance (Benevino, 2015). Secondary school students' performance in Biology have made Sokoto States government to embark on many measures to ensure effective teaching and learning. One of such measures was the free Science extra academic coaching for SS classes sponsored by the then executive governor of Sokoto State in 2016 (Aliyu Foundation, 2016). According to the Ministry of Education report on performance trend Sokoto State was among the States that was recorded to have 23.15% of 5 credits points and above (WAEC, 2019). This is still an indication of the decrease in the credit level of academic performance in school results. To improve student's engagement performance in classroom and to facilitates the use of more effective instructional model that will enable the students to learn more, retain more and apply what is learned. Several versions of learning models have been proposed ranging from 3E's to 7E's.

5E's instructional model is a consequence of constructivist learning theory which basically asserts that students construct their own knowledge. It is this situation that motivated the researcher to investigate the impact of 5E's instructional model on performance, in cell division among Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State Nigeria. There is a need to engage in significant and appealing activities. As a result, the 5E instructional model may be appropriate in this regard. The 5E's instructional model is a type of constructivist approach that can be used in biology to increase the quality of teaching and learning. Bybee (2002) asserted that the use of 5Es instructional model can helps students redefine, organize, examine and change the ideas they already have through interacting with their peers and environment. According to Bybee (2002), the 5E's instructional model is a technology enriched model which enable the learners to develop 21st century skills as well as the teachers to teach specific concept in biology and to provide good reform-based instruction. The cycle consists of cognitive stages of learning that begins with letter E engage, explore, explain, elaborate, and evaluate. Science teachers and curriculum developers may integrate or apply the model at several levels. The model can be the organizing pattern of a sequence of daily lessons, individual units, or yearly plans. Each phase of the 5E Instructional Learning Cycle is described as follows;

The engage phase enable the teacher as an instructor to open a lesson with an activity or questions meant to engage students, snag their interest, and offer the opportunity for them to share what they already know. This phase is aims to assess student prior knowledge and or identify possible misconceptions. This student-centered phase should be a motivational period that can create a desire to learn more about the upcoming concept. Students may brainstorm an opening question or ask themselves: "What do I already know about this concept?" Discrepant events, demonstrations, questioning, or graphic organizers may be included to create interest or generate curiosity. Students are to brainstorm and record what they Know, want to know, and (eventually) have Learned about the concept.

The Exploration phase following an engagement phase, promotes a mental focus on the concept, the exploration phase provides the students with a common, concrete learning experience. This phase is also student-centered and incorporates active exploration. Students are encouraged to apply process skills, such as observing, questioning, investigating, testing predictions, hypothesizing, and communicating, with other peers. This phase of the learning model tends to incorporate the main inquiry-based activity or experience, which encourages students to develop skills and concepts. The teacher's role is one of facilitator or consultant. In addition, students are encouraged to work in a cooperative learning environment without direct instruction from the teacher. This phase is also unique because the students are given a "hands-on" experience before any formal explanation of terms, definitions, or concepts are discussed or explained by the teacher.

The Explanation phase is a "minds-on" phase following the exploration phase, and this is more teacher-directed and guided by the students' prior experience during the exploration phase. The explanation phase enables students to describe their understanding and pose questions about the concepts they have been exploring. It is likely that new questions will be generated. The explanation phase is an essential, minds-on part of the 5E lesson. Before the teacher attempts to provide an explanation, the students must first have the opportunity to express their own explanations and ideas. Thus, the initial part of the explanation

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phase is a time for the teacher to serve as a facilitator and ask the students to describe and discuss their exploration learning experiences. After the students have had the opportunity to share their own explanations, the teacher introduces scientific and technical information in a direct manner. This phase includes clarification of student misconceptions that may have emerged during the engagement or exploration phases. Formal definitions, notes, and labels are provided. The teacher may also decide to integrate video, computer software programs, power point presentations or other visual aides to help with student understanding. The students should then be able to clearly explain the important concepts to the teacher and to their peers.

Elaboration phase activities of the learning cycle should encourage students to apply their new understanding of concepts, while reinforcing new skills. Students are encouraged to check for understanding with their peers, or to design new experiments or models based on the new skills or concepts they have acquired. The goal of this phase is to help develop deeper and broader understandings of the concepts. Students may conduct additional investigations, develop products, share information and ideas, or apply their knowledge and skills to other disciplines. This is a great opportunity to integrate science with other content areas. Elaboration activities may also integrate technology, such as web-based research or Web Quests.

Evaluation phase is the assessment inquiry-based setting which is very different from traditional science lessons. Both formal and informal assessment approaches are appropriate, and should be included. For instance, the use of non-traditional forms of assessment, such as portfolios, performance-based assessment, concept maps, physical models, or journal logs may serve as significant evidence of student learning. During an inquiry-based lesson, assessment should be viewed as an ongoing process, with teachers making observations of their students as they apply new concepts and skills and looking for evidence that the students have changed or modified their thinking. Students may also have the opportunity to conduct self-assessment or peer-assessment

Several studies have been reviewed on the efficacy of 5E's instructional model on academic performance such as Nelvin (2017) who conducted a meta-analysis study to evaluate the effect of the 5E learning model on academic achievement, and scientific process skills. The result of the study shows that 5E learning model had an effect on the students' academic achievement, attitude towards science and science process skills. To determine the effects of learning cycle as an instructional strategy on biology students' achievement, Ajaja and Eravwoke (2012) included two instructional groups (experimental and control groups). The samples of the study were six senior secondary schools with 112 science students, and 12 biology teachers. The instruments used for this study were: teacher's questionnaire on knowledge and use of learning cycle (KULC); on Biology Achievement Test (BAT). The data collected were analyzed with simple percentage, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and student t-test statistics. The major findings of the study revealed that, only 30.43% and 26.31% of biology teachers have the knowledge that learning cycle as an instructional method; all the biology teachers sampled have never used learning cycle as an instructional method; learning cycle had a significant effect on students' achievement in biology. Students taught with learning cycle significantly achieved better in biology Post-test than those taught with lecture method; the post-test scores of students in the 5E's learning cycle group increased over the period of experience; It was concluded that the method seems to be an appropriate instructional model that could be used to solve the problems of science teaching and learning since it facilitates learning and retention

The impact of using 5E's Instructional Model on academic achievement in biology and retention of learning among fifth grade students was investigated by Mohammed (2016). Experiment group were 30 student, and control group were 29 students. Pre and post tests were used to determine the difference in the two groups. Experiment group was taught using the 5E's instructional model. T-test was used to check the significant difference between experiment and control group after experiment. It is explored that both the groups were equal regarding their achievement scores in pre-test before the experiment, but after experiment both were different in their achievement test scores in favor of experiment group. It is concluded that this significant performance of experiment group may be due to use of 5E's instructional model. The study recommended that modern and practical instructional techniques using constructivist approaches would enhance the need to improve students learning at the elementary schools. Appropriate training for teachers to use (5E's) instructional model to teach mathematics would enhance the active learning. The findings of Odagboyi (2015) who examined the effect of gender on the achievement of students in biology using the 5E's method. Results shows that there was a significant difference between the mean scores in favor of the female. This implies that the females gained more from the 5E's instructional; method compared with the males.

The investigation of the effects of 5E learning model on creativity, performance and retention in ecology among Secondary school Students in Zaria Education Zone was done by Jesulowo (2019). The result of the study shows that the experimental group had significantly higher scores than conventional lecture method group. The study recommended that teachers should be encourage to use 5E instructional model to teach ecology concepts in secondary schools.

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The investigation of gender differences in biology academic achievements levels using 5Es instructional model among secondary school students in Kenya. Was carried out by Busola (2012) who found out that girls performed better than boys.

The impact of 5E's teaching cycle on attitude retention and performance in genetics among Pre-NCE students with varied ability conducted by Ibrahim (2015), revealed that Pre-NCE students exposed to 5E's teaching cycle showed better performance when compared to those not expose to it. The study also recommended that the, teaching of biology especially genetics should be conducted using 5Es' teaching cycle as it makes students learn meaningfully, enhance better performance and retention of knowledge and develop positive attitude towards the subject. The investigation of gender differences among biology students in a cooperative class was carried out by Mathew and Young (2007) who conducted a study on 149 students, not randomly selected in biology. They found there was a significant difference in the performance females with regard to the males. The mean Scores of the females were higher than that of males.

The fluctuating trend in Senior Secondary School Students Performance in external examination in Biology has become a source of worry to researchers in science education. Many factors have been identified to be responsible for this menace. This include the use of inappropriate and non-effective teaching methodology, students lack of interest, existence of abstract concepts, student's misconception of science, improper use of instructional materials, large class size, lack of well-trained teachers, constant use of lecture method and over loaded curriculum. Table 1 below depicts the fluctuating trends of student's performance in Biology.

Table 1: Trends of Students' Performance in May \ June Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination in Biology, 2016 to 2022.

Year	Total Students that Sat	No of Students with C6 and above	% Percentage Pass	% Parentage Fail
2016	1646150	587040	35.66	64.34
2017	1648363	736970	44.70	55.30
2018	1365384	685970	50.02	49.98
2019	1471151	583486	39.66	60.34
2020	1572396	758424	48.23	51.77
2021	1522321	647212	23.51	76.49
2022	1628356	623873	26.10	73.90

Source: West African Examination Council (WAEC 2022) National Head Office Yaba, Lagos

Table 1 shows the fluctuating trend in Nigerian Secondary Student Performance in West African Senior School Certificate Examination in Biology, between 2016 to 2020. In 2016, only 35.66% of students passed out of the total enrolment of 1,646,150. The trend increased in 2017 and 2018 to 44.70% and 50.02%. While 39.66% and 48.23% in 2019 and 2020 respectively. There was a decrease in students' performance in 2019, which recorded 39.66% credit pass. The performance is not satisfactory acceptable because 64.34%, 55.3%, 60.34% and 51.77% of the students failed which is still large. The concern of every well-meaning stakeholder in education is therefore expected to be geared towards improving the performance of students in Biology with a view to reducing the percentage failure and upgrading the percentage pass. The WAEC chief examiners Reports consistently claim that there is the need for students to improve in understanding and application of cell division, genetics concepts and principles, laws and theories. Despite the emphasis and importance of various teaching methods and facilities in science process, there is still a high rate of failure in biology. This is as a result of the poor presentation of Biology by teachers as abstract and uninteresting subject. The findings of previous studies Ibrahim 2015, Mohammed 2016, Ajaja and Erawoke 2012 and Jesulowo 2019 Shows that students have difficulties, misconceptions and confusion in cell division. This makes students hate the topic and the situation lead to poor performance of students in biology especially at the Senior Secondary School Level. The prevailing teaching method does not allow active students participation in biology lessons. Students only memorize and regurgitate facts and concepts. However, some teachers are not aware of the significant suitable method due to inadequate knowledge or perhaps low professional training. Teachers are not competent enough to adapt hard but suitable method.

Therefore, 5E's instructional model is the hard but suitable 21st century constructivist- oriented teaching approach which improves the teaching of science by actively engaging learners in authentic practical investigation that enable them to develop more realistic ideas about scientific study as well as offer a more motivating and learner-centered environment. Education Researchers found out that the use of 5E's instructional approach could assist teachers and learners, promote positive change in students attitude. Towards learning, increase student's willingness to learn and foster performance (Opara, 2011).

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The problem of this study therefore is about effects of 5E's Instructional Model on Students Academic Performance in cell division among senior secondary schools' students in Sokoto State Nigeria. How can the use of 5E's instructional Model improve academic performance in Sokoto State?

Objectives of the study

1. Investigate the differences in academic performance between secondary school students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model and those exposed to cooperative method State the objective in clear, unambiguous and should reflect thrust of the study.
2. Investigate the differences in academic performance between secondary school male and female students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested in the study

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference between academic performance of secondary school students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model and those exposed to conventional method.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference between academic performance of secondary school male and female students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model.

Methodology

The study adopted quasi experimental research design. the subjects were grouped into two groups experimental and control group. The experimental group were exposed to 5E's instructional model while the control group were exposed to conventional method. Both groups were subjected to pre-test and post-test. The population comprises of 14, 567 SSII students drawn from the six educational zone in Sokoto State. The total schools in the six educational zone is 118. One school was selected randomly in each zone and two intact classes were used in each school, comprising of 123 males and 389 females. Purposive sampling technique was employed to select a total of 512 students for the study. The instrument used for data collection was Cell Division Performance (CDPT) which contains 30 relevant items on cell division drawn from past WAEC and NECO questions. The researcher considers questions from WAEC and NECO appropriate because they have already been standardized. The instrument was validated by experts from the Department of Science and Vocational Education and the Department of Biological Sciences of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto. The reliability of the instrument (BPT) was established using Split-half method during the pilot study at the pretest stage. Two public Secondary Schools that were not part of the sample of this study was selected for this exercise. The experimental group was taught cell division using 5E's while the control group was taught cell division using cooperative method. The scores of the instruments were computed and split into odd and even numbers. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to correlate the scores and obtained the index of 0.61. This is the reliability of the half of the instrument. The index was beefed up using Prophecy formula to obtain the reliability index of 0.85 for the whole instrument. This is considered high enough for administration. All the research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while inferential statistics was used to test the null hypotheses on performance. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was most appropriate for the research since the subjects are not randomized and the data contain pre-test and post-test.

Results

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between academic performance of secondary school students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model and those exposed to conventional method.

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Table 2: Summary of Tests Between-Subjects Effects of 5E's Instructional Model and Cooperative Method on Performance of Students in Cell Division

Source of Variance	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	η^2
Corrected Model	7756.82	2	3878.413	347.721	.000	.577
Intercept	2939.050	1	2939.050	263.502	.000	.341
Pre-test scores	166.722	1	166.722	14.948	.000	.029
Strategy	4087.215	1	4087.215	366.442	.000	.419
Error	5677.282	509	11.154			
Total	214531.000	512				
Corrected Total	13434.107	511				

Table 2 revealed the result of a one-way between-group analysis of covariance conducted to determine the difference in the performance of students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model with those taught using cooperative method. The independent variable was instructional method (5E's & Cooperative), and the dependent variable consisted of post-test scores on Biology Performance Test (BPT) administered after the intervention was completed. Biology Performance Test (BPT) administered before intervention were used as the covariate in this analysis. After the effect of pre-test scores (covariate) has been partial out, the result revealed that there was a significant difference between the post-test scores of experimental (5E's) and control (cooperative method) groups taught cell division using 5E's instructional model and those taught using cooperative method. ($F(1, 509) = 366.422, p = .000, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .419$). Since p value is less than .05, the stated null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, this result implies that there was a significant difference in the performance of students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model with those taught using cooperative method. Experimental treatments were able to account for 41.9% of the observed variance noticed in the dependent variable.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between academic performance of secondary school male and female students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model.

Table 3: Summary of Tests Between-Subjects Effects of Gender on Performance of Students taught Cell Division using 5E's Instructional Model

Source of Variance	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	η^2
Corrected Model	2679.774	2	1339.887	162.300	.000	.540
Intercept	2621.810	1	2621.810	317.578	.000	.535
Pre-test scores	101.924	1	101.924	12.346	.001	.043
Gender	2572.963	1	2572.963	311.661	.000	.530
Error	2278.555	279	8.256			
Total	156905.000	281				
Corrected Total	4958.330	280				

η^2 = Eta Squared

Table 3 revealed the result of a one-way between-group analysis of covariance conducted to determine the gender difference in the performance of students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model. The independent variable was gender (male & female), and the dependent variable consisted of post-test scores on Biology Performance Test (BPT) administered after the intervention was completed. Biology Performance Test (BPT) administered before intervention were used as the covariate in this analysis. After the effect of pre-test scores (covariate) has been partial out, the result revealed that there was a significant difference between the post-test scores of male and female students taught using 5E's instructional model ($F(1, 276) = 311.661, p = .000, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .530$). Since p-value is less than .05, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This result implies that there was a significant difference between academic performance of secondary school male and female students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model. Gender was able to account for 53.0% of the observed variance noticed in the dependent variable.

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Discussion of Finding

The paper investigated the Effect of 5E's instructional Model on Performance in Concept Cell Division among Secondary School Students in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Table 1 shows Tests Between-Subjects Effects of 5E's Instructional Model and Cooperative Method on Performance of Students in Cell Division ($F(1, 509) = 366.422, p = .000, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .419$). Since p value is less than .05, the stated null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, this result implies there is significant difference between academic performance of secondary school students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model and those exposed to conventional method. The study agrees with the findings of Ajaja and Eravwoke (2012). They determine the effects of 5E's learning cycle as an instructional strategy on biology and students' achievement. The result shows that 5E's learning model had a significance effects on the student's academic achievements in biology. The post-test scores of students in the 5E's learning cycle group increased over the period of experience.

The result of the study of Jesulowo (2019) which investigated the effects of 5E learning model on creativity, performance and retention in ecology among Secondary school Students in Zaria Education Zone shows that the experimental group had significantly higher scores than conventional lecture method group. This result is unanimous with the findings of this presents study. Similarly, this study also agrees with the findings of Ibrahim (2015), on the impact of 5E's teaching cycle on attitude retention and performance in genetics among Pre-NCE students with varied ability revealed that Pre-NCE students exposed to 5E's teaching cycle has better performance when compared to those not expose to it and therefore, encourage the teaching of biology with the use of 5E's instructional model as it makes students learn meaningfully, and enhance better performance.

Table 2 shows Tests Between-Subjects Effects of Gender on Performance of Students taught Cell Division using 5E's Instructional Model the findings shows that there was a significant difference between the post-test scores of male and female students taught using 5E's instructional model ($F(1, 276) = 311.661, p = .000, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .530$). Since p -value is less than .05, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Female students have a significant higher mean score than their male counterparts when taught using 5E's instructional model. Gender was able to account for 53.0% of the observed variance noticed in the dependent variable. The findings of this study contradict the results of the investigation conducted by Ibrahim (2015) And Jesulowo (2019) who investigated the effect of gender and the academic performance of students taught ecology using 5E learning model. The result of the study shows that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of both male and female students taught Ecology using 5E-Learning model. Both male and female students have relatively the same level of increased academic performance.

The present study agrees with the result of Busola (2012) who investigated gender differences in Biology achievements levels among secondary school students in Kenya. The findings revealed that, girls performed better than boys. The findings of the present study also agree with the result of Odagboyi (2015) who examined the effect of gender on the achievement of students in biology using the 5E's instructional method. Results shows that there was a significant difference between the mean scores in favor of the female. This implies that the females gained more from the use of 5E's instructional method compared with the males.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of this study, it was concluded that there was a significant difference in the performance of students taught cell division using 5E's Instructional model with those taught using cooperative method. It was also discovered that there was a significant difference in the performance of male and female students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model. 5E's instructional model is not gender friendly as it is very effective for the enhancement of female students' performance in cell division concepts. Female students have a significant higher mean score than their male counterparts when taught using 5E's instructional model. When the effects of cooperative method on performance of gender was investigated, it was found that there was a significant difference between male and female students taught using cooperative method.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were based on the findings of this study

1. It is recommended that teachers should be trained in the use of 5E's as instructional strategy in teaching cell division concept because the study shows that it is more effective than cooperative method.
2. The use of 5E's Instructional Model should be encouraged among male and female students through careful supervision.
3. It is recommended that in cooperative learning strategy, integration of groups should be encouraged.

Effect of 5E's Instructional Model ... (Suleiman & John, 2023)

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Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy on Abstract Creative-Thinking Skill in Basic Science among Secondary School Students in Gboko, Benue State

Ayua, Geoffrey Aondolumun¹

Email: ayuageoffrey@gmail.com,

Gamat, Grace Bala²

Email: gracegamatnendi@gmail.com,

Agbidye, Anna³

Email: annagbidye@gmail.com

Terhemba, Wisdom Kwaghfan⁴

Email: kwatexwisdom@gmail.com

^{1,3&4}Department of Science & Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

²Department of Integrated Science, Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya, Nigeria

Abstract

Effect of Creative-Teaching strategy on abstract creative-thinking skill in basic science was investigated using pretest and post-test quasi experimental research design. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. A multistage sample of 70 (34 males and 36 females) students was drawn from two intact classes of a population of 674 (356 male and 318 female) students in all government secondary schools (government grant aided schools only) in Gboko, Benue state, during the 2021/2022 academic session. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking instrument with reliability coefficient of 0.83 was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistic. Data were analyzed using mean and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Findings showed no significant difference in the ACT among varied-ability students within the teaching methods, $F(2, 63) = 0.319, p(0.728) > 0.05$. However, those taught Basic Science using CT exhibited significantly higher ACS than those taught using Lecture Method. $F(1, 63) = 39.117, p(0.000) < 0.05$. Moreso, no significant difference existed in the students' ACS based on gender $F(2, 28) = 0.791, p(0.463) > 0.05$. It was concluded that abstract creative-thinking skill among varied-ability students was enhanced without gender disparity, if Basic Science is taught using Creative Teaching. Therefore, Creative Teaching was recommended for teaching science at the basic education level.

Keywords: Creative-Teaching (CT), Abstract Creative-thinking Skill (ACS), Basic Science, Varied-ability and Gender.

Introduction

Education is the strength, wealth for national building and above all a key instrument to make learners at basic, post-basic and tertiary education to live and flourish in the 21st century. Also, the global community wants people who have the capacity that could face thought-provoking socio-economic situations and could solve up-to-date unemployment, poverty and pandemic problems. It is important to note that one of these capabilities is Abstract Creative-thinking Skill (ACS), which is an aspect of creative thinking. Abstract Creative-thinking Skill (ACS) refers to the degree beyond labelling; based on an idea that creativity requires an abstraction of thought (Terhemba et al., 2023). Creativity is an indescribable idea, hitherto it creates a significant facet of daily living. Therefore, as teaching methods and resources are the bases of effective classroom instruction, science objectives as incorporated in the policy document on education in Nigeria can be boosted through creativity that encompasses the nature of ACS which may lead to cultivating productivity into students at the basic education level. Basic education level is the foundational class to which any further study of sciences can be built and if students at this level are nurtured with ACS, hopefully productivity, economic growth, development and sustainability may have its course since science has to do with our environment.

Science is a creative endeavour of the human mind. To understand the natural world, scientists discover new problems, think of multiple ways to approach problems, come up with hypotheses, figure out how to collect meaningful data, explain

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those data, and come up with new theories (Peng, 2019). Those scientific thinking processes require creative thinking such as the application of analogy, metaphor, brainstorming, lateral thinking, imagination and all these may have to do with abstract thinking. An example of how scientists used creative thinking during scientific discovery, for instance, the wave theory of light was derived from an analogy between light and sound, the idea that the earth was a giant magnet and was created from many shared properties between the planet earth and magnet (Peng, 2019). Scientists develop new and useful ideas, which correspond to the description of abstract creative thinking that may yield productivity and sustainability. Therefore, it is unquestionable that science for productivity and sustainability maybe real if students gain abstract creative thinking through creative teaching.

Creative Teaching (CT) is tending to create classroom instruction excellently and in a novel style, teaching creatively and teaching for creativity. Creative-teaching of Basic Science refers to demonstrating how to think skilfully amidst tactics, resources in Basic Science content for inspiring learning and fostering students' creativity using Torrance incubation model and exhibiting creative-teaching behaviours (Ayua & Eriba, 2023). Ismail et al (2018) viewed it as involving teachers making learning more interesting and effective; using imaginative approaches or exhibiting the behaviours during lessons. It involves teachers making learning more interesting and effective and using imaginative approaches or exhibiting Creative Teaching Behaviours (CTB) during science classroom interactions (Suhvan; Cremin as cited in Terhemba, 2022) and giving room for effective teaching and learning to occur among different ability learners in science education. This could be why McFinn (2015) confirmed that it is based on individuals' needs and abilities, which need freedom in learning as an active mode that influences innovative personality development, which creates something exceptional and turns it into an entrepreneurial activity for productivity and ensuing sustainability.

There are several creative teaching models which include Misutova's (2003) as cited in Ayua (2021) Creative-Teaching Model which was developed for mathematics and technical courses of basic study at the university level; and Schnapp's (2018) Creativity Pedagogical Model which is targeted for teachers and education institutions. However, Torrance Incubation Model (TIM) of creative teaching and learning which can be applied at any level of education was emphasized and adopted for this study. TIM of creative teaching and learning is a 3-stage (heightening anticipation, deepening expectations and keeping it going) model for delivering both subject and content. According to Torrance and Safter (as cited in, Terhemba, 2022), the model was designed to make teaching more effective in any subject at any age. TIM of creative teaching and learning can be applied to a lesson unit or project in any subject including Basic Science at the upper-basic school level with varied-ability students. Torrance (as cited in Ayua, et al., 2022) believed that people are inquisitive, exploring and searching kind of beings. Similarly, Bruner's (1960) theory of intellectual development, which states that learning is best through discovery and interaction with mental development advancing from non-abstract to abstract alongside age. It holds that knowledge via discovery is fundamental to learning and emphasizes that learning is by doing and thinking creatively. So, when given a choice, students would choose to learn creatively. They would continue to find problems and cannot keep from digging into things, turning ideas over in their minds, trying out new combinations, searching for new relationships and struggling for new, unique and abstract insights. Therefore, the link between this theory and creative teaching is linked to examine, if it could inculcate ACT to harness scientific creative-thinking knowledge for productivity and sustainability among varied-ability students in Basic Science.

Creative-thinking is the ability to come up with novel ideas and turn such ideas generated into fashionable, unique products for human use. Creativity is the interaction among aptitude, process, and environment by which an individual or group produces a perceptible product that is both novel and useful (Plucker & Begetto, as cited in Irugalbandara, 2020). A process of becoming understanding to problems, lacks, gaps in knowledge, missing essentials, conflicts, and so on; finding the difficulty; searching for answers, making guesses, or framing suggestions about the deficiencies; testing and retesting these hypotheses and possibly modifying and retesting them, and finally communicating the results (Torrance, as cited in Terhemba, 2022). It is one's cognitive process to generate effective ideas in solving problems under certain aims and conditions. Therefore, Torrance (as cited in Irugalbandara, 2020) identified what he termed five main elements of creative thinking: fluency, flexibility, elaboration, originality and abstractness of titles. To this end, abstractness of titles also known as abstract creative thinking was used for this study.

Abstract creative thinking has to do with Basic Science male and female students with varied-ability to think beyond normal description of available resources, items, problems and/or products. That is why Ng and Lee (2019) affirmed that it is the ability to go beyond a concrete physical description. Abstract creative thinking which goes beyond simple description relates to the subjects by synthesizing, organizing processes and thinking creatively with resources. At the highest level, there is an ability to capture the essence of the information involved, to know what is important, and to enable the viewer to see available resources more deeply and richly, where male and female students with varied-ability may use abstract creative

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thinking that go beyond simple description and communicate something unique about resources (Scholastic Testing Service, 2018). With this unusual trait required for carrying out successful entrepreneurial venture, if truly integrated in the classroom instruction, it may perhaps be assumed that male and female Basic Science students with varied-ability at the basic education level could think abstractly when posed with resources for productivity and keeping it going sustainability may have its course. Varied-ability in one way or the other is as old as man and cut across all areas of life including students' ability levels and Basic Science students at the basic education level not been an exception. Ability grouping according to Ikyernum (2022) is the practice of assigning students into different educational groups based on past academic performance and it is used synonymously with tracking and streaming of school learners. Maikano (2016) maintains that ability grouping is based on educators' judgments of students' abilities; and that when assigning students' to tracks, prior test scores or other performance measures provided from other grades or schools are used to determine the ability levels. In this study, Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME (2018) and Benue State Examinations Board – BSEB (2018), grading system with six performance grades (A-F) was used for the students into: High Ability Level (HAL) = A (75-100%) and B (65-74%); Average Ability Level (AAL) = C (55-64%) and D (45-54%); and Low Ability Level (LAL) = E (40-44%) and F (0-39%).

Gender variance is as old as the world and has been used severally in academic discourse. It is the nature of being masculine or feminine; gentleman or lady; lad or girl. Gender disparity according to Danjuma (2015) globally militates against equitable participation of boys and girls in science education especially in Africa. Ali et al (2014) submitted that females face a number of inequitable difficulties that limit their potentials in participation in the sciences. United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation - UNESCO as cited in Ikyernum (2022), females from over 50% of the world's active population make immense contributions to development, although they still face a number of inequitable difficulties that limit their potentials in participation in the science subjects. With such discourse, it is pertinent to look at previous empirical whether creative teaching on creativity is male and female with varied-ability biased or unbiased.

Ng and Lee (2019) investigated creative thinking of Hong Kong undergraduate students using the Torrance tests of creative thinking and found that the students tended to be good at producing a large number of relevant abstract thinking (abstractness of titles dimension) ideas. Similarly, Özgenel et al (2019) explored Creative Thinking of Hong Kong Undergraduate Students Using the Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking and found that the enriched workshop trainings given to the students have affected and developed the students' creative thinking skills (abstractness of titles inclusively) positively. Marzieh and Nesa (2016) examined Comparison of Creativity Dimensions between bilingual elementary students in Urmia City, Iran and found that the dimensions from creativity were significantly different between the two groups of bilingual students. Similarly, Midilli et al. (2022) examined Turkish gifted primary school students' creative thinking skills and found that in the abstractness of titles sub-dimension of students who received pre-school education scored significantly higher than the students who did not receive pre-school education and there was no significant difference between the scores of the students in TTCT based on gender. Moreso, Madar et al. (2019) facilitating Torrance Test of Creative Thinking in Malaysian TVET research: the initial step of inter-rater reliability determination indicated that the correlation among the three sets of marks for abstractness of titles were at an excellent level and not significantly different based on gender. Ulger and Morsunbul (2017) examined differences in creative thinking aspect: comparison of male and female students in Turkish university students and found that there was a significant difference between male and female university students on creative thinking skills in favour of female.

The previous study's findings used Torrance Test of Creative thinking (TTCT), creative thinking skills with different teaching methods and found useful results, however, gap still exist. These studies did not use TIM of creative teaching, the studies failed to consider students at basic education level with varied-ability and the studies were geographically limited to Nigeria. Therefore, there is the need to examine whether creative teaching could enhance one of these aspects of creativity among varied-ability students in Gboko. Creativity is an element like gold for functioning of children, young people, the old even the society at large, making it a necessary factor in a balanced and democratic education system and the global society in the 21st century for productivity and sustainability. Rosenstock and Riordan (2017) highlighted the role of creativity as a key disposition necessary in a modern, innovation economy, characterised by global and rapid change. In a similar vein, Bakhshi et al (2017) reported that skills such as creative problem solving, and also abilities including abstractness of titles, will be amongst those in extreme demand in future workforce. However, there is a problem between policy and practice due to poor teaching methods. Ayua and Agbidye (2020) established that the gap between policy and practice is occasioned by poor teaching methods resulting in unemployment due to lack of entrepreneurial creativity for self-reliance after school. Since the global economy is shifting to a new paradigm which people may be expected to have creativity skills, it is therefore, vital to

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develop new skills like abstract creative thinking in students. It is against this background that effect of creative-teaching strategy on abstract creative-thinking skill in basic science among secondary school students in Gboko, Benue state was studied.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were examined to:

1. Determine the Abstract Creative-thinking (ACS) of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using Creative Teaching (CT) and Lecture Method (LM).
2. Find the ACS of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using Creative Teaching (CT).

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean difference in ACS scores of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT and LM?
2. What is the mean difference in ACS scores of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ α -level:

1. There is no significant mean difference in the ACS scores of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT and LM.
2. There is no significant mean difference in the ACS scores of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design was used for this study. After pre-test, the experimental group was taught the topic “chemicals” using Creative Teaching (CT); while the control group was taught the same concept using Lecture Method (LM) for six weeks before post-test. This was to enhanced abstract creative thinking by producing unimaginable, novel, and unique product through abstract thinking. A multistage sample of 70 (34 males and 36 females) students was drawn from two intact classes of a population of 674 (356 males and 318 females) students in all government secondary schools (government grant aided schools only) in Gboko, Benue state in Benue state, during the 2021/2022 academic session. Firstly, the schools were stratified into two (2-single schools with 290 students and 5-mixed schools with 384 students). Secondly, the five schools were purposively selected (4 in Gboko-North and 1 in Gboko South) and this was because, the schools were co-educational. Creativity equivalence test was administered to the students in the five schools and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine students’ ACS homogeneity and equivalence. Out of the five schools, four schools in Gboko North had homogeneity and equivalence TTCT scores. To determine the Experimental and control group, the researcher casted a lot (A= Experimental Group, B = Control Group, C = Not involved in any group and D = None of the above) for the four schools since the four were homogeneous. Thirdly, the two schools that had correct draw from the lot, students in each of the schools were randomly assigned into 35 experimental and 35 control groups. This was for the purpose of honesty, objectivity, ensuring a bias-free sampling and assignment of subjects into groups.

Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data collection. Section “A” collected students’ bio data; while section ‘B’ had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students’ ACS in Basic Science. Students’ ability levels were determined based on previous term’s performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). TTCT-Figural B was validated by two experts: a senior lecturer in Mathematics Education and a Professor of Chemistry, both from the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi. The instrument was pilot tested on 15 Basic II students in one of the schools in Gboko other than the sample for the main study. A reliability coefficient of 0.83 was determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistic. Extraneous variables like group initial difference, group interaction effect and priming were controlled by homogeneity test, distant locations and impromptu tests respectively. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using two-way Analysis of Covariance due to normality of the distribution, homogeneity of variance, randomness of selection, data measured based on interval scale and independence of samples.

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Results

Research Question One

What is the mean difference in the ACS scores of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT and LM?

Table 1: ACS Mean and Standard Deviation of Students Taught Basic Science using Creative Teaching (CT) and those Taught using Lecture Method (LM).

Ability Level	Sample (n)	Teaching Method	TTCT-Pretest		TTCT-Posttest		\bar{x} Gain	\bar{x} Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	14	CT	2.04	1.480	4.93	1.678	2.89	2.51
	14	LM	2.80	1.917	2.42	1.384	0.38	
Average	9	CT	3.29	2.088	3.62	1.787	0.33	0.12
	11	LM	1.72	0.930	1.51	1.075	0.21	
Low	12	CT	2.27	1.029	4.47	2.529	2.20	1.83
	10	LM	1.84	0.901	1.47	1.313	0.37	
Cluster		CT	2.53		4.34		1.81	1.49
		LM	2.12		1.80		0.32	

The result in Table 1 shows the pre-test ACS mean scores among varied-ability students, between CT and LM with cluster means of 2.53 and 2.12. The Table also shows that all the ACT mean scores among varied-ability students in the CT were higher than those in the LM with cluster mean gain difference of 1.49.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in ACS scores of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT?

Table 2: ACS Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Taught Basic Science using Creative Teaching.

Ability Level	Sample (n)	Gender	TTCT-Pretest		TTCT-Posttest		\bar{x} Gain	\bar{x} Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	5	Male	1.24	0.868	5.36	1.717	4.12	1.91
	9	Female	2.48	1.602	4.69	1.709	2.21	
Average	7	Male	3.10	2.273	3.11	1.917	0.01	0.86
	4	Female	3.63	1.991	4.50	1.291	0.87	
Low	6	Male	2.33	0.999	4.62	2.550	2.29	0.22
	4	Female	2.18	1.220	4.25	2.872	2.07	
Cluster		Male	2.22		4.36		2.14	0.42
		Female	2.76		4.48		1.72	

The result in Table 2 shows the pre-test ACS mean scores among varied-ability levels between male and female students with cluster means of 2.22 and 2.76. The table also shows that the ACS mean scores in the post test between male and female students with cluster mean gains of 2.14 and 1.72 respectively.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant mean difference in the ACS scores of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT and LM.

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Table 3: Summary of Two-Way ANCOVA Analysis on ACS among Varied-ability Levels Based on Teaching Methods.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	130.476 ^a	6	21.746	7.693	.000	.423
Intercept	206.544	1	206.544	73.065	.000	.537
Pre TTCT	1.129	1	1.129	.399	.530	.006
Teaching Method	110.578	1	110.578	39.117	.000	.383
Varied Ability	15.252	2	7.626	2.698	.075	.079
Teaching Method * Varied Ability	1.805	2	.903	.319	.728	.010
Error	178.092	63	2.827			
Total	991.850	70				
Corrected Total	308.569	69				

a. R Squared = .423 (Adjusted R Squared = .368)

The result in Table 3 shows no significant difference in the ACS among varied-ability students within those taught Basic Science using CT and those taught using LM, $F(2, 63) = 0.319, p(0.728) > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. However, the table showed that student's ACS in the CT was better than those in the LM $F(1, 63) = 39.117, p(0.000) < 0.05$. The implication of this result is that, although creative teaching enhances ACS, it is not dependent on students' academic ability.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant mean difference in the ACS scores of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT.

Table 4: Summary of Two-Way ANCOVA Analysis on ACS among Varied-ability Levels Based on Gender.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	17.602 ^a	6	2.934	.689	.660	.129
Intercept	161.736	1	161.736	37.991	.000	.576
Pre TTCT	.267	1	.267	.063	.804	.002
Gender	.055	1	.055	.013	.910	.000
Varied Ability	8.328	2	4.164	.978	.389	.065
Gender * Varied Ability	6.737	2	3.369	.791	.463	.053
Error	119.201	28	4.257			
Total	810.010	35				
Corrected Total	136.803	34				

a. R Squared = .129 (Adjusted R Squared = -.058)

The result in Table 4 reveals that no significant difference existed in ACS among varied-ability male and female students taught Basic Science using CT, $F(2, 28) = 0.791, p(0.463) > 0.05$. The null hypothesis was therefore, not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Within creative teaching and lecture method, students' Abstract Creative-thinking Skill (ACS) were not significant different among varied-ability levels. However, students' ACS in the creative teaching was higher than those in the lecture method. With regards to field experience, the finding is not anomalous because students in the creative teaching were engaged through heightening anticipation, deepening expectation and keeping it going. They tickle their imaginations, acquire and create ideas, look beyond the information on the surface, give abstract description and find what was beneath all the resources. With ACS, Basic Science students construct their knowledge and use resources for productivity and if allowed it will enhance sustainability. This study agrees with Ng and Lee (2019) who found that the students tended to be good at producing a large number of relevant abstract thinking (abstractness of titles dimension), Özgenel et al. (2019) who found that the enriched workshop trainings given to the students have affected and developed the students' creative thinking skills (abstractness of titles inclusively) positively. Similarly, this study concord with Marzieh and Nesa (2016) who found that the dimensions from

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creativity were significantly different between the two groups of bilingual students. The study also agrees with Midilli et al. (2022) who found that students who received pre-school education scored significantly higher than the students who did not receive pre-school education and Madar et al. (2019) who indicated that the correlation among the three sets of marks for abstractness of titles were at an excellent level.

Regarding students' ACS based on gender, no significant difference existed in ACS between male and female students with varied-ability levels taught Basic Science using creative teaching. This implies that, creative teaching on ACS is without gender disparity among different ability levels in Basic Science students. Following field experience, the finding is not bizarre since both boys and girls explored their ideas, constructed and used available resources for productivity and with expectation of more resources for future visions and/or sustainability through active involvement in creative teaching and learning processes. This study agrees with Midilli et al (2022) who found that there was no significant difference between the scores of the students in TTCT and gender. The study also agrees with Madar et al. (2019) indicated that the correlation among the three sets of marks for abstractness of titles were not significantly different based on gender. Dissimilarly, this study disagrees with Ulger and Morsunbul (2017) who found that there was a significant difference between male and female university students on creative thinking skills in favour of female. This difference may occur as the results of variation in the teaching method, location, and probably time and space.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that ACS among varied-ability students was enhanced without gender disparity, if Basic Science is taught using Creative Teaching.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were advanced:

1. Teachers not only at the upper basic school level, should be trained by the Federal, State Ministries of Education and other stakeholders through seminars, workshops on how to effectively utilize Creative Teaching.
2. Government through the Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers to maximize Creative Teaching lesson delivery.
3. Teacher training institutions in Nigeria should include constructive teaching strategies such as creative teaching in the teacher training programmes.
4. School proprietors, head and parents' teachers' association should provide materials/funds needed by teachers for creative teaching of Basic Science at basic education level.

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Effective Utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Tools in Management of large class size in Nigerian Universities: Challenges and Way forward

*Shehu, Suleiman Abdullahi Ph.D.¹

Email: shehusuleman78@gmail.com

Tel: 07033674799/08027303904

Bello, Abdulaziz¹

Tel: 08030776713

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Federal University, Gusau PMB-1001, Gusau-Zamfara State

Abstract

The paper examined Effective Utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Tools in Management of large class size in Nigerian Universities: Challenges and Way forward. This is because, the current developments have opened up opportunities for educationists to design and implement Information and Communication Technology (ICT) based lessons especially in tertiary institutions of learning where there are explosion and overcrowding of students. It was based on this premises that, the paper conceptualized ICT Tools in education; Identified the broad objectives of its use and they include: Providing accessibility through online medium of education; Improving the quality of teaching, especially in remote areas and To increase transparency in the education system. Similarly, It Discussed specific ICT Tools for managing large classes in the Nigeria universities' such as: Mobile learning tools; Cloud computing; Individualized learning resources. Highlight and discussed educational advantages of the use of ICT Tools in managing large class which include: Individualization of learning; Online learning & Accessibility to all. Moreso, the paper identified the theoretical framework and explain major challenges affecting the use of ICT Tools in managing large classes and these were: Basic technology infrastructure in Nigerian Universities; Access, Equity and Quality; Training and Technical Support. Furthermore, Conclusion and recommendations on the utilization of ICT tools were enlisted and such recommendations include: Basic technology infrastructure, needed and required for effective use of students and teachers in the university should be ensure and provided

Keywords: ICT; Management; Large Classes, Challenges & Way-forward

Introduction

Educational system around the world has been greatly influenced by the use of materials and tools in teaching and learning from time immemorial, which has been proven in making the process more meaningful, relevant and up to the task. Therefore, the current developments which have opened up opportunities for educationists to design and implement Information and Communication Technology (ICT) based lessons have only poured to the long standing pool of a wider education and technology association existing as bridge which further unified educational course at all levels This bridge between education and computer and internet technology use has made a great impact on perspectives about teaching and learning process especially in tertiary institutions of learning where there are explosion and overcrowding of students commensurate to the broader environmental and societal context. (Ajadi, 2010: Isuku, 2018: Lam, 2021: Marquès,2018). Therefore, advances in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have turned the world into a global village and are transforming the world economy presenting challenges that were hitherto un thought of. Nigeria aspires to attain sustainable development and enhance global competitiveness, a status that requires innovations especially in the development of human capital. There is no gainsaying that ICT has become sine qua non in bringing these about. Educators and policy-makers alike agree that ICT is paramount to the future of education and that successful contributions to meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are most likely to be made by ICT in Education initiatives that focus on increasing access through distance learning as ICT can provide new and innovative means to bring educational opportunities to greater numbers of people of all ages, thereby ensuring life-long learning especially for those who over the years have been excluded, such as populations in rural areas, women facing social barriers and people with disabilities. The Federal Ministry of Education is charged with policy formulation, monitoring of implementation, and setting and maintaining standards in the Nigerian education sector. However, the Constitution places education on the Concurrent Legislative List, making education a shared responsibility of the Federal, State and Local Governments. Thus, while the policy and standards with regards to ICT in education are the responsibilities of the Federal

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Government, the implementation of ICT in education rests heavily on the State and Local Governments. ICT occupies a very strategic place in Education in the country. This is encapsulated in the Ministerial Strategy Plan: Education for Change and in series of initiatives and strategies targeted at integrating ICT into education. (Federal Ministry of Education, 2019).

ICT stands for Information and Communication Technology, and it refers to the use of various tools and devices to communicate, create, store, and manage information. It has gained incremental importance for education, employment and communication in recent years. ICTs have become significant tools to access information, educate individuals and conduct interactive instructional activities regardless of time and location (Ajadi, 2010; Isuku, 2018; Lam, 2021; Marquès, 2018). Similarly, Information and Communications Technology, as the name suggests are tools that handle information and produce, store, and disseminate information. ICT comprises of both old and new tools. Old tools include radio, TV, Telephone. New tools comprise computers, satellites, the Internet, and wireless technology. It exists in multiple forms like audio, video, audio-visual, and texts. It refers to the latest technologies and a repository of simple audio-visual aids such as slides, radio, cassette, and film. ICT is defined as “A diverse set of technologies, tools, and resources used to communicate, create, disseminate, store, and manage information.” These technologies include computers, the internet, radio and TV. (Mannreet, 2021).

Scholars asserted that ‘Information and Communication Technology’ (ICT) needs not be overemphasized because it first appeared in the mid-1980s to represent an umbrella term for all kinds of electronic systems used for broadcasting telecommunications and mediated communications in its popular use then and this included personal computers, video games, cell phones, internet, and electronic mediation and payment systems etc. The main justification advanced as the reason for the emergence of the term in such a compound form was the fact that the computer technology is regarded as the tool for storing, processing and retrieving information in electronic form whereas the communication technology facilitates transmission of that information from source device (usually regarded as client) to destination device (usually regarded as server). This simultaneity of function made the component words inseparable in usage ever since. Other scholars simply considered ICT as combination of computing and networking technology with the dual function of information processing provided by the former and information transmission carried out by the latter. Thus, ICT came to mean the generality of tools used for gathering, processing, storing and disseminating of Information. The invention of the internet and its liberalization at the turn of the century led to 2.0 and 3.0 generations of the ICT which can be appreciated in the fullest in the Education realm. (Haugsbakk & Nordkvelle 2017).

Although, the developments in 3.0 generations of ICT included machine learning and other aspects of augmented reality that embody complex interactions of learner and technology to the point of relegating the human teacher, the ICT in the education system is still largely regarded as arbiter of educational interactions. In a one of the study conducted following Covid-19 pandemic, stressed ICT usage as arbiter of educational interactions as the dominant trend. ICT usage in educational institutions has undergone a significant evolution from its inception to the present time, moving from simply facilitating administrative tasks to being an important aid for class management and integral part of the learning process itself, the desired outcomes on students' performance cannot be delivered by the ICT automatically. The bizzare of ICT may be considered as comprises the computer hardware, software, application of telecommunication technologies, projection devices, Local Area Network (LAN), Wide Area Network (WAN), digital cameras, Compact Disks (CDs), Digital Video Disks (DVDs), cell phones, satellites, and fiber optics among others (Affouneh, Salha & Khlaif, 2020).

Following this trend, it is important to note that, the demand for university education in particular is usually tracked through official gateways to educational institutions of respective countries. In Nigeria the data from the joint admissions and matriculations board (JAMB) provides enough proof to support these assertions. A study conducted by Isuku (2018) which reported patterns of admission applications into tertiary institutions and the rate of admissions offered indicates a consistent trend of gross imbalance between the figures of admissions sought and admissions granted. According to the data the highest percentage of admissions offers then was 33%. This wide gap gave a recipe for utilization of the potential of the ICTs to attend to educational needs of the large swaths of the unadmitted as well as the admitted who are also in unmanageably large numbers. In a paper on Private Universities in Nigeria—the Challenges Ahead, Ajadi (2010) suggests that the vivid inability of governments' institutions to accommodate the rising demand for education necessitated the establishment of additional universities in the past few years. This scenario was what led to argue that the zeal for providing education as a social service in Nigeria has not been matched with a zeal for funding it. These prospects made the ICTs significant path and to an extent a means to penetrate all aspects of educational pursuit providing newer and more efficient means of teaching, learning and educational administration. That, the resulting ICT integration phenomenon served to strengthen the government's regulatory and institutional framework of the educational system rather than educational delivery to the public. Consequently, it became clear that no education system can afford to ignore the issue of developing an appropriate ICT-in-education policy and

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implementation strategies at a national system level keeping in mind its diverse prospects and challenges. This is because, it covered wide areas encompassing distance education and the facilitation of teaching methods and delivery in conventional educational institutions. Within these conventional institutions, one of the biggest problems believed to be addressed by proper Instructional ICT integration is the problem of large classes and over crowdedness (Ajadi, 2010: Isuku, 2018: Lam, 2021: Marquès, 2018)

The term large class is context-dependent which implies that its usage differs from one environmental or cultural circumstance to another. However, Large class environments are not new to students and teachers in Nigeria's tertiary educational institutions, the phenomenon is commonly believed to pose significant challenges for the teaching-learning process. Such challenges include coping with inadequate space and equipment, classroom management problems, poor quality of teaching, difficulty in marking students' tests and examination scripts, poor teacher-student interactions, teachers' stress due to heavy workload, and inability of teachers to adequately meet the learning needs of individual learners. So it has been envisaged that, the application of ICT and Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), will not only improve and enhance the relationships between teachers and students but undergone a phenomenal change, of the role of the teachers, the nature and context of learning as well as the function and relative importance of the contents of courses all will be challenged and redefined with the use of information and communication

Conceptualization of the term ICT tools in Nigerian Universities:

ICT stands for Information and Communication Technology, and it refers to the use of various tools and devices to communicate, create, store, and manage information. More so, it can be seen as tools that handle information and produce, store, and disseminate information. ICT comprises of both old and new tools. Old tools include radio, TV, Telephone. New tools comprise computers, satellites, the Internet, and wireless technology. It exists in multiple forms like audio, video, audio-visual, and texts. It refers to the latest technologies and a repository of simple audio-visual aids such as slides, radio, cassette, and film. ICT is defined as a diverse set of technologies, tools, and resources used to communicate, create, disseminate, store, and manage information." These technologies include computers, the internet, radio and TV. There are three ways by which ICT can be considered as an important tool in education. These are as follows: (Mannreet, 2021),

1. **ICT education:** ICT education means using trained personnel who can meet the needs and deliver information effectively to society. The vision is to train people and to equip students with ICT skills and knowledge.
2. **ICT-supported education:** It is also known as multimedia education. Around the world, many institutes and universities use ICT tools for printed study materials. It includes broadcast media, like radio, TV, audio-visual aids among others
3. **ICT-enabled education:** ICT-enabled education means the content is disseminated through ICT tools. Here, ICT is considered as a medium required for the teaching-learning process. (Mannreet, 2021)

Before now it has been established that, the central role of ICT in effective teaching and learning has made its adoption imperative for teachers in teaching situations as a result of an increase in the student population. However, Eze and Aja, (2014) further buttress that knowledge explosion has brought a lot of development to learning through myriads of media which has led to an upgrade of human knowledge in the 21st Century. The role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in sustaining education cannot be overstated due to its importance in both teaching and learning. Effective integration of ICT plays an important role in improving the quality of instruction delivery within and outside the classroom. Yusuf (2015) posited that no country can claim to be educationally advanced unless it embraces technology for its educational activities. ICT as tools within the school environment include use for school administration and management; teaching and learning of ICT related skills to enhance class work presentation; teaching/learning repetitive tasks; teaching/learning intellectual thinking and problem solving skills; stimulating creativity and imagination; for research by teachers and students, and as communication tool by teachers and students (Alshmrany & Wilkinson, 2017: Amuchie, 2015: Basargekar, & Singhavi, 2017: and Olawale, et al: 2020)

Broad objectives of the use of ICT Tools in Nigeria Universities:

The following are the objectives and rationales for the use of ICT tools in university system of education as identified by (Mannreet, 2021)

1. Providing accessibility through online medium of education.
2. Improving the quality of teaching, especially in remote areas.
3. To increase transparency in the education system.
4. To strengthen the policies, rules, and laws in the education system.

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5. To analyze the learning and participation of the students and measure its effectiveness.
6. Measuring and evaluating students' behavior, involvement, and retention in the learning process.
7. To analyze students' performance, placement, and application of knowledge. (Mannreet, 2021)

Specific ICT Tools that can be used for managing large class in Nigeria Universities;

ICT Tools that can be used in teaching and learning are broadly divided into hardware, software, and network communication. The tools are suitable for students and teachers. This is because, over the time ICT has become integral to the teaching-learning interaction, sometimes through such approaches as replacing chalkboards with interactive digital whiteboards, using students' own or schools' devices for learning during class time, and e-learning models where students learn at home or workplace. these approaches can lead to higher order thinking skills, provide creative and individualized avenues for students to learn and express their understanding. A plethora of groupings of these tools and resources have been proposed by different scholars. Some of the commonest among them as identified by scholars (Ajadi, 2010: Isuku, 2018: Lam, 2021: Marquès, 2018)

Mobile Learning tools in Nigerian Universities;

New advances in hardware and software are making handheld "smartphones" indispensable tools for present day learning. High levels of digital penetration in countries enabled adoption of mobile learning tools as suitable learning devices. According to Nigerian National Communications Commission, NCC as at June 2022, the Nigerian Digital penetration stands at 44.3% predominantly represented by internet enabled mobile devices (Vanguard, 2022). This figure establishes high potential for ICT Educational integration in the country

Cloud computing in Nigerian Universities;

Applications are increasingly moving off of the standalone desktop computer and increasingly onto server farms accessible through the Internet largely hosted in cloud. Educational systems take advantage of this trend to further their course. Given the fact that connectivity provided by cloud computing resources have relative immunity from natural disasters made its adoption more ubiquitous and popular in education system.

Individualized learning resources in Nigerian Universities;

This is often referred to as personalized or customized learning, the application of individualized methods of learning in education predates the current association of education and ICT. However, the trend even in physical classrooms around the world today provides an information appliance to average and special learners with varying learning abilities. It creates learning environments and adopt tools that assume universal access to the learning. These tools not only helped in achieving smaller class sizes and mitigation of negative effects of poor student-teacher interactions but also facilitated customization of learning to individual learners' needs and characteristics (Bello, 2021: Lam, Tse, Lu & Wong 2021).

Ubiquitous learning tools in Nigeria Universities;

Appearance of increasingly robust connectivity infrastructure particularly in the area of open source Technology largely accessed freely or at subsidized cost make it possible for learners to study "anytime" and "anywhere". Here also the global Covid-19 pandemic has exerted considerable influence on its emergence. Research shows that in its wake different countries in the world often in collaboration with international partners helped made a significant addition to the ubiquitous ICT tools for learning purposes. at both lower and higher institution levels (Reyes-Chua, Sibbaluca, Miranda, Palmario, Moreno & Solon 2020). In Nigeria also, the federal ministry of education launched a robust e-learning facility that students and teachers can access freely (Nigerian Tribune, 2021). Even though ubiquitous learning tools have been critiqued by researchers for paucity of direct student teacher interactions, the availability of virtual mentors or teachers and affordances of peer to peer and self-paced learning make it advantageous (Yeung, Carpenter & Corral 2021).

Virtual teaching platforms in Nigerian Universities;

Another well-known tool in the educational field for the great amount of benefits it provides to students and to maintained large classes are the virtual teaching platforms, it is understood as that tool which allows the student to study the subject (Curriculum content) at a distance without the need to travel to the classroom/ lecture venue and or training center. This has the advantage to allowed for different modalities of study such as e-learning or e-learning in Spanish or b-learning or blended learning. (Yeung, Carpenter & Corral 2021).

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Educational advantages of the use of ICT Tools in managing large class in Nigeria Universities;

The use of ICT technology in teaching and learning is expanding rapidly in this twenty-first century. As a result of that, studies about the importance of ICT technology in teaching and learning are also appearing in a growing number. Previous research shows that the use of technologies, particularly the new ones could facilitate communication, reduce anxiety, encourage oral discussion, develop the writing/thinking connection, nurture social or cooperative learning among others. But more specifically, the below were enumerated as educational advantages of the use of ICT Tools in teaching and that could help manage large classes as postulated by (Vinay.2021)

Individualization of learning in Nigerian Universities: It is an established fact that, no two individual student learn within the same rate, this is for the individual differences in existence, hence, it means that people learn as an individual and not as the same group. As learners are varied, ICTs provide flexibility so that learners learn according to their own pace and this check the problem around most learn at the same pace and time

Online learning in Nigerian Universities: ICT and its tools had led to the emergence of online learning. Through this, the teachers and the students are learning innovative ways in the education process. Online learning has gained popularity amidst the corona pandemic to ensure that the learning continues. ICTs have looked after that education reaches through it worldwide and even in remote areas. No matter where the students are, but it has ensured that every learner derives its benefits.

Accessible to all in Nigerian Universities: ICT in education allows accessibility to all types of learners. All students can learn through the material provided. Even the special needs students can maximize the benefits through the usage of it. ICT has also covered issues like the “digital divide” and allows even less fortunate people to access the tools for their educational needs and enhance learning.

Higher-order thinking & skill developments in Nigerian Universities: ICT promotes high order thinking and reasoning skills. These skills enabled the process of evaluation, planning, monitoring, controlling, reflecting, etc. To use ICT tools effectively, one must be able to explain and justify the solutions to the problems. For using ICTs, the students should be able to discuss, test, and evaluate the strategies and methods they use.

Better subject learning in Nigerian Universities: The key role of ICT is to enhance subject learning and acquire skills. It promotes key learning in areas of literacy and numeracy.

Develops ICT literacy and capability in Nigerian Universities: Literacy and capability are the 21st-century skills that are needed. One of the best ways to develop these is to equip the subject-matter with purposeful activities.

Encourages collaboration in Nigerian Universities: ICT fosters collaboration as children work collectively. It also enhances communication skills as they discuss, talk, and learn together. All you need is a laptop, tablet, or desktop computer to understand it's working. ICT tools open up the doors for developing language through fostering communication.

Motivates learning in Nigerian Universities: ICT motivates children towards learning. Children learn better through the usage of technology. They get mesmerized with technology tools and get motivated to learn effectively in the classroom or at home.

Improves engagement and knowledge retention in Nigerian Universities: With the inclusion of ICT in education and its tools, students get more engaged and show greater participation in learning. It is all because of technology. It has made learning fun-filled with creativity and games. It enhances learning in multiple ways. Because of it, the students learn better, leading to knowledge retention.

Effective differentiation instruction with ICT technology in Nigerian Universities: There are varied learners with distinct learning styles in this society. So, technology does the task of providing differentiated instruction to different learners.

A key part of the curriculum in Nigerian Universities: As per the latest curriculum, ICT plays an important part in the education system. So, many governments across the globe have started using ICT as a major part of education and the curriculum. (Vinay.2021)

Challenges around the use of ICT Tools in managing large classes in Nigerian Universities

There are some identified challenges militating against the effective use of ICT tools and resources to curtail challenges of large classes facing university educational provisions in Nigeria. These challenges were grouped by scholars having relationship with the major three ones of the following: (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016): Access, Equity and Quality. While from the above, they deduced the following generic challenges which can include the following:

1. Basic technology infrastructure in Nigerian Universities;

Governments all over the world shoulder the responsibility for installing technology basic infrastructure such as electricity and internet connectivity. However, increased affordability and flexibility of ICT within a short span made it possible to be large

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swaths of the teachers/lecturers and other members of the population to acquire internet enabled device with or without Institutional direct support. (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

2. Hardware in Nigerian Universities;

No matter the robustness of the internet connectivity and software, access to hardware by the end user remains critical. Early accounts of technology integration focused much of their interest on increasing the availability of computers in schools. But with the later developments the focus has relatively shifted toward content and software development. In the Nigerian case access to mobile devices come mostly by personal funding. However for effective technology integration to be achieved to avert the negative consequences of large classes, access to official equipment necessary must be increased. In a number of developed countries, 1-1 lecturer computer ratio by official provision or facilitation has since been achieved. In addition, the official computer/device possession by lecturers averts the problems of none-regularity and non-dependability of hardware (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

3. Software in Nigerian Universities;

Educational institutions have since been keeping large reservoir of knowledge in print form in libraries. The surge in ICT made them to put their academic resources and services online, bringing the global community onto a common platform and awakening the interest of stakeholders. Despite continuing technical challenges, online education shows great potential. The popularity of open source software yet offers flexible and affordable approach to addressing the technical problems in providing optimal delivery of online learning. Open source refers to both the concept and practice of making program and content source openly available. Development of wikis made users and to have access to the core designing functionalities that enable them to modify or add features to the source code for redistribution. It is stressed extensive collaboration and circulation are central to the open source movement (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

4. Training in Nigerian Universities;

Mostly, cited reason for lack of technology implementation in the classroom for effective management of large classes is inadequate professional development and training. Therefore, with relevant training on technology adoption and use teachers/lecturers will show increasing confidence in technology integration to mitigate Negative effect of large classes. But given that technology is constantly changing, it is more important than ever that lecturers of higher Institutions stay up-to-date with their technological expertise and pedagogical expertise. professional development and training to break through the challenges (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

5. Technical support in Nigerian Universities;

In cases where the professional training of lecturers do not enable them to use Technology for proper management of large classes, technical support must be sought and be provided appropriately (Johnson, Jacovina, Russell & Soto 2016).

6. Curriculum:

There is generally lack of regular review and updating of existing ICT curricula, especially at the tertiary level, to meet changing societal needs. There is also low capacity of curriculum developers and implementers. The challenge of outdated curriculum is even more pronounced in view of the dynamic nature of ICT Tools

7. Funding in Nigerian Universities:

Although, funds are being provided for ICT in education, they are largely inadequate to provide the drive necessary to position the sector for the attainment of the national goals. The foregoing reveals that the state of ICT in education in Nigeria falls below global standards. This reinforces the need for focused intervention in ICT in education.

Use of ICT for effective classroom instruction in Nigerian Universities

ICT Tools plays a significant role towards creating an improved teaching and learning environment is of utmost importance to teachers in creating a new learning culture. Many teachers lack the knowledge and skills to effectively use ICT tools in facilitating learning in increasingly ICT-pervasive learning environments. Some teacher-training programme shave over-emphasized computer literacy while not enabling teachers to integrate technology with pedagogy and facilitate ICT-assisted interactive teaching-learning at classroom level, therefore, a theoretical framework is a conceptual model of how one theorizes makes logical sense of the relationship among the several factors that have been identified as important to the problem. A framework is a representation of reality; it delineates those aspects (variables) of the real world the scientist considers to be relevant to the problem The figure 1 & 2 below depicts the interrelationships of the necessary organs surrounding the use of ICT Tools for teaching and learning and as well an interrelated variables that would bring about its effective integration and use in tertiary institution of learning.

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Conclusion

Implementing ICT for management of large classes is both challenging and a rewarding endeavor this is because, The notable increase in the social use of ICTs and their enormous impact is an aspect that cannot go unnoticed in the world of education. ICT is already becoming a fundamental tool for new teachers and students in the classroom. It has been proven that the use of ICT in the classroom increases the motivation of the students, showing more interest and becoming more involved in the areas they study. ICT enables the use of innovative educational resources and the renewal of learning methods, establishing a more active collaboration of students and the simultaneous acquisition of technological knowledge. Therefore, Schools use a diverse set of ICT tools to communicate, create, disseminate, store, and manage information. In some contexts, ICT has also become integral to the teaching-learning interaction, through such approaches as replacing chalkboards with interactive digital whiteboards, using students' own smartphones or other devices for learning during class time, and the "flipped classroom" model where students watch lectures at home on the computer and use classroom time for more interactive exercises. When teachers are digitally literate and trained to use ICT, these approaches can lead to higher order thinking skills, provide creative and individualized options for students to express their understandings, and leave students better prepared to deal with ongoing technological change in society and the workplace thereby ensuring learning at university system turn to be any-where and any-time, any place a phenomenon that will bring about learning management and help checkmate challenges of overcrowding

Recommendations

The following recommendations if implemented will go a long way to improve on the use of ICT in the management of large class in Nigeria University System

1. Basic technology infrastructure, needed and required for effective use and functionality of students and teachers should ensure are in place, such to include high bandwidth connectivity of online and internet services within and around the campus should be intensify
2. Hardware components suitable for functioning alongside with the software should be made available and adequate for students' and teachers uses
3. Training Series of on the job and induction training for staff on the uses of ICT tools should be prioritized and University system should ensure time to time training of teachers in order to updates knowledge and skills
4. Tactical support is required from the government for maximizing productivity

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Impact of Curriculum Development on Entrepreneurship and Innovation Skills among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria

Ohadiugha, Marian N. Ph.D.

Email: egobekeohadiugha@yahoo.com

Tel: 08147399330

National Open University of Nigeria

Abstract

Nigeria's curriculum has evolved to emphasize critical thinking, innovation, and entrepreneurship, vital for addressing unemployment and economic growth. However, graduates often struggle to find employment due to curriculum implementation issues and insufficient focus on innovation. This study employs a descriptive survey design to investigate the "Impact of Curriculum Development on Entrepreneurship and Innovation Skills among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria". The population of the study consisted of two hundred and fifty-eight (258) public and private universities within Nigeria. Employing a non-probability purposive sampling method, the researchers selected a sample of three hundred students (300) from both public and private universities representing all six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. Data is collected from 300 students across public and private universities using a Likert-scale questionnaire. The t-test is employed to analyze mean assessment scores, showing significant differences in both entrepreneurial mindset and innovative skills between public and private universities. The reliability coefficient was calculated as 0.84. The data collected were analyzed using mean scores and simple percentages to answer research questions to address the research inquiries, while t-tests were employed to assess the test hypotheses at a 0.05 significant level. The study recommended among other things that, to address these issues and promote economic growth, Nigerian universities should adopt a practical and forward-thinking curriculum, with a particular focus on integrating collaborative curriculum development involving stakeholders and more funding for entrepreneurship programs. It also highlights the importance of innovative teaching methods to prepare graduates for the modern economy.

Keywords: Curriculum development, Innovative teaching methods, Entrepreneurial mindset, Entrepreneurial innovative skills

Introduction

The quality, sustainability, and progress of an educational system within any nation hinge upon the nature of its curriculum. Irrespective of its type, structure, or form, the curriculum stands as a masterpiece and the core of the educational system. The effectiveness and practicality of a country's educational framework are equally dependent on its curriculum. It goes beyond being a planned activity to transmit societal values, norms, virtues, and attitudes to the next generation. Rather, it encompasses subjects and courses offered across elementary schools, secondary schools, and higher learning institutions. It serves as a blueprint, meticulously designed for high-quality, impactful learning experiences that are standardized and finely crafted by educational institutions or governmental bodies. This blueprint guides students mentally and developmentally in achieving societal goals while preparing them for the challenges of their environment. According to Ikelegbe and Odiachi (2017), the curriculum is a series of organized experiences in a logical sequence, designed to equip individuals for proficient performance in specific vocations.

Curriculum development involves the input of curriculum experts who significantly influence the scope and nature of curricular activities. This process should also involve teachers and students at every stage of designing the curriculum, spanning from planning and structuring to organization, implementation, and assessment. The goal is to achieve educational objectives that prepare students for life beyond schooling. Curriculum development is a continuous, dynamic, and progressive process aimed at maintaining the curriculum's relevance, adaptability, and responsiveness to societal needs. It remains open to revision or alteration according to society's evolving demands. Educational systems worldwide are built upon curricula, albeit with variations tailored to individual societal needs and purposes. The traditional Nigerian curriculum reflected past societal norms, beliefs, attitudes, values, knowledge, and skills passed down generations within a close-knit, communal community. While reading and writing weren't integral components of the traditional Nigerian curriculum, it was pragmatic and aligned with the community's needs. The present Nigerian curriculum, following multiple revisions post-Independence, is divided into Basic Education, known as Universal Basic Education (UBE), encompassing a mandatory 9-year continuous schooling period (6 years in primary school and 3 years in junior secondary school). This is followed by 3 years of senior secondary school and 4

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years of tertiary education, known as the 9-3-4 system. The modern Nigerian curriculum aims to instill value reorientation, critical thinking, innovative skills, entrepreneurship mindset, and lifelong skills among its youth to meet the demands of the technology-driven 21st century.

Nigerian policymakers and educators recognize the pivotal role of science and technology in achieving education for all and national development in the present era. Entrepreneurial mindset and innovation skills play a vital role in employment, critical thinking, creativity, decision-making, wealth creation, and economic prosperity. Thus, these attributes are now part of the Nigerian curriculum. Entrepreneurial mindset integrated into the curriculum aims to equip students with the necessary foundation to expand their entrepreneurial thinking from an early stage. This is to ensure they possess the requisite background and knowledge to embark on entrepreneurial ventures once they enter the workforce.

Entrepreneurship involves identifying, initiating, organizing, and realizing ideas or visions, whether they pertain to products, services, processes, strategies, or markets. In the current economic climate, there's a pressing need to cultivate students' general cognitive abilities over personal attributes. This is particularly important due to high unemployment rates and limited job opportunities. Developing entrepreneurial skills among university students entails fostering critical thinking, idea generation, and a commitment to entrepreneurial goals upon graduation. Innovation is the ability to introduce or use new ideas or methods. It involves thinking creatively, manipulating variables to create models, discovering possibilities, and forming objects and images that didn't exist before.

To achieve sustainable development, an entrepreneurial mindset, and innovative skills must be embedded within the curriculum. Nigeria's potential for creativity, human capital, and unique resources positions it well for economic growth and development. Therefore, the curriculum should encourage inventiveness, reflective thinking, rationality, creativity, innovation, and overall better output. This will contribute to fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship, leading the nation toward a more sustainable and prosperous future. In Nigeria, despite the abundant human and material resources, the educational system, including higher institutions, grapples with unstable and inconsistent educational policies. These policies have led to tumultuous curriculum implementation. Over time, Nigerian educational institutions have been producing graduates lacking essential skills, such as self-reliance, employability, innovation, and an entrepreneurial mindset. This deficiency hampers the nation's progress, even in the face of available resources. This situation has dire consequences, including a dwindling economy, high unemployment rates, unsuitable economic policies for small and medium-scale businesses, inflation, and an inability to meet the technological demands of the 21st century.

A publication by the National Bureau of Statistics (2016) reveals that 52 million economically active citizens in Nigeria are unemployed, mainly comprised of recent university graduates. This situation is exacerbated by the fact that Nigeria boasts a youth population of 80 million, representing 60% of the total population. Within this demographic, 64 million youths are unemployed, while 1.6 million are underemployed. In the first quarter of this year, Nigeria's youth unemployment rate reached a staggering 53%, second only to South Africa's 61%. This escalating unemployment trend is alarming and presents a significant challenge to Nigeria's stability and growth. To address these challenges, a curriculum that instills an entrepreneurial mindset and innovation skills is essential. However, despite the incorporation of entrepreneurship education into the curriculum, the unemployment rate remains high. Inadequate curriculum implementation, the lack of focus on innovation skills, and insufficient funding hinder the development of an entrepreneurial mindset among students. Flexibility is vital to cater to student's needs and create an environment conducive to entrepreneurship education. The concept of entrepreneurship education aims to provide students with the knowledge and skills to cultivate entrepreneurial thinking from an early stage. Entrepreneurship involves identifying, initiating, and bringing ideas to fruition, while innovation entails introducing new ideas or methods. A robust curriculum should equip students with these skills, enabling them to be self-employed and contribute positively to the economy.

However, despite the incorporation of entrepreneurship education into the Nigerian curriculum, many graduates remain unemployable. Inadequate funding, underfunding by state governments, and low-quality teaching contribute to this challenge. To truly harness the potential of an entrepreneurial mindset and innovation skills, a functional and pragmatic curriculum is necessary. This curriculum should be developed collaboratively with input from teachers, professionals, curriculum experts, and successful entrepreneurs. Innovation in the curriculum should emphasize broad competence, integrative learning experiences, and innovative instructional methods. Other countries also recognize the importance of entrepreneurship education. For example, the United States' Bridging Disciplinary Program at the University of Texas combines courses from various fields to teach students how ideas, inventions, and skills are transformed into commercial ventures. To achieve similar success in Nigeria, the government should provide adequate funding for entrepreneurship programs, train teachers to promote creative and entrepreneurial skills and encourage practical and collaborative extracurricular activities. In conclusion, while

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Nigeria's curriculum incorporates entrepreneurship education, its implementation and effectiveness remain challenging due to poor funding and inadequate execution. A robust curriculum promoting an entrepreneurial mindset and innovation skills is crucial for Nigeria's economic growth and development. The collaboration of stakeholders, the provision of adequate funding, and innovative teaching methods are essential to ensuring graduates are equipped to thrive in the 21st-century economy.

Purpose of the study

The general objective of this study is to investigate the “Impact of Curriculum Development on Entrepreneurship and Innovative Skills among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria” The specific objectives were:

1. to ascertain the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting entrepreneurial mindset in public and private universities in Nigeria.
2. to determine the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting innovative skills in public and private universities in Nigeria.

Research Question

1. Is there a significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students' promotion of entrepreneurial mindset between public and private universities in Nigeria?
2. Is there a significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students' promotion of innovative skills between public and private universities in Nigeria?

Hypothesis

From the specific objectives of this study, the following null hypotheses were raised at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting entrepreneurial mindset in public and private universities in Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting innovative skills in public and private universities in Nigeria

Methodology

The researcher employed a descriptive survey research design to investigate the Impact of Curriculum Development on Entrepreneurship and Innovation Skills among undergraduate Students in Nigeria. The study's target population comprised two hundred and fifty-eight (258) public and private students within Nigeria. Employing a non-probability purposive sampling method, the researchers selected a sample of three hundred students (300) from both public and private universities representing all six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. Among these, two hundred students were selected from public universities (200), while one hundred students (100) were chosen from private universities. From each of the six universities, fifty students (50) were invited to participate in the study. The research had two objectives and corresponding hypotheses that guided the study and were tested at a significance level of 0.05. Data collection was facilitated through a questionnaire developed by the researcher, using a four-point Likert Scale that included Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) options, rated as 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. The research instrument was validated by experts in test and measurement from the University of Abuja, ensuring alignment with the study's purpose and objectives; its reliability coefficient was calculated as 0.84. The data collected were analyzed using mean scores and simple percentages to answer the research questions, while t-tests were employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant level.

Results

Hypothesis Testing

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting entrepreneurial mindset in public and private universities in Nigeria.

Table 1: T-test results on the difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting entrepreneurial mindset in public and private universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	X	SD	df	t-value	sig.(p)	Decision
Public University	200	2.61	0.101	298	-3.045	0.0029	Rejected
Private University	100	2.54	0.111				

*=significant at 0.05level (p<0.05)

Table 1 displays the statistical summaries and analysis of the mean assessment scores related to entrepreneurship education's impact on fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among students within both public and private universities in Nigeria. The computed mean for public universities stands at 2.61, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.101. In comparison, the mean for private universities is calculated as 2.54, with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.111. The t-test conducted to assess the equality of means yields a p-value of 0.002, which falls below the 0.05 significance level. This outcome leads to the inference that a significant difference exists in the mean assessment scores for entrepreneurship education's influence on students' entrepreneurial mindset promotion between public and private universities in Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting innovative skills in public and private universities in Nigeria.

Table 2: T-Test Results on the Difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting innovative skills in public and private universities in Nigeria

Variables	N	X	SD	df	t-value	sig.(p)	Decision
Public University	200	2.81	0.109	298	3.67	0.0000	Rejected
Private University	100	2.74	0.117				

*=significant at 0.05level (p<0.05)

Table 2 presents the statistical summaries and analysis concerning the mean assessment scores related to entrepreneurship education's influence on enhancing innovative skills among students in both public and private universities in Nigeria. The computed mean for public universities is established at 2.81, with a standard deviation of 0.109 and a standard error mean of 0.00465. In comparison, the mean for private universities is calculated as 2.78, with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.08160. The t-test conducted to evaluate the equality of means produces a p-value of 0.000, which falls below the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, this outcome leads to the deduction that a notable difference exists in the mean assessment scores for entrepreneurship education's impact on students' promotion of innovative skills between public and private universities in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings illustrated in Table 1 unveil a substantial disparity in the mean assessment scores concerning entrepreneurship education's influence on fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among students in both public and private universities in Nigeria. These outcomes align with the insights gleaned from a study conducted by Ebringa, Ewenwa, and Ebringa (2015), which underscored the involvement of students in practical and collaborative entrepreneurial extracurricular activities, coupled with mentorship from seasoned entrepreneurial-minded academics. This approach equips students with critical thinking proficiencies conducive to entrepreneurial endeavours post-graduation. Further corroborating these findings is the research undertaken by Bodnar, Renee, and Mary (2015), which similarly demonstrated that the provisions within entrepreneurship curriculum content carry implications for cultivating entrepreneurship among university students, chiefly by inciting critical thinking capabilities and fostering competencies in generating business concepts.

Equally, the outcomes depicted in Table 2 unveil a marked variance in the mean assessment scores reflecting the impact of entrepreneurship education on enhancing innovative skills among students within both public and private universities in Nigeria. This alignment is consistent with the assertions posited by Mbanefo and Eboka (2017), who define innovativeness as the aptitude for introducing novel ideas or novel approaches to solving challenges. They further emphasize the innovation

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process, encompassing creative ideation, the imaginative manipulation of variables and instruments, the formulation of models, the exploration of potentials, and the creation of novel objects and images. This viewpoint resonates with the viewpoint of Mbanefo and Chiaha (2014), who contend that innovative learning environments prioritize the facilitation and application of novel modes of knowledge acquisition, the embrace of problem-solving strategies, the integration of diverse knowledge sources, the encouragement of self-directed learning, and the extension of knowledge through intricate creative expression.

Conclusion

The caliber, durability, and trajectory of advancement within the educational systems of all nations are intrinsically linked to the essence of their curriculum. Against the backdrop of Nigeria's considerable unemployment rate and the challenges faced by certain university graduates in securing employment, let alone creating jobs, a formidable obstacle emerges that hampers Nigeria's advancement in terms of economic growth and overall national progress. This situation underscores the pressing need for Nigerian universities to adopt a forward-looking approach in the context of our innovative era. The potential solution rests in the adoption of an educational curriculum that is not only practical but also pragmatic and hands-on. At the core of this endeavor lies the integration of entrepreneurship education, which serves as the cornerstone for cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset. This approach imparts vital attributes such as creativity, critical thinking, adept problem-solving skills, heightened productivity, and proficiency in innovation, among other competencies. Consequently, these attributes comprehensively prepare university students to confidently confront and adeptly overcome the imminent challenges posed by our continually evolving, technology-driven society. This aligns with the recommendations derived from the findings of this study.

Recommendation

In light of the outcomes obtained through this research, the ensuing recommendations are put forth:

1. University administrations in Nigeria should establish a conducive milieu within their institutions by equipping them with fundamental facilities and tools that foster a hands-on environment for entrepreneurship education. This will effectively cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset among students in both public and private universities throughout Nigeria.
2. The government should allocate sufficient resources to support entrepreneurship education initiatives in Nigerian universities. Additionally, initiatives for the ongoing training and professional development of lecturers should be incentivized. This step is pivotal in nurturing innovative skills among students in public and private universities across Nigeria.

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Impact of Finley-Jensen Problem Solving Model on Retention in Algebraic Concepts among Students in Public Polytechnics, North West, Nigeria

*Jamilu Aliyu Abubakar¹

Email: Jamilualiyu16@gmail.com

Tel: +2348135177149

Mukhtar Nuraddeen¹

Email: nuraddeenm14@gmail.com; nmukhtar14@nubapoly.edu.ng

Tel: +2348034987045

Lawal Lukman¹

Email: lukmanmathbuk@gmail.com

Tel: +2347032856874

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Abstract

This paper investigates the Impact of Finley-Jensen problem solving model on retention in algebraic concepts among students in public polytechnics, North West Nigeria. A pretest, post-tests and post-post-test Quasi-experimental research design was used for the study. Fourteen public polytechnics made up the population of the Study with a sample size of 6,985 national diploma one (ND I) students during the 2021/2022 academic session. Two schools were randomly selected as population Samples. The experimental and control groups were exposed to Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving model and Lecture Method respectively. The experimental group was taught algebra (MTH 112) using Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving model while the control group was taught MTH 112 using Lecture method. Algebraic Achievement Test (AAT) was designed by the researchers for data collection. The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Achievement Test (AAT) was determined to be 0.76 using Cronbach alpha at $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level. There was significant difference in the mean scores of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley – Jensen problem model and their counterpart taught using conventional lecture method. The finding revealed that students that were taught using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model retained better than those exposed to Lecture method. Teachers (Lecturers) were advised to integrate Finley-Jensen problem-solving model in their pedagogy

Keyword: Algebra, Finley-Jensen, Problem Solving and Retention

Introduction

Mathematics is essential to national prosperity in providing tools for understanding science, engineering, technology and economics. It is essential in public decision-making and for partaking in the knowledge economy. Mathematics equips pupils/students with uniquely powerful ways to describe, analyze and change the world. It can stimulate moments of pleasure and wonder for all pupils/students when they solve a problem for the first time, discover a more stylish solution, or notice hidden connections. Pupils/students who are functional in mathematics are able to think independently in applied and abstract ways, and can reason, solve problems and assess risk (Tudunkaya & Jamilu, 2019). The need of mathematics in human life can not be over emphasize. According to National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 2000) mathematics is regard to as a cultural heritage for science and technological community. As part of the National Board for Technical Education Curriculum, algebra is a core course for all sciences, engineering and environmental technology. Algebra is one of the studied areas of mathematics that deals with the representation of problems or situations in the form of mathematical expressions. All the branches of mathematics needs algebra. The study of algebra starts with solving of equations such as polynomials equations. Algebra and elementary trigonometry is almost a general course to all students of sciences, engineering technology, environmental technology and even in some management courses. Knowing the importance of mathematics in human life, then the learning of mathematics needs to be well prepared. For effective learning to be efficiently taken, we need the right approaches and methods. For effective learning, the teaching activities should centred on students' activities (Overy, 2011). These activities include problem-solving strategy which improve student attendance and attitude toward learning, by making them to have mastery of the concepts and skills.

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The Finley-Jensen problem solving model (1996) is based on Dewey (1933) and Bruner (1973) theories of learning. These scholars have agreed that meaningful learning can only be achieved through active participation of learners. Farooq (1980) points out that a “problem” usually indicates a challenge, the meeting of which requires study and investigation. Skinner (1984) states that the term “problem-solving” is defined as the frame work or pattern within which creative thinking and learning takes place. It is a process of overcoming difficulties that appear to interfere with the attainment of a goal. Polya (1945) defines problem-solving as the process used to solve a problem that does not have an obvious solution. Bay (2000) explains teaching about problem-solving as the teaching of strategies, or heuristics, in order to solve problems. Despite the applications of mathematics in science and technology, student’s retention ability use to be very poor at the end of semester examination.

Retention as defined by Yero (2011) is the ability of a learner to recall, remember and recollect a body of Knowledge after passing through instruction. According to Chauchan in Neboh (2012) retention is direct correlate of positive transfer of learning. For students’ retention Umar (2011) observed that students’ experience is a significant factor in retention and that the strategies of improving retention rate can be adopted by the teacher. Bichi, (2002) opined that anything which aids meaningful learning improves students’ retention and while things that lead to interference among learned materials decrease the speed and efficiency of learning and accelerates forgoing. Idris (2014) observed that, retention is the ability to keep and consequently remember things or materials experienced or learned at a later time. Chibabi, *et al* (2018) in their study found that teaching methods play a great impact in secondary school students’ retention especially in science related subjects. Retention is imperative in any academic activity. Low academic performance as well as retention amongst students in Sciences seems to be as a result of use of teacher ‘s-centred method which lead to poor academic retention. Many researches had carried out to improve the students’ retention abilities.

Gloria (2020), investigated the Effects of Problem-Solving Strategy on Retention in Reading comprehension, the study reveals that there was a significant difference in the retention of students taught reading comprehension with problem-solving strategy and that of those taught same contents with the conventional read, reread method. Many studies were also carried out to investigate the effect of problem – solving strategy on student retention ability and their results shows that there is a significant difference in retention ability of students taught using problem-solving compare to those taught with lecture method. Charles, *et al* (2021), studied the Effectiveness of Learning Activity Package Instructional Strategy on secondary school student’s retention in chemistry, it was shown that chemistry students that were taught Basic Chemistry using Learning Activity Package recorded higher Retention than those taught with lecture method.

Obochi (2018), investigated the impact of Problem-solving strategy on retention and academic performance in biology among low ability secondary school students in Zaria, Kaduna State Nigeria. Jamilu *et al* (2023) investigated the Impact of Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving Model on Performance and Retention in 3-D Geometry among SSII Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. It was revealed that Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving Model enhances the Performance and Retention of Secondary School Students on 3-D Geometry concepts. Mukhar *et al.* (2021), studied the effects of Jigsaw IV Cooperative Learning Strategy (J4CLS) on students’ retention in Geometry among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis. It was shown that, the Students that were exposed to J4CLS had retained geometrical concepts compare to those that were taught using the conventional teaching method. Still poor retention ability among national diploma I students has become a challenging problem to educators in our institutions, more especially in mathematics which lead to poor performance at the end of semester examinations which may be as a result of conventional lecture method used for teaching in them. This paper attempts to investigate the impact of Finley-Jensen problem solving model on retention in algebraic concepts among students in public polytechnics, North West Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

To examine the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concept using Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving model and those expose to lecture method.

Research Questions:

Is there any significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

Null Hypotheses:

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0,05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

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Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test-post-test and post posttest non-equivalent control group design. The essence of pre-test was to determine the academic equivalence of the two groups before the treatment while post-posttest was to determine the performance of the student after the treatment. The students in the experimental group were exposed to algebraic concepts through problem solving model for a period of eight (8) weeks and the control group were taught the same concepts using conventional lecture method after which post-test was administered to both groups. The population of the study comprised of public polytechnics in north-west zone of Nigeria. There are fourteen public polytechnics in North-West with the total number, of 6,985 NDI students taking algebra (MTH 112) as at the time the data was collected. For the purpose of this study a simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample institutions. The instrument for this study is Algebraic Achievement Test (AAT). The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Achievement Test (AAT) was determined to be 0.76. For the purpose of generating and analysing data AAT comprises ten (10) essay test questions were developed for the study, which allowed the students to write their understanding on the algebraic concepts.

Results

The result of the analysis was used to answer the research question using descriptive statistics while inferential statistics was used to test the null hypothesis at alpha (α) = 0.05 level significance.

Research Question 1

Is there any significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation for Retention ability

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	Experimental	22.93	5.31
2.	Control	12.73	4.09

(Field work, 2023)

The results in table 1 shows that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 22.93 retained higher than their counterparts in the control group with a mean score of 12.73. This shows that Finley-Jensen enhances students' retention ability.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Table 2: T-test on students' retention ability of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	df	Remark
Experimental	117	22.88	5.31	18.07	1.65	223	S
Control	108	12.73	4.09				

S=significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 2 shows that the mean scores of post posttest for both the experimental and control groups with the mean of 22.88 and 12.88 respectively. The hypothesis says "there is no significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method". But from the table above we have $t_{critical} (18.07) > t_{calculated} (1.65)$ at $\alpha=0.05$ significant level. Thus, H_{01} is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

Results of testing null hypothesis shows that significant difference exist between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method. The analysis of the hypothesis showed that the use of Finley-Jensen problem solving model lead to higher retention than the

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traditional method of teaching. The result of the mean scores of the student in the experimental group maintained a higher retention rates than their counterparts in the control group (see table 1). The nature of Finley-Jensen problem-solving model is learning by doing and elaborating. In Finley-Jensen problem-solving model the students worked individually and later discuss their finding in pairs, where each student developed self confidence in the topic taught. The consistent elaboration of MTH 112 concepts at Finley-Jensen problem-solving model provides students who either received the explanation or those who gave the explanation with a deep understanding and a more complete retention of the concepts being learnt for a longer period of time. The post post test was administered after two weeks and the result was showed in table 1. This finding agrees with the findings of Charles *et al* (2021), Obochi (2018), Mukhtar *et al* (2021) and Gloria (2020) who found that there is significant difference on retention abilities on students that are exposed to problem solving than those in control group, taught the concepts using traditional method. This is because problem-Solving in general and specifically Finely-Jensen problem-solving model encourages verbalization and made students communicate their ideas very well to classmates.

Conclusion

The paper study the impact of Finley-Jensen problem solving model on retention in algebraic concepts among students in public polytechnics, North West Nigeria. It was shown that better retention ability was achieved when using Finley – Jensen problem solving model in teaching algebraic concept (MTH 112) among national diploma one students compared to normal conventional lecture method

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend that: Lectures (teachers) should incorporate Finley – Jensen problem solving model in teaching Mathematics more especially at ND level.

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Impact of Industrial Chemistry Content Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State

Sodangi, Umar¹

Email: sodangiumar@fugusau.edu.ng

Tel: 08036076752

Akanbi, Ganiyu Adedo²

Email: adedoganivuakanbi@gmail.com/adedoganiyu@fugusau.edu.ng

Tel: 07035236585

Ibrahim Adamu³

Email: adamugwoza@fugusau.edu.ng

Tel: 08065108662

¹Department of Science Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Abstract

This research is descriptive and experimental using the Hannifen-Peck design model and motivation theory, respectively. The population consists of eighty students, who were randomly selected. A pretest and posttest of the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) is used to determine the achievement, while a structured questionnaire is used to determine the interest and awareness of the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on entrepreneurship skills and acquisition in chalk production among secondary school students in Zamfara State. The structured questionnaire consists of 10 (ten) question items on Interest in the Impact of Industrial Chemistry Concept Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production (IIICKESACP) and 10 (ten) on Awareness of the Impact of Industrial Chemistry Concept Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production (AIICKESACP). Using the Linkert Scale, statistical tools were used for data analysis. A pilot test was administered to 20 non-participants with reliability coefficients of 0.82, 0.83, and 0.72 for CAT, (IIICKESACP), and (AIICKESACP), respectively. The null hypothesis stated on the awareness with the mean scores of the respondents of 3.25 and 3.81, which is greater than the decision rule of 2.50, was rejected. From the result, it was concluded that the student was aware and the null was rejected. From the result, it was concluded that the student was aware and had an interest. This result can be used to inform the educational policy of industrial chemistry in secondary school education. This finding can also provide useful insights into the potential of industrial chemistry and entrepreneurship to create job opportunities for secondary school students in the state.

Keyword: Education, Entrepreneurship, Chemistry, Metacognitive, Chalk

Introduction

The economic situation today in our country is becoming unbearable to the citizens. It's not because the government folds its arms; they are also trying to do their best to make everything better for the common citizens, but because the needs and aspirations of the people are beyond the government's capacity to meet them. It's high time for the government to have a total holistic approach by looking into the education content to which every subject is established in order to achieve the stated educational goals. The development of an economy to sustain human problems must have a concerted action policy on different sectors like education, health, and the agricultural system with holistic approaches that foster qualitative and quantitative economic changes. A nation can only develop if a robust and structured education is given that can help in providing solutions to human problems. Education is seen as the tool for the effective integration of individuals into a society so that the individual can achieve self-realization, promote unity, strive for social, economic, political, scientific, cultural, and technological processes, and develop national consciousness. This shows that any nation or country that produces better education for all will be able to meet global competitiveness (Adedo, Umar, & Adesoji 2022).

The inability of the government to meet the yearnings and aspirations of its citizens has now become a treat, leading to unemployment, poverty, and other social crimes, which have now become a canker worm deep in the fabric of every individual just to get a daily bread. These are only some of the intrinsic motivations that can lead people down the path of entrepreneurship or other combinations of reasons that will inspire one to start a business. These developments necessitate the wiliness of every

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individual to look for education that will suit their demands. The only way out is to integrate entrepreneurship skills into our teaching and learning in the classroom. Education effectiveness and efficiency during teaching and learning situations in the classroom setting if they must survive, a teacher needs to pay attention to the three teaching and learning domains, which include cognitive, affective, and psychomotor (National Policy on Education 2013). NPE revised in 2013 that it was to promote functional education for skill acquisition, job creation, poverty reduction, and the quality of instruction at all levels of education. Educational institutions perform the significant function of providing learning experiences to lead their students from the darkness of ignorance to the light of knowledge. Efficiency in education is when the aims of educational goals are achieved efficiently and effectively through the stated curriculum contents. The student will become a skilled learner, and that's the only tool to achieve national objectives. Shulman (2007) sees content knowledge as a teacher's achievement, or it's considered a measurable performance indicator for assessing a teacher's achievement. The way out for now is to see how entrepreneurship skill acquisition education will be developed into our teaching within the classroom setting.

The emergence of entrepreneurial education in Nigeria can be attributed to rise in unemployment, crime rate and other social verses due to inappropriate implementation of good policies and bad governance on the utilization of the available resources to meet the yearnings and the aspiration of citizens introduction of entrepreneurship education can serve as substitute in management and utilization of available resources to meet the demanding issues (Nwosu, 2014). Odiagbe and Otemuyiwa (2021) revealed that entrepreneurship education as a learning which involves one towards self-reliance, a reasonable channel that will greatly assist in curbing unemployment and leading to national development if entrepreneurship education is introduced the problem of unemployment will be greatly reduced. If the government pays more attention to skills acquisition and entrepreneurship education is quickly identified and packaged well into trainings, it will serve as substitutes for employment opportunities, reduce crime rate and will also assist individuals to contribute to economic development. Odiagbe and Otemuyiwa (2021) state that entrepreneurship education as a process that involves idea generation, opportunity identification, and business plan, which result in business or product creation. If the country must move forward, this demand for entrepreneurship education must be looked into most especially in our secondary school education.

Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN, 2013) give that entrepreneurship education at the senior secondary education level is the teaching and learning at the post basic geared towards inculcating entrepreneurial skills in the learners towards becoming self-reliance. Knowledge acquisition is the process of absorbing and storing new information in memory, the success of which is often gauged by how well the information can later be remembered (retrieved from memory). Guastello, Beasley & Sinatra, (2000) see the process of storing and retrieving information depends heavily on the representation and organization of the information. Moreover, the utility of knowledge can also be influenced by how the information is structured. The most important part of entrepreneurship is that it's a cognitive process using mental approaches where the potential of human knowledge is demonstrated; it's a process where assumption and aspiration can only be established through innovation of mind to become an inventor; sharing of these innovative ideals by interpretation is what it means to be an entrepreneur. Cognitive science shows how concepts are formed in students' minds and, most importantly, how they are connected, which might imply students' conceptual understanding. Ogundeji (2019) states that students' conceptual understanding will continue to require both knowledge of and the ability to use scientific concepts to develop mental models about the way the world operates, following a current scientific theory.

According to Aliu, Kadir, Rasheedat, and Abdulrasaq (2020), metacognition and its related processes have been shown to affect the human performance, functions, and behavior of individuals in an array of situations, including performance in education. Amutha & Sudha (2016) define metacognitive as enabling the learner to detect their weaknesses in learning and determine the better way to learn. One of the aims of education today is to make the student gain the thinking skills and strategies that they will use throughout their lives rather than storing information. The National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP, (2005) states that conceptual understanding in science means understanding the principles of science, especially the concepts used to explain and predict observations of the natural world, and knowing how to apply this understanding efficiently in the design and execution of scientific investigations and in practical reasoning.

The role of secondary education in national educational system cannot be underrated. It is the intermediate level between the primary and tertiary education. As a conciliator, it absorbs the product of primary education, and serves as an input unit for tertiary education being a midpoint in the pecking order of education. Secondary school education indicates its value and its quality influences on the standard of education and shows the level of literacy in the country. (Ogundeji., Umar, Olubunmi & Adedo 2022),

Chemistry is one of the subjects offered at the upper level in Nigerian secondary schools. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) describes chemistry as one of the science subjects that senior secondary school students take. It is a very important

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science subject and a requirement for further learning in a number of science-related professional courses, like medicine, agriculture, pharmacy, etc. According to Oloyede (2010), chemistry pervades literally every field of human endeavor and plays a fundamental role in educational advancement. It occupies a unique position among the various science subjects offered at the senior secondary school level because it is a fundamental requirement for most core science-based courses. Tbilisi, (2012) Chemistry as a subject is conceptual. Students learning chemistry at the school level, or in colleges and universities, are taught about and asked to master a wide array of concepts. Concepts are central to understanding chemistry, and the understanding of chemical concepts is therefore a core concern in chemical education. This research was carried out using chalk production as one of the numerous contents in chemistry because it's one of the essential tools that are commonly and widely used in teaching and learning situations and accepted throughout the world. If students are taught to demonstrate it practically in the classroom by transforming chemical combinations into chalk products, it will greatly improve their understanding of scientific principles and phenomena while at the same time serving as skill acquisition, which seduces the researchers. Chalk is a white soft limestone that is formed as a result of the combination of POP (Plaster of Paris) and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) in in form of burning limestone that is deposit and develops as coccoliths (a minute calcareous plate created by the decomposition of plankton skeleton), a tiny marine organism. (Evans, Hopson, Royle, & Woods, 2004).

The knowledge acquired in learning chemical concepts is not straightforward and thus requires special training and orientation that would make one carry out the necessary teaching. This has contributed to no interest in or awareness of its importance in daily activities and in the production of common household products. Students at all levels often do not understand or have a partial understanding of the scientific principle behind the knowledge of chemical chemistry concepts or, indeed, misunderstand it when they come across it within the key concepts they meet in their studies of chemistry. This is one of the core issues in chemistry education. The understanding of these scientific concepts and principles behind its operation is certainly still unclear; introducing the student to the aspect of turning chemical contents into products would make some of these concepts and principles behind scientific operation understood.

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the level of awareness on the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State.
2. To examine the level of interest on the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State
3. To determine the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge of achievement on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State

Research Questions

The following proposed research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of student awareness of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State?
2. What is the level of student interest in industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State?

Hypotheses

The following Research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge of Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production and student academic achievement among Secondary School students in Zamfara State.
2. There is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method.
3. There is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production in Zamfara State

Methodology

This research is descriptive and experimental using the Hannifen-Peck design model and motivation theory, respectively. The state has fourteen local governments, which are divided into three senatorial councils: Zamfara Central Zone, Zamfara West, and Zamfara North. One senatorial council was selected using simple random sampling. The senatorial councils consist of different local government areas, which include Zamfara Central Zone with four local government areas, Zamfara North Zone with four local government areas, and Zamfara West Zone with six local government areas. Out of the selected senatorial

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councils, two local government areas were selected using a multistage process. Selection of two schools each from the selected local government area using purposeful selection based on the availability of the laboratory and students offering chemistry as part of their science subject. The population for this study comprised all science senior secondary schools in Zamfara, with a random sampling of 80 (eighty) senior secondary school (SSS I) students that offered chemistry subjects drawn from four public senior science secondary schools in Zamfara Central Zone in the Gusau Local Government area of Zamfara State. A pretest and posttests on Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) is used to determine the achievement while a structured questionnaire were used to determine the interest and awareness on the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. The structured questionnaire consists of 10 (Ten) question items on Interest of the Impact of Industrial Chemistry Concept Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production (IIICCKESACP) and 10 (Ten) on Awareness of the Impact of Industrial Chemistry Concept Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production (AIICCKESACP). Using Linkert Scale, statistical tools were used for data analysis, A pilot test was administered to 20 non participant with the reliability coefficient of 0.82, 0.83 and 0.72 were obtained for CAT, (IIICCKESACP) and (AIICCKESACP) respectively.

Results

Research Questions

What is the level of student awareness of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State?

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Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on level of students' awareness

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
Are you aware that the production of some non-consumable products is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.60	.704	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of some consumable product is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.25	.948	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of some technological equipment's made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.37	.919	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of some home appliances and equipment's is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.26	.910	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of chalk is made through transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.59	.774	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of chalk is made from combinations of some elements through transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.84	.462	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of kampala is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.63	.663	Accepted
Are you aware that kampala design products is made from combination of some elements through transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.71	.508	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of herbicide in insect killer products is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.81	.480	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of herbicide in insect killer is made from combination of some elements through transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.72	.595	Accepted

From the result in table one, what is the level of awareness of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. The mean of the respondents is between 3.25 and 3.81 which is greater than decision rule of 2.50. This was subjected to descriptive analysis it's here by concluded that student were aware, This show that there is no practical demonstration of most industrial chemistry content teaching that could hinder more explanation to scientific principles for better understanding.

Research Question 2

What is the level of interest in industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics showing level of Interest of Secondary School Students on Industrial Chemistry Contents

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Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
Teaching practical production of insect killer in the classroom will help to increase student learning interest in in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.80	.461	Accepted
Teaching practical production of chalk in the classroom will help to increase student learning interest in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content.	3.79	.520	Accepted
Teaching practical production of kampala in the classroom will help to increase student learning interest in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.79	.495	Accepted
Use of practical method to teach some chemistry chemical concept in the classroom will help student learning interest in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.69	.608	Accepted
Use of practical method to teach some chemistry chemical concept in the classroom will increase student entrepreneurial interest	3.64	.621	Accepted
Exposing student to use of knowledge in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content on consumable products production increases student learning interest in chemistry as a subject	3.48	.763	Accepted
Exposing student to use of knowledge in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content on non-consumable products production increases student learning interest in chemistry as a subject	3.55	.692	Accepted
Practical teaching on how to transform industrial chemistry chemical content to product will assist and expose student to element's familiarization leading to an increase in student learning interest of entrepreneurial concept	3.69	.493	Accepted
Exposing student to use of knowledge in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content production increases student learning interest in chemistry entrepreneurial concept	3.54	.728	Accepted
Exposing student to use of knowledge in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content production improve student learning understanding in chemistry entrepreneurial concept	3.56	.709	Accepted

From the result in table two, what is the level of student interest in industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. The Mean score of the respondents is between 3.54 and 3.80 which is greater than decision rule of 2.50. This was subjected to descriptive analysis it's here by concluded that student have interest of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. This shows that student have interest in entrepreneurship skills acquisition.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge of Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production and student academic achievement among Secondary School students in Zamfara State.

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Table 3: t-test on student academic achievement

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig.	Mean Difference
Pretest	80	25.38	8.998	25.222	.000	25.375
Posttest	80	55.05	27.950	17.617	.000	55.050

From the result in table three, there is no significant difference in students' achievement on the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. This was subjected to T-test analysis. From the result it was observed that there is positive increase on student academic achievement the mean scores of pretests 25.38 the posttest mean scores is 55.05 with mean difference of 25.375 and significance level of .000 lesser than 0.05. It is concluded that the null hypotheses is here by rejected there is significance influence in student academic achievement.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method.

Table 4 Group mean of experimental and control

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pretest	experimental	40	29.38	6.732	1.064
	Control	40	21.38	9.267	1.465
Posttest	experimental	40	76.95	17.548	2.775
	Control	40	33.15	17.048	2.696

From the result in table four, there is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method. This was subjected to descriptive analysis. This show the difference in the performance of each group based on experimental and the control group in the pretest, the mean score of experimental is 29.38 with standard deviation 6.732 and the mean scores for the control is 21.38 with standard deviation 9.267 while in the posttest mean score of experimental is 76.95 with standard deviation 17.548 and the mean score control is 33.15 with standard deviation 17.048. The mean difference between the pretest and posttest of experimental group is 47.57 while that of control difference between the pretest and posttest is 11.77. There is influence on the academic achievement for experimental group than the convectional group.

Table 5: ANCOVA of students Achievement in Chemistry Chemical Contents

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	50300.355 ^a	2	25150.177	169.674	.000
Intercept	1920.861	1	1920.861	12.959	.001
Pretest	11931.555	1	11931.555	80.495	.000
Group	15958.406	1	15958.406	107.662	.000
Error	11413.445	77	148.227		
Total	304154.000	80			
Corrected Total	61713.800	79			

The result from table five, there is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method. This was subjected to ANCOVA analysis of covariance. The mean square value of the group is 15958.406 with .000 level of significant lesser than the p-value at 0.05. This

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implies that there is significant influence of the group achievement when taught with it and does taught with conventional method of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State The null hypothesis is here by rejected at 0.05 level of significant and concluded that there is significant influence on the group on industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production in Zamfara State.

Table 6: ANCOVA of gender influence

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	37198.274 ^a	2	18599.137	58.417	.000
Intercept	774.903	1	774.903	2.434	.123
Pretest	37030.074	1	37030.074	116.307	.000
Gender	2856.325	1	2856.325	8.971	.004
Error	24515.526	77	318.383		
Total	304154.000	80			
Corrected Total	61713.800	79			

The result from table 6, there is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production in Zamfara State. This was subjected to analysis of covariance the mean square value of the group is 2856.325 with .004 level of significant lesser than the p-value at 0.05. This implies that there is significant influence of the gender on industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State The null hypothesis is here by rejected at 0.05 level of significant and concluded that there is significant influence of gender on industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production.

Discussion of Findings

There is no significant impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge of Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production and student academic achievement among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. The result of the analysis of hypothesis shows that there was significant impact of the content knowledge on chalk production the hypothesis is rejected. This is in line with Syden and Gordon (2014), who conducted a study to analyze the entrepreneurial awareness among high school students. A sample of 150 high school and higher secondary school students from 6 schools were selected for the study. The result revealed that majority of the respondents heard about entrepreneurship and it suggests that entrepreneurship education can create awareness from the school level itself so that self-employment career option can instill at the earlier. According to Verheul and Stel (2007) increase in education level of entrepreneurs leads to an increase in entrepreneurial income and productivity. Moreover, education is claimed to be an important factor when starting entrepreneurial activity. This shows that a good ability to turn ideas into action make individual aware and understand the chemistry chemical content of their work and able to seize opportunities that's available for new acquisition.

There is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method. The result of the analysis of hypothesis shows that there was significant difference on chemistry students' achievement when taught using industrial chemistry content knowledge and does taught without using it for entrepreneurship skills acquisition among secondary school students in Zamfara State the hypothesis is rejected. The result was in line with related study by Malebana (2014) showed that students were more pulled rather than pushed into entrepreneurship. In other words, students were interested in entrepreneurship mainly as a result of positive factors such as the opportunity to make use of creative talents, independence and prospects for higher earnings than through negative factors such as high prevalence of unemployment. Olatunbosun (2019) observed that science practical work plays a vital role in developing scientific knowledge and enhancing scientific skills, attitude and enquiry based learning that student learn by performing

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concrete activities by comparing experimental activities to normal learning this have an effect on learning achievement This shows that it's not unemployment that leads to entrepreneurship but for self-reliance.

There is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production in Zamfara State The result of the analysis shows that there was significant influence of the gender on industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State the hypothesis is also rejected. The result is in line with Asoegwu (2008) observed from it study breaking gender barrier on performance in science, he used hand-on and minds-on science that students either male or female that were expose to scientific process oriented learning, students engagement, manipulation of materials assist in problem solving skill in respect of the gender., while Duyilemi and Olusa (2016) gender and performance, in their experiment discover that there is no significant difference in performance of male and female performance in science subject.

Conclusion

The result shows that the student were aware and they have interest of the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. It also observed that the student taught with the practical demonstration using industrial chemistry content knowledge have better achievement in entrepreneurship skills acquisition than those taught with conventional methods its concluded that gender and academic achievement is influenced by entrepreneurship skills acquisition this will gear up student interest and give more awareness with better understanding to scientific principle which in turns boost student academic achievement and reduce the rate of unemployment and social crimes.

Recommendations

1. Government need to look into how curriculum content of every course can be attained and
2. Government need holistic approach to the type of education needed to its citizen that would lead to reduction in unemployment and social crimes.
3. Both the government and the stake holders in education to create more awareness on the need to transform most of the contents that will serve as entrepreneurship skills acquisition.
4. The teacher in chemistry and other science related course for more training.
5. Adequate finance must be put in place proper implementation of the skill to survive.
6. Teacher of sciences must see skill acquisition beyond the out the school curriculum.

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Impact of Single Parenting on Academic Performance among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone

Zubairu, Zainab Ph.D.

Email: zubairu022@gmail.com

Tel: 08037872125

Department of Educational Foundations, Kaduna State University, Kaduna

Abstract

This study investigated impact of single parenting on academic performance among secondary school students in Zaria Educational zone of Kaduna State. The study intended to appraise how academic performance of secondary school students in Government as a school subject is influenced by single parenting viz-a-viz income status, educational attainment and occupational status. Three research questions and two null-hypotheses each were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The research design used was survey and quasi experimental. Questionnaire and achievement test were the duo instruments used for data collection. The study population is comprised of teachers and students of public secondary schools in Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of twelve (12) teachers and Three Hundred and Twenty- Three (323) students were randomly selected from the study population. Achievement test was administered on the students, the questionnaire was filled and returned to the researcher by the teachers. Findings from this study showed that educational attainment of single parents has significant impact on students' academic performance in Government. The study equally identified that occupational status of single parents has a great impact on the academic performance of students in the subject". Based on the findings of this study, it became obvious that the nature of single parental homes determines their wards academic performance in school. Academically, there are various variables that predict one's performance in school subject. These could be those from the family and others from the teachers. The study therefore recommended that stigmatization of single parents and their children should be discouraged forthwith by enacting relevant laws, parents should also be mindful of their children's education as something very important at least before contemplating on divorce and/ or separation from their homes. On a final note, the government should institute a special scholarship to assist students of poor single parents who are presently enrolled in school to caution the effect of their financial weaknesses.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Impact, Single Parenting, Secondary School Students

Introduction

The focus of this study was to investigate impact of single parenting on academic performance among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. Single parenting has replaced the widely known traditionally intact family. Ortese in Muhle (2020) observed that "parents are the first point of contact of a child or children. In situation where both parents are present, it implies that the child would derive more care and attention under their custody. A single parent however is a parent not living with his/her spouse or partner". The entire obligation of raising the child or children therefore falls solely under the care of a single father or mother as the case maybe. Studies by Falana, Bada and Ayodele (2012) asserted that "single parenting results from divorce, separation of various kinds, having children from wedlock or death of one spouse, and leaving the role in the hands of a single parent". Thus, society continues to grapple with the breaking down of the traditional family forming new structures that adversely affect the development of children and in particular, their academics. Education as a whole is believed to recreates both the individuals and the nation, influences values and attitudes for a worthwhile living. It is no surprise that the National Policy on Education (2014) asserted that education is "an instrument par excellence" and the world at large had keyed into this, by recognizing education as the panacea to development and survival of man itself. In defining single parenting, Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, conceived the term as a mother or father who looks after children on their own, without the other partner. It is a situation in which one of the two individuals involved in the conception of the child is being responsible for the upbringing of the child (Whitting and Child in Tenibiaje and Tenibiaje, 2011). In Nigeria, the existence of single parent was formerly unknown and where they exist they were mostly ignored as exceptional cases. Presently, single parenting is the fastest growing family system both inside and outside the shores of the land (Nwachukwu, as cited in Chukwuemeka, 2018). There are widespread cases of single - parenthood across all regions and tribes

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where human beings lived which has further become a major source of concern to the socio - economic and socio - cultural development.

Another important variable known to have been captured in this paper is academic performance. Academic performance is very important in any educational setting, as it indicates the level of a student's competence in respect of the academic content. Indeed, academic performance does create competition among students and it may thus shift focus to the academic content of a course; however, academic performance is a prerequisite in order to achieve success at every other level of educational pursuit. Academic performance is represented by the actual mark obtained by the participants in an examination. Success is typically defined in terms of performance, and grades represent the most obvious and universally accepted indicator of academic performance in the educational context (Hampden - Thompson and Pong in Jaiyeola and Akinjide, 2016). The academic performance of a student determines whether he or she will be considered successful or not. As a result, academic performance is very important in education. Therefore, it is crucial to know and understand which factors are responsible for determining, predicting or causing variance in academic performance.

The family lays the psychosocial, moral and spiritual foundations upon which the overall development of the child can take off. A mother's role in laying the right foundation cannot be over - emphasized. Likewise, studies on father - child relationship suggest that the presence of a father in the home influences significantly the development of a child (Ushie, Emeka, Ononga and Owolabi, 2012) Thus, parenthood is a responsibility that requires the full cooperation of both parents who must ensure the total development of their children. The inference to be drawn from the above submission is that, structurally, a family is either broken or intact. In Nigeria, parental roles are culturally determined and distributed. Maternal roles include child - rearing, home training and playing of complementary roles, while paternal roles include financial provision (food, clothing, and shelter) for the family and discipline of the children. (Uwaifo, 2012). The inference from this submission is that a child is likely to be morally, mentally and emotionally balanced when the caring responsibilities are carried out by both parents. However, these balances may be jeopardized when the responsibilities are being carried out by a single parent.

The above analysis becomes necessary because life in a single - parent family can be stressful for both the child or children and the parent. Such families as Chang and Min (2002) rightly observed are faced with the challenges of diminished financial resources, assumption of new roles and responsibilities, establishment of new patterns in intra - familial interaction and re - organization of routines and schedules. These conditions may not be conducive for effective parenting. This is because when the single parent is overburdened by responsibilities and by their own emotional reaction to their situation, they often become irritable, impatient and insensitive to their children's needs. (Biblarz and Gottainer, in Jaiyeola and Akinjide, 2016) As a result of the substantial prevalence of single parenthood, researchers such as (Ebenuwa - Okoh; 2010; Farooq, Chaudhry, Shafiq and Berhanu, 2011) have extensively examined the consequences of growing up with a single parent for children's education. The outcome of their researches revealed that single parenthood is negatively associated with children's academic performance, however, recent comparative studies show that the strength of the negative relationship varies significantly across countries. (Mandara and Murray, 2006).

Likewise, emerging facts from other studies of developing societies have found no apparently negative effects of single parenthood (Park, 2008; Osunloye, 2008 in Jaiyeola and Akinjide, 2016), rather they found that in sub - Saharan African countries, children in female - headed households tended to have greater educational opportunities in terms of school enrolments and attainment relative to children in male - headed households. On his part, Fadeiye in Jaiyeola and Akinjide (2016) concurred that both parents have their own roles to play in child's education. The father is to provide every necessary tools for the educational advancement while the mother is expected to supplement the efforts of the father. But in the case where the father is absent and the mother is not privileged enough (in terms of income) to cater for all the necessary and basic needs as well as supervising the academic performance of the child, by checking the academic records of the child or by going through their class and lesson notes or books daily. Also giving of counselling supports when needed, these will affect the educational state or level of the child. So also, if a child is not well nurtured and mentally assisted, it will also affect his/her educational outcome. If it were to be a male child, it's likelihood for the child to be anti - social in nature by joining gangs, also, if it were to be a female child, there is likelihood for her to become wayward.

Contributing, Nwachukwu in Asaah (2021), found children from single parent homes to be more hostile, hyperactive and aggressive in nature. Many of the problems that single parents have, are similar as those of two - parents family, but these problems seem more difficult to bear or manage when the home is being tutored by only one person. For example, all children feel hostile towards their parents as they grow - up and try to be independent. But in a situation, where the anger and rebellion are all directed towards one person, it may seem worse, if there is only one to bear it, and not for the two to share. No doubt, a herculean task which may not be easy for an individual parent alone. In case of divorce, separation or death of a parent, children

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are somewhat at greater risk for symptoms of poor psychological adjustment, behavioural and social problems, low self - esteem and poor performance in school. Coupled with this, it is believed in many quarters that children from broken homes have higher incidence of academics, emotional and behavioural problems than other children from intact homes. Recall that single parenthood has existed as a practice of raising children or building family without a spouse or a partner. With this form of building a family, single parenting is now permissible in our societies which formerly stigmatize such a system because it was not much acceptable. Research studies even suggested that children from poor single parent households do not perform well in school as their counterparts from wealthy single parent households (Majoribanks in Watt, 2019).

For the single mothers, they are stigmatized because of patriarchal system of family run in our society (Falana, Bada and Ayodele, 2012). Culturally, it is not acceptable to live with opposite gendered parents. A parent conjointly leaves remarkable impacts on children's behaviours, personality and health. For instance, a girl cannot share every little matter with her father as she can with her mother or vice versa. Attachment is a basic human need to secure relationship between children and caregiver. A child psychiatrist John Bowlby (1958) gave a theory of attachment which clearly explains how children and their parents relationship emerges and influence the emotional and social development of a child. Bowlby designed four stages of attachment from infancy as pre-attachment, attachment in making, clear cut attachment, and formation of reciprocal relationship. All these stages build up a bond and this bond binds parents and their children emotionally (Conor and Scott, 2007). Bowlby's colleague built up another three stages he called detachment, protest and despair experiences children faced when they are separated from their caregivers/parents (Chapman, Whitefield, Felitti, Dube and Edwards, 2004).

When parents are not able to build stronger relationship in their homes, then there are higher chances that children will face some problems such as psychological disorders, such as decrease intelligence, increase anger and violent behaviour (Conor and Scott, 2007; Chapman, Whitefield, Felitti, Bube and Edwards, 2004). This theory is considered best for this work owing to its nature. In all these, children at the primary schools are nonetheless the most fragile group because they are still in their formative years, meaning that any disruptions could have everlasting effect on them. Many studies in Nigeria actually have focused more on parental involvement in children's school activities, compared with family structure such as single parenthood and its effects on the pupils' academic performance. In terms of their educational pursuit, this is relatively determined by the pattern of family or home one comes from, be it wealthy or poor, educated or otherwise. Parents are primarily responsible for the educational and career development of their children (Salami and Alawode, cited by Asah, 2021).

Parents who failed in their responsibilities to assist and guide their children through every stage of development in life may likely have to contend with the poor academic performance of their children sooner or later. The development of wholesome behaviours, as foundation to success in any child is laid upon the home and at the initial stage in life. Parents therefore have a great role to play in seeing to it that students acquire the appropriate social, psychological, moral and academic development. The benefits of two - parents family far outweigh that of a single parent family, as mothers play the traditional role of child care and home-making while the father's role is that of economic responsibilities and discipline of children. Although, these traditional responsibilities of parents are gradually changing. But in single parent families, double responsibilities are required of time, attention and money of the parent. Hence, less attention is given to the education of the child. The situation has become worst today because of the prevailing cost of receiving education as most single parent may not be financially handicapped to handle it. For the few wealthy single parents who are economically viable, the nature of their job will always affect adequate supervision of children's growth and development which may hamper on their academic performance. By and large, Uwaifo (2008) found that differences in academic performance of children exist in terms of those from single parent and those from two parent families. Arising from this, it therefore became imperative to examine the impact of single parenting on academic performance of secondary school students in the study locality.

In recent times, the controversies surrounding academic performance of secondary school students is worth something of discourse and urgent attention. This is especially in view of the roles of families and its subsequent make - up which have assisted or otherwise. Family, as it is known is the first contact for every child born into this world and her contributions no doubt to its academic prowess or otherwise in life cannot be under - estimated. A family type that is headed by a single parent before now is being stigmatized but fast becoming the societal norm. This type of family in the real sense is undoubtedly going to be overburdened with the absence of the other partner for known reason(s). Of concerned, the academic status of students from such homes will suffer the consequences of poor or inadequate funding and character disposition of parents towards them. The national policy on education (2014) recognized the importance of funding on education have suggested that adequate financial provision from all tiers of government for successful implementation of educational programmes are required. It therefore shows that access to education by the ward(s) of a single parent depends on their financial capability. Not too surprised, that children of single parents in the study locality attend public secondary schools.

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Also, single parenthood plays a vital role in determining or otherwise of a person's academic performance in and out - of - school. This is because the level of education of a single parent will go along way to determine what their ward (s) would eventually become in life. The situation is worsened by the fact that the so - called illiterates and unskilled single parents have absolutely no plan for their ward(s) compared to their counterparts who are not only financially buoyant but determine to provide the best for their children's education. There are other categories of single parents with little or no education and at the lower class of a society but determined to give their wards a higher - level education than they could not have achieved. Evidently, the researcher observed that larger population of children attending public schools from single parental homes does not have access to educational facilities, resulting in their mass failure in public and internal examinations due to poor preparation.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated impact of single parenting on academic performance among secondary school students in Zaria Educational zone of Kaduna State. Specifically, the study determined:

1. Find out the impact of income of single parents on academic performance of students in Biology in senior secondary schools of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State.
2. Assess the impact of educational attainment of single parents on academic performance of secondary school students in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study

1. What is the impact of income of single parents on students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State?
2. Of what impact was educational attainment of single parents on academic performance of secondary school students in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State?

Hypotheses

The following null-hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

1. There is no significant impact between income of single parents and academic performance of students in Biology in senior secondary schools.
2. There is no significant impact between educational attainment of single parents and students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools.

Methodology

In this study, descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of this study was comprised of students and teachers of public senior secondary schools under Zaria Educational zone of Kaduna State. There are well over forty - one (41) public and private secondary schools from the selected zone. Out of this, about twenty - eight (28) are public secondary schools with students and teachers' population put at thirty - six thousand, seven hundred and eleven (36,711) and one thousand, three hundred and sixty - six (1,366) respectively. A sample size of three hundred and thirty - five (335) respondents was selected at random from the target population of this study. The study employed the use of questionnaire and achievement tests as major instruments for data collection. A pilot study was carried out in Government Commercial College, Zaria on thirty (30) SS 2 students and eight (8) teachers in different arms of the selected class. The reliability test scores for the instruments was 0.86 and 0.81 both for the achievement test and questionnaire respectively. Data collection was undertaken within ten (10) weeks. Research assistants were identified, trained and motivated on how to assist in the administration of instruments. The data analysis was carried out on the formulated hypotheses using inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

Results

Research Question 1

What is the impact of income of single parents on students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State?

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Table 1: Respondents Opinion on the Impact of Single Parental Income on Students' Academic Performance in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone

S/N	ITEMS n = 335	RESPONSE CATEGORIES						
		SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD	SE
1.	In my school, enrolment of students from single parental homes are high due to the cheap cost of education by parents	-	5	4	3	2.1667	.83485	.24400
2.	In spite of the poor facilities in my school, poor single parents in their large numbers prefer to sent their ward to us	2	7	2	2	2.8667	.9847	.2842
3.	Most wealthy single parents in my school promptly pay their ward school fees and acquire other educational materials	3	2	2	5	2.25000	1.2880	.3718
4.	Children from wealthy single parental homes send their wards to boarding school system to display affluence.	3	3	3	3	2.500	1.1.677	.337
5.	Most students from poor single parental homes do not have access to educational material books.	1	2	5	4	2.0000	.9534	.2752
6.	Children from wealthy single parent homes do not have much financial support compared to their counter parts from poor single parents homes.	4	3	2	3	2.6667	1.2309	.3553
7.	Children from poor parental homes do not have much financial support compared to those from wealthy single parental homes	3	2	2	5	2.4500	1.2880	.3718

Source: Field work (2021)

According to the table above, the highest mean response of 2.8667 is on the item that says that in spite of poor facilities in the selected schools; single parents in their large numbers prefer to send their wards there. This item on the influence of income status of single parent on children academic performance showed that a total of 9 of them agreed with this item while 3 disagreed.

Research Question 2

Of what impact was educational attainment of single parents on academic performance of secondary school students in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State?

Table 2: Respondents opinion on the influence of single parental educational attainment on the academic performance of students in Biology in Zaria Educational Zone

S/N	ITEMS n = 335	RESPONSE CATEGORIES						
		SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	SE
1.	Most educated wealthy parental homes deny their girls access to formal education	-	2	6	4	1.8333	.71774	.20719
2.	As a teacher and parent, single parent do not sponsor the education of their wards as a result of their poor life situation	1	-	6	5	1.7500	.2500	.86603

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3.	Most of the poor single parental homes are headed by women with little or no education	2	3	3	4	2.2500	1.13818	.32856
4.	Most educated single poor parent enroll their wards in schools their counterparts cannot afford	1	4	4	3	22500	.96531	.27866
5.	Children from poor parental homes are privilege to receiving qualitative education as one of the parents will at least be educative.	5	2	3	2	2.8333	1.19342	.34451
6.	It is evident that poor educational status of most single parents encourages them to offer the best education to their wards	3	3	3	3	2.5000	1.16775	.33710

Source: Field work (2021)

According to the response rate on the influence of parental educational attainment on students' academic performance, children from two parental homes are privileged to receiving qualitative education as one of the two parents would at least be educated. This item attracted the highest mean response of 2.8333 and details showed that item 7 agreed while the item found in 5 disagreed.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho1: There is no significant impact between income of single parents and academic performance of students in Biology in senior secondary schools.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Impact of Income Status of Single Parents on the Academic Performance of Students in Government as a Subject.

Variables	N	X	Sd	Df	Correlation index r	P
Students' Academic performance in Biology	333	10.08	4.05	318	.96**	0.000
Income Status	73	33.35	1.53			

Source: Field work (2021)

The result of the correlation test revealed that significant impact exists between the income status of single parental homes and the academic performance of their students in Government. The reason was that the calculated P value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 alpha level of significance at a correlation index value of 0.96. By implication, the null hypothesis stated above is hereby rejected.

Ho2: There is no significant impact between educational attainment of single parents and students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Impact of Educational Attainment of Single Parents and Academic Performance of Students.

Variables	N	X	Sd	df	Correlation index r	P
Students' Academic performance in Biology	333	10.08	4.05	331	.973**	0.000
Educational Attainment	333	33.35	3.79			

Source: Field work (2021)

Correlation is tied to be significant at 0.05 level of significance. The details of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics revealed the existence of significant impact between the educational attainment of single parents and academic performance of students. This was because the PPMC calculated P value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 alpha level at a correlation index t-value of .97. This therefore implies that the null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

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Discussions of Findings

The results from tables 1 and 3 of this study revealed that significant impact exists on the income of single parents on academic performance of students in Biology in the study area. It is worthy of note, that income is the conduit pipe to decision making in anything one does. In fact, this had remained the root causes of family conflict and finally separation of homes. Many have attributed the amount of money available to homes to how much they are likely to enjoyed themselves and even provide a sound education to their wards. The aforementioned was in conformity with research studies which suggested that children from poor single parent households do not perform well in school as their counterparts from wealthy single parent households (Majoribanks in Watt, 2019).

Report from the analysis in tables 2 and 4 showed the significant impact existed between educational attainment of single parents and students' academic performance in Biology. Information is power and thus, the reason why it constitutes an essential factor for consideration of successes in any given tasks not to mention the academic lifestyle of students in schools. The works of Dale and Griffith cited by Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) supported this finding in which they found out that a parent's education contribute maximally to any child's performance in school.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it became obvious that the nature of single parental homes determines their wards academic performance in school. Academically, there are various variables that predict one's performance in school subject. These could be those from the family and others from the teachers. However, since this study is concerned with the home factors. Such variables identified to have one impact or the other on the student's academic performance are parental education, number of children in the home, parental occupation and income among others. The fact established in this study has brought about the conclusion that more negative impact could super cede the positive ones on single parental upbringing on the student's academic performance in government within the study area.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations put forward as a result of the outcome of this study:

1. The government should institute a special scholarship to assist students of poor single parents who are presently enrolled in school to caution the effect of their financial weaknesses. To this end, modalities for accessing the funds should be clearly spelt out by setting up a committee.
2. Stigmatization of single parents and their children should be discouraged forthwith by enacting all relevant laws.
3. Parents should be way mindful of the decision they take with respect to their children's education as something very important at least before contemplating on divorce and/ or separation from their matrimonial homes.

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Impact of Van Hiele's Model on Mathematical Thinking in Longitude and Latitude among Secondary School Students in Sokoto State, Nigeria

*Aliyu Bello Shehu¹

Email: saliyutureta77@gmail.com

Tel: 07034514761

Hassan Muhammad Nasir¹

Email: mohammad.nasiruhassan@ssu.edu.ng

Tel: 08067788633

Ibrahim Nasiru Tambuwal¹

Email: nasiru.ibrahimtambuwal@ssu.edu.ng

Tel: 08036084320

Maccido Isah¹

Email: isahmaccido20@gmail.com

Tel: 07037106344

¹Department of Science Education, Sokoto State University, Sokoto

Abstract

This research aims at examining students' mathematical thinking ability. In order to achieve these objectives two research questions with their equivalence null hypotheses were generated to guide the study. A quasi-experimental design entailing pretest and posttest was employed. A sample of 267 (155 Male and 112 Female) students were selected using simple random sampling techniques through balloting method out of 28,897 students during 2022/203 session. Mathematical Thinking Ability Test (MTAT) was the instrument used for data collection. The validity of the instrument was established by four experts and a pilot study was carried out. The result of the pilot study through test re-test approach Using PPMC statistical tool indicated a reliability index of 0.72. Independent sample t-test was used to analyze the two null hypotheses. The result of the first null hypothesis indicated a significant difference between the two groups in favor of the EG. Moreover, the second null hypothesis shows no significant difference in gender. It was recommended that Van Hiele's instructional model should be incorporated in the curriculum as model of teaching longitude and latitude.

Keyword: mathematical thinking, van Hiele, longitude and latitude

Introduction

Advancement in science and technology requires a great deal and mastery of Mathematics. The aim to achieve technological goal cannot be achieved unless and until Mathematics is given a sufficient time and consideration. Moving to achieve a particular level of technological know-how cannot be restricted by other factors like Mathematics do. As the universe is moving and accepting the pen less system with the aim of making a computer-based society, the role of Mathematics is like an engine to a machine. The importance of Mathematics in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized as it is core subject taught from primary one up to the terminal level of secondary education. It is because of the role of Mathematics to the nation building and in nutshell to the development of science and technology in Nigeria was made a compulsory requirement for admission into any tertiary institutions. Therefore, method, strategy, technique, model, materials and personnel should be sufficiently deployed to the area.

Many researches have been conducted in order to improve teaching and learning Mathematics in general. The researches had pin point the weakness of the curriculum, teaching methodology, the instructional materials, teacher development and professionalism, culture and many more variables. These had also called for application of specific strategies, techniques or models to a specific concept in Mathematics. Even with application of some specific strategies, methods or models to various concepts of Mathematics there's one that best fit for particular concept. These may yield fruitful results. This

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make Lince (2016) to believe that Mathematics improve students’ logical thinking, analytical, systematic, creative thinking as well as ability to cooperate. These thoughts can be reared through the use of innovative and modern techniques of teaching and learning.

Mathematical thinking ability is creative thinking (Lince, 2016). Mathematical thinking ability is a cognitive process of analyzing, synthesizing and comprehending the concept or ideas. According to Yulianti, Sumarmo and Kustiana (2020) mathematical critical thinking signifies the ability to be able to clarify an idea or concept with sufficient and genuine reasons. Mathematical thinking ability is important in decision making. It involves rational thinking and passing judgments with a valid conclusion. It helps the students to identify relevant and irrelevant idea or thought so as to make right deduction to pass a reasonable judgment. This ability needs to be cultivated from the basic to make a sufficient utilization of it. It can build in students through the use of innovative teaching techniques. Students taught by traditional teaching method have low mathematical thinking ability (Yulianti, Sumarm & kustiana, 2020). It indicated that the use of innovative models such as Van Hiele’s model can improve students’ mathematical thinking ability. So also Casing and Roble (2021) indicated that the use of innovative teaching techniques or models improve students’ mathematical thinking ability rigorously. Teachers need to imbibe new teaching techniques or models such as Van Hiele’s model in order to improve students’ mathematical thinking ability. Similarly, the findings of Brojonegoro (2020) indicate that the use of innovative teaching models increase students mathematical critical thinking ability. This Mathematical critical thinking ability involves mental construction of a genuine and unique idea. It also involves the ability to make a justifiable deduction from infinitely unassembled ideas or concepts. Furthermore, Van Hiele’s learning model can increase the mathematical thinking ability of students even at the advance level. This was also re-affirmed by Armah, Cofie & Okpoti (2018)

Gender had always been a concern to the researchers. This is because many people believe that Mathematics is male dominated area. It makes the female students lose interest and develop math phobia. The cause of this had been investigated by the concern educationists. Many attached this to poor teaching method, lack of instructional materials, teachers’ personality, school environment and other related factors. According Brojonegoro(2020) Mathematical thinking ability is not an innate ability but can be develop through the use of the right and appropriate teaching model. Female students can as well develop mathematical thinking ability as much as their male counterpart or even better if appropriate techniques are employed. Many researches had portrayed the ability of female students in competing with their male counterpart in various concepts of Mathematics. Such researches include Hassan, Abdullah and Ismail (2020), Conolly (2010) and Aliyu and Ibrahim (2017). All these researches indicated the power of innovative teaching strategy or model in neutralizing the gender inequality.

An education practitioner always tries to find out challenges and problem face by education and come up with a possible solution. Van Hiele was not left out as a teacher; his concern was to improve teaching and learning in some of the most difficult areas of Mathematics. A Dutch educator was hit by the difficulty encountered by students in learning geometry. This make him to pursue an applied research and come up with a model that is so simple and precise. The model is a hierarchical and sequential arrangement of the possible steps to follow in teaching and learning geometry. This had help a lot during the time and many researchers applied the model in various location. The result is fruitful. The steps indicate the geometric thinking level of the students. Learning from the basic level to the highest level. At each level the complexity of the model rise to match the cognitive demand of the students. The steps are applied in learning geometry and other related concepts which may involve the use of geometrical figures. The steps are listed below.

Figure 1: Steps in Geometrical Figures

As human knowledge grows twice in every 24 hours in this 21st century as Ben Carson stated, the knowledge is now beyond recall and retrieved of already stored information. The nation and society in particular require innovation, creativity,

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thinking ability, abstract decision making to solve their immediate problems. This dynamism of nature called for mathematical thinking ability to acquire or access the basic proficiency to explain or find the solution to immediate needs of the society. Thinking is the ability of a person to grasp an idea, concepts or techniques (Lince, 2016). This requires a person to intellectually scrutinize the ideas or concepts with the hope of fishing out the most beneficial component to the society. Creative thinking is mathematical in nature (Lince, 2016). Mathematical thinking is the ability to analyze, synthesize, making generalization, deduction, drawing a conclusion, hitting the ideas from every angle, discuss and be able to solve mathematical problems precisely and concisely with a unique and best method possible (Brojenogoro, 2020). Mathematical thinking may be ability to think out of the box when confronted with a mathematical problem and by extension to a real problem in the society. It is therefore, imperative to develop such Mathematical thinking in the students for fruitful outcome.

Generally, the importance of Mathematics cannot be overemphasized and in particular geometry. Geometrical figures are so useful that we make extensive use of the concepts in our daily activities such as measuring of land and in the building constructions. Such geometric figures play vital role in identifying various location on Earth through the use of longitude and latitude. These concepts become a heart of aviation industry. Clements and Sarama (2011a) in Hassan, Abdullah and Ismail (2020) affirm that geometrical concepts in Mathematics supersedes all other concepts in terms of usefulness. While according to Hassan, Abdullah and Ismail (2020) geometric skills form the bedrock for advancement in science and technology. This shows the immense benefits found in the concepts. It is paramount important that these concepts should be given much attention and consideration in terms of the teaching methodology, model, instructional materials and personnel. Unfortunately, many students find it difficult to understand these concepts as they failed to get a minimum required mark in the external examination such as WAEC and NECO. This issue was identified by WAEC Chief Examiner's report of 2016-2019. Even in 2020 and 2021 the report shows evidence of the lack of understanding geometrical concepts. Some of the remedies to this failure as suggested by chief examiner was teachers to imbibe a new strategy or techniques or models to simplify the concepts in order to improve students' performance. Many efforts were made to remedy this situation such as the improvisation of geometrical figures both wooden and plastic. School and other professional bodies' efforts such as conferences and seminars. But yet the failure persists up to 2021. It is because of this the researchers deemed it necessary to measure the impact of Van Hiele's instructional model on longitude and latitude in order to assess students' mathematical thinking ability.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to assess and measure the mathematical thinking ability level of senior secondary school students in Sokoto State through the intervention of Van Hiele's learning model on longitude and latitude concepts. Specifically, the following objectives are addressed in this research.

1. To examine Mathematical thinking ability on longitude and latitude using Van Hiele Model among secondary school students in Sokoto State.
2. To investigate mathematical thinking ability on longitude and latitude using Van Hiele's model between male and female secondary school students in Sokoto State.

Research Questions

The research was guided by the following questions

1. What is mean difference in mathematical thinking ability between students taught longitude and latitude using Van Hiele's model and those expose to traditional model in Sokoto state?
2. Would there be mean difference in the mathematical thinking ability between male and female students taught longitude and latitude using Van Hiele's Model in Sokoto state?

Null Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were generated and tested at 0.05 level of statistical significance.

1. HO₁: There's no significant difference in the mathematical thinking ability between students taught longitude and latitude using van Hiele's model and those expose to traditional model in Sokoto State.
2. HO₂: There's no significant difference in the mathematical thinking ability between male and female students taught longitude and latitude using Van Hiele's model in Sokoto State.

Methodology

This research aims at investigating mathematical thinking ability on longitude and latitude using Van Hiele's model among secondary school in Sokoto State. Because of the inability of the researchers to make random assignment to the various subjects a quasi-experimental design was employed entailing pretest and posttest. 28,897 students form the population for this

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study. The sample size was determined through the use of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of determining sample size. 267 students were selected from two secondary schools used as intact class. The secondary schools were selected using simple random sampling techniques through balloting method. The two schools were randomly allocated to experimental and control group. 125 and 142 students form the control and experimental group respectively. There are 72 male and 53 female students in control group. While in the experimental group there are 83 male and 59 female students. Mathematical Thinking Ability Test (MTAT) was the instrument used to capture the required data. The test undergoes serious scrutiny by four experts and a final draft was drawn and administered to the sample. A portion of the population was tested and retested with the instruments. The result was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. An index of 0.72 was found as such the reliability of the instrument is guaranteed. Descriptive statistics was employed in answering research questions. The data collected was from two independent samples as such an independent sample t-test was used to analyze the two stated null hypotheses.

Results

Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions one and two. Independent sample t-test was used to analyze null hypotheses one and two.

Research Question 1

What is mean difference in mathematical thinking ability between students taught longitude and latitude using Van Hiele’s model and those expose to traditional model in Sokoto state?

Table 1: Mathematical Thinking Ability Mean Score in EG and CG

Group	N	Mean	Std Dev.	Std Error Mean
Experimental	142	3.82	2.44	0.12
Control	125	2.59	0.95	0.09

Field data (2023)

From the table above, the mathematical thinking ability of students when exposed to Van Hiele’s learning model was improved. Even though the mean difference is meager but at least the intervention had shown in the mean score

Table 2: Mathematical Thinking Ability Levels of Experimental and Control Group

Group	Mathematical Thinking Ability Level							
	Level 1		Level 2		Level 3		Level 4	
	Passed	Failed	Passed	Failed	Passed	Failed	Passed	Failed
Control	120 (96%)	05 (4%)	50(40%)	75 (60%)	43(34%)	82(66%)	31(25%)	94(75%)
Experimental	139(98%)	03(2%)	114(80%)	28(20%)	101 (71%)	41(29%)	97(68%)	45(32%)

Research Question 2

Would there be mean difference in the mathematical thinking ability between male and female students taught longitude and latitude using Van Hiele’s Model in Sokoto state?

Table 3: Mathematical Thinking Ability of Male and Female in the Experimental Group

Gender	N	Mean	Std Dev.	Std Error Mean
Male	83	3.62	1.71	0.12
Female	59	3.20	1.60	0.20

Field data (2023)

The table above indicated that Van Hiele’s learning model is gender friendly. Even though there’s difference in the mean performance of male and female mathematical thinking ability. The difference is meager not sufficient enough to justify a change due to gender.

Table 4: Mathematical Thinking Ability Level of Male and female Students in EG

Gender	Mathematical Thinking Ability Level of Male and Female
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	Level 1		Level 2		Level 3		Level 4	
	Passed	Failed	Passed	Failed	Passed	Failed	Passed	Failed
Male	83	0	80	3	71	12	68	15
Female	56	3	34	24	30	29	29	30

Hypothesis 1

HO₁: There’s no significant difference in the mathematical thinking ability between students taught longitude and latitude using van Hiele’s model and those expose to traditional model in Sokoto State.

Table 5: Analysis of Mathematical Thinking Ability of Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Mean	Std Dev.	P-Value	Decision
Experimental	142	3.82	2.44	0.001	Rejected
Control	125	2.59	0.95		

Decision Criterion: Reject H₀ if P≤0.05. Field data (2023)

From the table above the p-value is 0.001. Therefore, the stated null hypothesis is rejected. This indicated there’s significant difference in mathematical thinking ability of students taught longitude and latitude using Van Hiele’s learning model and those taught using traditional method. The result favors the experimental group.

Hypothesis 2

HO₂: There’s no significant difference in the mathematical thinking ability between male and female students taught longitude and latitude using Van Hiele’s model in Sokoto State.

Table 6: Analysis of Mathematical Thinking Ability of Male and Female in the Experimental Group

Gender	N	Mean	Std Dev.	P-value	Decision
Male	83	3.62	1.71	0.100	Accepted
Female	59	3.20	1.60		

Decision Criterion: Reject H₀ if P≤0.05 Field data (2023)

Table 4 above shows p-value of 0.100 which greater than 0.05. Therefore, the stated null hypothesis is accepted. This indicated no significant difference in the mathematical thinking ability of male and female students when taught longitude and latitude concepts using Van Hiele’s learning model. The model is gender friendly.

Discussion of Findings

From the analysis, the first null hypothesis indicated a significant difference in the mathematical thinking ability of students taught longitude and latitude using Van Hiele’s learning model and those exposed to traditional method in favor of experimental group. This finding is not void because it further confirms the result submitted by Yulianti, Sumarmo and Kustiana (2020). Van Hiele’s learning model is an innovative technique to improve students’ mathematical thinking ability in geometrical figures and other related concepts. So also Casing and Roble (2021) submitted a similar finding. They posited that the use of innovative strategy or model improve students’ mathematical thinking ability vigorously.

The second null hypothesis indicated no significant difference in mathematical thinking ability of male and female students exposed Van Hiele’s learning model. This confirm no gender disparity when Van Hiele’s model is used in teaching longitude and latitude. This finding was supported by some recent results such as Aliyu and Ibrahim (2017), Hassan, Abdullah and Ismail (2020) and Conolly (2010). Therefore, Van Hiele’s model as an innovative teaching model if properly used and utilized can bridge gender disparity in geometric concept and other related topics such longitude and latitude.

Conclusion

At the terminal of this research, the findings indicated that Van Hiele’s instructional model improve students’ mathematical thinking ability better than the dominant method used. It further revealed an equal chance for female students to perform and enhance their mathematical thinking ability as well as their male counterpart.

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Recommendations

1. Van Hiele's learning model should be used in teaching and learning longitude and latitude
2. The model can also be use in teaching other geometry aspect such as trigonometry.
3. Workshops can further be done in other state by ministries of education or other education stakeholders in order to make the model widely known

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Policy Formulation and Implementation at Secondary Level of Education in Nigeria: Challenges and Way Forward

***Burwa Umar Muhammad Ph.D.¹**

Email: umar.muhd@udusok.edu.ng, umarmuhd619@yahoo.com

Tel: +2348037855482, +2348080408743

Muhammad Rabi'u²

Email: rabiumuhammad52@yahoo.com

Tel: +2348036010685

Abubakar Ibrahim Sahabi¹

Email: @udusok.edu.ng, ibrahimsahabi@gmail.com

Tel: +2348037855482,

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

²Department of Education, Maryam Abacha American University, Niger

Abstract

Secondary school level education in Nigeria as enshrined in the national policy on education shall make contributions to national development in the Provision of trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades. This paper reviewed issues such as, Scope and Purpose of Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria's Context, Features of Policy in Education, Sources of Education Policy, Types of Education Policy, Importance of Education Policy, Policy making process, The National Policy on Education, Policy Implementation, Purpose of Policy evaluation, Criteria for evaluating Public Policy, Characteristics of a good education Policy, A brief history of education policies formulation and implementation in Nigeria, and Problems of Policy Implementation in secondary Education in Nigeria, were discussed, The paper concludes that, the failure of educational policies in Nigeria has been traced to poor monitoring and implementation of educational policies the secondary education as enshrined in the national policy on education has stipulated specific goals and objectives which can only be achieved through implementation and evaluation via effective management. The goal attainment may be viewed as a destination, where management represents the vehicle, leadership style represents the fuel and people (government and school administrators) are the (drivers) implementers. It was recommended, Governments should ensure continuity in the implementation of education policies before embarking of formulating new ones More effort should be put to carve the menace of corruption in the implementation of education policies and finally, effective education policies implementation mechanism should be put in place so as to ensure optimal result.

Keywords: Educational Policy, Formulation, Implementation,

Introduction

Secondary Education is one of the bedrocks and the foundation level in Nigerian educational system. As a result of its importance, there is need to effectively and efficiently manage or administer resources (Human and materials) in Secondary Schools in order to realize the laudable Goals and objectives of Secondary Education as enshrined in the National Policy on Education. Secondary Education has been described as the bedrock of every society and tool for nation building. For qualitative education to be achieved in a nation the principal actors of learning who are the teachers, learners and the environment must be cooperatively organized. Secondary Education is described as an instrument per excellent for effecting national development (FRN, 2014). However, realizing the role that education plays in national development, Nigeria government have to venture into various educational policies and programmes with the expectation of meeting the country's needs in the areas of human and infrastructure development. According to the National Policy on Education (2014), Secondary education in Nigeria has the following objectives to:

1. Provide holders of the basic education certificate and Junior Arabic and Islamic studies certificate with opportunity for education at a higher level, irrespective of gender, social status and religious or ethnic background.
2. Offer diversified curriculum to cater for the difference in talent, disposition opportunities and future roles.

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3. Provide trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades.
4. Provide Entrepreneurial, technical and vocational jobs, specific skills for self-reliance, and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development.
5. Develop and promote Nigerian Languages, art and culture in the contexts of world heritage.
6. Inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence.
7. Foster patriotism, rational writing and security education with the emphasis on the committees in spite of our diversity.
8. Raise morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, respect the views and feelings of others and appreciate the dignity of labour.

According to Jumare (2019) these laudable objectives can only be achieved with the help of several individuals within and also outside the school. However, within the school a number of efforts especially by the school head in relation to the administration of secondary schools.

Scope and Purpose of Secondary Education in Nigeria's Context

Secondary education is provided for children after primary education, that is, before tertiary education. It is aimed at developing a child better than the primary level, because it is obvious that primary education is insufficient for children to acquire literacy, numeracy, and communication skills (Ige, 2011; Yusuf, 2009). Such education is provided in secondary school, which can be owned by government (State or Federal), individuals or community. It is divided into two phases as follows:

Basic level of Education

This is the first three years of secondary education. The curriculum at this level is pre-vocational and academic in scope. Core, pre-vocational and non-prevocational subjects are included in the curriculum. The core subjects include: English Language, Mathematics, French, and a major Nigerian Language other than that of environment. A child has to do the junior school certificate Examination (JSCE), being coordinated by State Ministries of Education or Federal Ministry of Education.

Senior Secondary School Level

This is the next three years after Basic level education. It has wider scope than the Basic level (JS) phase and aims at broadening the knowledge and skills of a student beyond the Basic level and thus prepares him/her for further education. It is academic and vocational in scope. A student has of minimum of seven and maximum of eight subjects, comprising of six core subjects: English Language, Mathematics, a major Nigerian Language, one science, an art, and vocational subject. One or two others elective are to be selected from the art, science, technical, social science, and vocational subject. Certificate at the end of this phase depend on the performance of a student in the continuous assessment (CA) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE), coordinated by West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO). A child must obtain a minimum of five credits at not than two sittings including English Language and Mathematics to be able to proceed to the tertiary level of the education system.

Basic Concepts of Education Policy at Secondary level of Education

Policy is an official prescription promulgated the authority to guide the attainment of goals. Education policy is binding guideline which describe and prescribe the objectives and strategies for the systematic of the business of education. Education policy entails specific goals, programmes and activities set by Governments on education for the attainment of education needs of the citizenry for economic growth and national development. Policy on education means Governments decisions on how actions on education can be carried out at different levels of educational system so as to improve the standard and performances in the education practice (Jumare, 2015).

Features of Policy in Education at secondary school of Education

There are specific features of policy in education as outlined by Jumare (2015) as follows

1. It involves actors (policy makers) and executers (policy implementers)
2. Most policy are in the form of summary statements of government line of action
3. Education policies are statutory functions of the government (control of education)
4. Education policies are futuristic in nature
5. Policy changes as needs of the society changes (policy is always dynamic)

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6. Most policies are made by the government

Sources of Education Policy at secondary school level of Education

Policy in education has different sources some of which are as follows:

1. Political leaders: Political leaders initiate and formulate education policies as captured by their political party's manifestos. For example, the Universal Primary Education (UPE) in 1955 in the Western Region and Universal Basic Education (UBE) in 1999/2000 and 6-3-3-4 system.
2. Legislative Arm of Government: The law-making body as an independent arm of government could also formulate policies that has to do education
3. Commission of Enquiry: Reports from Commission set by Government look for the needs and agitations of the populace, recommendations could be used to formulate education policies.
4. Educational Administrators and Planners: These are experts and professional in educational administration. Researchers and findings carried out by them became source of government policy in education. For example, the Curriculum Conference in 1977 (Jumare, 2015).

Types of Education Policy at secondary school level of Education

Many scholars have classified different types of education policies. Classification depends on the background and orientation of such scholars they are follows:

1. Distributive policy: This involves allocating or sharing of government resources to a particular group of population; states, regions and or individuals. This in education is always manifested in the process of admission into Nigerian universities as quota system, scholarships/fellowship school location and other government programmes in education.
2. Redistributive Policy: This policy entails change in allocating, sharing and distribution of resources or program formular. Okeke in Jumare (2015) sees this policy as policy equilibrium. This policy involves balance distribution of resources between areas that have and those that are lacking. For example, Jonathan administration in 2012 promised to established federal university in each of the 36 states of the federation.
3. Constituent Policy: This involves policies formulated for the use of a particular area, state or region. Universal Primary Education (UPE) in the Western region in 1955 and Almajiri system school in the Northern part of the country are good examples of this policy.
4. Regulatory Policy: This refers to a policy that involves regulating and controlling government agencies to fulfil the needs and yearnings of the citizenry. For example, National Universities Commission (NUC), National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) and National Board for Technical Education (NBTE).

Importance of Education Policy at Secondary level of education

Nwangu in Jumare (2015) states the importance of education policy as follows:

1. Policy statements are designed to guide implementation of education programmes and activities.
2. Policy provides the form and strategies on how the implementation of a given programme whether the desired result is being achieved for future development.
3. Policies determine the direction of future development of education program.
4. Administration of a program through policies confirm confidence on the personnel and education managers.
5. Policies help management in decision making and also assume continuity.
6. Policies give confidence to all stakeholders (in education) because there is something to guide decision making process.

Policy making process at secondary level of education

There are three variables in the public policy making process especially at the secondary level of education they are INPUT, CONVERSION and OUT PUT. Input consists of demands and support from the government. Not all demands made become policy agenda. There is also what is referred to as gate-keepers who select issues to be placed on the agenda. What informs their decision are the moral values of the people and the availability of economic resources to implement the policy. After the selection the agenda is forwarded to the institution responsible for making the policy (Ujo, 2011). Manga (2015) stated that policy making process is an organized activity that should be done in logical stages. The following constitute the steps in policy making process at secondary level of education:

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Step I: Problem identification: It must be as serious contemporary problem affecting the public

Step II: Problem Analysis: It must be broken down to establish its genesis, scope and implication

Step III: Formulation of strategies: Various alternatives for solving the problems are formulated.

Step IV: Selection of strategy: The best strategy is to select after considering the relative advantage and disadvantages of each.

Step V: Implementation: This involves putting into practice or action the selected strategies.

Step VI: Evaluation: The impact of the policy is assessed to determine areas of strengths and weaknesses.

Step VII: Policy Revision and adaptation: It is revised to correct mistakes and adopted to make it binding.

The National Policy on Education at secondary level of education

The National Policy on education is a document published by the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The Educational Research Council to serve as official guidelines to govern the educational system at all levels. The National policy on education gives the objectives and strategies to be pursued at national level as a whole. It also specifically provides guidelines on Early childhood/pre-primary education, Basic education, secondary education, mass literacy, Adult and non-formal education, science technical and vocational education, tertiary education, Open and distance education, special education, educational services, planning, administration and supervision of education as well as financing of education. A nation's policy on education is government way of realizing that part of the national goals that can be achieved education as a tool. No policy on education can be formulated without first identifying the overall philosophy and goals of the nation. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) the overall philosophy of Nigeria is to:

1. Live in Unity and harmony as one indivisible, democratic and sovereignty nation founded on the principles of freedom, equality and justice.
2. Personate inter-African solidarity and world peace through understanding. The five known National Goals of Nigeria which have endorse as the necessary foundation for the national policy on education are the building of:
 3. A free and democratic society
 4. A just and egalitarian society
 5. A united and self-reliant nation
 6. A great and dynamic economy
 7. A land full of bright opportunity for all citizens

Nigeria's Philosophy of education theories is based on:

1. Developing individual into a sound and effective citizen
2. Full integration of the individual into the community
3. Provision of equal access to educational opportunities for all citizens at all levels from primary to university (Manga, 2015)

Policy Implementation at secondary level of education

Policy implementation is the process of putting a policy into action. Anderson in Ujo (2011) defined public policy implementation as "whatever is done to carry a law into effect, to apply it to a target population to achieve its goals". Anderson further asserted that the study of public policy implementation is concerned with the agencies and officials they employ and the political support and the opposition that they may encounter. Rushefsky (2007) described public policy implementation as the carrying out or execution of a programme that has been adopted by legislator or by executive or judicial order.

Characteristics of a good education Policy at secondary level of education

Manga (2015) asserted that, a good education policy at secondary level of education should have the following certain features:

1. Desirability: the policy must be desired by the people to whom it is made. It must not be forcefully imposed on people.
2. Clarity: A good policy must be stated in a very clear and understandable language to ease interpretation.
3. Relevance: A good policy must be relevant to the social, cultural and educational needs of the people.
4. Comprehensiveness: A good policy must contain detailed information on its objectives methods procedures and standard to be pursued.
5. Enforcement: A good policy must be one that is enforceable with punishment for violators
6. Flexibility: A good policy must make room for amendment and changes when circumstances require it.

Challenges of Secondary School Education in Nigeria

It is not a gainsaying that secondary education is unique in the educational development of a child, being the link between primary and tertiary education. The knowledge, skills, values, and traits which a child acquires at this stage will complement those acquired at the primary level and when these are combined will prepare such child for tertiary education. In spite of the role of secondary education, (Ajayi, 2004) reported that it is riddled with crises of various dimensions and magnitude all of which combine to suggest that it is at crossroad. An examination of secondary education in Nigeria reveals the following challenges that are plaguing it and undermining the achievement of its objectives.

1. **Inadequate and low-Quality Teachers Inadequate staffing:** One of the reasons for the low level of quality assurance in Nigerian secondary schools is a severe shortage of teaching staff.
2. **Under funding:** One of the greatest challenges that appears to face Nigerian secondary schools is that of under-funding. Finance is so crucial to any organization that it continues to dominate discussions on the state of secondary level education in Nigeria. Running the institution, therefore, requires significant investment in providing and maintaining a basic level of infrastructure – such as facilities, staff salaries, and residential housing. Secondary Schools in Nigeria have been supported largely by government in the past, but with the economic down-turn, these Secondary Schools have been grossly under-funded and this has invariably led to the quality being adversely affected. Some of these institutions are characterized by poor infrastructures, overcrowded classrooms, incessant strikes and student unrest.
3. **Enrolment Explosion:** This over enrolment has become a common feature in Nigerian universities. Many of the facilities on the ground are being overstretched. This development will surely affect the quality of Secondary Schools education in Nigeria, since excess enrolment usually leads to overcrowded classrooms, ineffective teaching and
4. **Poor Management:** The way and manner some of the Nigerian secondary schools are being managed by the some school administrators has also had a consequential effect on quality assurance in the secondary schools. For most of the secondary school administrators, management means little more than playing the role of “Caretaker”. This vital function has been largely reduced to the maintenance of the status quo. This unfortunate development significantly negates the concept of a secondary education, particularly in a developing country like Nigeria. It seems certain that as long as management continues to play this non-challant role, the quality assurance will continue to be jeopardized in the secondary schools (Ujo, 2011).

Educational Policies in Contemporary Nigeria

In Nigerian educational system, there are numerous policies geared to better the system, this paper will discuss some of these policies. Their role in achieving primary and secondary education objectives.

Establishment of Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN)

The Council was established by the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria Decree (Now act) 31 of 1993. Several decades of agitation by professional teachers and other stakeholders for the establishment of a regulatory agency led to the enactment of the Act. The council finally became operational by June, 2000.

Responsibilities of the TRCN

The Act that established the council in section 1 (1) charged it with the following responsibilities

1. Determining who are teachers for the purpose of this Act
2. Determining what standard of knowledge and skill are to be attained by persons seeking to become registered as teachers under this Act and raising those standards from time to time as circumstance may permit.
3. Securing in accordance with the provisions of this Act the establishment and maintenance of a register of teachers and the publication from time to time of the lists of those persons
4. Regulating and controlling the teaching profession in all it's aspects and ramifications
5. Classifying from time to time members of the teaching profession according to their level of training and qualification
6. Performing through the council established under this Act the functions conferred on it by this Act. (TRCN Teachers Hand book, Revised Edition, 2005).

A brief historical of education policies formulation and implementation in Nigeria

According to Odiba and Igono (2014) certain historical antecedents have impact on how educational policies are formulated and implemented in Nigeria. The Lagos Colony, Southern and Northern protectorates were British Colonies which

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were amalgamated in 1914 and named Nigeria. The Territory remained a British colony till 1960 when it attained independence. Nigeria has witnessed several educational reforms which started at pre-independence. It was to the credit of Nigerians agitators for self-rule that led the British colonial rulers to change the educational system in operation in 1954 from 8-6-2-3 system 8year primary, 6year secondary, 2year higher school certificate and 3year university to a new system 6-5-2-3 that is 6year primary, 5year secondary school, 2year higher school certificate and 3year university. The change resulted in reducing the number of years at the primary and secondary school levels. Nigerians then were more concerned about education. The hope in the educational reforms continued to rekindle after independence. The freedom of self-rule Nigeria was enjoying had no match with educational progress.

In September 1969 there was a National Conference held in Lagos. Participants at the conference were eager to see Nigeria chart a new course in its educational system. Such a system they reasoned will empower the country towards the path of scientific and technological development. They criticized colonial education system as lacking in vitality and reference. The conference recommended changes in the system from 6-5-2-3 system to 6-3-3-4 system that is 6year primary, 3year junior secondary, 3year senior secondary and 4year university education. The recommended system is simply American system of education which Japan copied and succeeded. In 1977 a new document known as National Policy on Education came to stay

Problems of Policy Implementation at secondary level of education in Nigeria

Problems of policy Implementation in Nigeria are many that hampered the successful implementation of education policy in the country some of which are as follows:

1. **Frequent change of Government:** Frequent change of government has resulted in frequent change of policy. Every government of the day in Nigeria comes with new policy by ignoring the previous ones. Most of the policies were not fully implemented let alone being evaluated. Most of these changes were during the military regimes. For example, Universal Basic Education (UBE) which is still facing numerous challenges in preparing students to senior secondary school level.
2. **Inadequate dependable data:** Data refers to statistical information that are used for making decisions. Therefore, data gives insight into policy formation, implementation, and success or otherwise. Thus, most data in Nigeria especially on secondary level of education are grossly inadequate and or alliterated due to political reasons. This affects policy implementation and decisions.
3. **Inadequate involvement of education stakeholders in policy formulation:** Most policies in education especially on secondary level of education lack incorporation of implementers and other stakeholders at the formation stage. Such stakeholders could include teachers, parents, religious leaders, traditional leaders, students and non-governmental organizations. This becomes a setback since the implementers have no in its formation.
4. **Inadequate funding:** this serves as a major setback in many education policies. For example., the UPE in 1955 (Western Region), the UPE of 1976 and the current UBE of 1999 without adequate funds to run the program. Thus, the program remained only paper.
5. **Corruption and misplacement of priority:** Several cases have shown that the scarce funds dedicated for policy implementation were either stolen or diverted for self-aggrandizement. Many times, governors read budgetary allocation dedicated to education policies and programs but unfortunately the program will end there. While in some cases the funds are diverted to other government activities. In fact, due to self-interest within the education sector, funds are made more available in some of a program while other not provided. Owolahi in Jumare (2015),

Conclusion

The conclusion of the paper is that, the failure of educational policies in Nigeria has been traced to poor monitoring and implementation of educational policies. It was discovered that these problems are policy formulation vurus policy implementation, poor budgetary allocation, logistic problems, Nigeria philosophy of education, frequent changes in government and policies, corruption, inadequate awareness, lack of data for planning, lack of adequate consultation of policy implementers at the planning stage, inadequate skill manpower, inadequate provision of human, materials, infrastructure and financial resources among others.

Recommendations

1. **Governments** at all levels should ensure continuity in the implementation and evaluation of education policies before embarking of formulating new ones.

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2. Adequate and dependable data should be provided as data gives insight into policy formation, implementation, evaluation and success or otherwise.
3. All stakeholders should be included at the formation stage of education policies
4. Adequate funds should be provided for the implementation and evaluation of education policies.
5. More efforts should be put to carve the menace of corruption in the implementation and evaluation of education policies.
6. Effective education policies evaluation mechanism should be put in place so as to ensure optimal result.

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Prevention of Relapse/Reoccurrence and Preparedness of a Post COVID -19 Pandemic in Cross River State, Nigeria

*Anake, P. M.¹

Email: anakepaulina@gmail.com

Abuo, C. B.¹

Anake, G. A.¹

Dibang, S. T.¹

¹Department of Guidance and Counselling, University of Calabar, Calabar

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the preventive measures of relapse/reoccurrence and preparedness of a post COVID 19 outbreak among individuals in Cross River State of Nigeria. The study made use of both primary and secondary data; one-on-one interview was conducted by the researchers and also works on covid-19 were assessed and used to gather information for the study. The study looked at the historical and origin, control and prevention of Covid-19. The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak, which originated in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, has gradually spread to over 215 countries. It was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization in March 2020. Since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, more than 79 million cases and over 1.7 million deaths have been recorded globally as at December 29, 2020. The paper also discussed the multimodal strategy towards a long term COVID-19 control and prevention. For a successful immunization programme, there is a need to have a high rate of vaccination coverage. The study concluded that the COVID-19 pandemic is not over yet and with the emergence of new waves of the disease and other strains of viruses that could emerge in future, preparedness should be continuous to curtail the spread of the infection.

Keyword: Prevention, relapse, preparedness, post covid-19, Cross River State

Introduction

The Corona Virus pandemic is both a public health and economic emergency and has posed a devastating and painful experience which the presence of emergence pathogens can be consequential to lives and livelihood worldwide. By January 2020, WHO declared COVID-19 a Public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC), the highest alarm the organization can sound (Sylvia, 2020). The global response, however, has being a transformative moment, which had exposed our inherent deficiencies, inequalities and weakness in the face of the pandemic preparedness and response (Thomas & Stewart, 2020). COVID-19 pandemic is far from over and could yet evolve in unanticipated ways. However, one of its most important lessons will involve, Preparation, prevention and early execution, aimed as an essential tool in detecting, containing, and rapidly responding to and mitigating the spread of potentially dangerous emerging infectious diseases.

There is a multimodal strategy towards a long term COVID control and prevention. A protocol that sets up multiple barriers of protection so as not to only contain or eliminate covid-19 as a major-life threatening disease, but also in the long term prevent and limit the emergence of novel viruses and a return to a new socioeconomic life. It is important because of the likelihood that COVID will become endemic (Lavine, et al, 2020). The aim therefore is to eliminating the disease from our communities, even when there are limitations to applying these same measures globally (Brookings Global working paper, August 2021). The World Health Organization (WHO) defines pandemic preparedness as “having national response plans, resources, and the capacity to support operations in the event of any pandemic”. It includes prevention, detection and containment measures, as well as programmes that respond to and mitigate issues that arise from the spread of pandemics, such as (PPE) shortages, limited hospital capacity, and acquisition of vaccines and other countermeasures (Sylvia et al, 2020).

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak, which originated in Wuhan, China, in December, 2019, has gradually spread to over 215 countries. It was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization in March 2020. Since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, more than 79 million cases and over 1.7 million deaths have been recorded globally as

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of December 29, 2020. In Nigeria 255,937 cases have been confirmed, 249,996 cases have been discharged and 3,143 deaths have been recorded in 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory as of 19th to 20th May 2022 (NDCC, 2022). Most people who develop COVID-19 fully recover, but current evidence suggests approximately 10%-20% of people experience a variety of mid- and long-term effects after they recover from their initial illness. These mid- and long-term effects are collectively known as post COVID-19 condition or long COVID. It is important to remember that the understanding of post COVID-19 condition, along with COVID-19, continues to evolve. Researchers are working with patients who develop post COVID-19 condition to better more understand about its cause, symptoms and effects. World Health Organization update information and materials as we learn more.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a devastating effect on many countries' economies, health systems, education systems, and infrastructure. The disease presently has no cure, and disease management is mainly supportive. Regular hand washing, use of facemasks, social distancing, and cough etiquette are vigorously recommended to limit community transmission of the virus. Researchers across the world have been working assiduously to develop vaccines against the highly contagious virus (Ita, 2021). Approximately 60 COVID-19 candidate vaccines are undergoing clinical evaluations and another 172 COVID-19 candidate vaccines are at the preclinical evaluation stage as of December 29, 2020. However, there are widespread skepticism and divergent views regarding the legitimacy of the various COVID-19 vaccines among people across the globe. The pandemic has significantly impacted health systems and economies globally. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has been described as a global health pandemic that has the potential to cause unprecedented devastating socio, economic and political crises (Lone & Ahma, 2020). To stem the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, Nigeria received an estimated 4 million doses of the AstraZeneca/Oxford vaccine through the COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access (COVAX) facility, a partnership between Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI), Global Alliance for Vaccines and Immunizations (GAVI), United Nation Children's Fund (UNICEF) and WHO in March 2021 (Ita, 2021). The National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA), through the State's Primary Health Care Board, commenced the vaccination of Nigerians' priority groups in March 2021, starting with frontline healthcare workers, strategic leaders, security officials and other public personnel identified as eligible for the first phase of vaccination. While the government is doing its best to ensure that most Nigerians gets vaccinated, there has been hope, fear, government distrust, hesitancy, rejection, and conspiracy theories as the COVID-19 vaccination exercise continues (Kimble; Coustasse & Maxik, 2021). Studies both globally and locally have shown that there is a diverse rate of variability in the awareness, perception, willingness, and acceptance rate of the COVID - 19 vaccine (Mohammed, 2020); Cavaleri, Enzmann, Straus & Cooke, 2021; Coustasse & Maxik, 2021).

Generally, for a successful immunization programme, there is a need to have a high rate of vaccination coverage. It is important to understand the Cross-River State of Nigerian factors such as awareness, perception, and willingness to receive the vaccine especially as the first phase of the vaccination exercise kicked off with health workers and frontline personnel. It is hoped that this will guide towards planning for the subsequent phases that will involve a larger population of Nigerians.

Thrust of the Paper

The thrust of this paper is to examine the preventive measures of relapse / reoccurrence and preparedness of a post COVID 19 outbreak among individuals in Cross River State of Nigeria. This can be done through:

1. Occasional checkups to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
2. Social distancing to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
3. Regularly washing of hand and sanitizing to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
4. Regularly wearing of nose mask to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
5. Physical and environmental hygiene to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence
6. Vaccine Hesitancy and COVID 19 reoccurrence
7. Peer education influence and COVID 19 reoccurrence

Occasional checkups to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence

The novel coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has become a major public health problem since the initial outbreak in Hubei, Wuhan, China. The pandemic has significantly impacted on health systems and economies globally. Countries with weaker health systems, particularly those in Africa, were projected to be devastated by the COVID-19. Several vaccines are presently at different phases of clinical evaluation. In addition, some of the vaccines have since obtained Emergency Use Authorization (EUA) from the World Health

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Organization (WHO) and other relevant authorities; notably, BioNTech/Pfizer (BNT162b), Moderna (mRNA-1273), Janssen (Ad26.COVS), AstraZeneca (ChAdOx1 nCoV-19) vaccines and host of others. Since vaccination coverage is a defining factor for successful herds immunity, there is a need to explore the determinants of COVID-19 vaccine uptake that could guide effective vaccination strategies (Lone & Ahmad, 2020). However, "relapse" is the manifestation of symptoms after recovery, while recurrence is referred to infection with the same species and strain of SARS-Cov-2 that may occur due to immunodeficiency of the host. The patients with COVID-19 recurrence evidence ranged in age from 4 to 80 years old and need to repeat test to confirmed status of wellness. Hence, reoccurrence on an individual, means that a person was infected with an agent, recovered, and then become infected later. New infection can be due to a previous infectious agent or becoming infected with a new variant of the agent. According to the CDC's protocol, based on clinical recovery and discharge criteria, recovered patients should have at least one negative SARS-Cov-2 PCR result.

Globally, the virus is believed to be transmitted through droplets and contact transmission although speculations about airborne transmission exist (Anaesthesia, 2020). While research is focusing on the epidemiology, transmission, vaccine development, and therapeutics for COVID-19, there remain gaps in our understanding of the natural history of this disease. One of those gaps is the possibility of disease relapse. Patients reinfected with a strain determined to be of a different genotype or subtype than the previous strain they were infected with can easily be identified using genotyping assays. However, when relapse with a similar strain of the same subtype occurs, phylogenetic analysis is required to distinguish reinfection from a virologic relapse (Xiao & Wong, 2020). In the quest to better understand the incidence natural history of COVID-19, this systematic review of published evidence aims to identify the trends of COVID-19 relapse, the effects of co-morbidities on its relapse, and relapse-associated mortality rates. Batisse, Benech, Botelho-Nevers, Bouiller, Collarino and Conrad (2020) reported that recurrence of COVID-19 after apparent recovery is increasingly globally. According to them, a Collaborative study COVID recurrences (COCOREC) proposed a COVID-19 recurrence to be considered if the second episode occurred 21 days following a symptom free period and alternative etiologies are excluded. In a study conducted by Ye, Pan, Pan, Deng, Chen and Li (2020) on clinical characteristics of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 reactivation from Wuhan China, and the authors observed that 9% (5/55 patients) had a recurrence of the disease. Both asymptomatic and minimally symptomatic patients had the potential to reactivate.

A retrospective study by Agarwal et al. (2020) who analyzed 851 SARS-CoV-2-positive patients with at least two positive PCR tests found that 99 of them remained SARS-CoV-2-positive after 28 days from their initial diagnosis date. The report showed that the median lower and upper bounds for viral RNA shedding in COVID19 patients occurred between 2 to 3 weeks. This raises serious concerns on whether a more precautionary measure should be considered in declaring the recovery phase from COVID-19 infection, and the significance of follow-up, especially in the most vulnerable population (CDC, 2021). There are still a lot of unknown clinical features related to COVID-19 epidemiology, especially in recovered patients. In this regard, it is necessary to understand the epidemiological features of RP-SARS-CoV-2 in recovered patients and to examine whether they are potential threats to public health. Several studies that reported the situations of RP-SARS-CoV2 suggested that subsequent infection mostly occurs due to reactivation or reinfection rather than testing errors or prolonged viral shedding. However, this issue needs urgent attention to investigate whether RP-SARS-CoV-2 patients could be a serious public health problem.

However, some studies such as Hansen, Michlmayr, Gubbels, Mølbak and Ethelberg (2020); Perez, Banon, Gazit, Moshe, Wortsman and Grupel (2021) reported that a small proportion (about 1%) of the population can be RP for SARS-CoV-2, and possibly due to reactivation or relapse. Furthermore, previous reports from Ravioli, Ochsner, and Lindner (2020); He and Dong (2020) highlighted that RP-SARS-CoV-2 is less likely to cause serious problems to public health since the rate of RP seems low (about 1%), and new infections declining after recovery from the first episode of the infection which is likely due to the suspected herd immunity. This suggests that previously infected individuals have a significantly lower risk of being infected for the second time. Consequently, the aforementioned studies highlighted the possibility of reactivation and/or reinfection of SARS-CoV-2, which is less likely to cause a serious public health problem. However, caution should be exercised especially for vulnerable populations even after recovery from SARS-CoV-2. Also, close monitoring on an outpatient Basis appears crucial, since the clinical features and potential reasons for possible reactivation and reinfection remained unclear.

Vaccine hesitancy and covid-19 recover

The World Health Organization (WHO) Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on Immunization (SAGE) has described vaccine hesitancy as the delay in acceptance or refusal of vaccination despite the availability of vaccination services. Vaccine

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hesitancy is considered a significant threat to global health, and thus, due to regional and population variability, there is a need to explore local data to add to the global data pool on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance and hesitancy. Despite the wide availability of the COVID-19 vaccine, safety measure of COVID 19, previous experience suggests huge limitations on vaccination uptake. Sometimes, available information on the COVID-19 are misleading, resulting in confusion and overload. The unfortunate experiences from the previous pandemics (e.g., Influenza), particularly the low acceptance in many countries, suggest the need for an improved understanding of adherence to COVID 19 post condition and vaccine's hesitancy to prevent the spread or re-occurrence the pandemic. The National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) of Nigeria has approved the use of the AstraZeneca (ChAdOx1 nCoV-19) vaccine for use in the country, and presently several others. The Nigerian government has received several batches of the vaccine via the COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access Facility (COVAX), a partnership between the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI), Gavi the Vaccine Alliance, the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the World Bank, and the WHO. The COVAX is part of the Access to COVID-19 Tools (ACT) Accelerator, a global collaboration to accelerate development, production, and equitable access to tests, treatments, and vaccines for COVID-19. Nigeria's National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA) has since commenced stage wise vaccination with priority groups, starting with frontline healthcare workers. The agency has also deployed a self-registration portal online to roll out a country-wide vaccination programme (Xiao & Wong, 2020).

Social distancing, regularly washing of hand and sanitizing to prevent COVID 19 reoccurrence

The Federal Government of Nigeria in partner with NDCC has approved the guidelines for safety measure to prevent COVID-19 Pandemic and re-occurrence COVID-19 as the key strategies for implementing safe, efficient and equitable plans for elimination of COVID 19 in the country. The document focuses on attendance, social distancing, hygiene, cleaning, and non-pharmaceutical interventions for safe and healthy activities and programs. Fortunately, we have observed that many people not only have resisted unethical practice during this crisis, but also have proactively engaged in various COVID-19 guideline activities, particularly those that can offer immediate help and assistance to the fight against the virus.

Precautionary measures to limit the spread of the virus necessitated a shift in the communication paradigm when it comes to greetings and handshakes. The arising situation required people to adopt salutations that do not entail physical contact, such as the "peace sign," the "hand on chest" and the "namaste" (Bergdahl & Nouri, 2020). Protective measures, such as social distancing, hygiene practices and face masks, are essential to mitigate efforts against the virus, but pose challenges on daily face-to-face communication (CDC, 2020).

According to UscherPines, Schwartz, Ahmed, Zheteyeva, Meza, Baker and Uzicanin (2018) the aim of safety measures are important to protect the health of our society. These include quarantines; travel restrictions; limiting travel, use of rose mask, hand sanitizer, regularly washing of hand, avoiding crowded areas, using no-contact greetings, and physically distancing themselves from others. The approaches were more on causes and remediation strategies in Nigeria. However, available justification showed that the variables mentioned above have direct impacts of COVID 19 outbreak among individuals in Cross River State which is the main focus of the study.

COVID-19: The ravaging pandemic

COVID-19 is a potentially severe acute respiratory infection caused by Severe Acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). Infectious diseases such as COVID-19 have demonstrated an ability to ravage populations, overwhelm health systems and economies and destabilize governments. The WHO had reported an outbreak of a novel coronavirus(nCOV) which started in China in December 2019, and has since then spread to the rest of the world. This new strain of Coronavirus causes a myriad of symptoms which includes; fever, cough, shortness of breath and difficulty breathing; respiratory symptoms. In more severe cases infection can cause pneumonia, severe acute respiratory syndromes (SARS) and even death.

Robust strategies for domestic pandemic preparedness

A coordinated and comprehensive approach towards the prevention of relapse/reoccurrence of covid-19 requires investments to be made. Contending COVID-19 require using all available tools at our disposal, while also been aware of our limitations, inequities and disparities within our region which pose a challenge to mitigating the disease. Some nations have been successful so far in containing the spread through public health measures such as testing, contact tracing, and isolation of

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confirmed and suspected cases, vaccination and so forth, keeping the number of deaths within their territories low. The following are some of the proposed coordinated and organized strategy towards COVID-19 control in the Cross-River State:

7. Social Measures & Services
8. Safe waste management; environmental cleaning, sterilization of patient care equipment and linen.
9. Maintaining safe distancing from others (at least 1 meter), even if individual don't appear sick.
10. With the gross disparities within the country, identifying at risk populations most vulnerable to infectious conditions – like the marginalized at-risk and underserved communities and villages in the sub regions of the country inaccessible to COVID-19 preventive measures will be a moral imperative and critical dimension of the COVID-19 pandemic preparedness, response and security.
11. Sensitization, social mobilization and awareness
12. Advocacy for safer environment – Ensuring a clean and hygienic home and working place – regular disinfectant cleaning of surfaces and objects; because contaminated surfaces is one of the main ways infections spreads.
13. Advocacy for practices of cough etiquettes – maintaining social distance, cover coughs and sneezes with disposable tissues or clothing and wash hands.

Information and data sharing

With international cooperation and participation in response to COVID-19 as to our principal donor - The World Bank support and government agencies, will pave notable success. The presence of international community and government will boast both local and global development and equitable distribution of safe and effective vaccines, therapeutics and diagnostics for novel coronaviruses.

Secondary prevention measures

4. As a notifiable disease: Early recognition of cases and prompt reporting to local health authorities or agencies.
5. Immediate isolation of suspected and confirmed cases and implementation of recommended and standard infection and control procedures in line with our Local protocols, including standard precautions at all times.

Areas for infections control and surveillance

13. Point of entry (POE): In line with the WHO recommendations, point of entries – State and local Government level; health facilities, especially the Primary Health Care (PHC) centres should be utilized.
14. Collaborating with Primary Health Services (PHS) on strengthening preparedness: There should be plan to re-train stakeholders and expanding intensive care capacity.
15. Reminder of the basic principles to reducing the general risk of transmission acute respiratory infections, following standard precaution measures.
16. Avoiding close contact with infected persons; frequent hand washing, cough etiquette practices for persons with symptoms of acute respiratory infection, advocating standard infection prevention and control practices within the health care facilities.
17. Identifying common signs and symptoms of communicable diseases
18. Reporting to/inform PHS of any identified cases.
19. Activating the Public Health Emergency contingency plan as necessary, in line with the country's surveillance and response.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic is not over yet and with the emergence of new waves of the disease and other strains of viruses that could emerge in future. Preparedness is a continuous process and the objective is to curtail the spread of the infection, provide a road map to better prepare and execute in future waves of the current pandemic and inevitably when the next pandemic threat emerges.

Recommendations

8. Preventing infection and control is avoiding exposure to the virus with standard preventive measures of public health containment.
9. Public enlightenment and awareness campaigns/education: For any pandemic, disseminating information and providing regular update of its public health message is key to prevention and control.

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10. Support for vulnerable groups and populations; Example women, children, elderly, individuals with chronic medical conditions etc.
11. Isolation and restrictive measures: Avoiding close contact with anyone showing symptoms of respiratory illness such as coughing and sneezing. Staying at home if sick and isolating from other people.
12. Regular and proper hand washing with soap and water, or alcohol-based sanitizers.
13. Practicing respiratory hygiene: Cover mouth and nose when coughing or sneezing, discard tissue immediately in a close bin, and wash hands. Good respiratory hygiene prevents the spread of the virus.
14. Encourage vaccination: Available safe and effective vaccines provide strong protection against serious illness, hospitalization and death for COVID-19. Getting vaccinated is a core strategy to protecting against the virus and a necessary reality of contentment helping to end the pandemic and also stop new variants emerging. Encouraging vaccination will prevent symptomatic infection and severe diseases, which is critical to controlling the spread.

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Qualitative Study on Belief and Attitude of Secondary School Students on Effective Teaching and Learning of Mathematics in Nigeria

*Julius, Elizabeth Ph.D.¹

Email: elizabeth.julius@ksusta.edu.ng

Tel: 08030767562

Dantani, Emmanuel¹

Email: gwamirisiking@gmail.com

Tel: 08068705457

¹Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Aliero

Abstract

This paper focused on qualitative study on belief and attitude of secondary school students on effective teaching and learning of mathematics in Nigeria. The study employs the method of narrative reviews for the synthesis of findings and emphasizes the importance of the role of attitude and belief toward mathematics, which contributes to achieving high performance in the subject. It was suggested in the study that teachers should always examine their students' attitude and provide appropriate support to stimulate the development of a positive attitude toward the subject. Furthermore, it was recommended among others that researchers should conduct additional studies to identify the factors leading to the development of students' negative attitude toward mathematics. These efforts might help students to develop a positive attitude toward mathematics and therefore achieve a higher performance level in the subject.

Keyword: Student's belief, Student's attitude, Mathematics teaching, Mathematics Learning, Students, Teaching and Learning

Introduction

The competence gain in the study of mathematics is widely used in all spheres of human life. Mathematics plays a key role in shaping how individuals deal with the various spheres of private, social, and civil life (Leal et al. 2022). This justifies the compulsion of the study of the subject by all students who go through basic and secondary education in most countries. Mathematics is therefore a core subject at these levels of education in Nigeria. It is regrettable, therefore, that in the contemporary times many students struggle with mathematics and perform terribly low in their final examinations in most jurisdictions. Students' performance in mathematics at the senior secondary school has not been encouraging. Candidates are reported to exhibit poor understanding of mathematical concepts and are unable to form the appropriate mathematical models which could be tackled with the requisite skills" (Chief Examiner's Report, 2016, 20017, 2018, 2022). It has also been realised that many students have developed negative attitude towards the study of mathematics as a result of mass failure of students of the subject. It is an irrefutable fact that the successfulness of learning the subject is contingent on myriad of factors. School, classroom, student and teacher factors all impinge on the learning of mathematics. In particular, the seriousness or otherwise attached to the teaching of mathematics invariably affects students' performance in their final examinations.

Educational researchers have expended time and energy trying to unravel the possible causes of students' poor attitudes and performance in mathematics. An area that has not been explored extensively is the influence of teacher attitude on student attitude towards the study of the subject. Research findings indicate that effective teachers facilitate learning by truly caring about their students' engagement and creating the right atmosphere that enhances student learning (Fernandez et al., 2020). They have high yet realistic expectations about enhancing students' capacity to think, reason, communicate, reflect upon and critique their own practice, and they provide students with opportunities to ask why the class is doing certain things and with what effect (Watson, 2021). The relationships develop in the classroom become a resource for developing students' attitudes and mathematical competencies and identities. These resources are very essential to the learning of mathematics.

Attitude as a concept is concerned with an individual's way of thinking, acting and behaving. It has very serious implications for the learner, the teacher, the immediate social group with which the individual learner relates, and the entire school system. Attitudes are formed as a result of some kind of learning experiences students go through. This is mimicry, which also has a part to play in the teaching and learning situation. In this respect, the learner draws from his teachers' disposition to form his own belief and attitude, which may likely affect his learning outcomes (Malvasi & Gil-Quintana 2022).

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Learning mathematics does not only involve thinking and reasoning, it is dependent on the attitudes of the learners towards learning mathematics. Han and Carpenter (2014) state that attitudes consist of cognitive, affective and behavioural reactions that individuals display towards an object or the surrounding based on their feelings or interest. The cognitive component of attitude is what the individual thinks or believes about mathematics. The affective component of attitude is the feeling or emotions of the individual associated with learning mathematics (Ingram, 2015). Thus, the affective component is the source of driving the engagement of students towards mathematics. Furthermore, the affective aspect is also influenced by the belief formed from the cognitive component of attitude, which creates a mindset that becomes constant overtime and influences the feelings of the students towards learning mathematics (Ingram, 2015; Zan & Di Martino, 2010). As such, the cognitive and affective components of attitude are interrelated and deeply interact with each other.

The behavioural aspect of attitude is the tendency to respond in a certain way towards learning mathematics. Behavioural attitude is also influenced by affective attitude. Student feeling confident in doing mathematics is linked with being successful in mathematics, which is regarded as a positive behaviour. If students are not confident in doing mathematics, they may not experience success, and unsuccessful behaviour is regarded as negative feelings (Zan & Di Martino, 2017). Hence the behavioural component of attitude impacts on the cognitive component of attitude as well. When students see the importance of mathematics in real lives, they feel engaged, confident and connected to their learning. As such, the three components of attitude, confidence, awareness on the importance of mathematics and engagement are interrelated (Mensah et al., 2013).

An important question that arises here is how can an increased level of confidence, awareness on the importance of mathematics and engagement be achieved so that students' attitudes towards learning mathematics become more positive? Teaching mathematics in a meaningful context could be the solution. Setting mathematical problems in a context can help students see the application of mathematics (Ministry of Education, 2020). In mathematics education, a range of meanings exists for the term context. According to Hidayatullah & Csikos, (2023), a context is an event that takes place in a set environment. The learning environment is the situation context and the characteristics of the task make up the task context.

Boyd and Hipkins (2015) confirmed in their report, which was based on Sport in Education Programme, that students feel more engaged and confident being taught in a sporting context. Students who were part are reported to have an increased sense of belonging and pride in their school. Afari et al., (2013) investigated the impact of using mathematical games on college students' attitudes towards learning Mathematics. A pre-post design method was used to assess students' perception of the learning environment and their attitude towards learning Mathematics. Eight classes out of 33 used a games context. The students from the classes that used games found their lessons more interactive, got involved and enjoyed learning Mathematics. Rarujanai et al., (2022) stated that games and sports are the best way to build students' engagement and confidence in mathematics. There are a number of advantages of using a sporting context to teach mathematics as most students can relate to sports and can understand the rules and meanings that are presented to them. Students enjoy sports and show a greater level of interest when sports is applied to mathematics. Yuanita & Zulnaidi (2018) argues that mathematics is the science of space, number, quantity and arrangement and these four elements feature in every sport, making it the most relevant context in which mathematics can be taught.

Attard (2012); Grootenboer et al., (2008); Mata et al. (2012), have identified important factors that contribute to students' attitudes towards learning mathematics, these include the students themselves, the school, the teachers' beliefs and attitudes and their teaching methods. The teachers' teaching methods have a major influence on students' attitudes. Teachers can do many things to facilitate the classroom learning to alleviate students' engagement level and confidence in learning mathematics (Attard, 2012; Kele & Sharma, 2014). According to Sullivan and McDonough (2007), teachers can find ways to encourage student engagement and confidence in learning mathematics. This can be achieved by implementing meaningful activities embedded in real-life contexts.

Learning mathematics has become a necessity for an individual's full development in today's complex society. Despite its utility and importance, mathematics is perceived by most pupils as difficult, boring, not very practical, and abstract, etc (Ignacio, Nieto & Barona, 2006). Therefore, students' low success level in mathematics has been a worry for a long time in many countries and Nigeria in particular. There are a lot of factors affecting students' success in mathematics. One of these factors is their mathematical attitude of fears (Peker & Mirasyedioglu, 2008). One of the reasons for mathematical fears is attitude towards mathematics (Baloglu, 2001). It is generally believed that students' attitudes towards mathematics determine their mathematical success. A student's constant failure in mathematics and his/her mathematics anxiety can make him to believe that he can never do well on the subject thus accepting defeat. On the other hand, his successful experience can make him develop a positive attitude towards learning mathematics. So, the importance of measuring students' attitudes increases every passing day into educational system (Gerçek et al. 2006). In a teaching setting in which student's attitudes are not considered,

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expected learning experiences become difficult and hence teaching activities are not precisely performed. Whereas, conducting teaching activities are the signs for students' success in education. To achieve the expected student success, it is required to understand students' attitude because one of the objectives of elementary mathematics education is to get student improve affirmative attitudes towards mathematics (Vosniadou, et al. 2020).

Determining how much students reached the educational objectives will be beneficial for assessing of the current education and, determining student attitudes which can be affected by different variables beneficial for remediation of students' disregard, biases and learning difficulties about mathematics (Vosniadou, et al. 2020) Considering education as a process which is deliberate, has goals and aims to have students gain a positive behavioral change through this process, it is hoped that attitudes of students towards mathematics positively improves through this process in all levels of elementary schools. Students' attitudes towards mathematics changes according to some variables such as gender, whether receives private tuition, mathematics achievement score, educational background of parents, profession of parents and grade levels etc.

The terms 'conceptions' and 'beliefs' are used interchangeably, as conceptions and beliefs are not directly observable and have to be inferred, therefore, it is problematic to have a common definition of these notions. Nevertheless, educationalists have tried to define these terms in a variety of ways. For instance, Sangcap, (2010) defines 'beliefs' as personal principles, constructed from experience that an individual employ, often unconsciously, to interpret new experiences and information and to guide action. Saadati et al., (2019) refers to 'conceptions' as conscious or subconscious beliefs, understanding, meaning, mental images, and preferences. Based on these definitions, the working definition of these terms for the study is that 'conceptions are conscious and unconscious cognitive and affective beliefs, personal meaning, mental images and preferences constructed from experiences within and beyond schooling.

Mathematics is at the heart of many successful careers and successful lives for societal development, particularly in the extraordinary and accelerating change circumstances. However, in reality, most people in general and students in particular dislike mathematics. The review of school-based educational research has revealed that the majority of secondary school students find mathematics as the most difficult, abstract, tedious, deadly, and boring subject (Prendergast et al., 2018). Moreover, study found that students in primary schools enjoy Mathematics but when they move to secondary school their interest towards the subject declines (Perera & John, 2020). The negative conceptions or beliefs about mathematics have a major impact on students' achievement, enrollment in higher education and their future career decisions.

Generally, students' views of mathematics are developed based on their school learning experiences and how the public image of mathematics is portrayed in the society. To elaborate, in general it is believed that males are born with innate capabilities of making sense of abstract ideas and as mathematics is also an abstract level subject boy can do well as compared to girls (Iannone & Simpson, 2019). Some of the other viewpoints' students hold about mathematics include: mathematics problems have one and only one answer and they can be solved in a particular way; mathematics is a solitary activity, done by individuals in isolation; mathematics requires good memory and is only for clever ones (Iannone & Simpson, 2019).

People's incorrect beliefs about and negative attitudes towards mathematics have had a devastating impact on the teaching and learning of mathematics in our culture. Intense negative emotions around mathematics are not uncommon and are recognised as 'mathematics trauma' or 'mathematics anxiety'. Mathematics, more than any other subject, has the power to crush students' spirits, and many adults do not move on from mathematics experiences in school if they are negative (Boaler, 2016). Taking a cultural perspective of mathematics will engage students' imagination and creativity and provide students with a strong understanding of what mathematics is and why we do it. Connecting culture and mathematics will allow indigenous students to learn mathematics from their own cultural knowledge and first language (Matthews, 2015). Changing learners' experience of mathematics is not as simple as changing the nature of the mathematical tasks that teachers set: 'For change to be successful, teachers' beliefs, attitudes and practices need to be aligned' (Ontario Principals' Council, 2019).

Stipek and colleagues found that teachers who didn't enjoy or feel confident about teaching mathematics were also those who articulated very traditional beliefs about mathematics. However, teachers who were more positive and confident about teaching mathematics expressed beliefs that were more reform-based (Stipek et al. 2001). They suggested that increasing teachers' self-confidence in mathematics by building their mathematical understanding could be important in moving teachers towards more inquiry orientated beliefs and practices. This is best achieved by involving teachers in ongoing job-embedded staff development that revolves around mathematics teaching and learning to improve their understanding and confidence (Ontario Principals' Council, 2019).

Recent brain research tells us that everyone with the right experiences, messages and effective teaching can be successful in mathematics at the highest level (Boaler, 2016). Professor Jo Boaler acknowledges that some teachers find this difficult to accept 'especially if they have spent many years deciding who can and who can't do mathematics and teaching them

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accordingly'. This is not saying that everyone's brain is the same; it is saying that brain differences at birth are far less significant than the influence of learning experiences in rich and challenging environments. Therefore, the message struggling learners should tell themselves is not 'I can't do this', but 'I can't do this yet'. This is a really important message because people need to believe in their ability to learn mathematics, mathematicians are made not born. Too often we talk about 'mathematical ability' whereas emphasis is put much more on effort than ability (Churchman, 2015).

The work of Carol Dweck on fixed and growth mind-sets is particularly relevant to the learning of mathematics (Darmawan et al., 2020). Researchers have shown that learners, who develop a growth mind-set, believing that they can develop their intellectual ability through perseverance and effort, have positive attitudes and on-going growth in mathematical achievement (Boaler 2016). On the other hand, those with fixed mind-sets perform poorly across the achievement spectrum, as they believe that talent is something you either have or you don't and, no matter how much effort is expended, it does not change. High achieving girls can be particularly vulnerable if they believe in a fixed mind-set, losing confidence when faced with intellectual challenge, becoming fearful of no longer being seen as smart if they make mistakes. On the other hand, when they recognise that working hard develops skills and ability, it is less likely that their confidence or their performances are undermined (Darmawan et al., 2020).

Neuroscientists Erin Maloney and colleagues found that parents with mathematics anxiety who frequently helped their children with mathematics homework in the early years diminished their children's learning of mathematics (Maloney et al. 2015). Research shows that when parents experience mathematics anxiety, they often hold poor attitudes about mathematics, considering it of little use and expressing low motivation to succeed in mathematics. This in turn demotivates their children, increasing mathematics anxiety and reluctance to embrace challenges. However, if parents' mathematics fears can be reduced, this will lead to more positive homework experiences, and most likely result in improved mathematics achievement and diminished mathematics anxiety for their children.

Brouseau (1997) identified a common expectation in many mathematics classrooms which he termed the 'Didactic Contract'. When students ask for help, they expect their teacher to break down the problem and make it easier, thus diminishing the cognitive demands of the task. Thus, rather than thinking, reasoning and sense making, students consider their role is one of 'paying careful attention' (Boaler, 2016). However, when learners seek relational understanding (knowing what to do and why), ideas make sense and there is an affective as well as a cognitive benefit. This fosters a positive self-concept and gives learners the confidence that they can learn and understand mathematics, diminishing mathematics anxiety. Many Aboriginal students will need encouragement to take risks when learning mathematics, as they are traditionally taught to observe and wait until they are confident, they have mastered a skill (Rinco et al., 2021).

Teaching and learning like any other subject taught in school other than mathematics implies to the act of belief and attitude displayed either by the teacher, student, parents, school authority, etc which will result to positive or negative outcome in teaching and learning. When students constantly fail mathematics subject, even if they have positive expression about the subject their belief system will change thereby accepting any negative impression to the subject and if they already have negative impression on the subject their belief system will be overpowered in failing the subject (Dantani, 2023). The attitude of fear of mathematics by students is one of the major problems for researchers to conduct investigation and answer question of what, why, where, and who? That is, what is the reason for the fear? Why do you fear mathematics? Where is the fear in mathematics begin and who is responsible for the fear of mathematics? Answers to these questions and more others will help in addressing the issue of fear by the students. And also, if students' attitude towards learning mathematics is negative or positive, their belief toward the subject should be questioned whether they consider it as the most difficult, abstract, tedious, deadly and boring subject. The school, the teachers and their teaching methods will serve as a medium of change to student attitude toward the subject (Dantani, 2023). When teachers motivate their students, the attitude student have on mathematics can change automatically. Teachers have a lot to do in helping students to regain their interest toward mathematics learning especially adopting different techniques and strategies, either through games, storytelling, demonstration, music, etc. This will assist them develop positive mindset about the learning of mathematics subject (Dantani, 2023).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine secondary school students' beliefs and attitudes toward mathematics teaching and learning.

Research Question

What is the belief and attitude of secondary school students toward mathematics teaching and learning?

Methodology

The method of narrative reviews is selected for the synthesis of finding. Baumeister (2013), states that narrative reviews combine results for several studies that may use different procedures and methods to answer different questions. In this paper, the researcher presents the contributions with the available literature and previous studies to draw its findings. The studies presented how related student's beliefs and attitudes toward mathematics teaching and learning are connected. Therefore, the studies presented are synthesized and used to make conclusions and recommendations of this paper.

Results

This study is a small-scale study for some of the insights into students' conceptions, beliefs and attitudes towards teaching and learning mathematics. Interestingly, most of the students consider mathematics as an important subject which has relevance in their daily life. This idea needs to be sustained among students learning mathematics.

Baloglu (2001), found that one of the reason for mathematical fear is attitude towards the subject, also found that when students failed constantly in mathematics, the anxiety can make he/she believe that he/she can never do well on the subject which will lead to failure and defeat or unsuccessful. In line with this Peker & Mirasyedioglu (2008), found that one of the factors of student's attitude towards mathematics teaching and learning is their mathematical attitude of fears, this hinders their success in learning mathematics and achievement. If fear is dealt with, it will yield a better and positive attitude toward teaching and learning. Also, Attard (2012), identified important factors that contribute to students' attitudes towards learning mathematics, these include the students themselves, the school, the teachers' beliefs and attitudes and their teaching methods. The findings show that attitude has very serious implications for the learner, the teacher, the immediate social group with which the individual learner relates, and the entire school system and it resulted to some kind of learning experiences students go through.

Nardi & Steward (2023), in the review of school-based educational research has revealed that the majority of secondary school students find mathematics as the most difficult, abstract, tedious, deadly, and boring subject. As such, Hançer, et al. (2017), found that students' attitudes towards mathematics changes according to some variables such as gender, whether receives private tuition, mathematics achievement score, educational background of parents, profession of parents and grade levels etc. it is required to understand students' attitude because one of the objectives of elementary mathematics education is to get student improve affirmative attitudes towards mathematics (Hançer, et al. 2017).

Afari et al., (2013) investigated the impact of using mathematical games on college students' attitudes towards learning Mathematics. A pre-post design method was used to assess students' perception of the learning environment and their attitude towards learning mathematics. The students from the classes that used games found their lessons more interactive, got involved and enjoyed learning mathematics. In line with this, Boaler (2016), when students are motivated by their teachers their mindsets, self confidence and hard work developed skill and ability in mathematics and will provide students with a strong understanding of what mathematics is. Thus, learners who develop a growth mindset, self confidence, believing that they can develop their intellectual ability through perseverance and effort, have positive attitudes and ongoing growth in mathematical achievement. Belief is crucial in learning mathematics because it required self confidence and mindset which will lead to positive attitude in learning of mathematics. However, Boaler (2016), stated that leaders should ask themselves positively and their teachers, parents and students about their beliefs concerning: what is mathematics and how is it best taught and learnt, and is one's mathematics ability fixed and immutable or can it be developed? Any positive response from teachers, parents and students will also develop a positive mindset to teaching and learning of mathematics.

Students' belief system is the powerful instrument that can change their attitude toward learning mathematics. If teachers' attitude and method of teaching mathematics are positive it has a powerful influence on student's belief and attitude formation toward mathematics. Students' positive attitude towards mathematics leads to better performance and may influence their overall achievement and application of mathematics in real-life. Success in learning mathematics depends on belief students have and positive attitude towards mathematics. It also influences the participation rate of learners (Dantani, 2023).

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Conclusion

This study has identified students' profiles of belief and attitude toward mathematics teaching and learning. It is concluded that students can have different attitudes toward mathematics, and they might need different kinds of support according to the individual components of their attitude toward mathematics. Therefore, teachers need to examine their students' attitude and provide appropriate support to stimulate the development of a positive attitude toward the subject. Furthermore, researchers should conduct additional studies to identify the factors leading to the development of students' negative attitude toward mathematics and offer suggestion on how students can be helped to develop a positive attitude.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. Teachers should appropriately adopt instructional techniques that include learners' diversities or barriers to learning, minimize fear, enhance active interest, and enjoyment in what is being taught and learnt.
2. Teachers should prepare interesting mathematical tasks to engage their students in mathematics lessons that will enable them to enjoy mathematics. They should adjust the difficulties of mathematical tasks by considering their students' mathematical performance to ensure all students experience success in the mathematics classroom.
3. Mathematics teachers should develop positive attitude towards the subject and make mathematics interesting and appealing to students in order to help them develop a positive attitude towards it without any inhabitation and improve their performance.
4. Students should use their time wisely so that they can have enough time to practice and internalise mathematical concepts learned in classrooms. This may help them acquire competencies, and thus improve their mathematics performance.
5. Student should monitor and reflect on the processes of mathematical problem solving. This will help them improve in learning the subject.
6. Government should provide teaching and learning resources. These should include enough qualified teachers, books, teaching and learning resources, and other instructional materials for effective learning of mathematics.
7. School administrators should provide teachers with educational resources (e.g., technological devices) and professional development programs to help them implement various instructional strategies in the mathematics classroom that would allow students to learn about the subject in an enjoyable manner.
8. Parents and teachers could provide accurate feedback and support to help students acquire accurate mathematical knowledge and develop confidence in mathematics. They should help students acquire awareness of the value of mathematics in their present and future life.

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Qualitative Study on Sustainable Girl Child Education at Middle School Level of Education in Mirriah, Niger Republic

*Abdou Illiassou Sani¹

Email: saniabdou9192@gmail.com

Tel: (+227) 86269926

Tankari Moussa²

Email: mtankari@gmail.com,

Tel: (+227) 96492547

¹Collège d'Enseignement Général de Gogo, Zinder/Niger

²Département d'Anglais, Faculté des Lettres et Sciences Humaines (FLSH), Université André Salifou (UAS) de Zinder, République du Niger, Laboratoire Lettres, Education et Communication (LaboLEC),

Abstract

This study was carried out to investigate factors influencing girl child' education sustainability at middle school level of education in Mirriah. Two rural middle schools in Mirriah were selected at random to conduct this study. A sample of twenty-four participants among whom seven unschooled girls, seven out-of-school girls, five administrators, and five COGES members were selected purposively. A qualitative grounded theory was used to conduct this study. The general objective of this research was to assess the degree of peer influence on girl child education in rural middle schools. The specific objectives were formulated as follow: to investigate the influence of out-of-schooled peers and unschooled peers on girl child education in Gogo and Fotoro middle schools. The data were collected through direct interviews and the results revealed that peers in general have some levels of negative influence on girl child education. It was concluded that unschooled peers have a high negative influence on the girl child education that's why recommendations related to the parents' follow up and the choice of friendship were addressed.

Keywords: Girls child education, out-of-school, influence, rural area.

Introduction

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948, as cited in Yacine, 2015, p.54), "Everyone has the right to education" (Art.26, para.1). "Education is the process through which individuals acquire adequate and appropriate knowledge, skills, attitudes, values and behaviour necessary to function optimally as a citizen" stated by (Boonprasert, 2010, as cited in Rachel 2013, p.25). It is evident that education is the most formidable weapon to transform or develop a country because the place where education progresses, ignorance withdraws. In this sense, no nation can develop without qualitative education of its citizens, especially female citizens. According to the popular adage, "educate a man, and you educate an individual, but educate a woman and you educate a nation". Thus, girls' education is a fundamental aspect in the development of a nation. This adage is supported by Puri (2016, p. 1) when she said, "Girls' education is like sowing the seed which gives rise to a revitalized, cheerful and full-grown family plant". This explains the fact that education of the girl-child is a key factor in the development of a country, communities and individuals. In this case, girls' education contributes to the improvement of the maternal health, the reduction of infant death, and ensures a good family education. However, the girls' education cannot find its full meaning only when there is good school retention. The issue of keeping girls at school continues to be a topic of discussion (Ahmed, 2013; Mnguni, 2014; Amelie, 2015; Abungu, 2015; Puri, 2016; Johannes, 2018; Abdou, 2020; Mohamed, 2022; Bogosi, 2021). Indeed, "the poor school retention of girls continues to impact their academic results and often causes their permanent drop out from school in rural areas in Niger" (Sani, 2020, p.12). In this respect, according to the Ministry of Education and Professional Training of Niger republic (MEPT, 2020), "the rural population is much more affected by this phenomenon. This population accounts for nearly 80% of the whole country's population" (p.12, para2).

In the education framework, school retention constitutes the second issue after that of enrollment. This place offers to this issue a very remarkable importance in education. Nowadays, despite the big number of the societies which recognize the importance of girls' education, the question of sustainable education remains so problematic. Abungu (2015, as cited in Sani, 2020) mentions that "In almost all developing countries, School dropout, and retention rate has been a subject of interest to

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academics, researchers and policy makers for a long time” (p. 2). The matter of retaining girls at school has been widely discussed in the research world: (Ahmed, 2013; Mnguni, 2014; Amelie, 2015; Abungu, 2015; UNESCO, 2015; Puri, 2016; Juhannes, 2018; Lokonon, 2018; Bogosi, 2021; Mohamed, 2022; etc.). Many are the factors that influence the school retention of girls (Abungu, 2015; Espace Femmes, 2019; Abdou, 2020; Bogosi, 2021). One among those factors is the peer influence. According to Bogosi (2021) “peer group influence has a negative and positive effect in modelling the behaviour of students and their academic performance” (p. 69).

Peer pressures among students are of various natures. Ombuya et al. (2012) and Rumberge (2001) identified three main categories of peer influence that can lead to dropout. These include: Outside influences-brought by friends and peer pressure from other secondary school dropouts, lack of interest in gaining education and teen pregnancies which has accounted for a higher percentage of girls who drop out of secondary schools. These categories can only be managed by the head of the institutions with the support of the parents and other education stakeholders. A cross sectional study conducted by Omollo and Yambo (2017) revealed that peer pressure influenced student drop out was at 43.75%. High dropout was as a result of parent/guardian financial status and family headship which lead to inadequate guidance/ mentorship to the students. The study concluded that in most cases where students are most often sent home there are high chances that some never returned to school and most schools did not support the learners who were coming from poor background. It can therefore be concluded that socio-economic factors highly influence the retention of students in secondary school. Other studies by Duflo, Pascalia, and Michael (2010), Yambo and Tuitoek (2014) on gender gaps in education also realized that adolescent pregnancy brought by peer influence mostly results in the dropping out of girls’ and their continuity to secondary school education. Many of such girls end up in marriage or abandoned at home without any academic achievement realized. Similarly, boys are equally endangered because when they drop out of school they engage in some activities which are detrimental to their dear lives and prone to poor.

The issue of school enrolment and retention has also been discussed (INS, 2006; SUD Education, 2013; Espace Femmes, 2019; Abdou, 2020). These studies found that the academic repetition and the drop out of the students constitute the negative consequences of low school retention of students. This social phenomenon of school retention can be seen through three major indicators in Niger. The first one is the national rate of academic level repetition of the students present. Data from DRES/Zinder (2020), revealed that the national rate of the academic repetition in middle school of the past six years shows that there is weak school retention especially for girls from 2013 to 2018.

Table 1: National rate of academic repetition in Niger

Gender/Years	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
Boys	20.4	21.5	18.9	20.6	22.8	25.9
Girls	21.2	22	18.2	20.4	22	25.8
Total	20.7	21.7	18.6	20.5	22.4	25.8

Source: DRES/Zinder (2020)

The second indicator that displays the weak school retention is the national rate of school completion. In spite of the progressive rate of the school completion from 2013 to 2018, this rate remains low and can be explained by the permanent and temporary dropout of the students.

Table 2: National rate of school completion

Gender/Years	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
Boys	16.5%	20.3%	21.7%	23.7%	24.9%	20.4%
Girls	10.9%	14.1%	15.9%	17%	18.7%	16.4%
Total	13.7%	17.8%	18.8%	20.3%	21.8%	18.5%

Source: DRES/Zinder (2020)

In Zinder region, when you take from 2015 to 2020, the rate of pass-repeat-dropout of middle school female students who repeated the year is around 25% but the rate of those who dropped out is around 30% during the same years. This rate which constitutes our third indicator, shows that there is a problem about young girls’ school retention because there is a steady decline in the percentage of girls who pass to the next academic level. Moreover, the rate of girls who dropped out is around 30%, which can be considered as high because almost one third of girls drop out of middle school every year. As far as the repeat rate, it goes up and down from year to year and generally oscillates between 21% and 29.76% (DRES/Zinder, 2021).

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Table 3: Rate of passages-repetition-dropout in middle school in Zinder

Academic years	Middle school					
	Pass %		Repeat %		Dropout %	
	Global	Girls	Global	Girls	Global	Girls
2015-2016	47.28	47.60	23.42	22.90	29.20	29.39
2016-2017	46.46	47.49	24.70	24.29	28.80	28.18
2017-2018	49.22	49.11	22.64	22.73	27.79	28.10
2018-2019	45.82	47.95	26.16	24.56	28.02	27.55
2019-2020	56.17	57.99	22.03	21.27	21.73	20.78
2020-2021	45.08	47.8	30.06	29.76	24.78	22.97

Source: DRES/Zinder (2021)

This study is initiated in view of the studies cited above and the high rates of school repetition and dropout presented in table 3.

Regarding the importance of girl child education mentioned above and the existence of the weak school retention in Zinder, this paper aims to investigate a factor that influences the sustainable girl child education at middle school level of education in rural middle schools.

Objectives of the study

1. Assess the extent of out-of-school students' influence on girl child education at middle schools in mirriah.
2. Assess the extent of unschooled girls influence on girl child education at middle schools in Mirriah.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do out-of-school students influence the girl child education at middle school?
2. To what extent do the unschooled girls influence the girl child education at middle school?

Research Hypotheses

1. The out-of-school girls have no influence on the girl child education at middle school.
2. The unschooled girls have no influence on the girl child education at middle school.

Methodology

The present study was conducted using a qualitative grounded theory design to assess a phenomenon through the interaction and experience of the targeted population. According to Creswell (2012, p.423) "Because a theory is "grounded" in the data, it provides a better explanation than a theory borrowed "off the shelf," because it fits the situation, actually works in practice, is sensitive to individuals in a setting, and may represent all of the complexities actually found in the process". More particularly, this study used a process approach as it is "a sequence of actions and interactions among people and events pertaining to a topic (Corbin & Strauss, 2008 as cited in Creswell 2012, p.431). Mnguni (2014) defines "population" as "a predetermined number of convenient cases that the researcher assumes to be the sample which corresponds to the population of interest. This is what the researcher intends to use to generalize the results of the research" (p. 23). In this study, the population refers to the selected participants who are concerned by the phenomenon of school retention. The respondents for this study consist of seven unschooled girls, seven out-of-school girls, five administrators, and five members of the management Committee of Secondary Education (COGES /ES). These participants are selected purposively according to their social and/or professional place for fighting to keep young girls in school. The data collection instrument used in this study was a direct interview. The data collected in French were translated into English and those collected in the local language were transcribed and then translated into English.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent do out-of-school students influence the girl child education at middle school?

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Table 1 : Statistical analysis on extent to which out-of-school students influence the girl child education at middle school

	Statistiques descriptives		
	N	Moyenne	Ecart type
Do you think that the participation of school girls to the village activities like (traditional week of naming ceremony and marriage) influences the school retention of girls ?	24	3,13	,797
Do you think that the participation of school girls to the village night recreation influences the school attendance of the student?	24	3,42	,717
Are there other activities that influence the girl retention at middle school?	24	1,83	,917
N valide (listwise)	24		

Source: Field data (2023)

The statistical analysis in table 1 showed that $SD < 1$ that means that out-of-school girls have no influence on the girl child education at middle school.

Research Question 2

To what extent do the unschooled girls influence the girl child education at middle school?

Table 2 : Statistical analysis on extent to which unschooled girls influence the girl child education at middle school

	Statistiques descriptives		
	N	Moyenne	Ecart type
Do you think that the participation of school girl to the activities organized by her unschooled peers helps her to remain in school?	24	2,17	,917
Does the desire to belong to a group of unschooled friends push the girl to stay and work hard at school?	24	2,46	,932
Do you think that a female student can be influenced by another unschooled female?	24	3,21	,833
N valide (listwise)	24		

Source : Field data (2023)

The statistical analysis of the second research question in table 2, expresses that the SD is very close to 1, which means the disparity is almost there. However, as $SD < 1$, this can tell us that unschooled girls have a negative influence on the sustainable girl child education at middle school.

Discussion of finding

In view of the above result of statistical analysis of the research question 1, where the results showed that out-of-school girls influence more the girl child education, and these corroborate to the studies carried out by Daniel (2014); Omollo, (2017); and Abdou (2020). Other studies carried out by Johannes, (2018); Abdou, (2020); and Bogosi, (2021) stated the influence of unschooled peers on the sustainable girl child education presented in research question 2 through the table 2 of the statistical analysis.

Conclusion

In general, the phenomenon of sustainable girl child education constitutes a topic of discussion for researchers and educational policy makers. This research discovered that the sustainable education of girls who are studying in rural areas is influenced by peers, personal motivation, environment, shared values and beliefs. Findings from research questions revealed that unschooled peer groups do not allow the girl to decide by 'herself' in the truest sense of the word. Furthermore, this

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research revealed the high value placed on social friendships. It is also well established that school girls are highly influenced by out-of-school girls, but they are more highly influenced by unschooled friends. Peer influence has been established to have direct influence on the school attendance of the learner and academic performance. This study found out that students, who were rejected in their class, were negatively affected either emotionally or academically.

Recommendations:

In view of the above findings, the following recommendations should be adopted in order to overcome the issue of peer influence in rural middle schools.

1. The regional teaching office, the departmental teaching office and the girls' education partners should follow the implementation of the laws carrying the protection and the follow up of girls at middle schools especial the rural ones.
2. The school administration and COGES members should also sensitize the parents and the students on the danger of unschooled and out-of-school peers' influence.
3. The COGES members should guide students on the importance of carefully choosing friends so that their attitudes towards learning would be improved as the peer group they belong to can have an effect on their learning.
4. The school administration and the COGES should think of organizing periodic school activities for students in order to motivate them.

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Assessment of Causes and Implications of Violent Behaviours among Secondary School Students in Kwara State, Nigeria

*James, Joke Felicia Ph.D.¹

Email: james.jf@unilorin.edu.ng

Tel: +2348034278244

Kperogi, Ismaila Ibrahim Ph.D.²

Email: kperogi.ii@unilorin.edu.ng

Tel: +2348103524600

Sindama, Hellen Ph.D.³

Email: sindamahelen@gmail.com

Tel: +2348036401823

Obaditan, Opeyemi Funke Ph. D.⁴

Email: Opeobad2016@gmail.com

Tel: +2348038599979

^{1&2}Department of Health Promotion and Environmental Health Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

³ Department of Physical and Health Education, Faculty of Education, University of Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria

⁴ School of Nursing, University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study assessed the causes and implications of violent behaviours among secondary school students in Kwara State. The research investigated if peer pressure and family problem are causes, and if poor academic performance and suicide thought are implications of violent behaviours among secondary school students in Kwara State. Descriptive research design of the survey type was adopted for the study and the population consists of all Secondary Schools students in Kwara state. Two hundred (200) respondents were selected through multistage sampling technique. A researcher structured questionnaire titled: Assessment of Causes and Implications of Violent behaviors Among Secondary School Students (AVBASS), validated and tested for reliability through test-retest method was used for data collection. A reliability coefficient of 0.72r was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient. Inferential statistics of Chi-Square was used to analyze the four hypotheses postulated at 0.05 alpha level. The result revealed that; peer pressure and family problem are causes (calc. χ^2 value of 162.39; 39.93 > tab. value of 16.92) respectively while poor academic performance and suicide thought are implications of violent behaviours (calc. χ^2 value of 41.30; 55.82 > the tab. χ^2 value of 16.92) at 9 df @ 0.05 alpha level. The researchers concluded that peer pressure, and family problem are causes of violent behaviour while poor academic performance and suicide thought are implications of violent behaviours among secondary school students in, Kwara State. The researchers recommend that students should be guided and encouraged to keep good company and maintain wholesome relationships among their peers.

Keyword: Students, violent behaviours, peer pressure, family problem, suicide

Introduction

School has always been an institution for learning and behavioural uprightness. It is looked up to by many stakeholders as an area for moral upbringing as well as avenue to correct moral decadence. Instead of living to this standard, school has been the major avenue for many moral decadences and violent behaviour lately. It houses bullying, indecent dressing, rape, cultism, alcoholism, among others. School, which ought to be the safest place for learners and teachers, has been the most dangerous place to be for them. It loses its aims, mission and vision. This could be a result of transfer of parent aggressiveness, peer influence and teachers' neglect or nonchalant attitudes. School violence in all its forms has led to students in particular, to many forms of physical disability, injury of various types, psychological distress, mental disorders, to list view.

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Violent behaviour among students is a major concern to the teachers, parents and all that are interested with the education of learners (Bardick & Bernes, 2018). The increasing school violence has become a problem that hinders the perception and reality of a school as a safe place for both pupils and teachers. Violence in schools may sometimes undermine the notion that school days are the happiest days in the learner's life. School violence wears many faces which include gang activities, locker theft, bullying, intimidation, discrimination, stigmatization, gun use and fighting (Basch, 2017). The focus of violence can be individuals, objects or the school itself. Both teachers and students may be affected by violence in schools. A learner can act violently towards other learners or can violently attack teachers.

Violence is a pervasive problem for Nigerians and at times, it is expressed in the most unlikely places under unexpected and unsettling conditions. It is usually expressed at home, school, in the neighborhood or in the community. In the secondary school system, the expression of aggressive behaviour is evident in the numerous and untold cruelties that some children inflict on their fellow learners. Over the years, a lot of blood lettings, massacre, maiming and killings have been observed in secondary schools (Carlson, 2020). At different-occasions students have been observed damaging school property, harassing their fellow students, threatening teachers who try stop them, especially in cases of examination supervision. These actions are confrontational and distractive, and could hinder adolescents from meeting up with the demands of their goals.

Violence could potentially make the learning environment threatening and uncondusive to learning, which, according to Denga (2018), could limit the learning performance of students. It could be argued that when students perceive threat arising from one form of aggression or the other, they may become destabilized as they would tend to spend the time meant for studying in finding ways to cope with the perceived threats. Clearly, any form of distraction within a learning setting is counter-productive. It is the researcher's belief that such distractions could constitute a hindrance to the State's ability to achieve her goal of self-reliance over the years. Nigeria as a nation understands and appreciates the fact that education is a precursor to nation building (National Policy on Education, 2013), and therefore considers education to be a catalyst for all aspects of development. In view of this, and in acknowledgment of the fact that the youth of today are the leaders of tomorrow, a great deal of resources has been directed toward providing education at both primary and secondary school level s. But rather than students of secondary schools devoting their times to learning, there is a tendency for many to spend their energy on the perpetuation of violence. This reduces the amount of time and level of concentration they put into their studies. It has been noted that students who experience stressful conditions are susceptible to go through unstable lives and poor academic performance (Addison-Wesley; Weaver, & Clum 2015).

Violent behaviour is a very complicated behaviour with a variety of multidimensional causes. In the past, social factors were mainly the center of attention for the researchers as causes of aggression in humans. But, with recent scientific and technological advancements, researchers are now trying to explore new areas, including biological factors. Nelson (2016) in his book has summarized the recent advancements in finding a relationship between biological factors and aggression. The major areas of interest include; molecular biology, genetics, nervous system, 5-HT, monoamines, neurotransmitters, nitric oxide (NO), the stimuli and situational factors, stress and drug abuse. Exposure to violent home and community environments, as well as injury due to violence, contribute to both reduced academic progress and increased disruptive or unfocused classroom behaviour for children, adolescents, and teenagers. It is estimated that between 10 and 20% of children in the United States are exposed to domestic violence annually and are physically injured (Carlson, 2020). Violence is positively associated with family size. Households who have more children are more likely to experience increased family conflict and child maltreatment which may lead to intrapersonal, interpersonal and academic limitations. Children affected by family and community violence suffer from lowered social and emotional competence and diminished academic performance (Burnham, 2019). With repeated exposure to traumatic events, a proportion of individuals may develop disorders characterized as Posttraumatic Stress and Oppositional Defiant. Given these issues, there is an increased need for school personnel to address the effects of violence on youth achievement in the classroom. Several researchers have shown the negative influence of school aggression on the classroom environment, and correspondingly how that negative environment affects students' behavioural adjustment at school and increases their involvement in misbehaviours and aggressive activities in the classroom (Carrasco & Trianes, 2015).

A classical experiment by Solomon Asch explains how a group of individuals can influence somebody in making a decision. Shuttle Worth (2017) noted that the Asch experiment was designed to test how peer pressure would influence the judgment and individuality of test subject to conform to the majority. It was found out that people frequently followed the majority judgement, even when the majority was wrong. People often accept to be influenced just for the desire to achieve a sense of security within a group that is of similar age culture, religion or educational status. Any unwillingness to be influenced carries with it the risk of social rejection and this is what young people fear most. Steinberg and Chung (2016) in their study found out that there was a link between peer group and aggressive behaviours. They established that children begin to depend

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on their peers for acceptance rather than their parents during adolescence. In addition, peer pressure becomes harder to resist at this stage such that the opinions of peers often matter more than those of parents. When adolescents formed relationships with people who displayed aggressive behaviours, they are likely to take part in the behaviours themselves. This was supported by Erickson, as cited by Kendra, (2022), that the resolution of adolescent developmental crisis depends on the interactions between the individual and whether support is provided by the environment. Therefore, if the significant person is practicing aggressive behaviours, the adolescent may engage in the same behaviour. Sense of belonging is a basic psychological need which will make students adapt to goals set by their peers. An adolescent would conform to peers because of the acceptance and the sense of belonging they got from the group. Affiliation to deviant peers represented the strongest predictor of deviant behaviour.

Bandura, as cited by Morales and Duenas, (2018), stated that adolescents are likely to do the same as their closest friends and will emulate the behaviour of their idol through observation and imitation. Peer group therefore provides a powerful opportunity for the formation of identity. According to Bandura peers may illicit or may serve as role models to other children who have a predisposition to act aggressively. He says that aggressive children are often friends of other oppositional, aggressive children. Current literature in education challenges school counsellors to expand their knowledge of social, environmental and family dynamics and the corresponding influences of those dynamics on violent student behaviour. This is because the roots of most violent behaviours appear to develop during childhood, the time when family members and family processes are characteristically the most prevalent influences in an individual's life (O'Moore 2018). Youth who commit the most serious violent acts, and who continue their violent acts beyond adolescence began their behaviours during childhood (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Substance Abuse Mental Health Services Administration [SAMHSA], 2017). The family is a central factor in the development and reduction of antisocial behaviours and delinquency. Consequently, school-based interventions to strengthen positive family involvement seem best suited to address the current trends in youth aggression and unmet mental health needs. To apply family-inclusive prevention and intervention approaches to student violence, school counsellors must first understand the antecedents of student violence that originate in the context and structure of the family.

A proportional relationship existed between academic performance and behaviour. Accomplishment issues can surface when students don't set objectives, don't arrange for how to achieve them, and don't sufficiently screen their advancement toward the objectives. Forceful conduct of a man has ability to disrupt the achievement of a set objective. For example, physical attack, tossing objects, property demolition and verbal dangers can hinder concentration on academic activities. Although the rate of suicidal behaviour among adolescents has increased dramatically over the last three decades, little is known about the prevalence and correlates of these behaviours in nonclinical samples of young people. Instead, current information relies heavily on data obtained from one of the following sources: clinical psychiatric populations; psychological autopsies; mortality statistics; attempted suicides reaching medical attention, and large-scale surveys, which have often failed to differentiate among specific categories of suicidal behaviours, thoughts, plans, attempts not requiring medical care, and attempts requiring medical care. Frequency estimates of all categories of suicidal behaviours in community samples of adolescents have varied from a low of 2% to a high of 63%(Carlson, 2020). Although a number of different correlates or predictors of suicidal thoughts, plans, and attempts have been addressed in many literatures, two factors-aggressive/impulsive behaviour and drug and alcohol use are rated very high among adolescents. Investigations focusing on the relationship between aggression and suicide have indicated that there is a very strong association between the two behaviours than has previously been identified. Shaffer, (2018) pointed out that there are two different clusters of suicidal individuals, the first characterized by aggressive and violent outbursts and the second characterized by depression or withdrawal. High incidences of suicidal behaviour have been described in samples of juveniles selected because of their history of violent or aggressive behaviours. Other researchers have reported that up to two thirds of suicide attempts among adolescents are impulsive in that they occur with little premeditation and are preceded only by a short period of planning (Cairns, Peterson & Neckerman, 2018). The widespread use of alcohol, other illicit drugs among adolescents is associated with violence and is identified as an influential factor contributing to observed increases in the rate of adolescent suicide.

Violence is a critical public health problem that has been increasing. Every year, more than one million people die because of violence and several nonfatal injuries occur as well. Moreover, violence adversely influences the quality of life apart from contributing to disease, death, and disability. Because violence affects the lives of millions in the long term, it is a risk factor for lifelong health and social problem. Adolescents as a whole are among the groups that are the most vulnerable to violence. In addition, violence caused by adolescents is one of the most overt forms of violence prevailing in the society. This period is a dynamic period wherein physical, psychological, and social maturity reach completion and adulthood-specific roles, responsibilities, and behaviours are acquired. Conversely, adolescents are both perpetrators and victims of violence, which does

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not only influence them but also affects their families, friends, and societies. Adolescents who are involved in an act of violence during high school usually continue this behaviour during their adulthood. Thus, there is a need to study the dimensions of violent adolescent behaviour to improve the health of adolescents and reduce problematic behaviours associated with violence. The aim of this study was to determine the causes and implications of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Ilorin metropolis, kwara State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

Generally, the study aims to investigate the causes and implications of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

6. to determine whether peer pressure is a cause of violent behaviour among secondary students in kwara state.
7. to assess whether family problem is a cause of violent behaviours among secondary school students in kwara state.
8. to examine if poor academic performance is an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara state
9. to investigate whether suicidal thought is an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara state

Research Questions:

The study sought to provide answers to the following questions:

15. What is the extent of peer pressure being a cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria?
16. What is the extent of family problem being a cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria?
17. What is the extent of poor academic performance being an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria?
18. What is the extent of suicide thought being an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were tested in the study;

1. Peer pressure will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.
2. Family problem will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in . Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria?
3. Poor academic performance will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.
4. Suicide thought will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Meropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Descriptive Survey research design was adopted for this study. The population for the study comprises all secondary school students in both private and public secondary schools in kwara state, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique consisting of purposive, proportionate and simple random sampling techniques was adopted for the study. Purposive sampling technique was used to select three senior secondary schools that have the highest population in each of the three political districts in the population. Proportionate technique was used to select 5% from the total number of classes available in each of the selected schools, while random sampling method was used to select 200 respondents across the selected schools and classes. A well-structured researchers' developed questionnaire titled Assessment of causes and implications of violent behavior among secondary school student (AVBASS) was used in collecting data for the study. The instrument was validated by experts in the related field and reliability of the instrument was ascertained through test re-test method. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to calculate the reliability of the instrument. A reliability coefficient of 0.72r was obtained and this was considered high enough for adoption for the study. Inferential statistics of Chi-Square was used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

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Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of peer pressure as a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state?

Table 1: percentile analysis of peer pressure as a cause of violent behavior among students

ITEMS	SA	A	PR	D	SD	NR
20. At adolescent age, children are greatly influence by their peer behaviour which may be violence and aggressiveness	78 (39.0%)	80 (40.0%)	158	26 (13.0%)	16 (8.0%)	42
21. Students who associate with tout and delinquent friends are more likely to be violent in behaviour.	68 (34.0%)	88 (44.0%)	156	26 (13.0%)	18 (9.0%)	44
22. At adolescent age, children are characterized with action like bullying and they may be influence by their friends action in school	64 (32.0%)	62 (31.0%)	126	42 (21.0%)	32 (16.0%)	74
23. Friends in school and other places can force a students to engage in violent behaviour like cultism and vandalism.	62 (31.0%)	86 (43.0%)	148	28 (14.0%)	24 (12.0%)	52
Column Total Mean	272	316	147 (73.5%)	118	91	53 (26.5%)

Key: PR=Positive response, NR=Negative response

Table 1 shows that 147(73.5%) responded positively while 53(26.5%) responded negatively to the statements on the table, this implies that higher percentage agreed that peer pressure is a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state, Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the extent of family problem as a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 2: Percentile analysis of family problems as a cause of violent behavior

ITEMS	SA	A	PR	D	SD	NR
24. Children from a violent family are more likely to behave violently at school.	78 (39.0%)	80 (40.0%)	158	26 (13.0%)	16 (8.0%)	42
25. Lack of parental love, care and attention can lead to violent behaviour on students	68 (34.0%)	88 (44.0%)	156	26 (13.0%)	18 (9.0%)	44
26. Students whose family looks after are less susceptible to violent behaviour than students who are neglect.	62 (31.0%)	86 (43.0%)	148	28 (14.0%)	24 (12.0%)	52
27. Violent behaviour among adolescent can emanate from poor family background	64 (32.0%)	62 (31.0%)	126	42 (21.0%)	32 (16.0%)	74
Column Total Mean	272	316	147 (73.5%)	122	90	53 (26.5%)

Key: PR=Positive response, NR=Negative response

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Table 2 shows that 147(73.5%) responded positively while 53(26.5%) responded negatively to the statements on the table, this implies that higher percentage agreed that family problem is a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara state, Nigeria.

Research Question 3

What is the extent of poor academic performance as an implication of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state?

Table 3: Percentile analysis of poor academic performance as an implication of violent behavior among secondary school students

ITEMS	SA	A	PR	D	SD	NR
28. Violent behaviour in school disrupt the school environment and affect school academic productivity.	80 (40.0%)	70 (35.0%)	150	34 (17.0%)	16 (8.0%)	50
29. Students who engage in violence behaviour doesn't have time for class and may affect their performance.	78 (39.0%)	78 (39.0%)	156	26 (13.0%)	18 (9.0%)	44
30. Teachers who teach in a school characterized by violent behaviour are going to teach under extreme fear which may affect their productivity.	82 (41.0%)	74 (37.0%)	156	30 (15.0%)	14 (7.0%)	44
31. Violence behaviour in school by students will generally affect the academic performance of every students	72 (36.0%)	90 (45.0%)	162	28 (14.0%)	10 (5.0%)	38
Column Total Mean	272	316	156 (78%)	118	58	44 (22%)

Key: PR=Positive response, NR= Negative response

Table 2 shows that 156(78%) responded positively while 44(22%) responded negatively to the statements on the table, this implies that higher percentage agreed that f is a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara state, Nigeria.

Research Question 4

What is the extent of peer pressure as a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state?

Table 4: Percentile analysis on suicidal thoughts as an implication of violent behavior among students

ITEMS	SA	A	PR	D	SD	NR
32. Victims of school violence like cultism are susceptible to suicide thought due to emotional and physical trauma	33 (15.0%)	106 (48.2%)	139	69 (26.8%)	22 (10.0%)	91
33. Violence behaviour like bully can make some students look down on themselves and try to kill themselves to avoid the bully.	16 (7.3%)	85 (45.9%)	101	101 (45.9%)	18 (8.2%)	119
34. Student who engage in violent may feel guilty of his or her action at one point and decide to commit suicide to avoid punishment.	55 (25.0%)	85 (45.9%)	140	61 (27.7%)	19 (8.6%)	80

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35. Violent behaviour in school and home is one of the leading causes of suicide and suicidal thoughts among adolescents.	55 (25.0%)	77 (35.0%)	132	75 (34.1%)	13 (5.9%)	88
Column Total Mean	159	353	128 (64%)	306	72	93 (36%)

Key: PR=Positive response, NR= Negative response

Table 4 shows that 128(64%) responded positively while 46(36%) responded negatively to the statements on the table, this implies that higher percentage agreed that suicidal thought is an implication of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara state, Nigeria..

Hypothesis 1

Peer pressure will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Chi-square (χ^2) Results of Peer Pressure and Violent Behaviour among Students

S/N	ITEMS	df	Cal. Value	Table Value	Remarks
1	At adolescent age, children are greatly influence by their peer behaviour which may be violence and aggressiveness				
2	Students who associate with tout and delinquent friends are more likely to be violent in behaviour.				
3	At adolescent age, children are characterized with action like bullying and they may be influence by their friends action in school	9	162.39	16.92	Ho rejected
4	Friends in school and other places can force a students to engage in violent behaviour like cultism and vandalism.				
Column Total					

0.05 alpha level

Table 5: shows that the calculated chi-square value is 162.39 and the table value is 16.92 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the calculated χ^2 value is greater than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the alternative hypothesis upheld. This implies that peer pressure is a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Hypothesis 2:

Family problem will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Table 6: Chi-square (χ^2) Results of Family Problem and Violent Behaviour among Students

S/N	ITEMS	df	Cal. Value	Table Value	Remarks
5.	Children from a violent family are more likely to behave violently at school.				
6.	Lack of parental love, care and attention can lead to violent behaviour on the part of a students.	9	31.93	16.92	Ho rejected
7.	Students whose family looks after are less susceptible to violent behaviour than students who are neglect.				
8.	Violent behaviour among adolescent can emanate from poor family background				
Column Total					

0.05 alpha level

Table 6: shows the calculated chi-square value is 31.93 and the table value χ^2 is 16.92 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the calculated chi-square value of 31.93 is greater than the table χ^2 value of 16.92 at 9 degree of

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freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that family problem is a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Hypothesis 3:

Poor academic performance will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Table 7: Chi-square (χ^2) Results of Poor Academic Performance and Violent Behaviour among Students.

S/N	ITEMS	df	Cal. Value	Table Value	Remarks
15.	Violent behaviour in school disrupt the school environment and affect the overall school academic productivity.				
16.	Students who engage in violence behaviour doesn't have time for class and this may affect their academic performance.				
17.	Teachers who teach in a school characterized by violent behaviour are going to teach under extreme fear which may affect their productivity.	9	41.30	16.92	Ho rejected
18.	Violence behaviour in school by students will generally affect the academic performance of every students directly or indirectly involved.				
Column Total					

@0.05 alpha level

Table 7: shows that the calculated chi-square value of 41.30 and the table value of 16.92 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the calculated chi-square value is greater than the table value, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that poor academic performance is significantly an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Hypothesis 4: Suicide thought will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Table 8: Chi-square (χ^2) Results of Suicide Thought and Violent Behaviour among Students.

S/N	ITEMS	df	Cal. Value	Table Value	Remarks
19.	Victims of school violence like cultism are susceptible to suicide thought due to emotional and physical trauma				
20.	Violence behaviour like bully can make some students look down on themselves and try to kill themselves to avoid the bully.	9	55.82	16.92	Ho rejected
21.	Student who engage in violent may feel guilty of his or her action at one point and decide to commit suicide to avoid punishment.				
22.	Violent behaviour in school and home is one of the leading cause of suicide and suicidal thoughts among adolescents.				
Column Total					

@ 0.05 alpha level

Table 8: shows that the calculated chi-square value is 55.82 and the table value χ^2 is 16.92 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the calculated chi-square value of 55.82 is greater than the table χ^2 value of 16.92 at 9 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that suicide thought is significantly an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of research questions one and two reveal that higher percentage (73.5%) of respondents believed that peer pressure and family problem are some of the leading causes of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara

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state. This is because secondary school students are mostly adolescents, and adolescence age is the age when young adults seek recognition and acceptance among their peers. Some adolescent even get depressed when they are isolated or got rejected by their class mates. Also, problems in the homes can push adolescents into the hands of violent friends who will teach them violent behaviours like bullying and fighting. Furthermore, higher percentage of the respondents agreed that violent behaviours can lead to poor academic performance and suicidal thoughts. This corroborate the fact about adolescents suffering from depression as a result of having to meet the demands by their violent peers. This is in line with the results of the postulated hypotheses which are reported below:

Hypothesis One which stated that peer pressure will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State was rejected and alternative hypothesis upheld. This means that peer pressure is a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State. This is because peer influence is associated with family role in promoting healthy or unhealthy behaviour during adolescence. Peer group is a model that influence behaviours and attitudes, towards accepting and adopting violence and fight due to excessive aggression. This finding corroborates the finding of Okorodudu (2015), who conducted a study to determine factors that are responsible for aggressive behaviours among secondary school students. His findings indicated that, as young people grow; they begin to surrender to the influence of their peers as they shed off their parental orientation and replace it with dependence on their peers. In the process, friends encourage their peers to engage in undesirable acts like fighting, alcohol consumption, sexual promiscuity and destruction of property. It is also observed that whenever incidence of violence are witnessed in school, a group of youths’ team up to engage in criminal activities. Peer groups do not only provide positive settings but peer pressure can also lead to risky behaviour and irresponsibility. Children who form friendships with anti- social peers are at the risk for later anti-social behaviour. When adolescents formed relationships with people who displayed aggressive behaviours, they often take part in the behaviours themselves. This was supported by Weerman,(2019),that the resolution of adolescent developmental crisis depends on the interactions between the individual and the environment. Therefore, if the significant person is practicing aggressive behaviours, the adolescent may engage in the same behaviour. If adolescents spend time with deviant peers who consumed drugs, fights, do not attend school regularly and are physically aggressive, the adolescents are more likely to engage in aggressive behaviours as well. They often do this to keep their friends and peers; to have a sense of belonging in a group or to boost their self-esteem.

Hypothesis Two which stated that family problem will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State was rejected and alternative hypothesis upheld. This means that family problem is a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State. This is because the family plays a major role in shaping the behaviour, attitude and morals of children. Family problems, such as physical abuse, battering and chaotic home environment have great influence on the temperament of children in adolescence and adulthood. Maladjustment, parent-child physical abuse, and Child-to-parent lack of emotional support, father and wrong parenting styles can be a precursor to violent behaviour among secondary school student. This result is in-line with the report of O’Moore, (2018) (who noted that the roots of most violent behaviours appear to develop during childhood, the time when family members live together and interact closely. Youth who commit most serious violent acts, and who continue their violent acts beyond adolescence began their behaviours during childhood (Weaver and Clum,2015).

Hypothesis three which stated that poor academic performance will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State was rejected. This is so because violence and fights due to excessive aggression could lead to absenteeism, lateness to school, distraction in classroom and poor academic achievement. This result is in-line with the report of Taylor; Davies & Malanchuk, (2017) who watched how and understudy self-regard, and levels of aggression influenced the academic performance in school. From the information, the authors identified a strong relationship between aggression and academic failure. Peaceful and friendly school and classroom environment foster better attention in the classroom and better attention and concentration improve learning and fosters better retention of knowledge. Hostile school environment, where bullies and haters display violent behaviour will affect better academic performance.

Hypothesis Four which stated that suicide thought will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State was rejected. This means that suicide thought is significantly an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State. This implies that prolonged exposure to threat and other violent behaviours can lead to suicidal thought and attempts. This is supported by Shaffer (2018), who reported that there are two different clusters of suicidal individuals, the first characterized by aggressive and violent outbursts and the second characterized by depression or withdrawal. Investigations focusing on the relationship between aggression and suicide have indicated that there is a stronger association between the two behaviours than has previously been appreciated. Developmental research

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consistently documents the high levels of covariance between peer and youth deviance. It is becoming clear that one of the major ways that deviant youth become even more deviant is through unrestricted interaction with deviant peers. Adolescents sometimes join groups that readily accept them; even if the group is involved in illegal or negative activities. For them, the need for affiliation or closeness is often greater than the need to “do the right thing.” When adolescents are rejected, threatened or bullied, they often result to suicide to end it all rather than coping with rejection and isolation or constant threat from their classmates or school mates.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the significant role of peer pressure and family problems as causal factors contributing to violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria. Furthermore, it underscores the detrimental consequences of such behavior, including poor academic performance and the presence of suicidal thoughts among these students. These findings emphasize the urgent need for targeted interventions and support systems to address these issues and promote a safer and healthier educational environment for secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

14. Students should be encouraged to keep good company, avoid the company of the violent people. Jingles, drama presentations and seminars should be organized periodically to correct any violent behaviour that might have been learnt at home.
15. Parents should be educated during school sport days and parents-Teachers’ association meetings to avoid violent behaviours at home and be very close to their wards.
16. Government should create and implement policy that will prevent hateful speech and violence in the school compound.
17. Schools should motivate counsellors to provide students with adequate knowledge on effect of violent behaviours so that they can also to make informed decisions about their academics and health. Teachers should ensure that students are well coached on implication of violent behaviour on their psychological wellbeing.

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Impact of Improvised Materials on Creative-Thinking–Abstractness of Title in Basic Science among Secondary School Students in Makurdi, Benue State

*Agbidye, Anna¹

Email: annagbidye@gmail.com

Ayua, Geoffrey Aondolumun¹

Email: ayuageoffrey@gmail.com

Gamat, Grace Bala²

Email: gracegamatnenadi@gmail.com

Ikyernum, Gabriel Sesugh³

Email: sesughgabriel05@gmail.com

¹Department of Science & Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

²Department of Integrated Science, Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya, Nigeria

³Department of Agricultural Technology, School of Sciences, Federal Polytechnic, Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Abstract

This study determined impact of improvised materials on creative-thinking –abstractness of title in basic science among secondary school students in Makurdi, Benue state. A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group research design was used adopted for the study. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The study’s population was made up of 1337(680 male and 657 female) Upper Basic two (JSS II) government secondary school students during the 2021/2022) academic session. A multistage sample of 52 (23 male and 29 female) students in two intact classes from two schools was drawn. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used for data collection. Data were analysed using mean and two-way ANCOVA. Findings showed no significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material, $F_{(2,45)} = 1.641$; $p = .205 > .05$. Although, there existed a significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles in favour of those taught using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material, $F_{(1, 45)} = 42.733$; $p = .000 < .05$, no significant difference existed in the students’ creative-thinking abstractness of titles based on gender, $F_{(2, 17)} = .982$; $p = .395 > .05$. Therefore, it was concluded that, enhancing creative-thinking abstractness of titles among students with different abilities can be achieved without any gender discrepancy by actively involving learners in the improvisation of instructional materials. Thus, teacher-learner improvisation approach was recommended for teaching Basic Science in basic schools.

Keywords: Teacher-Learner Improvised Material (TLIM), Teacher Improvised Material (TIM), Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles, Diverse-Ability and Gender.

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of the 21st century, creativity has emerged as a fundamental driving force behind innovation, problem-solving, and progress across various domains. As technology advances, economies globalize, and societies become more interconnected, the ability to think creatively and adaptively has become indispensable (Alfiyah, Sunyono & Andra, 2022; Dianita, 2023). Creativity transcends traditional boundaries, enabling individuals to envision novel solutions to complex challenges, sparking artistic expressions that resonate with diverse audiences, and fostering a culture of continuous growth and exploration (Long, Balakrishnan, Yan & Chiet, 2020; Nazhifah, Wiyono, Ismet & Azairok 2023). In a world defined by constant change, nurturing and harnessing creativity is not just a luxury; it is an essential skill that empowers individuals and societies to thrive in the face of unprecedented opportunities and uncertainties. In the dynamic landscape of the current age, the realm of science education stands at a crossroads, poised to adapt and innovate in response to the rapidly emerging challenges that our world presents. As technological breakthroughs, environmental shifts, and complex societal issues redefine the boundaries of scientific inquiry, fostering creativity within science education has never been more critical (Trisnayanti,

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Ashadi, Sunarno, & Masykuri, 2020; Oliveira, Brown, Su, Zhang, LeBrun, Eaton & Yemen, 2021). To equip the next generation with the tools they need to address these challenges head-on, science education must embrace and prioritize creativity as an integral component, enabling students to not only comprehend the intricacies of scientific principles, but also to wield their creativity in shaping a sustainable, innovative, and adaptive future.

Creativity is our capacity to find new solutions to the problems we encounter by using our existing knowledge. Creativity is an act arising out of a perception of the environment that acknowledges a certain disequilibrium, resulting in productive activity that challenges patterned thought processes and norms, and gives rise to something new in the form of a physical object or even a mental or an emotional construct (Balci, Baykal, Göksun, Kisbu & Yantaç, 2023; Apaydin, 2023). Creativity thus implies the act of turning new and imaginative ideas into reality. In our age, where information is developing and changing very rapidly, societies need individuals who are proactive, thinking creative, problem-solving, and constantly improving them in order to adapt to this change and development (Apaydin, 2023). Therefore, this infers that in order to confirm a sustainable development, the creativity potential of the individuals who create the society must be continuously improved by innovative approaches which will engender creativity skills such as creative thinking. Creative thinking refers to the ability to generate diverse and numerous responses to a particular issue that increases the likely output of creative ideas (He & Wong, 2021; Aldossari, 2021). According to Ayua, Terhemba, Omega and Samuel (2023) creative thinking is one's cognitive process to generate effective ideas in solving problems under certain aims and conditions. Creative thinking abilities hold immense value for nations, researchers, educators, and workplaces alike, driving their efforts to enhance creativity through innovative teaching. In line with this, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) in her National Policy on Education emphasizes the exposure of learners to Basic Science concepts to develop skills and knowledge necessary for meeting contemporary societal needs. One of the principal objectives of Basic Science education is to foster learners' creative thinking ability, facilitated by effective teaching/learning materials. Nevertheless, the National Teachers' Institute - NTI (as cited in Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhemba, 2022) noted that the materials for science teaching are lacking and thus compelling teachers to improvise.

Improvisation refers to making provision for something not readily available. It is the process by which educational materials are locally made to meet the purpose of the realia (Ayua, Ikyernum & Terhemba, 2022). To teach science at the basic school level, having sufficient teaching aids is key to making teaching-learning processes more engaging and interesting. Improvisation according to Ayua (2021) could be by substitution, modification and construction either solely by the teacher (Teacher Improvised Material) or by the combined efforts of the teacher and learners (Teacher Learner Improvised Material). Teacher Improvised Material (TIM) refers to teaching aid(s) made by the teacher alone and brought to the classroom for Basic Science teaching. TIM is an improvisation approach that is teacher-based because learners are not involved in the process of producing the improvised instructional material(s) (Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhemba, 2022). Teacher-Learner Improvised Material (TLIM) on the other hand refers to teaching aids that are collaboratively produced by both the teacher and the learners for the purpose of Basic Science teaching and learning (Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhemba, 2022). This approach emphasizes the active involvement of both the teacher and the students in creating these materials. By adopting a teacher-learner-based improvisation method, students gain essential knowledge about the subject matter and are encouraged to think creatively even before the actual lessons take place. This process fosters a more engaging and interactive learning environment, allowing students to actively participate in their education and take ownership of their learning experiences. In the realm of effective Basic Science education, two pivotal concepts come to the forefront: creative thinking and improvisation. These concepts hold immense significance in crafting, selecting, and utilizing appropriate instructional materials, particularly in regions where production technology is still evolving (Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhemba, 2022). The integration of improvisation into the teaching and learning process is increasingly acknowledged as a means to cultivate and amplify creative thinking among students (Navarro, 2018). Fostering creative thinking through improvisation not only equips students with vital skills for societal success but also contributes to economic advancement in our technology-driven 21st-century world. Consequently, prioritizing the cultivation of creative thinking and improvisation within educational contexts becomes imperative. Creative thinking comprises five sub domains of fluency, originality, elaboration, resistance to premature closure and abstractness of titles (Tehemba, Ayua & Gamat, 2023). Nonetheless, this paper focused on creative-thinking abstractness of titles.

Creative-thinking abstractness of titles is the ability of learners to synthesise and organise processes of thinking, capture the essence of information involved, know what is important and produce good titles (Chua, Balakrishnan, Choong, & Koh, 2020). Creative-thinking abstractness of titles is the degree beyond concrete labelling or physical description of the picture drawn which relates to the respondents' ability in synthesising and organising processes of thinking (Ng & Lee, 2019; Hahm, Kim & Park, 2019; Chua, Balakrishnan, Koh & Chiet 2020). Creative-thinking abstractness of titles is a vital aspect of creative thinking as it plays a crucial role in fostering valuable ideas which equips individuals with the essential competencies needed

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to thrive in modern societies driven by creativity. Özgenel, Canpolat, Yağan and Canlı (2019) in their study “the effects of enriched workshop training given to pre-school students on creative thinking skills of students” found that there was a significant increase in creative thinking abstractness of titles after students were exposed to the enriched training to foster creative thinking. Likewise, Ng and Lee (2019) in their study “assessment of creative thinking of Hong Kong undergraduate students using the Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking” found that learners’ creative-thinking abstractness of titles was well above average. In contrast Chua, Balakrishnan, Choong and Koh (2020) and Chua, Balakrishnan, Koh and Chiet (2020) in their respective studies on creative thinking established that there was no significant improvement in the creative thinking abstractness of titles after learners were exposed to the creative thinking module. Though the studies assessed the creative-thinking abstractness to titles of learners, they however were not concerned with creative-thinking abstractness of titles as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation across diverse-ability learners.

In this research, the term "diverse-ability" refers to the different educational performance levels of students in Basic Science, which can be categorized as high, average, or low based on their past academic scores. Maikano (as cited in Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhamba, 2022) maintained that ability grouping is determined by educators' assessments of students' abilities. When assigning students to different tracks, their prior test scores or performance measures from previous grades are considered to determine their ability levels. Students' ability levels for this study were guided by Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME (2021) and Benue State Examinations Board – BSEB (2019) grading system for basic schools. Based on the grading system, High Ability Level (A = 75-100% and B = 65-74%), Average Ability Level (C = 55-64% and D = 45-54%) and Low Ability Level (E = 40-44% and F = 0-39%). By using this grading system, the researchers were able to distinguish and group students based on their academic ability levels in Basic Science. Ikyernum, Ayua and Terhamba (2022) in their study “Effect of teacher-learner improvised material on creative thinking among diverse-ability upper basic science students in Makurdi metropolis” established that the level of creative thinking among diverse-ability students was significantly enhanced without gender disparity as a result of learners’ active involvement in the improvisation of instructional materials. However, Balci, Baykal, Gökşun, Kisbu and Yantaç (2023) in their study “My Creative World (MCW): Improving Creative Thinking in Elementary School-Aged Children” found that there was no significant treatment effect of creative thinking abstractness of titles after learners were exposed to the creativity intervention programme. These studies however were not concerned with creative-thinking abstractness of titles in relation to improvisation and did not tell whether a difference existed in creative-thinking abstractness of titles based on gender as a result of learners’ involvement in improvisation of instructional materials.

Gender differences encompass the characteristics associated with being male or female, man or woman, boy or girl. Research by Danjuma (as cited in Ayua, 2021) indicates that these gender disparities have a worldwide impact, particularly in Africa, by hindering the equal participation of boys and girls in Science Education. Consequently, these gender-specific factors influence the teaching, learning, and creative thinking of students in Basic Science. Empirically, Ulger and Morsunbul (2017); Zhang, Ren and Deng (2020), in their respective studies on differences in creative thinking found that a significant difference existed in creative thinking abilities between males and females in favour of females. However, Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ayua, Terhamba and Ikyernum (2022) and Midilli, Özsoy, Aslan (2022) found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking abstractness of titles respectively. However, none of the studies were concerned with creative-thinking abstractness of titles as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation. That is why determining creative-thinking abstractness of titles among upper basic science students using improvisation is imperative. The problem of this study is that, the modern world has undergone significant paradigm shifts. These changes, attribute to the knowledge revolution and rapid technological advancements, highlight the importance of creativity skills in an ever-evolving world. To effectively navigate this dynamic environment, educational strategies need be realigned to match these transformative trends with anchorage at basic education for cultivating creative-thinking. Although, improvisation is a common term in education, the extent to which it may aid creative-thinking abstractness of titles among upper basic science students remains a subject that requires deeper exploration. Hence, the need for this study.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles (CTAT) scores of students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material (TLIM) and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material (TIM)
2. To find out the CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM based on gender.

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Research Questions

1. What is the mean difference in CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM and those taught using TIM?
2. What is the mean difference in CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM based on gender?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM and those taught using TIM.
2. There is no significant difference in CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM based on gender.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group design was used for this study. After pre-test administration, the experimental group of an intact class of 1:24 was taught concept of work, energy and power with 5 lesson plans using demonstration method blended with Teacher-Learner-Improvised Materials (wooden toy car and wooden electric fan) constructed through active involvement of learners together with the teacher using procedures outlined in the lesson plans; while the control group was taught the same concept using same method blended with Teacher-Improvised Materials. This treatment lasted for five weeks. Thereafter, the students in both groups were given post-test. Students diverse-ability were based on previous term’s performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). A multistage sample of 52 (23 male and 29 females?) Upper-Basic II students in two schools drawn from the population of 1337 (680 males and 657 females) Upper Basic II students in all the 21 secondary schools during the 2021/2022 academic session (Teaching Service Board Makurdi, 2021) was used for the study. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data collection. Section “A” collected students’ biodata; while section ‘B’ had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with the opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students’ creative-thinking abstractness of titles in Basic Science. TTCT-Figural B was validated and trial-tested with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Extraneous variables like group initial difference, group interaction effect and priming were controlled by homogeneity test, distant locations and impromptu tests respectively. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using a two-way Analysis of covariance due to normality of the distribution, homogeneity of variance, randomness of selection, measurement based on interval scale and independence of samples.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material?

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores of students taught using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material and Teacher Improvised Material.

Ability Level	N	Group	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	12	TIM	1.77	0.615	1.96	0.392	0.19	2.15
	10	TLIM	1.70	0.327	4.04	1.265	2.34	
Average	8	TIM	1.58	0.493	1.71	0.476	0.13	1.31
	7	TLIM	1.46	0.113	2.90	0.829	1.44	
Low	8	TIM	1.55	0.414	1.59	0.181	0.04	1.75
	7	TLIM	1.64	0.395	3.43	1.449	1.79	
Cluster		TIM	1.63		1.75		0.12	1.74
		TLIM	1.60		3.46		1.85	

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Table 1 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores among diverse-ability between experimental and control group with cluster means of 1.63 and 1.60. The table also shows that creative-thinking abstractness of titles mean scores among diverse-ability in the experimental group were higher than those in the control group with cluster mean gain difference of 1.74.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material based on gender?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation of Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles Scores of students taught using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material based on gender

Ability Level	Gender	N	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	Male	7	1.80	0.252	3.83	0.969	2.03	0.03
	Female	3	1.47	0.416	3.53	0.966	2.06	
Average	Male	2	1.50	0.000	3.30	0.707	1.80	0.78
	Female	5	1.44	0.134	2.46	0.808	1.02	
Low	Male	2	1.50	0.000	3.30	0.707	1.80	0.15
	Female	5	1.67	0.427	3.62	1.491	1.95	
Cluster	Male		1.60		3.48		1.88	0.21
	Female		1.53		3.20		1.67	

Table 3 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores between male and female in the experimental group with cluster means of 1.60 and 1.53. Likewise, the table also shows that the creative-thinking abstractness of titles mean scores in the post-test was higher than those in the pre-test in both male and female with cluster mean gains of 1.88 and 1.67 respectively

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material.

Table 3: Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles Test Scores of Students Based on Improvisation Technique

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	45.001 ^a	6	7.500	9.754	.000	.565
Intercept	27.627	1	27.627	35.929	.000	.444
Pre-TTCT	.022	1	.022	.029	.865	.001
Improvisation	32.860	1	32.860	42.733	.000	.487
Diverse-ability	5.859	2	2.929	3.810	.030	.145
Improvisation* Diverse-ability	2.523	2	1.261	1.641	.205	.068
Error	34.602	45	.769			
Total	420.800	52				
Corrected Total	79.603	51				

a. R Squared = .565 (Adjusted R Squared = .507)

Table 2 shows no significant difference in the creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TIM and those taught using TLIM, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.641$; $p = .205 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. However, the result also showed that students' creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores in the experimental group was better than those in the control group, $F_{(1, 45)} = 42.733$; $p = .000 < .05$. This implies that, although Teacher-Learner Improvised Material (TLIM) enhances creative-thinking abstractness of titles, it is not dependent on students' academic abilities.

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Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material based on gender.

Table 4. Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles Scores of Students Taught Using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material Based on Gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	11.336 ^a	6	1.889	1.181	.362	.294
Intercept	4.522	1	4.522	2.827	.111	.143
Pre-TTCT-TLIM	.388	1	.388	.242	.629	.014
Gender	.701	1	.701	.438	.517	.025
Diverse-ability-TLIM	6.221	2	3.111	1.945	.174	.186
Gender *	3.142	2	1.571	.982	.395	.104
Diverse-ability-TLIM						
Error	27.194	17	1.600			
Total	327.650	24				
Corrected Total	38.530	23				

a. R Squared = .294 (Adjusted R Squared = .045)

Table 4 showed no significant difference in the creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores between male and female diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material, $F_{(2, 17)} = .982$; $p = .395 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that, Teacher-Learner Improvised Material is gender unbiased; hence it enhanced creative-thinking abstractness of titles in both male and female diverse-ability Basic Science students.

Discussion of Findings

Concerning students' creative-thinking abstractness of titles based on their involvement in the improvisation of instructional materials, it was found that significant difference existed in creative- abstractness of titles between students in the control and experimental groups in favour of those in the experimental group. However, among the ability levels there existed no significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles. Following field experience, the finding of this study is not odd because during the construction process, students were given ample opportunity to fully synthesise and organise processes of thinking, capture the essence of information involved, know what is important and produce good titles which thus entail creative-thinking abstractness of titles. This finding is similar with Özgenel, Canpolat, Yağan and Canlı (2019) who found that there was a significant increase in creative-thinking abstractness of titles after students were exposed to the enriched training to foster creative thinking. The finding also agrees with that of Ng & Lee (2019) who established that learners' creative-thinking abstractness of titles was well above average. However, the finding does not only contrast with, but is a potential solution to those of Chua, Balakrishnan, Choong and Koh (2020), Chua, Balakrishnan, Koh and Chiet (2020) and Balci, Baykal, Gökşun, Kisbu and Yantaç (2023) who found no significant improvement in the creative thinking abstractness of titles after learners were exposed to creative thinking enhancement programmes. The indifference among diverse-ability students in creative-thinking abstractness of titles as found out, is similar to Ikyernum, Ayua and Terhemba (2022) findings of no significant difference in creative thinking among diverse-ability students.

Regarding students' creative-thinking abstractness of titles based on gender, it was discovered that no significant difference existed in creative-thinking abstractness of titles between male and female diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material. Thus, involving students in the improvisation of instructional materials to enhance their creative-thinking abstractness of titles is gender unbiased. This finding is similar to those of Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ayua, Terhemba and Ikyernum (2022) and Midilli, Özsoy, Aslan (2022) who found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking abstractness of titles respectively. This finding however does not only differ but also is solution to Ulger and Morsunbul (2017), Zhang, Ren and Deng (2020) who found out that a significant difference existed between females and males upon creative thinking in favour of females.

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Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that: Creative-thinking abstractness of titles among diverse-ability students can be enhanced without gender discrepancy if learners are actively involved in the improvisation of instructional materials.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made to effectively implement this approach:

1. Teacher-Learner Improvisation approach should be adopted in teaching Basic Science.
2. School administrators should encourage researchers to organize workshops on the use of Teacher-Learner Improvisation.
3. Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers on Teacher-Learner Improvisation.
4. School proprietors, heads and parents' teachers' association should materially/financially support Teacher-Learner Improvisation in Basic Science.

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Political Will as a Panacea for Good Governance and National Development: An Overview of the 2022 Electoral Act in Nigeria

Idoko, Alison Abutu

Email: alison.idoko@fulokoja.edu.ng

Tel: [08056846613](tel:08056846613)

Department of History and International Studies, Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State.

Abstract

Studies have indicated that myriad of policies and programs initiated by political elite in Nigeria were geared towards national development and good governance. The passing of the 2022 Electoral Act is pursuant to the desire to entrench good governance and democracy in Nigeria. This work “Political will” a Panacea for Good Governance and National Development; an Assessment of the 2022 Electoral Act in Nigeria is aimed at assessing to what extent the political elite are willing to entrench good governance and development in Nigeria. The study adopted the decision-making theory as tool for analysis and analytical cum descriptive method of data collection. Information were collected for the purpose of describing and interpreting the willingness or otherwise of the elite in achieving goals of the Act, through textual methodology. Finding reveals that lack of political will of the elites is a major clog in attempts at entrenching of good governance in Nigeria. It is recommended therefore that elites in Nigeria be strictly guided by their oath of office, that is not to allow personal interest, ethnic consideration, political association or affiliation and region influence/interfere with decision they make but national interests.

Keywords: Political Will, Good Governance, National Development, Electoral Act, National Interest.

Introduction

Several scholars have written on the impact of colonial heritage on the nation Nigeria. This heritage according to Matthew and Holly (2022) has left deep scar on the country’s history. The question of the civil war between groups within the nations border, political rift, regional mutual suspicion has characterized relation between a nation of about 250 ethnic nationalities bound together not by their consent but colonial contraption of the Berlin conference (Oluwaseun, 2021). Having understood this precarious position, successive government since independence has put in place reform agendas and policy instruments in attempts at achieving ethno-regional balance. A centralizing nation building drive started in 1966 to 1979 through constitutional reform which introduced in the management of interethnic relations (Mustapha 2005). The 1979 federal character principles aimed at ensuring representation and power sharing is one of such management policies. However, efforts at reforming inter-ethnic relation and creating inclusive institutions have limited success. This lack of success is hinged on “political will”. Political will could be explained as the extent of committed support among key decision makers for a particular policy solution to a particular problem (Iori, A. et-al 2010). It should be noted that this concept (political will) is a complex one having many sides to achieving same. On the other hand, there is the authority, capacity and legitimacy of the key decision makers or reformers which is also dependent on whether those who want an outcome have the power and means to achieve it. There is also the question of commitment to preference.

Analyzing the passage of the 2022 electoral act, scholars have argued and criticized the premise of the then president Muhammadu Buhari withholding of assent to the bill. The basis of the criticism of withholding assent is on the willingness to improve on the electoral system. According to the former governor of Rivers state Nyesom Wike, the refusal for the president to assent is based on the inclusion of a clause which is not going to be favourable to the authorities. The clause he argued is the electronic transmission of results embedded in the act. He further argued that there is an opportunity for clauses in a bill to be further amended, citing the petroleum bill which was signed in spite of unresolved issues and bill sent back for an amendment (Nathaniel 2021). Ayida (1987) had argued that Nigeria is a land of promise and hope in Africa and basically stable and structurally well balanced but that ominous signs of crack are ever present. He further argued given the right leadership, the cracks will be overcome.

According to Kevin Casaszamoia, the secretary general of the International institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance (IDEA), a sub unit of the United Nations assembly, in a press release, opined that “in order to protect democracy, we must protect election” (UN office, 2023). It follows therefore that election and electoral processes must be seen to be

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credible to have integrity and acceptability. The electoral process, which includes reforms of electoral laws are ideal and integral part of the democratic process. A faulty electoral system results to maladministration or bad governance.

Theoretical Framework

The fulcrum of decision-making theory lies in the ability to choose between alternatives with emphasis on goal-directed guide with predetermined criteria or what could be referred to as means-ends rationality (Simon 1947). The theoretical framework adopted in this work is the decision-making approach. The theory seeks to explain how decision are made by states as it relates to their national interest. Herbert A. Simon, James G. March, Guetzkow H, Richard Synder, Bruk, H.W. and Sapin, B. are well known in this field (Johari, 1963). Richard Synder and his associates pioneered the decision-making approach to the study of foreign policy and policies generally (verma 2001). The basic assumption of the approach is that policies are not made by states but by individuals who act on behalf of the state. The analysis of state behavior centres on these individuals and groups who represent their states. The approach discusses decision makers as individuals who arrive at their decision by confronting their values with their image of the environment. It utilizes both internal and external factors as they influence decision (Ojo and Sesay 2022). This theory is relevant to this work because the analysis of state behaviour centres on individual and group who represent their state. All political actions are undertaken by concrete human being and we should view the world from the point of the perspectives of the persons responsible for taken decision. For instance, the National Assembly as an arm of government has identified personalities and not abstract contraptions. The behavior of these individuals at the National Assembly as well as their values and perceptions play significant role in the formulation of Nigeria policies. This theory suffers some limitations because it concentrates exclusively upon image and perception of decision makers and the psychological environment and ignores the objective realities that these reflect. It merely helps us to understand the mechanics but does not provide a satisfactory explanation of the broader aspect of policy. It does not show how the responses from the operational environment affect policy powers in its course. The theory does not adequately explain how decision are made in crisis situation when reactions to threatening problems are drastic and some are intuitive with no time to analyze issues critically.

Synder's contribution is said to be the most outstanding in explaining decision making. He refutes the static analysis as adopted by the system analyst and structural functionalists. He prescribes a process analysis capable of dealing with dynamic situation. A process analysis should explain the situation and reasons for the situation why it evolves in a particular way. He opines that in order to understand the dynamics of political actions, the world should be viewed from the perspective of persons responsible for taking decision. He is concerned mainly with who made the key decision that gave rise to a particular action and how to assess the intellectual and internal processes which decision makers followed to reach their decision. Decision making in relation to policy is an elite thing, therefore the decision making begins by considering all alternatives, causes of action and their consequences and then decide which of the alternatives will maximize her value. Through the decision-making theory, the goals of Nigeria as a state and her national interest are identified by the objective circumstance. The behavior of the Nigeria state is therefore the behavior of the decision makers as such the state action is the action of its officials. Notwithstanding the short coming of the decision-making theory it remains a useful tool of analysis as it pertains to policy.

Political Will, Good Governance and National Development

Political will presupposes a commitment to real or sincerely perceived solution to problems. In as much as the concept is often used in political discussions as rhetorical, it remains an ambiguous concept. Scholars have approached the definition of this concept using varying approaches and categories. Harmergen (1998) see it as a likelihood of reform; kpundeh (1998) perceives it as a demonstrated credible intent of political actors, whether elected or appointed leaders, civil society watchdogs, and stakeholder groups etc, to attack perceived causes or effort at a systematic level. Brinkerhoff and Kulibaba (1999) perceived political as a commitment of actors to undertake actions, to achieve a set objective and to sustain the cost of these actions overtime. Rose and Gveely (2006) perceive political will as a sustained commitment of politicians and administrators to invest political resources to achieve specific objectives. It is clear, the corollary of political will to good governance, but very often politicians fail to adopt and implement policies that they are aware, are necessary for sustained economic, social and political development. Most times, the political elite knows what is right but is willing to go against what they believe is right to fall lock-step with their party or their campaign finances. They are unwilling to follow their conscience but rather political expediency. It is the antithesis of political will which translates to lack of one. The political elites therefore must ensure that integrity policies aimed at preventing corruption and fostering high standards of behavior, helping to reinforce the credibility and legitimacy of those involved in policy decision making, safeguarding the public interest and restoring confidence in the

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policy making process. The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended 2011 (akande 2010), stipulates provisions aimed at enhancing preserving and protecting the people's right which ultimately translates to good governance. There is no gain saying a correlation exist between political will and good governance and development. Though there exist no one all-embracing definition of the term good governance; the United Nation refer governance to every activity of all political and administrative authority to govern their country. Thus, generally, governance has the meaning, the decision-making process and the process of determining which policy or policies will best suit a particular purpose or circumstance, (UCLG ASPAC, 2023).

From the above eight principles are deducible from the character of good governance, viz participation, rule of law, transparency, responsiveness, consensus, equity and inclusiveness, effectiveness and efficiency and accountability (UCLG ASPAC, 2023). Considering the 2023 Electoral Act, its correlation to good governance and development, YIAGA Africa in their report on the 2023 elections in Nigeria, titled 2023 election; dashed hope? Counsel the electoral body to rebuild public confidence. According to them, the big lesson from the 2023 general election in Nigeria is that electoral reform can deliver credible election if stakeholders, especially Independent National Electoral Commission and political parties comply with rules and guidelines (Ewepu, 2023).

Politics of the 2022 Electoral Act in Nigeria

The electoral act of 2022 has come with so much controversy. The reason is in view of the president (then) Muhammadu Buhari's refusal to assent to the bill at a time in which the electorates and Nigeria believed it would have been so signed, so as to give credibility to the electoral process. No law has created such anxiety and agitation as the electoral act, as it was supposed to guide the conduct of the 2019 general elections. According to the president, his refusal to sign was premised on the fact that the electoral process had begun and signing the act to guide the 2019 electoral process would open a flood gate of litigation as it would be seen as ultra-vires (business hallmark 2019). He further argues that the national assembly must include a clause indicating that if he signs the act, it would not be used to regulate the upcoming 2019 election. More so, the ECOWAS protocol which Nigeria is a signatory forbids members from replacing or changing the rules of an election, less than six months to election except majority of the parties agree to same. Assuming but not conceding that he was right recourse to the ECOWAS protocol was superfluous for he did not explore the window of having to consult with other political parties before declining assent. Conceding that it was his right to veto any bill passed by the national assembly, this has to be done judiciously in the interest of the public; the controversies that the decline of assent generated exacerbated the aggravated political cleavages in the country and putting the legitimacy of the process in jeopardy, his action capable of sending wrong signal to the international community of his commitment to free, fair and credible elections. It has been argued that the former president Muhammadu Buhari's decline to assenting to the electoral act in 2018 was a clear demonstration of lack of political will. As noted earlier, the political elites know what is right but are unwilling to follow their conscience but rather political expediency. This was exactly what was demonstrated during the build up to the signing of the electoral act.

Conclusion

There is no gain saying the advantages of the improvement in the regulations guiding electoral process envisaged in the signing of the electoral act of 2022 in Nigeria; on one hand, it enhances the realization of the goals of the united nations in election, that is sustainable development, peace and security, human rights and gender equality (UN office 2021). In the face of the much talked about controversy surrounding the withdrawal of assent to signing the 2022 electoral act in 2018, settled, there is a new controversy which is generating another debate and is capable of creating and or causing legal crisis; that is the conflicting sections in the 2022 electoral act and the independent national electoral commission guidelines for the conduct of election, particularly sec 62(1) & (2) and clause 38 respectively. These sections seem to conflict each other in the mode of transmission of election result. Whereas one gives strength to electronically transmitted result, the other seems to water it down. This controversy if not taken care of, is capable of derailing the gains of the goal of the reform.

Recommendations

It is expedient therefore that in achieving good governance and national development, policy makers must:

1. Adhere strictly to their oath of office as contained in chapter 333 of the Nigerian oath act 2003.
2. Legal professionals and experts should be engaged to draft legal instrument to avoid conflict of laws.

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3. Every successive government must as a matter of policy draw out electoral reform agenda it intend to carry out within a time frame with the view to improving upon flaws observed during the run up to and after its election year.

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Kidnapping as an Emerging Social Crime in Nigeria: Implications for National Security

***Umar Ali Magaji¹**

Email: magajiumar76@gmail.com

Tel: 08031169423

Umar Magaji Abubakar¹

Email: umarmagajia@gmail.com

Tel: 08030529940

Lawal Usman²

Email: lawalusmantilde@gmail.com

Tel: 08039316468

¹Department of Educational Foundations Faculty of Education, Federal University Kashere, Gombe State

²Department of Social Studies, Adamu Tafawa Balewa College of Education (ATBCOE), Kangere, Bauchi State

Abstract

The significant impact of kidnapping and other associated crimes is becoming worrisome and perplexing and not only to Nigerians but to the international community. This has heightened the fear of foreigners especially international investors, thereby threatening the foundation of economic development. However, the precarious state of kidnapping and other social crimes in contemporary Nigeria have assumed unimaginable dimension in recent times following the increase in kidnapping for ransom, Boko-Haram terrorists' and bandits' attacks on innocent Nigerians leading to loss of many lives and properties. This paper examined the state of kidnapping, types causes, consequences or effects, and measures undertaken by government to tackle the menace. The paper also adopted economic theory and concluded that security agencies and the general public should be more proactive in curbing the prevalence of the phenomenon. The paper also recommended practical ways to curb or end kidnapping in Nigeria, to include youth empowerment, ensure affairs and better harnessed equitable distribution of resources of the country in order to promote national unity.

Keywords: Kidnapping, social crime, and national security

Introduction

Kidnapping is a major problem in Nigeria in the early 21st century. Kidnapping by bandits and insurgents is among the biggest organized or gang crime in Nigeria and become a national security threat or challenge. Kidnapping as a crime phenomenon is not something that started in recent years. It is as old as the human race. Kidnapping is a crime that is endangering the life of people. This is evident whereby individuals are abducted every day for political or economic gains by the perpetrators of such crime. Kidnapping is seen as lucrative business and the shortest means to wealth by those involved in this crime. The current wave of abductions across the country makes every person a potential target regardless of social class or economic status unlike political kidnapping which started in the Nigeria's oil-rich Nigeria Delta region in the early 2000s and the one by Jihadist terror group, Boko Haram in Nigeria's northeast and northwest that began in 2009 when the conflict there started.

In the Niger Delta, agitators took expatriates working with multinational oil giant's hostage to force oil companies operating there to carry out community development projects for the benefit of the host communities or force government into negotiations for more of economic benefits accruing to the federal treasurer for the region. Abductions by Boko Haram terrorist is to further its agenda, recruit fighters, instill fear, gain more international popularity and force the government to negotiate with it for ransom which is one of the means of generating funds for its terrorist operations. Boko Haram has committed several mass kidnappings of students. Their 2014 kidnapping of over 250 teenage girls from a secondary school in Chibok, Borno state, was one of the talks about. Today the rapid spread of kidnapping has become alarming not only in Nigeria but in other countries across the globe. The prevalent rate of kidnapping in Nigeria is worrisome as almost everyone is affected by it directly or indirectly. Kidnapping cuts across every nook and cranny of Nigeria: places of worship, markets, schools, homes, highways, farms, recreational centres, and hotels are not left out. The current security challenges in the country can be understood against

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existing evidence that even government officials, traditional rulers, wealthy/business men are not spared. (Chidi, 2014 as cited in Dangiwa 2019). Thus, this portrays a great sense of concern regarding kidnapping in the country. Kidnapping has become an everyday event in Nigeria, as it is widespread and cuts across the country. It is booming in the country because perpetrators of the heinous crime continue to communicate with the family members of the victim and the police sometimes cannot locate the kidnapers.

Kidnapping of all sort and manner has gained momentum due to the monetary benefit/gain of the act and almost has left everyone in fear because one might not know who the next victim could be. As mentioned earlier the rich oil regions of the Niger Delta have witnessed this phenomenon on a large scale with the targets being mostly expatriates and Nigerians in the oil business. The kidnapping today has become one of the contemporary social problems in Nigeria, as it has spread almost all over the country extending to places as far as Kano, Katsina, Zamfara, Niger, Borno, Kaduna, Kebbi, Sokoto, Nassarawa States to mention but a few. Also, South-East, South-West and South-South of the country have become known as the kidnapers' den (Sanyaolu, 2009).

Conceptualization of Kidnapping

Kidnapping is a criminal offense consisting of the unlawful taking and carrying away of a person by force or fraud or the unlawful seizure and detention of a person against his will. In earlier times kidnapping meant carrying a person away to another country for involuntary servitude, to expose him to the commission of further criminal act against his person, or to obtain ransom for his safe release. More recently kidnapping for the purpose of extortion has become a tactic of political revolutionaries or terrorists seeking concessions from a government. Kidnapping can also be defined as the act of seizing and detaining or carrying away a person by unlawful force or by fraud and often with a demand for collecting ransom. (Uzorma and Nwanegbo-Ben 2012). It involves taking a person from their family forcefully without their consent with the motive of holding the person as a hostage and earning a profit from their family. In this regard kidnapping could be for a number of reasons, such as getting monetary reward or getting some sort of benefits from the victim. It is usually done for a motive or for oppressive intentions, the most common of which is extorting money from the family of the victim in the form of ransom for freedom and continual living. Based on this observation one finds in kidnapping cognate terms like capturing, hostage-taking, abduction, hijacking, withholding to mention but a few.

As a crime against humanity, kidnapping is a deviant and unwanted behaviour that is intended to harm both the victim and his family members to create tension within a society. Kidnapping as an organised crime is better noticed when a victim's relations are bringing the ransom. This shows how the perpetrators of the crime are organized so as to carry out their act of criminality. Moreover, this is evident that kidnapping in Nigeria is well organized and involves a network of professionals that are performing different tasks for the survival of their victims (Ugwuleb 2011).

Types of kidnapping in Nigeria

As kidnapping is alarming and becoming a threat to national security in Nigeria the following are identified as types: **Basic Kidnapping:** - By far the most common form of kidnapping, this can be accomplished in most parts of the world with minimal preparation with a relatively low risk of failure. Kidnapers will generally target local businessman or their families, those regarded as being "well-off" without having sufficient resources to spend a great deal of money on security precautions. The kidnapers' goal is a fast, easy, pay off- Generally, the ransoms requested are relatively easy for the victim's family or company to obtain. **High-net-worth Individual Kidnapping:** - Generally the intended target is studied for some time prior to the actual kidnapping, allowing the perpetrators to gather intelligence on security procedures and personal habits. After the victim has been taken his or her family or employer is contacted with the ransom demand. Generally, a negotiation process occurs as most of these incidents are perpetrated by experienced kidnap gangs, the victims is generally released if ransom is paid. As high net-worth individuals become increasingly security-conscious, this type of kidnapping has been on the decline in recent years in favour of less involved kidnappings with smaller, but easier to obtain pay off.

Tiger Kidnapping: - A crime involving a hostage taking in order to force the victim to commit or assist in a theft. The hostage or hostages is or are held as until the victim has met the demands of the criminals. All of the victims work in a location where cash is being handled, such as banks, post-office, currency exchange firms to mention but a few.

Express Kidnapping: - the victim is abducted, then forced to withdraw their own ransom from a bank or ATM. If all goes well the victim is released after wards, generally after having been relieved of all valuables on their persons (and occasionally in their residence). This type of kidnapping is popular in urban areas, due to the prolific ATM. In some cases, this will develop

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into a standard kidnapping, with further ransom demanded of the family or employer. In other cases, the victim is held overnight to get withdrawal limit.

Virtual Kidnapping: - A virtual kidnapping is more a scam than an actual kidnapping. The perpetrators will wait until their target is unreachable (visiting an area with no cellular coverage for example), then will contact the targets family or company, claiming they have kidnapped the target eventually returns unaware that anything untoward has occurred. Due to the need for haste the ransoms demanded are generally relatively modest. Another common technique is to call the target pretending to be a cellular phone company representative and ask them to turn off their phone for a short while for, a technical reason, during which the virtual kidnapping is conducted. Thus far virtual kidnappings are most common in America, especially Argentina, Brazil, Columbia and Mexico.

Political Kidnapping: - A kidnapping conducted to extort political concessions from government or security forces. As monetary ransom is no longer enough, it is more difficult to negotiate kidnap victim's freedom as in many cases the political concessions or demands cannot be met by the involved governments, putting the victim's life at greater risk (Dangiwa, 2019).

Bride Kidnapping: - A form of forced marriage in which the groom to be kidnaps his bride. In many cases the would-be couple has never met until the day of the kidnapping. This way of marriage is practiced in the Caucasus region, central Asia, and some nations in Africa. In many cases bride is raped in order to convince her to stay with her husband, as in many traditional cultures the loss of virginity is harshly judged. In some cultures, a bride price is customary, so the kidnapper may contact his victim's family to demand compensation (Dangiwa 2019).

Theoretical Perspectives to Kidnapping

Kidnapping can be seen as false imprisonment in the sense that it involves the illegal confinement of individuals against his or her own will by other individuals in such a way as to violate the confined individual's right to be free from the restraint of movement. This involves taking away of person against the person's will usually to hold the person in false imprisonment or confinement without legal authority. This is often done for ransom or in furtherance of another crime. No one is free from being kidnapped. In Nigeria kidnapers are everywhere targeting both foreigners and non-foreigners alike with little or no resistance from our law enforcement agents. Nigeria security system has been weakened in the face of this confrontation a little has been done to find the socio- economic and underlining factors precipitating this crime.

Several theories have been put forward to explain kidnapping within the Nigerian context. Accordingly, the "economic theory" views kidnapping from economic concept of making ends to meet, (Nseabasi, 2009) has raised the idea that kidnapping is regulated by the laws of demand and supply and is a type of social action that involves the calculation on the most efficient means to the desired ends. Kidnapping is a social enterprise, "kidnappers are businessmen, they just happen to be on the illegal side of it, if you deprive them of the demand then there is not going to be any supply. This is the reason why perpetrators of this crime choose their victims based on their ability to cough out good money.

As kidnapping was first used as a weapon to fight economic and environmental justice in the Niger Delta, The economic motivation was intermittently used as a means to fund and sustain the fight. The beginning of 2007 saw the emergence of various other deviant groups by various names that hide under liberation struggle to commit economic crimes.

Causes of Kidnapping in Nigeria

1. **Unemployment:** - The high unemployment rate in many countries has forced citizens to find other ways to make money and some of those ways are illegal. Kidnapping a rich person can be a lucrative business. A cash – strapped unemployed person may believe that when he kidnaps someone who is rich, he may be able to become rich himself.
2. **Poverty:** - Any person who lives belows \$1.25 dollar a day is living below the poverty line. Poverty can propel people toward crime as a way to make ends meet. Sometimes, a person who is poor might believe that kidnapping or other illegal acts could provide the necessary money to start a new life.
3. **Illiteracy:** - Illiteracy is the inability to read and write. When people know how to read and writes, they can gain the skills they need in order to become educated, get a job and live a productive life. Literacy and education can also be an important foundation upon which to build a deeper understanding of moral judgement and decision. The kidnapping and bombing perpetrated by bandits, and Boko Haram in Nigeria, are caused by illiteracy, at least in part. The leaders of these groups feed their men false information which the men cannot disprove by reading outside sources. Boko Haram fighters engage in suicide bombings killings and kidnappings. They are told that if they die while carrying out their mission, they will inherit the kingdom.

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4. **Loss of Social Value:** - Looking at Nigeria today we have mortgaged our culture of respect, love for human lives, hard work, friendliness and receptiveness to strangers in exchange of the western culture and ostentations orientation. This have given birth to the modern and social evil destroying the core value of our society, which is attributed to the rising crimes in different regions to the celebration of fraudsters by leader (Ahmed, 2015).
5. **Greed:** Some people are not contented with what they have and wish they could buy more and more things, whether its fancy clothes, cars, houses, or Jewelry. This kind of persons may turn to crime to make more money. A wicked business man can kidnap his business rival for a large ransom to become richer.
6. **Politics:** - Corrupt politicians may arrange for the kidnapping of their opponents, sometimes they do this so that their opponents will make concessions or change their votes on the issues.
7. **Corruption:** - A society where corruption is rife is likely to experience a high-level kidnapping. The truth is that if a government is corrupt and embezzling public funds, citizens may react by kidnapping those corrupt politicians or their families in attempt to recoup some of the stolen money, (Ahmed, 2015)

Effects or Consequences of Kidnapping in Nigeria

For the victims, there are many negative consequences of kidnapping, they include: -

1. **Psychological Trauma:** - The negative psychological effect of being abducted are huge, especially for a child. Depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress syndrome (PTSD) may last a life time.
2. **Fear and back of Trust:** - in a society where the incidence of kidnapping is high fear limit people lives and actions. They will always more with caution as they do not know who might be the next target. The rich surround themselves with security guards because of their fear of getting kidnapped.
3. **Socio-economic effects or Consequences:** - This include financial gain, some degree of panic, tension, feeling of insecurity and break of citizen's confidence in the government and the political leadership of the country. In some case kidnapping for reasons of revenge, punishment and/or sexual exploitation has social consequences on the health and social relation of the victims, since it can lead to injuries, death of love one's loss, of money or properties and also breaks the societal linkages that leads to societal unrest, as societal members lose confidence on social harmony.
4. **Political Consequence:** - Political consequences of kidnapping include the government spending a lot of time and money in crime combat ensuring its citizens of their safety of their lives and properties. This also hampers and hinders the image of the country in the international domain, as it scares foreigners from investing and this has a lot of consequence on the socio- economic development of the country (Ahmed 2015).

Current Efforts/Measures undertaken by Government to Curb Kidnapping and other Social Crimes in Nigeria

One of the measures taken by government to check kidnapping and other social crime include various joint security operations comprising in military and para- military agencies such as operation sting, Hadin Kai Hadarin Daji, Harbin Kunama, Ayam Kpatuma among others. The mounting of road blocks, markets ban and suspension are also part of military measures to stem the tides of kidnapping and other social crime across the country. Government and other well-meaning Nigerians have also taken steps in mitigating kidnapping by providing palliatives and social safety nets to the youths and other less privileged individuals, like job creation, youth empowerment social investment programs among others are also parts of the measures to alleviate poverty and reduce social crimes like kidnapping in the country. However, the federal government, as part if its measures has instituted amnesty and rehabilitation program to alleviate the suffering of repentant kidnapppers, Bako Haram, bandits and the Niger Delta militants (Kankia, 2016). In spite of the above measure taken by government and other critical stakeholders, the rate of kidnapping and other social crime continues to grow exponentially across the length and breadth of all geo-political zones in the country. Consequently, the need to reinvest a proactive and human friendly approach such as inclusiveness of all in its programs peace and security education to tackle the scourge becomes imperative.

Implications of Kidnapping on Nigeria's National Security

Nigeria is a state under perpetual internal security threat from various ethno- religious militias or political insurgents. From a broader perspective, the threat has social economic, political and environmental dimensions. Each of these dimension's singly and conjointly, greatly affects the nations' stability and well- being. Threats to national security can be said to range from the menace of separatist demands, militancy, terrorism, kidnapping, armed robbery and a host of other crimes which has negatively affected the security situation of the society, Oli, (2017) kidnapping has over time become endemic in Nigerian

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society especially in the Niger Delta region, and now affecting almost all north-western states and other parts of the country. It is fast becoming a lucrative alternative to armed robbery and other related offences. The gravity of kidnapping is so intense that it has virtually affected most persons in our society and has grossly undermined the security of the country. Nigerians and non-Nigerians residing in the country live in fear as regards who will be the next kidnap victim since kidnappers' spare no one as far as their motives are actualised. Over the last few years, the wealthy and other income earners have been picked up by kidnappers who only free their victims after payment of ransom. The incident of kidnapping has affected Nigeria's image as a nation abroad. It has also affected Nigeria's attempts to develop a viable tourism industry as visitors are regularly warned by their countries to be wary of coming to Nigeria. Many would-be investors have also stayed away for fears of being kidnapped, (Oli, 2017).

Conclusion

The menace of kidnapping, especially for ransom collection is fast gaining momentum in Nigeria. This calls for concern for both the security agencies and the general public in curbing the prevalence of the phenomenon; kidnapping is assumed to be business practice for criminals, who are in kidnapping act for ransom. This has remained one of the greatest drawbacks to investment in Nigeria. Nowadays social vices in the form of armed robbery, murder, assassination and recently kidnapping have attained a frightening level in terms of development in the country.

Recommendations

1. The government should provide employment opportunities and vocational training program to adequately equip people especially the youth with appropriate skills for entrepreneurship, so that they can have something because an idle mind is the devil's workshop.
2. The government should ensure a fair and better harnessed equitable distribution in resources of the country in order to promote national unity
3. The general population should encourage complete re-orientation away from get rich quick mind-set of the people that wealth acquired should be from a good source, thereby discouraging corruption
4. Appropriate sanction or penalty should be drafted in the constitution to curtail the menace of kidnapping in the country. Thereby culprits should be apprehended and punished accordingly in order to serve as deterrent to others.
5. Telecommunication companies should assist in tracking and determining the location of kidnappers and other criminals by monitoring calls made by the kidnappers to the victims and their families.
6. The use of armed youth groups and thugs by politicians should be totally discouraged and adequate measures should be taken to stop the youths of these groups by the security agencies.
7. Security agencies should strive hard to restore the public trust and confidence so that they can provide them with adequate information, through community policing. All the security agencies should be committed in serving the people at all cost.

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Effects of ASEI-PDSI Approach on Self-Efficacy in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Ilorin Educational Zone, Kwara State

Muhammed, Ashiat Bolanle Ph.D.

Email: bolaashiat@gmail.com

Tel: +2348034676566

Department of Science Education, University of Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract

Studies have consistently reported that students' self-efficacy is congruent to their achievement in chemistry, and that innovative instructional approaches promote self-efficacy. The Activity, Student-centered, Experiment, Improvisation-Plan, Do, See, improve (ASEI-PDSI) approach is a pedagogical model for strengthening mathematics and science education in Nigeria and thought to promote high self-efficacy among students. Hence, this study investigated the effects of ASEI-PDSI approach on Senior School students' self-efficacy in chemistry. The study adopted a quasi-experimental, non-randomized, pretest, posttest, control group design. The population was all the 40,379 Senior School students offering chemistry in Ilorin, Nigeria during the 2021/2022 academic session, while the target population was 13,460 Senior School I (SSI) students offering chemistry. The sample comprised 292 SSI (138 males and 154 females) students from four randomly selected co-educational schools in Ilorin, Nigeria. The ASEI-Instructional Package (ASEI-IP) was the stimulus instrument while the Chemistry Self-efficacy Scale (CSES) was the test instruments. The reliability of CSES was found to be 0.78. The data gathered were analysed using Analysis of Covariance and t-test statistics. The finding of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach (experimental) and those not exposed (control). The study concluded that ASEI-PDSI approach promote self-efficacy among students and ASEI-PDSI approach should be adopted by teachers to teach chemistry.

Keywords: ASEI-PDSI, Chemistry, Senior School Students, SMASE, Self-efficacy

Introduction

The Nigerian government through the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) saw the need to put innovations in education to practice. Thus, adopted the Strengthening Mathematics and Science Education (SMASE) in-service training and encouraged teachers to teach science and mathematics with ASEI-PDSI approach. The ASEI is an acronym for Activity, Student-centered, Experiment and Improvisation, an inherent strategy that promotes student-centered pedagogy among teachers while PDSI stands for Plan, Do, See, and improve that encourages culture of teachers' continuous improvement (Mwelese & Atwoto, 2014). The SMASE Nigeria project provides a forum for mathematics, biology, chemistry, and physics teachers across the country to gain new ideas, revise their knowledge on content matter, pedagogical issues and resource utilization through the ASEI-PDSI. The principle of ASEI-PDSI approach serves as a foundation upon which teachers can build a substantive and sustainable change in classroom practices with ultimate goal of enhancing the quality of teaching and learning of science and mathematics (SMASE, 2010). Thus, the ASEI-PDSI focused on student-centered, self-discovery learning with little or no facilitation, and reflective thinking.

Studies have consistently reported significant improvement in achievement when students are exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach (Kaman, Wilson, & Thinguri, 2014; Mwelese & Awoto, 2014; Kiige & Atina, 2016; Adamu, 2017; Protus et al., 2020). Besides these cognitive benefits, the students' affective domain should not be undermined. Although, improving students' achievement remains the focus of researches in science education, academic success encompasses enhanced achievement and positive psychological conditions. Affective factors such as self-efficacy, attitude, efforts, motivation, and anxiety are important outcomes of learning that also require fierce consideration. Of all these factors, self-efficacy is recognized as the most crucial affect-based learning outcomes (Huang, 2022).

Bandura, (1997) in Karin (2023) viewed Self-efficacy, as the confidence people have in their abilities to excel in a given task. Any individual that possesses a reasonable degree of self-efficacy is likely to attempt challenging task, and exert more effort while performing the task. Thus, when he/she succeeds, he/she credits his/her abilities (Karin, 2023). Self-efficacy, like achievement, should also be viewed as an outcome rather than influence since literature is replete with evidence that individuals' beliefs about their capacities is closely related to their achievement (Fernando, Lawra & Amparo, 2017). That is, the thought that people hold about themselves are double edged sword, they either enhance or hinder their progress (Koura &

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Al-Hebaishi, 2014). Similarly, Bandura, (1997) in Karin (2023) posited that there are assumptions that four factors are responsible for self-efficacy, which are: verbal persuasion; secondary experience; enactive mastery experience; and physiological and emotional states (Bandura, 1997). These factors contribute to self-esteem. Thus, self-efficacy may predict intellectual achievement better than skills alone. Also, past achievement raises self-efficacy, and students' interpretation of past successes and failures may be responsible for subsequent success (Ferrell & Barbera, 2015). Hence, self-efficacy predicts future achievement better than past performance.

Undoubtedly, gender as an important factor interacting with students' self-efficacy cannot be overlooked, especially with increasing emphasis on how to boost man power for technological development as well as increasing the population of females in the field of science and technology. The issue of gender differences in researches in science education is inconclusive. For instance, Louis and Mistele (2012); Kiran and Sungur (2012) reported no significant gender difference in students' self-efficacy while Huang (2013), Namaziandost and Cakmak (2020) noted that female had higher self-efficacy than their male counterparts in science subjects. There is no doubt that the knowledge of chemistry is germane to national and technological advancement. However, its teaching/learning is confronted with challenges of students' under-achievement and several affective factors, low self-efficacy inclusive. Factors, such as inappropriate teaching methods, poor classroom organization by teachers, lack of motivation and so on may be responsible for these. Although, studies have consistently reported that students' self-efficacy is intertwined with achievement in science with considerable evidence available to support direct effects of self-efficacy on science achievement (Kapucu, 2017; Davila-Acedo et al, 2022), in the past, little effort, if not any has been done in answering the question, "what can be done to promote self-efficacy among students"? However, in recent times, efforts are being made by researchers in science education to promote self-efficacy by advocating for use of innovative instructional strategies. This is evident in the studies of Rachmah, 2017; Davila-Acedo et al, 2022; Gungor et al, 2022; Huang, 2022 that explored the effects of jigsaw cooperative learning; active learning methodology; virtual reality; head-mounted display virtual reality respectively on students' self-efficacy. These studies reported significant improvement in students' self-efficacy and thus, enhanced achievement.

Having established that students' self-efficacy is congruent to their achievement, and that innovative instructional strategies promote self-efficacy, the ASEI-PDSI approach could also be used to promote students' self-efficacy. Studies on ASEI-PDSI approach have always focused on promoting students' and teachers' positive attitudinal change towards teaching and learning of science; and ultimately, improving students' achievement in science and mathematics (Ambasa et al., 2019; Kiige & Atina, 2016; Ayeigo et al., 2015; Barasa, 2015). In essence, examining the effects of ASEI-PDSI approach on self-efficacy should also be explored since the overall goal is to enhance achievement.

It is therefore, a focus in this study to contribute to literature by exploring the influence of gender on students' self-efficacy in chemistry. The overall aim of this research was to examine the effects of ASEI-PDSI instructional approach on senior school students' self-efficacy in chemistry.

Objectives of the study

This study examined the effects of the use of ASEI-PDSI approach on students' self-efficacy in chemistry in Ilorin, Nigeria. Specifically, the study found out:

1. the difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI instructional strategy and those not exposed to ASEI-PDSI instructional strategy; and
2. the difference in the self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Research Questions

To guide the present study, the following research questions were raised to address the objectives of the research:

1. What is the effect of ASEI-PDSI approach on students' self-efficacy in chemistry?
2. What is the difference in self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach based on gender?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance in this study

1. There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI and those not exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.
2. There is no significant difference in the self- efficacy of male and female students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

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Methodology

The study adopted 2 x 2 quasi-experimental research design involving pretest, posttest, non-randomized control groups. The first 2 represents the experimental and the control groups; the next 2 represents the students' gender, also at two levels of male and female. Also, in this study, intact classes of the students were involved so as to avoid distortion of the regular school program and to control for selection bias. The experimental and control groups were exposed to pre-self-efficacy test and the corresponding post-self-efficacy test. The population was all the 40,379 Senior School students offering chemistry in Ilorin, Nigeria during the 2021/2022 academic session; while the target population was all first year Senior School students (SSI) offering chemistry in Ilorin. The choice of SSI as the target population was based on the fact that SSI is the introductory class to chemistry as a subject, as such, it is essential to advocate for high self-efficacy among the students at this early stage. As at the time of the study, there were seventy-eight (78) public Senior Schools in Ilorin, Nigeria. Out of these 78 schools, seven (7) schools are not co-educational, thus, they were exempted from the study. Four (4) schools with qualified chemistry teachers which have been presenting candidates for Senior School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) for at least ten years, and not situated close to one another were selected from the remaining 71 schools in Ilorin using simple random sampling technique. The sampled schools were randomized into experimental and control groups and their intact classes were involved in this study with a total sample size of 292 students (138 males and 154 females).

Two instruments were used in gathering data in this study: the ASEI Instructional Package (ASEI-IP); the Chemistry Self-Efficacy Scale, (CSES). The ASEI Instructional Package (ASEI-IP) was a stimulus instrument that is made up ASEI activity sheet, the ASEI lesson plan, ASEI interaction plan, and ASEI chalkboard plan for the experimental group. The ASEI activity sheet provided the students with step-by-step procedures to employ during instruction; while the ASEI lesson plan is a plan on acids, bases and salts. The content of acids, bases and salts was considered appropriate because of its interwoven link with everyday phenomena and other chemistry concepts. Also, acid-base chemistry is a fundamental concept in chemistry that covers primary, secondary, pre-service education and postgraduate education. The ASEI lesson plan showed the intended lesson objectives, procedures in achieving the stated objectives through relevant class activities, linkage of the prior knowledge to the concept of acids, bases and salts, linkage of activities to acids, bases and salts through posing key questions, and content organization from simple to complex. The ASEI interaction plan contained the types of questions to be asked by the teacher, the expected responses from the students and the questioning techniques at each stage of the lesson. The ASEI chalkboard plan showed the logical flow of the lesson, corresponding to each step of the lesson plan.

The Chemistry Self-Efficacy Scale, (CSES) consisted ten (10) statements on students perceived self-efficacy on acids, bases and salts with responses on a 4-point Likert ranging from strongly agree (4) to strongly disagree (1). The scores from the CSES ranged from the lowest, 10 (25%) to the highest, 40 (100%) and any score below 62.5% were considered to possess low self-efficacy. The CSES was the modified version of the college chemistry self-efficacy scale (CCSES) of Uzuntiryaki and Aydin (2009). The CCSES was used to measure students' self-efficacy on chemistry as whole. However, the CSES in this study measured students perceived self-efficacy on acids, bases and salts only. Other modifications made include changing the response modes from very poorly, poorly, well, and very well to strongly disagree, disagree, agree and strongly agree respectively in the belief that the response modes better represent respondents' personal opinions. This change was also necessitated due to transformation of items in the CCSES from questions to statements. The instruments were given to two experts in Department of Science Education, University of Ilorin, Nigeria; two experienced Senior School chemistry teachers; a senior lecturer in the Department of Chemistry, University of Ilorin for both face and content validity. This ensured that these instruments were appropriate and the items measured what they were designed to measure. Also, in order to ascertain the internal consistency, the CSES was trial tested. A test-retest reliability method was employed involving 20 non-participating SSI students in Ilorin with an interval of two weeks between the first and the second test. The resulting data were analyzed using Cronbach's alpha. The reliability coefficients of CSES was found to be 0.78. Hence, the CSES was adjudged to be reliable.

A letter of introduction was presented to the principals of the sampled schools. This was to seek their permissions and consents to involve their schools, teachers and allow their students to take part in the study. The researcher interacted with the chemistry teachers, enlightened and acquainted them with the nature of the study and thus, formally sought their consents through the informed consent forms, to serve as research assistants for this study. Also, the researcher met with the students and apprised them of the significance and benefits of the study to their academic pursuits. Similarly, the researcher affirmed and disclosed to the students that: the data obtained from the study is strictly for research purpose; their identity would be treated with utmost confidentiality; the study would not be forced on them; and they may withdraw their participation at any stage of the study. Hence, the consents of the students and that of their parents were sought through filling of the informed

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consent forms. The researcher revisited the sampled schools to retrieve the informed consent forms and ascertained the participation status of the subjects of the study. The research assistants for the experimental group received a special training on how to use ASEI-IP and were provided with training manual for reference purpose. The experimental group was taught with ASEI-IP while the control group was taught without using ASEI-IP. The CSES was administered as pre-treatment self-efficacy test to both groups to measure their self-efficacy prior to the treatment. Six periods of forty minutes lesson were used in each of the schools for the actual treatments. The control group was taught using the conventional method of teaching. However, the students in the experimental group worked cooperatively in a group of seven, where each member of a group had specific task assigned and interacted with the materials provided, and the ASEI-activity sheet served as guide to reaching the lesson objectives. The researcher and the research assistants only facilitated the learning process in this group. Thereafter, the CSES was administered post self-efficacy test after the treatment.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Subjects

Group		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Experimental	F	83	70	153
	%	54.2	45.8	100
Control	F	55	84	139
	%	39.6	60.4	100
Total	F	138	154	292
	%	47.3	52.7	100

As shown in Table 1, there are 292 valid subjects with total of 138 male and 154 female participants in both groups. The experimental group exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach comprised 153 (83 males, 70 females) subjects while control group that was not exposed to ASEI-PDSI comprised 139 (55 males, 84 females) subjects.

Research Question 1:

What is the effect of ASEI-PDSI approach on students' self-efficacy in chemistry?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Self-Efficacy Test by Groups

Groups	N	Tests	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Control	139	Pre-test	26.37	6.22	Fair
		Posttest	25.79	5.92	Fair
Experimental	153	Pre-test	26.23	4.64	Fair
		Posttest	28.68	3.82	Better

Table 2 shows the arithmetic mean of students' posttest scores in the control and experimental groups as $\bar{x}=25.79$ and 28.73 respectively. Hence, a difference of 2.94 in the favour of experimental group was observed. Hence, there was difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach and those not. Consequently, a one-way between-groups analysis of covariance was conducted to find out if the difference was statistically significant using the pre-test as covariate. Preliminary checks were conducted to ensure that there was no violation of assumptions of normality, linearity, homogeneity of variances and reliable measurement of the covariate.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach based on gender?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students in Post-attitude Test

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Male	83	26.88	4.07	1.14
Female	70	24.77	3.77	1.35

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Table 3 shows the arithmetic mean of \bar{x} = 26.88 and 24.77 in the post self-efficacy test for male and female students in the experimental group respectively after the intervention. A mean difference of 2.11 was noted. Hence, there was difference in the chemistry self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI and those not exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance for Difference between Group Means in Self-Efficacy Test

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	789.86 ^a	2	394.93	18.39	.00	.21
Intercept	1768.83	1	1768.83	82.39	.00	.38
Pre-Self-efficacy	493.61	1	493.61	22.99	.00	.15
Group	328.75	1	328.75	15.31	.00	.10
Error	2919.94	289	21.47			
Total	108197.00	292				
Corrected Total	3709.799	291				

6. R Squared = .213 (Adjusted R Squared = .201)

Table 5: Bonferroni Post-Hoc Test on Students' Self-Efficacy between Groups

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Control	Experimental	-3.097*	.79	.00	-4.66	-1.53
Experimental	Control	3.097*	.79	.00	1.53	4.66

The result of ANCOVA in Table 4 reveals a statistically significant difference at $p < .05$ alpha level in self-efficacy scores for the experimental and control ($F_{(1,289)} = 15.32, p = .00$, partial eta squared = .10). Post hoc comparisons using Bonferroni in Table 4 indicated a Mean score for the experimental group ($\bar{x} = 3.09, p = .00$) was significantly different from control with Mean score ($\bar{x} = 0.79, p = .00$).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the self- efficacy of male and female students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach.

Table 6: The t-test Analysis for Difference between Male and Female Students' Mean Scores in Post Self-efficacy Test

	Levene's test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Mean						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
Equal variances assumed	.34	.56	2.70	151	.01	2.94	1.76	-1.63	5.37

Consequently, in Table 6, an independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the self-efficacy of male and female students in the treatment group reveals a statistically significant difference in scores for males ($\bar{x} = 26.88, SD = 4.07$) and females ($\bar{x} = 24.77, SD = 3.77, t_{(151)} = 2.70, p = .01$, two-tailed).

Discussion of Findings

This study explored the effects of using ASEI-PDSI approach to promote high self-efficacy among senior school students in chemistry. Hence, the main effect of ASEI-PDSI and influence of gender on chemistry self-efficacy were examined. The outcome of this study revealed that a significant difference existed in the self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach (experimental) and those not exposed (control), in the positive direction of the experimental group. This implies that the experimental group possessed high self-efficacy in chemistry than their control group counterparts. Perhaps, this could be because the confidence in handling materials was built as a result of sharing resources and ideas, each individual having a specific task assigned and interdependence on one another. This finding agrees statistically with the findings of Davila-Acedo et al. (2022); Gungor et al. (2022); Fitriyana, Niyarsi and Sugiyarto (2018); Rachmah (2017) that better mode of instruction could enhance students' self-efficacy. Conversely, the finding is not consistent with that of Huang, 2022, Mari and Gumel (2015); Abdelraheem (2014). These researchers also believed that when students are engaged in activities, self-efficacy is enhanced which could result in better achievement. Therefore, ASEI-PDSI approach may be used to enhance self-efficacy in chemistry.

The finding on influence of gender on self-efficacy of students exposed to ASEI-PDSI approach suggested a significant difference in self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to the treatment, which was in favour of the males. This implies that the male students possessed high self-efficacy than their female counterparts. The high self-efficacy of the male students could be as a result of the fact that, in most of the groups, the male students assumed the leadership role, were always the first to carry out any activity that involves manipulation of materials and were more favourably disposed to the activities. This finding is coherent statistically with the findings of Ahmad (2012); Fallan and Opstad (2016) that reported that male students possessed high self-efficacy in chemistry than their female counterparts. However, the findings of Sawari and Mansor (2013); Tenaw (2013) contrast the finding of this study as these researchers reported no significant difference in self-efficacy of male and female students. Also, Huang (2013), Namaziandost and Cakmak (2020) reported that female had higher self-efficacy than their male counterparts in science subjects

Conclusion

This article explored the effects of ASEI-PDSI approach on chemistry self-efficacy of senior school students. The result showed that ASEI-PDSI significantly enhanced students' self-efficacy in chemistry. That is, when ASEI-PDSI approach is used to teach chemistry, the students' self-efficacy is magnified. Also, male students possessed high self-efficacy than their female counterparts in ASEI-PDSI classroom. To this end, the following recommendations among others were made: ASEI-PDSI approach should be adopted by teachers to teach chemistry; self-efficacy of students should be monitored periodically to avoid plummet in students' self-efficacy; teachers should always pay attention to the need to promote students' self-efficacy when scheduling their teaching activities taking into consideration the gender differences; the teachers should also be gender conscious when assigning roles to the students during class activities.

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Ecotourism and Economic Development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria

Usang, Nkanu Onnoghen¹

Email: usangonnoghen@gmail.com,
Tel: +2348171953333

Unimtiang, Unimke Sylvanus²

Email: unimkefelaa@gmail.com,
Tel: +2347034477327

Ogban, Ogban Nkanu²

Email: ogbanogbannkanu@gmail.com,
+2348064358896

Michael Obi Odey Ph.D²

Email: odeyobi@yahoo.com,

Tel: +2348035280651

Igwe, Thankgod Abeng³

Email: igwethankgod62@gmail.com,
Tel: +2348063355660

Sam, Ime Edet¹

Email: imesam12@yahoo.com,
Tel: +2348063987888

Oham, Sunday Bassey¹

Email: bassevoham@gmail.com,

¹Department of Environmental Education, Faculty of Arts and Social Science Education, University of Calabar

²Department of Social Science Education, Faculty of Arts and Social Science Education, University of Calabar

³Department of vocational Education, Faculty of Vocational and Science Education, University of Calabar

Abstract

The aim of the study was to examine ecotourism and the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. A review of related literature was carried out based on the variable of this study. The survey research design was considered useful for the study. The research adopted multiple sampling approaches. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 232 subjects used as sample in each ward in the Local Government Area. A twenty-item modified four (4) points Likert scale questionnaire titled Ecotourism and Economic Development of Calabar Municipal Questionnaire (EEDCMQ) was the instrument used for gathering data for the study. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study, Pearson's product moment correlation statistical tools were used for data analysis. The hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 alpha level. The results from data analysis and hypothesis testing indicated that there is a significant relationship between ecotourism and the economic development in the study area. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the state government should ensure investment in basic infrastructure such as roads, better airports facilities and good transport system.

Keyword: Ecotourism, tourism, Calabar Municipal, Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Tourism has always been regarded as a means of economic modernization but has not been seriously considered as a means of social and cultural modernization, the concept of socioeconomic modernization emphasize improvement in various indicators, including improvement in living conditions and the quality of life and wellbeing of the population. Ezenagu (2013) posited that tourism is the sector with the biggest employer of labour in Nigeria as it is generating employment for millions of people and its effect rubs on every aspect of people from taxi drivers to Bank managers (Tunde, 2012) in 2002 the tourism industry generated an estimated 199 million jobs - one in every 13 jobs worldwide. Nigeria as at 2011, the Travel and Tourism industry was forecast to directly generate a total of 897, 500 jobs in 2012, and that happens to comprises of 1.4 % of total employment in Nigeria. Tourism generates finance for infrastructure development and generally increases citizen's welfare. It has also influenced they Nigerian aviation industry with the coming in of capital flights associated with oversea trip and an expansion of the same industry which had Nigerian Airways for a monopoly between the periods of 1985 to 1992. The increase is to the effect that as from 1992 there had been an influx of over 25 different carriers in the country. Tourist upon visitation, patronize local folk art such as straw baskets, hats, wooden carvings, ornaments, trinket and help improve the living standards of host areas (Onnoghen, Unimtiang, Ogban, Ogbaji, Iyam & Oham, 2023). Tourism comes with a multiplier effect that rubs on other sectors of Nigeria's economy, namely: financial institutions, hospitals, transport, agriculture, environment and aviation (Ezenagu, 2013). Tourism is the main foreign exchange earner and the main source of job creation in the country. And so, income and prices are generally linked to the variables of demand for tourism.

Ecotourism is the management of tourism and conservation of nature in a way so as to maintain a fine balance between the requirements of tourism and ecology on the one hand and the needs of local communities for new job skills, income generating employment and better status for women. Ecotourism has become a need for everyone who wants to refresh from the routine fast city life. Ecotourism provides many interesting tours to the heart of Mother Nature. Ecotourism focuses on socially responsible travel, personal growth and environmental sustainability. Ecotourism typically involves travel to destinations where flora, fauna and cultural heritage are the primary attractions. Ecotourism is intended to offer tourists an insight into the impact of human beings on the environment and to foster a greater appreciation of our natural habitats (Kumar, 2007).

Calabar Municipal has the potentials to become one of the leading tourist destinations due to her rich cultural heritage, tourism sites, cuisines, attractions etc. and traces of the different types of tourism being found in it, has stimulated the development of a variety of allied infrastructure and facilities such as Calabar International Convention Centre (CICC), National Museum, Calabar, sport stadium, airport and more. Owing all the above listed tourism locations and facilities, one wonders if tourism contributes to the economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River state. Tourism is the number one employer of labor in the world and jobs created by tourism spreads across the economy in areas of construction, telecommunications, retail and manufacturing, thus, creating jobs in large number for young people, women, and minorities whether in small or medium size companies (Akpan & Obang, 2012).

The Malthusian theory was propounded by Thomas Robert Malthus in the year 1798. Malthus contends that the process of economic development is not automatic. Rather conscious, deliberate efforts are needed to bring it about. For instance, Malthus explains that mere increase in population cannot by itself lead to economic development unless there is increase in effective demand. He rejects Say's Law which says supply creates its own demand and that savings are automatically invested and constitutes a demand for capital goods. Malthus' important contribution shows that savings in the sense of not consuming is a mere negative act and instead of creating more demand it will lead to a decline in effective demand. Only savings which are furnished by increased gains and are invested create an effective demand. Thus, according to him, abstinence on the part of capitalists, far from accelerating economic growth, will in itself retard it. Hence, Malthus brings out an important fact expand that in advanced economy consumption, saving and investment all should simultaneously. Malthus attaches great importance to the accumulation of capital for economic development. He regards capital as indispensable to development. According to him, no permanent and continued increase of wealth can take place without a continued increase of capital. Besides, Malthus underlined the importance of foreign trade for speeding up economic development. Foreign trade provides incentives for investing, since it leads to the extension of the market for the goods produced and for greater division of labour resulting in increased output.

Tourism also helps economic activities to grow in a given country. Most people go into other countries for business tourism and they invest in such countries. The more tourists are found in a country, the more economic activities that take place. The population of foreign people in a country who depend on the country's resources can enhance economic development. There is another important fact brought out by Malthusian analysis of economic growth, namely, the structured

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change that takes place in the process of economic development i.e., a decline in the relative importance of agriculture as the economy moves forward. We know that economic development in developing countries is regarded as synonymous with the development of industries. Malthus' contribution to economic growth contains several elements that are relevant to the developing economies. His emphasis on production and distribution, capital accumulation and the creation of congenial non-economic factors is as valid today as was in his time.

The implication of the theory to this study is that, tourism increases the number of people in a given state. Most of these tourists have high demand for local resources. When local resources are highly demanded, demand becomes effective. Effective demand increases economic development and also increases investment opportunities. As tourists are attracted to tourist destinations, they contribute to increase in population of such destination and hence raise the effective demand of goods and services in such areas. The producers of such goods and services demanded by tourists in a bid to maximize profit will demand for more labour to increase in supply and this consequently leads to employment generation.

Ecotourism is a form of tourism which embraces tourism in the biophysical environment in natural areas. It is also a travel to natural areas, conserving the environment and improving the wellbeing of the local people. It incorporates ecologically sustainable activities, conservation supporting measures and involvement of local communities. Ecotourism is the management of tourism and conservation of nature in a way so as to maintain a fine balance between the requirements of tourism and ecology on the one hand and the needs of local communities for new job skills, income generating employment and better status for women. Ecotourism has become a need for everyone who wants to refresh from the routine fast city life. Ecotourism provides many interesting tours to the heart of Mother Nature. Ecotourism focuses on socially responsible travel, personal growth and environmental sustainability. Ecotourism typically involves travel to destinations where flora, fauna and cultural heritage are the primary attractions. Ecotourism is intended to offer tourists an insight into the impact of human beings on the environment and to foster a greater appreciation of our natural habitats. Ecotourism is an amalgamation of two separate concepts; ecology and tourism, but viewed jointly. The coinage assumes great significance both for ecological conservation and development of tourism. Tourism is now becoming a major socioeconomic activity, which contributes to the country and its economy. He also points out Nigeria potentials to develop as a major tourism attraction in the country (Kreg, 2010). Kreg (2010) in his paper titled ecotourism and other services derived from forests in the Asia-Pacific region made an attempt to prove that the growth rate for ecotourism will be higher than tourism generally. Tourism makes a substantial contribution to the region's economy.

Ecotourism in region and global has grown faster than tourism generally, and this probably will continue over the next several years. Ecotourism can capture biodiversity values and provide incentives for conservation and integrated conservation and development project include an ecotourism component. One is that ecotourism business can achieve financial viability (Kreg, 2010). Sangpikul (2017) conducted a study titled ecotourism impacts on the economy, society and environment of Thailand. The study examined how ecotourism tour operators and their guided tours contribute to the development of economic, social and environmental dimensions at ecotourism sites and local communities. Data for the study were collected from ecotourism tour operators through the interview and observation methods, and the contents were analyzed in accordance with ecotourism concepts and principles. The study revealed that the practices of tour operators and their guided tours contributed economic, social, and environmental benefits to the ecotourism destinations and local communities. Interestingly, the study found that the length (duration) and types of guided tours had different contributions and impacts on the three dimensions of sustainability. In particular, guided tours with a local visit contribute greater economic and social benefits to the local areas than tours without a local visit. Taylor, Hardner and Stewart (2009) similarly conducted a study aimed at examining Ecotourism and economic growth in the Galapagos. The study was an island economy-wide analysis. The study revisited and updated a 1999 economy-wide analysis predicting that increases in tourism would result in rapid economic as well as demographic growth on the Galapagos Islands. The study findings indicated that total income (that is, the gross domestic product) of the Galapagos increased by an estimated 78 per cent between 1999 and 2005, making the Galapagos economy among the fastest growing in the world.

Tourism continued to be far and away the major driver of economic growth. Nevertheless, population growth via new migration to the islands nearly erased the effect of economic growth on per-capita household income. These findings raise questions about the compatibility of ecotourism and conservation in this unique ecological setting. Gumede and Nzama (2019) also conducted a research on ecotourism as a mechanism for local economic development: the case of communities adjacent to the Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. The study was conducted at the Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve and surrounding communities (Murchison and Eshobeni). The population of the study comprised of the municipal officials, community tourism organization, Oribi Gorge Nature Reserves Management, community leaders, and households of the communities adjacent to the Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve. A sample of 384 respondents was drawn from the population using

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a convenience sampling technique. Exploratory mixed methods design was adopted by the study, which suggests that both qualitative and quantitative modes of research enquiry were used during the collection, analysis and interpretation of data. Survey questionnaires were used to collect the data through face-to-face mode of enquiry. Qualitative data were analyzed through content analysis, while quantitative data were analyzed through Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version. 24). The findings of the study demonstrate that ecotourism contributes to the local economic development of the study area through employment creation and capacity building.

The study of Onnoghen, Unimtiang, Ogban, Ogbaji, Iyam and Oham (2023) investigated medical tourism and the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. A review of related literature was carried out based on the variable of this study. The survey research design was considered useful for the study. The research adopted multiple sampling approaches. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 232 subjects used as sample in each ward in the Local Government Area. A twenty-item modified four (4) points Likert scale questionnaire titled Medical Tourism and Economic Development Questionnaire (MTEDQ) was the instruments used for gathering data for the study. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study, Pearson's product moment correlation statistical tools was used for data analysis. The hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 alpha level. The results from data analysis and hypothesis testing indicated that there is a significant relationship between religious tourism and the economic development in the study area. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the State government should ensure investment in basic infrastructure such as roads, better airports facilities and good transport system. Rajasenan, Manaloor and Abraham (2012) in a study sought to examine the socio-economic aspects of sustainable ecotourism development in Kerala. Data for the study was obtained from a primary survey by dividing the ecotourism destinations in Kerala into three zones, 230 from south zone, 220 from central zone and 200 from north zone with a total sample size of 650 based on the notion of community-based ecotourism initiatives of the state. The result of the study confirms that ecotourism has helped to enhance the livelihood of the marginalized community. With well-knit policies it is possible to tag ecotourism of Kerala as an important tourism destination in the global tourism map.

The literature reviewed indicates a great potential of the various types of tourism reviewed to the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State and Nigeria as a whole. It comes with economic benefits to host destinations, including increased income, taxes, employment, and economic diversification and regeneration. This is to be achieved through the appraisal of the tourism resources of the nation and the combination of both natural and human capacities to transform the industry into a job creating and foreign exchange earner that will meet the economic wellbeing of the nation at large. Tourism, as an economic activity, is being used to help support bolster an economy and regional development.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to assess how ecotourism relate to economic development in Calabar Municipal.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide this study;

There is no significant relationship between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the survey research design. It involves the collection of data to accurately and objectively describe existing phenomena. This design is employed because the study intends to gather information ready existing among the population under study. Moreover, adopting the survey helps the researcher to gather required data from the sampled respondents and generalize it to a large population. The area adopted for this study is Calabar Municipal of Cross River State. Calabar Municipal lies between latitude 04° 57' 06"North of the equator and longitude 08° 19' 30"East of the Greenwich Meridian. In the North, the Municipal is bounded by Odukpani Local Government Area in the North-East by the great Kwa River. Its Southern shores are bounded by the Calabar River and Calabar South Local Government Area. It has an area of 33 1.551 square kilometres. It also has ten wards. Two ethnic groups form the indigenous population. These are the Quas and the Efiks. However, because of its cosmopolitan status, there abound people from all parts of the state and Nigeria in the city. Calabar Municipal Government Area plays a dual role. Apart from being the capital city of Cross River State, it also plays its role as headquarters of the southern senatorial district. By virtue of its location along the water front, the Efiks embraced western culture. They carried on successful trade with early Europeans. Fishing is another occupation identified with them. The Quas on the other hand occupy the bulk of the hinterland of Calabar where farmers, hunters, traders and blacksmiths are found. Calabar Municipal climate can be described generally as tropical within the equatorial hot-wet climate of southern

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Nigeria which is characterized by heavy amount of rainfall because of the south west wind that blows from Atlantic Ocean. Two seasons dominate the area; the wet and dry seasons. The wet season commences from late April, peaks in July/August and declines gradually till December/January.

The study area is endowed with many tourist sites/attractions such as National museum, Hope Waddel Training Institute, U.J Esuene Sport Stadium, West African People Institute (WAPI), Nigeria Port Authority (NPA), Export Processing Zone (EPZ), Pandrillus (Drill Ranch), CERCOPAN, Calabar International Convention Centre (CICC), Tinapa Business Resort, Millennium Park/cenotaph, Garment Factory and Peace Park etc. The targeted populations for this research are adults living in Calabar Municipal of Cross River State. The researcher considered males and females above the ages of 18 years to participate in the research because of their ability to understand and their knowledge of current trends. Calabar Municipal has a total population of 371,022 people from 2019 population estimates.

The sampling procedure adopted for this study is the simple random sampling technique (SRST). Simple random sampling technique is a means by which researchers give members of his or her population equal and independent opportunity of being selected. The simple random sampling technique was used to select ten (10) streets from Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. This was done using the hat and draw method. Here, the names of the streets were written on papers and folded in paper balls and put in a container. The researcher blindly picked one ball at a time until the 10 streets for the research was completed. In selecting the respondents that would be used for the study, the proportional simple random sampling technique will be adopted to select 0.5% of respondents in each of the selected streets. Finally, the researcher will adopt the accidental sampling technique to administer her questionnaire to the respondents in the selected communities. Only those willing to participate in the study will be given the opportunity to do so. These techniques will be adopted to avoid possible bias. The sample of this study comprise of 242 respondents selected from 10 streets in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. They consist of both male and female residents in the sampled streets.

The instrument employed for data collection was a questionnaire titled, Ecotourism and Economic Development of Calabar Municipal Questionnaire (EEDCMQ) designed by the researcher with the help of the supervisor. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A was design to collect the respondent's demographic data such as sex and age, while section B comprises twenty (20) items designed to measure tourism and economic development of Calabar Municipal. The questionnaire was the main instrument used for data collection. The data used for this research was sourced from primary sources, The Primary data were gathered through the respondents from face to face administration of questionnaires. This is because questionnaire can be more easily quantified and analysed. The construction of the questionnaire succumbs to the rule of simplicity, clarity, precision and relevant so as to elicit the quantitative data it seek. The questionnaire contained close ended questions to aid the respondent in minimize the risk of misinterpretation and allow them to understand the question carefully in order to give the correct response the questionnaire administered. After collecting the questionnaire, scores will be assigned to each item according to the sections. The four likert scale will be employed in this study. The scale is as follows; Strongly Agree (SA) = 4; Agree = 3; Disagree (D) = 2; Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Results

The demographic data of participants of this study is presented in Tables 1 ad 2.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	117	50.4
Female	115	49.6
Total	232	100.0

The above Table 1 show that 117 respondents out of the 232-population sampled were male constituting 50.4% while 115 respondents were female which constitutes 49.6% making it a total of 100%.

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Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
18-29	68	29.3
30-39	92	39.7
40-49	40	17.2
50 and above	32	13.8
Total	232	100.0

The percentage distribution table above shows that, 68 respondents out of the sampled were between the ages of 18-29 years constitution 29.3%, 92 respondents were between the age range of 30-39 years making 39.7% of the sampled population. 40 respondents fall between the ages of 40-49 which constitutes 17.2% while 32 respondents were within the age range of 50 and above representing 13.8% of the total population.

Hypothesis Testing

There is significant relationship between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal LGA of Cross River State.

This hypothesis was tested using Pearson product moment correlation analysis. This is because, the independent and dependent variables were both measured continuously. The result of the analysis is as presented in table 3.

Table 3: Result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between Ecotourism and Economic Development in Calabar Municipal Local Government

Variables	N	X	S.D	r-value	Sig.
Ecotourism	232	16.55	1.757	.233**	.010
Economic development	232	15.11	1.363		

**correlation is significant at .01 level, df=230, critical r=.158.

The result presented in table 3 shows the correlation between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. It revealed a calculated r-value of .233 which is statistically greater than the critical r-value or .158 at .01 level of significance with 230 degrees of freedom. As a result of this, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was upheld. The implication of this is that ecotourism has a significant effect on economic development in Calabar municipal local government area of cross river state.

Discussion of Findings

The hypothesis states that ecotourism has no significant effect on economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State. This hypothesis was however rejected on the ground that the calculated r-value of .233 was found to be significantly greater than the critical r-value of .158. The implication of this result is that ecotourism has significant effect on economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State. The findings of this study is in tandem with a study by Sangpikul (2017) whose study on ecotourism pacts on the economy, society and environment of Thailand found a significant relationship between ecotourism and economic development. The study is also in agreement with a similar study by Taylor et al. (2009) who examined ecotourism and economic growth in the Galapagos. The study found ecotourism to be a major driver of economic growth. Gumedde and Nzama (2019) study on ecotourism as a mechanism for local economic development also agrees with the findings of the present study as it found that ecotourism contributes to the local economic development of the study area through employment creation and capacity building.

Conclusion

Following the results that emerged from the analysis of data collected for this study, the following conclusions were made: There is significant relationship between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion made thereof, the State Government should ensure investment in basic infrastructure such as roads, better airports facilities and good transport system.

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Attitude of Youth to Sales of Arms and Ammunition in Riverine Areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State

Iniobong, Monday Eduok

Email: ieduok@noun.edu.ng

Tel: +2348027391394

National Open University of Nigeria

Abstract

This study examines attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State. This study adopted the survey research design. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 150 youths in Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State. One instrument was used for data collection: Questionnaire on Sale of Arms and Ammunition Questionnaire ($r=0.78$). Data collected were analysed using percentage scores, mean and standard deviation. Findings of the study revealed a weighted mean of 2.56 which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50; this signifies a positive attitude to sales of arms and ammunition among youth in Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that government should provide job opportunities for the unemployed youths in the country. Security personnel should be more proactive in maintaining peace in the country. Youths should not be allowed to legalize the selling of arms and ammunition in the country. Anyone caught with unlawful possession of arms and ammunition should be arrested and charged to court. Community leaders should work with government in maintaining peace and they should not condone criminals or criminal acts in their domain.

Keywords: Arms, Ammunition, Nigerian Youths, Riverine Areas

Introduction

Youth varies from culture to culture and from society to society. In most societies in Nigeria, the progression from childhood to youth involves some systematic rites of passage. These rites have symbolic importance in that, simply by participating in them, an individual achieves a new status and position. Such new status gains validity through genuine community action and recognition. Globally, youth is described as the time in individual's life and this runs between and the end of childhood and the entry into the world of work (Onyekwusi & Effiong, 2002). However, youth all over the world are important part of the society in which they live. A disciplined, focus and law-abiding youth can create a bright future for any nation. Conversely, a lawless indulgent and violent youth is a greater threat to a nation's peace and security. According to the report of the Political Bureau (1997) in Abdullahi (2003), classified youths as those between six years to 30 years. This refers to the classification conforms to the formal education years, tampering with which may endanger the youth's life and subsequently the larger society. Therefore, youths are termed as the active category from which so much is expected to achieve the societal goals like economic prosperity, political stability, and social justice. The National Youth Development Policy (2001) defines youth as people aged 18-35 years. Youth occupy a prominent place in any society. Apart from being the owners and leaders of tomorrow, they outnumber the middle-aged and aged (Onyekpe, 2007). Onyekpe added that, besides numerical superiority, youth have energy and ideas that are society's great potentials.

Moreover, The National Youth Development Policy (2001) asserts that youths are the foundation of a society. Their energies, inventiveness, character and orientation define the pace of development and security of a nation. Through their creative talents and labour power a nation can make giant stride in economic development and socio-political attainments. In their dreams and hopes, a nation finds her motivation; on their energies, she builds her vitality and purpose, and because of their dreams and aspirations, the future of a nation is assured. World Health Organization (2007) define "young people" as people between the ages of 10 and 24. Youth participation in development projects helps build their confidence and their ability to express themselves, it helps them make their own decisions, it helps them grow up to be active citizens, it enhances their understanding of issues which affect their society. At a personal level participation can increase the youth knowledge and practical skills that come from real life problem solving. It can also strengthen their social interest and nurture long term commitment to self fulfilment. It enables the youth to think critically and actively challenge situations.

The statement above acknowledges the role of the youth in the peace, development and security of the nation. As the most active segment of any society; youth are the major determinants of peace and stability of a nation (Ozohu-Sulaiman, 2006). Peace is a state of tranquility which all human beings seek. No nation can record any meaningful feat of development

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without relative peace. Adedoya and Fakokunde (2010) revealed that for any reasonable progress to be made in human life, peace must prevail. The level of restiveness and violence prevailing at individual, family, communal, national and international levels made it a necessity to build a culture of peace. If culture is a total way of life of a people, it means a culture of peace must be cultivated. Youths according to Adedoyin (2003) and Torimiro (2008) are said to possess the following characteristics which includes greater physical strength, greater knowledge acquisition propensity, faster rate of learning, faster reaction time, innovative proneness, love for adventure and preference for boldness, minimal risk aversion, less fear of failure and less conversation. Youth status in society has been valued in various models. Checkoway and Gutierrez (2006) state that youth have been viewed as potential community assets for the last couple of decades, and are no longer viewed as a social problem. This is because young people are able to utilize their skills and make use of their rights to engage themselves in the development of their society (Checkoway, 2010; Head, 2011).

Furthermore, individual youth are able to create chances for personal development in terms of new skills and knowledge. The second is a communal benefit to society in an indirect way in which it is recognized as a social capital. This participation can contribute to and be reinforced by social development, organizational capacity, and positive changes in the community so that shared benefits can be dispersed to community members as a whole (Checkoway & Gutierrez, 2006). Therefore, the status of youth can be promoted through their social involvements. In the late 1990s the trade in major conventional weapons, though drastically reduced, still accounts for tens of billions of dollars annually. At the same time the proliferation of small arms and light weapons appears to have increased, as indicated below. This is taking place in an environment where even the loose discipline previously imposed by the US and Soviet Union on their allies and client States has largely disappeared. In today's world of internal conflicts and civil strife accountability is much more difficult to impose and is often non-existent. The availability of weapons is increasingly governed by the laws of supply and demand with little or no regard to the behaviour of recipients. In the current 'buyers' market' suppliers, whether States or companies, are notably reluctant to condition sales on the behaviour or purposes of belligerents.

For many years now, the global trade in major conventional weapons (such as tanks, fighter aircraft, naval ships and armored personnel carriers) has been documented by organizations such as the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI), the US Arms Control and Disarmament Agency, and more recently, the UN Register of Conventional Arms. The sale or transfer of these weapons in the 1970s and 1980s, both among NATO and Warsaw Pact members and from these alliances to developing countries, was relatively easy to track in terms of both trade flows and dollar amounts. Over time, the international community became increasingly concerned that the proliferation of major weapon systems was fueling regional arms races that could break out into open warfare (e.g., the Iran-Iraq war of the 1980s). The end of the Cold War was followed by a dramatic fall in global exports of major weapons systems, from a high of \$40.5 billion in 1984 to \$20 billion in 1994 (with a recent increase to \$25 billion in 1997). In the developing world, economic constraints and the loss of favourable terms of credit from the superpowers to finance arms sales have resulted in similar reductions in arms imports, from \$31 billion in 1987 to \$12 billion in 1994 (with an increase to \$18 billion in 1997). A significant development since the 1980s has been the emergence among developing countries of a number of new exporters of major weapons systems.

The proliferation of light weapons and illicit arms trafficking in Nigeria pose a major threat to peace, security and development in the continent. Although they do not in themselves cause the conflicts and criminal activities in which they are used, the wide availability, accumulation and illicit flows of such weapons tend to escalate conflicts; undermine peace agreements; intensify violence and impact on crime; impede economic and social development; and hinder the development of social stability, democracy and good governance. In the current world environment in which the realities of globalization are literally forcing the rapid break down of border lines, low-intensity conflicts in which small arms are critical, and widely used, are threatening the nonnegotiable core value (national security) of especially developing countries of Africa and indeed the countries of the West African sub-region including Nigeria.

The proliferation of small arms is thus a brisk business in the West African sub-region. It has become a serious matter of concern not just to all countries in the region but also to the international community. Dokunbo (2003) provides a graphic picture of the perturbing effects of small arms generally and in West Africa in particular: Of the 500,000 people killed every year across the world, an estimated 300,000 of them are as a result of small arms (Dokunbo, 2003). An estimated 50 percent of illicit weapons that proliferate in Africa are used in internal conflicts, armed robbery and drug trafficking. West Africa alone is reported to have an estimated eight million illicit weapons. Availability of small arms outside the formal security structures had contributed greatly in creating continuous cycle of violence and instability in which particularly women and children are brutalized. (Dokunbo, 2003). Experts have agreed that, "the proliferation of small arms and light weapons, rifles, handguns, machine guns grenades and bazookas - is just as harmful as the increasing number of so-called weapons of mass destruction.

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Of the 50 or so conflicts fought since the end of the Cold War, the vast majority of them have been fought predominantly with small arms. Although Nigeria has a manufacturing capacity for small arms through the Defence Industries Corporation of Nigeria (DICON), the emphasis in recent years has been on importing weapons rather than domestic manufacture. Such domestic manufacture has been for the Nigerian military and police (Adamu, 2012). The late military Head of State, General Sani Abacha spent US \$17 million on imported rifles despite DICON having large numbers on its inventory. Nigeria sought to revive talks with a South African arms company about a joint venture agreement. Many of the weapons illicitly in circulation in Nigeria have been imported.

At a United Nations Small Arms Conference in 2001, the Nigeria Minister of Defence confirmed that there were a million light weapons illicitly circulating in his country (Dokunbo, 2003). Light weapons are widely available in the delta. According to community leaders in this region, many villages have small annouries of AK-47s. As elsewhere in West Africa, the preference is for industrially manufactured weapons and the cost of procuring the e is high - an AK-47 with two magazines can sell for US\$1,700. In Warri, an oil-rich town in the delta, youths have openly hawked pistols and automatic rifles (referred to by local dealers as 'pure water') for between US\$200 and US\$400. Pistols can be much cheaper. The high cost of purchasing an AK-47 in the delta suggests that there is a scarcity value. Some informants suggested that prices fall during escalation of conflicts, but the volume of sales increases considerably (Akhoragbon, 2010). The same weapon is sold in Senegal or Cote d'Ivoire for US\$300 by traders from Liberia (Checkoway, 2006). Apart from the Niger Delta Volunteer Force, the other ethnic group that has acquired small arms and light weapons is the O'odua People's Congress (OPC). The widespread availability of light weapons in the Delta Region of Nigeria is a particular challenge. The criminalization and political economy of conflicts in the region are establishing a basis for escalated, protracted and entrenched violence. Factors that contribute to the destabilization of the region include illegal oil bunkering, ready availability of weapons, endemic corruption, high youth unemployment and social disintegration. Combined, they contribute the resources, weapons and foot soldiers for continued conflict (Chuma, 2011). Micro-level conflicts in the Niger Delta are part of a complex conflict system that is issue-based, ethnic and geographic in nature. Hundreds of criminal and politically motivated gangs have sprung up - many with eye-catching names such as Blood Suckers, Gentlemen's Club and the Royal House of Peace. Most of these are linked to well-known politicians.

The Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force and the Niger Delta Vigilante Group have attracted international attention because of their public profile in 2004 and threats to disrupt the oil industry - threats sufficient to have an impact on world oil prices for a short period (Dokubo, 2003). A key stimulant is illegal oil bunkering has grown significantly over the last few years. According to the federal government, some 300,000 barrel/day are illegally freighted out of the country, but some estimate the true cost lies between US\$1.5 billion and US\$4 billion. The figure can fluctuate greatly depending on political efforts to deal with the practice. Such illicit bunkering is fostered by the sense of poverty and inequality among youth in the delta: in a situation where many communities feel they do not legitimately benefit from the oil industry, it is easy for criminal groups to make illegal oil bunkering appeal (Head, 2011). The Delta provides these illicit networks with both a pool of unemployed youth and armed ethnic militias who know the terrain well. It is also characterized by a corrupt or ineffective law enforcement effort, coupled with a weak judicial process. The criminal networks also enjoy patronage from senior government officials and politicians, who use bunkering as a source of funds for political campaigning (Igidi, 2012). These local groups are also linked into international networks, both West Africa (from Sao Tome, Liberia, Senegal, Cote d'Ivoire and the Gambia) and International (involving Moroccans, Venezuelans, Lebanese and French). At a meeting on 1 October 2004 in Abuja with representatives of the federal government, the leaders of two of the main armed groups, the Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force under Alhaji Mujahid Abubakar Asari Dokubo and the Niger Delta Vigilante Group led by Ateke Tom, agreed to disband and disarm. There followed further meetings in late 2004, and a disarmament process under which 1,000 guns were handed over, the majority of them AK-47s or SA Vz 58s (Kawu, 2012). The condition of the weapons was poor, suggesting that the best weapons have been retained.

To enable communities to defend themselves against extremist groups, some States have armed militias or other non-state actors, whose weapons are even more likely to be diverted than those entrusted to official national security structures (Nte, 2011). For example, in Burkina Faso, the Government launched a programme in 2020 to arm citizens who joined the *Volontaires pour la defense de la patrie* (VDP), a national self-defence movement.³³ However, reportedly, VDP members are easy targets for extremists who target them both for their weapons and to deter any future collaboration with the State.³⁴ Meanwhile, in central Mali, self-defence militias such as *Dan Na Ambassagou*, are alleged to have received resources from sympathetic elements within the state security forces (Okafor, 2012). kunrotifa (2007) defined evaluation as the provision of information involving selection of criteria, collection of data and analysis for the sake of facilitating decision making.

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Therefore, this study evaluated sales of arms and ammunition among Nigerian youths in Riverine areas: a study of Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State. Youths are the major determiners of peace and stability of a nation. They are the foundation of a society. Their energies, inventiveness, character and orientation define the pace of development and security of a nation. Despite the important of youths in the society, it has been observed that proliferation of light weapons and illicit arms trafficking in Nigeria existed among them and this has posed a major threat to peace, security and development in the continent (Ola, 2011). Although they do not in themselves cause the conflicts and criminal activities in which they are used, the wide availability, accumulation and illicit flows of such weapons tend to escalate conflicts. As a way of addressing this problem, numerous studies have been carried on how to put an end to sales of arms and ammunition among Nigerian youths (Vines, 2005). All these studies came up with good contributions but with less research focus on evaluated sales of arms and ammunition among Nigerian youths in Riverine areas: a study of Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State. Therefore, this study evaluated evaluated sales of arms and ammunition among Nigerian youths in Riverine areas: a study of Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Question

What is the attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State?

Methodology

This study adopted the survey research design. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 150 youths in Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State. One instrument was used for data collection: Questionnaire on Sale of Arms and Ammunition Questionnaire ($r=0.78$). Data collected were analysed using percentage scores, mean and standard deviation.

Result

Research Question

What is the attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Attitude of Youth to Sales of Arms and Ammunition in Riverine Areas

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	St. D.
1	I like selling of arms and ammunition.	3.40	.820
2	I prefer selling of arms and ammunition to other business.	3.24	.791
3	I am favorable disclosed to selling of arms and ammunition.	3.35	.715
4	Selling of arms and ammunition does not require a lot of stress.	1.63	.689
5	Selling of arms and ammunition is profitable	3.29	.585
6	I discourage people from selling arms and ammunition	3.28	.735
7	If I have my way, I will not stop people from selling arms and ammunition	1.63	.679
8	Selling of arms and ammunition has connected me with many people	3.38	.729
9	Selling of arms and ammunition is burdensome.	1.63	.584
10	I am not comfortable with the selling of arms and ammunition	1.64	.532
11	I always enjoy selling of arms and ammunition.	3.48	.540
12	If I have my way, I wish selling of arms and ammunition is made legal.	3.43	.536
13	Selling of arms and ammunition increases my sources of income.	3.34	.577
14	Selling of arms and ammunition is not beneficial.	1.54	.597
15	Selling of arms and ammunition is a waste of time.	1.45	.550
16	Selling of arms and ammunition consumes more time than necessary.	1.58	.581
17	I am not encouraged to selling arms and ammunition	1.51	.564
18	Selling of arms and ammunition is not convenient for me	3.34	.579
19	Selling of arms and ammunition does not guarantee good living.	3.41	.615
20	Selling of arms and ammunition does not promote peace.	1.78	.661

Weighted Mean = 2.56; Threshold = 2.50

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Table 1 shows the attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas, Eket Senatorial District. The result indicates a weighted mean of 2.56 which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50. This result implies that majority of the selected youths had a positive attitude to sales of arms and ammunition.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 revealed that majority of the selected youths had a positive attitude to selling of arms and ammunition. This may be because the proliferation of light weapons and illicit arms trafficking in Nigeria pose a major threat to peace, security and development in the continent. This is similar to the study of Chuma (2011) who revealed that the availability of weapons is increasingly governed by the laws of supply and demand with little or no regard to the behaviour of recipients. This is contrary to the study of Dokunbo (2003) who reported that availability of small arms outside the formal security structures had contributed greatly in creating continuous cycle of violence and instability in which particularly women and children are brutalized.

Conclusion

The study has shown that majority of youths had a positive attitude to selling of arms and ammunition. This study has provided a better understanding of that majority of the selected youths had a positive attitude to selling of arms and ammunition riverine areas especially in Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. Government should provide job opportunities for the unemployed youths in the country.
2. Security personnel should be more proactive in maintaining peace in the country.
3. Youths should not be allowed to legalize the selling of arms and ammunition in the country. Anyone caught with unlawful possession of arms and ammunition should be arrested and charged to court.
4. Community leaders should work with government in maintaining peace and they should not condone criminals or criminal acts in their domain.

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